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IRON AGE VULNERABILITY

THE FIMBULWINTER HYPOTHESIS AND THE ARCHAEOLOGY OF THE INLANDS
OF EASTERN NORWAY

DISSERTATION FOR THE DEGREE OF PHILOSOPHIAE DOCTOR (PHD)

DEPARTMENT OF ARCHAEOLOGY, CONSERVATION AND HISTORY, FACULTY OF HUMANITIES

AND MUSEUM OF CULTURAL HISTORY

UNIVERSITY OF OSLO

JULY 2021

This work contributes to the FRIPRO Toppforsk project VIKINGS "Volcanic Eruptions and their Impacts on Climate, Environment, and Viking Society in 500–1250 CE" (Research Council of Norway, grant 275191)

VITOD ÉR ENN, EÐA HVAT?

Völuspá, stanza 41

TO MY WIFE

FOREWORD

“You’ve become more egoistic”, she said. “Yes, I have to”, I answered, “and this is the only time in my life when I’m entitled to”.

This could have been a discussion between me and my wife during the last four years, and to a certain degree, it also was.

During this period I have battled with sentiments of confidence and doubt, often discouraged by the load of work in front of me, feeling guilty for being mentally and physically absent from my family and friends, and being literally exhausted, all at the same time as I have felt privileged and lucky to have time to delve into one of the most fascinating periods in Scandinavian prehistory. I have never been happier. I doubt my family feels the same. During the last weeks and months they have patiently waited for me to finish up. I could not be there when my daughter learned to swim, when my son bicycled two kilometres for the first time, and when my wife reached a new milestone at work and actually made a difference. This also means that I had to sacrifice something. I promise to make it up again. This thesis is therefore dedicated to my family, and my wife Annette in particular, without whom I would never have been able to see this through. If love proves itself in hardship, then we have really proved something during these four years.

I have often heard that doing a PhD is a lonely task. By certain means, it also is. You have to be your own demanding boss, your own worst critique, and your own cheerleader, simply because your own opinion is the one that matters the most. No one else can do the work for you. Nonetheless, during the course of this PhD I started to realise that it is really more complicated than that. You are dependent on people around you all the time, and as time progresses, and your body and mind start to struggle, you need even more people to back you up and help you through. In the beginning I thought having a family would be a handicap, as I couldn’t work around the clock and had to be home for dinner and the children’s bedtime. However, I soon understood that it helped me to separate between work and leisure, and constantly reminded me of what matters the most in life. During this last few months I have become more and more dependent on people around me. I am in debt to Wenche Kristiansen for keeping my body functional, to Julia Kotthaus and Alexa Spiwak for correcting my language and useful comments during the final months, to Glenn Heine Orkelbog for providing a refuge in Bergen where I could concentrate undisturbed on my writing, and to my mother- and father-in-law for being there for my children when I could not. I am particularly grateful to Alexa for her supporting role, and being there on short notice when chapters were completed and ready for dispatch.

Many people have willingly contributed with thoughts, tips, comments, source data, archive material, GIS-support, help, and advice. I would like to express my sincere gratitude to Brit Solli, Svein Nielsen, Kristina Videbech, Elin Lundstad, Kyrre Kverndokk, Helge Hellevang, Anne Engsveen, Bjarne Gaut, Kjetil Skare, Magne Samdal, Ermias Beyene Tesfamariam, Steinar Kristensen, and Kristian Løseth. Helge Høeg must be particularly mentioned, for contributing with bog coring and developing the pollen diagram for Ulberg in Fron, which has proven to become a very important part of the final conclusions. Arne Stamnes has also been very supportive during the development of the GIS models for agricultural vulnerability, whereas Espen Uleberg was essential for building the structural properties of the thesis database. Once again, thank you all!

Frode Iversen and Kirstin Krüger kindly invited me into the VIKINGS project, where I had the possibility to delve into the wonders of meteorology, volcanology, dendro-climatology – in other words, research areas far beyond the comfort zone for most archaeologists. I am indebted to Frode, Kicki, and the rest of the

VIKINGS team for valuable discussions, feedback, and learning, which without a doubt has been of great importance for the development of this thesis.

When I started on this PhD, I soon came to realise the importance of the library and archive at the Museum of Cultural History. Always efficient and helpful, no matter the task, Anne Britt Halvorsen, Hilde Sofie Frydenberg, Lisa Virginia Benson, and Lars Erik Lørdahl were ready to give a helping hand. I could not have done this without you! I once promised Anne Britt a golden statue erected in honour of the archive personnel in the middle street outside the museum. Maybe one day... And a second one for the library!

A few more should be mentioned. Lene Melheim for her supporting role, for always believing in me and my project, and reading and commenting on almost the entire manuscript in these final days until three o'clock at night – at vacation! Some boss... I hope your family is just as understanding as mine.

And to my fellow colleagues at 'stipendiatloftet' at the Museum of Cultural History: thank you for all the laughs, discussions, and support during these intense years! And DialPast for providing great seminars and platforms where we could meet other PhD candidates and researchers from throughout Europe, and share thoughts and ideas with each other.

During the last year I have almost harassed the Norwegian Meteorological Institute (MET) and the Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research (NIBIO) with questions and requests, and surprisingly often I have been met with sincere help, datasets, and advice. In particular, I would like to express sincere gratitude to Randi B. Frøseth, Ole Einar Tveito, Audun Korsæth, Unni Abrahamsen, Hugh Riley, Arne Oddvar Skjelvåg, Ove Klakegg, and Rebecca Cannell for patiently replying to all my strange emails on cereals, bio-productivity, soil classifications, weather data, and who knows what.

Last, but by no means the least, Per Ditlef Fredriksen has been my lone supervisor the whole way through, always with a clear focus on the matters at hand, constantly reminding me of collecting all the threads, and building the study methodically brick-by-brick from research questions, to research history, theory, methods, analysis, and conclusions. Our meetings have always been informal and encouraging, with many discussions on the study and its implications, on the wider socio-political context, and what to do next. Thank you for all the advices and suggestions, and sorry for not being able to follow them all through! Time is unfortunately too limited, but these last four years have really been educational and inspiring.

Minnesund, 8th July 2021

ABSTRACT

A growing body of climate data points towards a significant climate cooling in the northern hemisphere during the 6th century AD. Linked to multiple explosive volcanic eruptions between AD 536-547, the cooling event is the coldest that has been documented for the last 2000 years and seems to have persisted, to varying degrees, well into the latter half of the 6th century.

Several researchers have claimed that the 6th-century cooling must have resulted in extensive crop failure throughout Scandinavia, followed by famine, plagues, and social unrest. One hypothesis suggests that the population of the Scandinavian Peninsula may have been halved as a result. The combination of prolonged cooling and presumed crop failure is often compared to Norse myths about the Fimbulwinter, but critics argue that the Fimbulwinter hypothesis is rife with the uncritical use of climate data, a lack of source criticism and deterministic conclusions. In many ways, the ongoing discourse follows in line with previous discourses in archaeology, revolving around an artificial dichotomy between crisis and continuity.

In this thesis, I examine the climatic and archaeological premises for the Fimbulwinter hypothesis and discuss it against developing theoretical frameworks within the *environmental humanities*. By using vulnerability and resilience as analytical tools, the subsistence and settlement patterns of selected landscapes are analysed against the possibility of crop failure and famine, with emphasis on the Gudbrandsdalen valley and the Lake Mjøsa region in the inlands of eastern Norway.

I conclude that climate cooling had the potential to critically impact some areas, while others were seemingly less affected. These results suggest significant regional diversity in the consequences and adaptations in relation to the 6th-century cooling event. The hypothesis of a halving of the population is up for revision, but the crisis narrative still cannot be fully discounted.

SAMMENDRAG

Stadig mer omfattende klimadata peker i retning av en kraftig nedkjøling av den nordlige halvkulen på 500-tallet, forårsaket av flere eksplosive vulkanutbrudd mellom 536-547 e. Kr. Nedkjølingen er så langt den kaldeste som er dokumentert for de siste 2000 årene, og ser ut til å ha vedvart med varierende styrke til langt ut på 500-tallet.

Flere forskere hevder at nedkjølingen må ha ført til omfattende avlingssvikt i Skandinavia, med påfølgende hungersnød, ufred og epidemier. En rådende hypotese er at halve befolkningen på den skandinaviske halvøya kan ha strøket med. Kombinasjonen av langvarig nedkjøling og antatt avlingssvikt er satt i sammenheng med de norrøne mytene om Fimbulvinteren. Kritiske røster argumenterer imidlertid for at fimbulvinterhypotesen er preget av ukritisk bruk av klimadata, manglende kildekritikk og deterministiske slutninger. På mange måter trækker den pågående diskursen opp igjen gamle spor fra den arkeologiske faghistorien og kretser rundt en kunstig motsetning mellom krise og kontinuitet.

I denne avhandlingen går jeg inn på de klimatiske og arkeologiske premissene for fimbulvinterhypotesen og diskuterer hypotesen opp mot den teoretiske utviklingen innenfor det som gjerne blir definert som *the environmental humanities* i internasjonal forskning. Ved å bruke sårbarhet og resiliens som analytiske verktøy analyseres jordbruks-, subsistens- og bosetningsutviklingen i utvalgte landskapsområder opp mot muligheten for avlingssvikt og hungersnød, med vekt på Gudbrandsdalen og Mjøsregionen på det indre Østlandet.

Jeg konkluderer med at klimanedkjølingen hadde potensiale for å bli kritisk i noen områder, mens andre trolig i liten grad ble berørt. Resultatene åpner dermed opp for betydelig regional variasjon i forhold til konsekvenser og tilpasning i møte med 500-tallets kuldeperiode. Hypotesen om en halvering av befolkningen som helhet bør derfor revurderes, men krisehypotesen kan likevel ikke fullt ut avskrives.

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The databases on which this dissertation is based have been uploaded together with a digital version of the thesis to <https://zenodo.org/> and can be accessed through the following DOI address:

10.5281/zenodo.5782896

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ABBREVIATIONS

EBA	Early Bronze Age	GDD	Growing degree days
LBA	Late Bronze Age	CP	Cooking pit
IA	Iron Age	GR	Grave
EIA	Early Iron Age	PO	Posthole
LIA	Late Iron Age	CG	Cremation Grave
PRIA	Pre-Roman Iron Age	CL	Cultural layer
RIA	Roman Iron Age	CH	Charcoal pit
ERIA	Early Roman Iron Age	FP	Fireplace
LRIA	Late Roman Iron Age	PH	Pit-house
MP	Migration Period	H	House
EMP	Early Migration Period	PI	Pit
LJMP	Late Migration Period	AL	Agricultural layer
MvP	Merovingian Period	CR	Cropland
EMvP	Early Merovingian Period	PA	Pasture
LMvP	Late Merovingian Period	DL	Debris layer
VA	Viking Age	DP	Debris pit
EVA	Early Viking Age	CC	Clearance cairn
LVA	Late Viking Age	BL	Burnt layer
MA	Middle Ages	SM	Smithy
EMA	Early Middle Ages	OT	Other
HMA	High Middle Ages	T	Trench
LMA	Late Middle Ages	L	Layer
Mod	Modern times	FU	Furnace
		SE	Section/Profile
DCH	Directorate of Cultural Heritage	DI	Ditch
MCH	Museum of Cultural History		
OCA	Oppland County Administration		
ACA	Akershus County Administration		
HCA	Hedmark County Administration		
NGU	Geological Survey of Norway		
MET	Norwegian Meteorological Institute		
NIBIO	Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research		

1 INTRODUCTION

The profound changes in the archaeological record around the Early to Late Iron Age transition has been subject to considerable debate in Scandinavian archaeology for quite some time. In the 1940s and 1950s it was often explained in terms of crisis due to agricultural overextension, warfare, migration, plague, and climate change (Gundersen, 2019). Beginning in the 1970s, increasing critique was raised against the crisis narrative. Importance was given to the long-term trajectories and regional diversity of the Scandinavian archaeological record, which called for more complex explanations. At the same time, the evidence for widespread site abandonment, which had been a focal point of reference for much of the early studies, seemed to be of a more limited geographical extension than previously assumed; in Norway, widespread abandonment was mostly associated with the southern part of the country. Bjørn Myhre (2002) eventually described the crisis narrative as obsolete and inadequate for explaining the underlying mechanisms behind the development of the Iron Age societies around the mid-1st millennium AD. However, by the late 1990s and early 2000s, a growing body of high-resolution climate proxies were also starting to attract attention from archaeologists and historians, first among classicists working on late Antiquity, and then among Iron Age researchers in Scandinavia. Particularly intriguing was the evidence for a sudden and unprecedented climate cooling around the mid-6th century AD likely caused by one or several explosive volcanic eruptions on the other side of the globe. Current research suggests that at least three major eruptions seem to have taken place between AD 536 and 547, most likely in central and northern America. The tight sequence of explosive eruptions re-enforced the climate impact, leading to a prolonged Northern Hemisphere cooling lasting at least until the 550s, and argued by some to have lasted until the 570s or 660s. As a result, the geoscientific evidence brought forth previous ideas of a major crisis in Iron Age Scandinavia, caused by widespread agricultural failure due to diminishing summer temperatures.

In 2007, Bo Gräslund published a landmark article in which he argued that the 6th-century cooling event not only had caused widespread famine and social unrest throughout present-day Norway and Sweden, but that it was also the likely source for the Norse myths on the Fimbulwinter and Ragnarok – the end of the world. By building upon a large foundation of historical, mythological, archaeological, dendrochronological, and paleo-botanical sources, the study soon proved highly influential in Scandinavian Iron Age archaeology. Gräslund pointed out several similarities between the climatic effects of explosive volcanism and the Fimbulwinter myth, in particular the three winters without summer in between, a reddened sky, a sun with no effect, invisible stars, weather out of balance, and the moon being carried away by the children of the Fenris wolf, which were reminiscent of the effects of a volcanic dust veil event blocking for the sun, causing reduced temperatures and stratospheric optical illusions. Similar accounts can be also be found in contemporary Mediterranean sources. The Justinianic Plague was

also an important event at this time, causing several epidemic outbreaks in the Post-Roman world between AD 541 and 750, and by many archaeologists was believed to have reached Scandinavia as well (eg. Skre, 2019; Solheim & Iversen, 2019). Gräslund and Neil Price argue that the population of the Scandinavian Peninsula may have been halved due to a combination of famine, plague, and social unrest (Gräslund, 2018, pp. 193-196; Gräslund & Price, 2012, p. 433; Price & Gräslund, 2015, p. 127).

Despite offering an intriguing explanation for patterns of settlement reorganisation, settlement decline, changes in burial customs, reforestation of agricultural lands, and what has often been defined as a general finds lacuna from the late 6th and throughout most of the 7th centuries AD, the proponents of hypothesis still struggles with many of the same issues as previous crisis narratives, namely regional diversity and long-term trajectories. Critics point out the deterministic perspectives involved and the uncritical use of geoscientific research when analysing past social change (Moreland, 2018; Näsman, 2012). Several in-depth studies of selected finds categories, such as ceramics, cooking pits, settlement structure, weaponry, and brooches point out that the changes attributed to the 6th-century transition are embedded in Late Roman Iron Age and Early Migration Period dynamics (Fredriksen, Kristoffersen, & Zimmermann, 2014; Gjerpe, 2017; Grønnesby, 2019; Gundersen, Rødsrud, & Post-Melbye, 2020; Røstad, 2016; Ystgaard, 2014). Following a similar line of argument, Dagfinn Skre (2019) and Frands Herschend (2009) argue that the overall societal structure in Scandinavia was in a process of profound change originating in the Migration Period, ultimately culminating in the petty kingdoms of the Merovingian Period. As such, there is a distinct element of continuous change, but the cooling event is nonetheless generally believed by the referred authors, to a lesser or greater extent, to have contributed to the general development.

With the exception of Arne A. Stamnes (2016), few attempts have been made to analyse the possible social impact of a cooling event on agricultural production in Iron Age Scandinavia. The discussion has, so far, been mainly concerned with temporal issues, in particular whether concurrency can be identified between the climate event and major changes in the archaeological record, whereby claims of a causal relationship remain for the most part unexplored and unsubstantiated (Gundersen, 2019, p. 110). Consequently, the critique remains valid. Whether the climate cooling had profound consequences for Iron Age Scandinavia remains unresolved.

1.1. Research questions

This study targets the potential effect of the 6th-century cooling event on farming societies of Iron Age Scandinavia. By utilising a human-environmental approach, I aim at disentangling the mechanisms that

may have created vulnerability to climate change by focusing on two study areas and analysing the archaeological and paleo-botanical record up against topographical and climatic preconditions for farming. The following research questions will be sought resolved:

- a) How dependent were Iron Age subsistence strategies on agricultural outputs?
- b) Can profound changes/disruptions be identified in the settlement and agricultural records in the selected study areas?
- c) Can detected changes in subsistence strategies over time be related to climate cooling?
- d) In what ways, and to what extent, would climate cooling impact Iron Age farming strategies?
- e) What are the main differences between the two areas of focus in this study, and how do the results of my study compare with relevant case studies of contemporary Iron Age farming communities elsewhere in Scandinavia?

1.2. Thesis outline

The thesis is separated into four main parts:

1. State of research (Chapter 2 and 3)
2. Analytical framework (Chapter 4, 5 and 6)
3. Analysis (Chapter 7, 8 and 9)
4. Synthesis (Chapter 10 and 11)

In Part 1, the climatic and archaeological premises for the idea of a 6th-century climate crisis in Scandinavia is disentangled and discussed. As the climate factor constitutes a vital part of the crisis narrative, but is not always well-understood by archaeologists, I have found it necessary to begin with a thorough review of the geoscientific evidence and discuss the archaeological conclusions that may be drawn. Chapter 2 arrives at three key lessons, which inform the subsequent analysis and discussions. First, the climate response to volcanic eruptions varies along both temporal and spatial scales. This means that the climate event cannot be approached as a single uniform event for the whole of the Northern Hemisphere, Europe, or Scandinavia. Second, the social impact depends on numerous factors embedded within both the environmental and human domains, making a contextual approach necessary. Third, the geoscientific results are conditioned by data selection, methods, and interpretation, and should therefore not be used uncritically as 'hard facts' in archaeological research. In Chapter 3, the crisis narrative is discussed from a research-historical perspective, with particular emphasis on how the current debate is embedded in a century-long discourse revolving around a constructed dichotomy between crisis and change of practice. Moreover, there is a general lack of analytical approaches which are able to substantiate the claim of lasting substantial social impact from the cooling event, thus reducing issues of

causality to a mere matter of concurrency between geoscientific and archaeological datasets. Finally, few attempts are made to critically evaluate the significance of the geoscientific results, thus overlooking both the interpretative processes involved and the spatiotemporal heterogeneity of climate change, resulting in somewhat deterministic explanations that the cooling event must have had a deep social impact on the Scandinavian Peninsula.

In Part 2, I examine the development of disaster research in the humanities, with particular focus on the emergence of the so-called *environmental humanities* during the last three decades (Chapter 4). Despite a certain risk for catastrophic biases influenced by current environmental concerns, the environmental humanities represent considerable potential for progressing our understanding of the complex relationship between human and environmental dynamics. In Chapter 5, I discuss the possibilities and limitations of resilience theory and disaster risk research for archaeology. Of particular importance is how the consequences of disruptive events are conditioned by the social construction of vulnerability, in other words emerging in the intersection between human and environmental processes. Thus, when analysing disaster impact, contingency and long-term trajectories become fundamental, as well as identifying risk drivers that may have enhanced societal vulnerability to disruption. In Chapter 6, these perspectives are developed into a coherent method for analysing the potential impact of the cooling event by utilising vulnerability and resilience as analytical tools on the settlement and agricultural records from two research areas: the Gudbrandsdalen valley and the Lake Mjøsa region in the inlands of eastern Norway. The method is structured around a two-step approach: a statistical macro-level analysis focusing on the overall farming and settlement development in a long-term perspective, and micro-level case studies exploring the potential effect of climate cooling on the farming landscape by utilising GIS tools and local pollen diagrams. Chapter 6 also outlines the most important source-critical issues related to the paleo-botanical and archaeological record.

In Part 3, the environmental preconditions for farming, and how they have traditionally influencing farming practice in the Gudbrandsdalen valley and the Lake Mjøsa region, is examined in Chapter 7, which leads up to the statistical analysis in Chapter 8. The statistical analysis in Chapter 8 specifically targets **research questions A, B, and C** by examining the paleo-botanical, radiocarbon, and faunal data from excavated settlement and agricultural sites in order to identify farming practices, subsistence strategies, and site developments. The chapter concludes that the Iron Age communities in the two regions had a wide base of subsistence resources available that could be utilised during bad harvests. Moreover, the overall development towards a mixed farming economy predates the 6th century in both regions, but nonetheless at a somewhat later stage in the Lake Mjøsa region than the Gudbrandsdalen valley. Possible risk drivers and adaptational strategies to climate cooling are discussed. There are patterns of site

disruption during the Merovingian Period, especially in the Gudbrandsdalen valley. In the final part of the chapter, changes in the archaeological record are preliminarily discussed in light of **research question C**. The conclusions from **research questions A and B** in Chapter 8 inform the analysis in Chapter 9, which examines **research questions D and E**. Agricultural vulnerability to cooling is analysed using GIS-models of Fron in the Gudbrandsdalen valley and Hedmarken in the Lake Mjøsa region. The results are discussed up against local pollen diagrams, site evidence, and local environmental factors. In Fron, a combination of increased flood rates during the mid-1st millennium AD, low temperature margins, and settlement expansion towards vulnerable areas in the Roman Iron Age and Migration Period appear to have been instrumental in widespread site abandonment and fallowing in the Early Merovingian Period. Both excavation records and vegetation data indicate long-term consequences. Temperature margins are somewhat higher in Hedmarken, and site abandonment seems to be associated with site character, elevation above sea level, and soil conditions. The consequences of the cooling are short-term, as the Merovingian Period is characterised by renewed agricultural expansion. To supplement the analysis, additional studies are conducted on the Forsand area in Rogaland, the Borre area in Vestfold, and the Raknehaugen area at Ullensaker. The combined results testify to considerable regional diversity in disaster impact and responses, which appear connected to different levels of agricultural vulnerability.

In Part 4, the discussion on **research question C, D and E** is brought to conclusion in Chapter 10 and discussed up against the theoretical framework in Chapter 5, and the general socio-political context for Iron Age communities in Scandinavia around the mid-1st millennium AD. The overall conclusion is that the 6th-century environmental downturn had the potential of becoming critical in some areas, whereas a development towards crisis was less likely in other parts of southern Norway. In this perspective, crisis and a change of practice become complementary rather than contradicting, which ultimately opens up for a more dynamic and multifaceted view of the Iron Age in general, and the 6th century in particular. Chapter 11 brings the discussion back to where it originally started, the Fimbulwinter hypothesis, for some final remarks on where the debate stands and where its future potential lies.

1.3. Chronologies

The main periodization in Figure 1.1 is in accordance with the general chronological outline by Østmo and Hedeager (2005). Traditionally, the division between the Early Migration Period (D1) and the Late Migration Period (D2) is set to AD 475 in Scandinavian archaeology (Herschend, 2009, p. 7; Røstad, 2016, p. 43), although recent revision of the chronology for Norway has adjusted this division to AD 450 (see Fredriksen et al., 2014, p. 120; Kristoffersen & Magnus, 2015; Kristoffersen & Røstad, 2020). However, as periodization in this thesis is limited to being used as a tool for categorising the excavation records within overall time segments that are common for Scandinavia, and does not include any typological studies of artefact finds, I will keep AD 475 as the division between the Early and the Late Migration Period (Table

1.1). This choice is made in order for the results presented in this work to be more easily compared to existing chronologies and narratives for the Migration Period more broadly in Scandinavia (in particular Herschend, 2009. See also Røstad's (2016, pp. 42-44) discussion of the chronological division in typological studies).

Figure 1.1: Main periodization used in the thesis. Illustration by Ingvild Tinglum Bøckman.

Period		Age	
Stone Age	Mesolithic	>3950 BC	
	Neolithic	3950-1800 BC	
Bronze Age	Early	1800-1100 BC	
	Late	1100-500 BC	
Iron Age	Early	Pre-Roman Iron Age	500-1 BC
		Early Roman Iron Age	1-200 AD
		Late Roman Iron Age	200-400 AD
		Early Migration Period	400-475 AD
	Late	Late Migration Period	475-550 AD
		Early Merovingian Period	550-650 AD
		Late Merovingian Period	650-800 AD
		Early Viking Age	800-900 AD
Middle Ages	Late Viking Age	900-1050 AD	
	Early	1050-1200 AD	
	High	1200-1400 AD	
	Late	1400-1537 AD	

Table 1.1: Detailed periodization used in the thesis.

The transition between the Migration Period and the Merovingian Period has also been the subject of some debate. In this work I follow the established chronological frame for the Merovingian Period in eastern Norway. This means that Phase 1 is AD 550-650, Phase 2 is AD 650-750, and Phase 3 is AD 750-

800 (Gudesen, 1980, p. 71; E. Mikkelsen, 1973). In order to keep the chronological framework as simple and clear as possible, I refer to Phase 1 as the Early Merovingian Period and Phases 2 and 3 as the Late Merovingian Period.

1.4. Concept clarifications

The cooling event is labelled in different ways by different researchers. Büntgen et al. (2016) termed it the 'Late Antique Little Ice Age' (LALIA) due to its proposed duration until the 660s, thus resembling the 'Little Ice Age' (LIA) of the 16th to early 19th centuries. However, the duration of the former cooling event is under discussion, with 536-550s and 536-570s being alternative suggestions (Helama et al., 2018; Helama, Jones, & Briffa, 2017). In Scandinavian archaeology, it is sometimes simply called the 'Fimbulwinter', due to its suggested link to the mythological tales of the long cold winter preceding the Ragnarok (Price & Gräslund, 2015). As both the LALIA and the Fimbulwinter are concepts reflecting distinct interpretations of the duration and social impact of the cooling event, I have decided to use a more neutral term: the 6th-century cooling event. Admittedly, there are certain interpretative elements attached to this concept as well, but it is nonetheless a more inclusive definition that opens up for a wider array of alternatives.

With the term 'the Fimbulwinter hypothesis', I refer to the idea that widespread climate cooling, caused by distant major volcanic eruptions, resulted in crop failure, famine, plague, social unrest and population decline, ultimately leading to major socio-political change (Gundersen, 2019, p. 101). The term explicitly relates to works of Gräslund and Price (Gräslund, 2007, 2018, 2020; Gräslund & Price, 2012; Price & Gräslund, 2015), but in a wider sense it also concerns several more studies that aim at building on the interpretations of Gräslund and Price without critically evaluating the premises for the hypothesis (eg. Holmberg, Gräslund, Sundqvist, & Williams, 2020; Iversen, 2016; Løken, 2020; Löwenborg, 2012b; Solheim & Iversen, 2019; Tvauri, 2014).

Some of the Iron Age settlement sites presented in this thesis may best be described as regular farmsteads, in particular those where longhouses and barn/stables have been documented. However, the term is problematic in a prehistoric context, as the given criteria, such as the presence of fences, stables, barns, and fields, are only rarely applicable to the fragmented and partial nature of the archaeological record (Gjerpe, 2010, p. 12). 'Farmstead' is therefore used in a wide sense in this context, essentially on sites with identified longhouses within a primarily farming context.

'Site' refers to the extent of the individual excavation sites and the respective archaeological features documented at those sites. As such, two nearby sites that may have belonged to the same Iron Age farm are nonetheless listed as separate records in the database, but usually with related names. Grytting I and Grytting II are, for instance, situated close to each other and should be understood as belonging to the same farmstead (Villumsen, 2016a). In other cases, such as Brandrud I and Brandrud IV, the sites are associated with two different prehistoric farmsteads defined by spatially separated house plots (Loktu & Gundersen, 2016). The site names refer to the name of the present farms holding ownership of the respective excavation areas and should not be confused with prehistoric property rights, although this is likely to have been the case in several instances, such as the Åker complex (Pilø, 2005).

'Context' refers to a defined set of archaeological features at the excavation site that share common characteristics, such as cooking pits and clearance cairns. If distinct phases have been identified within a category, by for instance stratigraphic relations or radiocarbon dating, the record is divided into separate contexts reflecting the overall age interpretation of that phase. In other words, 'context' is understood as a defined activity, or related set of activities, within a certain amount of time on each archaeological site.

PART I

STATE OF RESEARCH

2 THE CLIMATE BACKGROUND

The climate evidence constitutes a fundamental part of the current Fimbulwinter hypothesis, as it has direct implications for the interpretations of the archaeological record as a suggested major driver for social change (eg. Price & Gräslund, 2015). However, the geoscientific datasets are rarely put under close scrutiny, leading to critique for simplified and uncritical use (Moreland, 2018). I will therefore begin my discussion on the crisis narrative by outlining some of the basic premises for volcanic-induced climate forcing and the main principles behind the climate reconstructions. The conclusions from this chapter provide an important foundation for the upcoming research-historical discussions in Chapter 3.

The well-documented 1815 Tambora eruption will be used to highlight some of the main issues, as it illustrates the regional impact character of distant major eruptions, both in societal and climatic terms. Furthermore, the Tambora eruption is often used as an analogy to the AD536/540 eruptions due to the eruption magnitude and spatial spread, hence providing useful insights to the possible societal outcomes of a 6th century cooling. The geoscientific evidence for the 6th century cooling will be presented and discussed in the final part of the chapter.

Volcanic induced climate forcing is a complex matter, as Earth's climate system causes considerable variability of responses across spatial and temporal scales (Brázdil, Řezníčková, Valášek, Dolák, & Kotyza, 2016, p. 1361; D'Arrigo, Wilson, & Anchukaitis, 2013, p. 7; Neumann, 1990, pp. 109-113; Oppenheimer, 2011, pp. 64, 69-76; Robock, 2000; Toohey et al., 2019). Important aspects which need to be considered for the climate impact are the geographical location of the eruption, seasonality, type of eruption, intensity, injection height and the amount of sulphur dioxide ejected into the stratosphere¹.

In order to assess the societal consequences and responses to volcanic eruptions, it is important to understand the mechanisms behind their climate outreach, as climate anomalies may differ greatly between geographical regions and over time. Source criticism is of equal importance, since the temperature reconstructions, which form the very basis of our understanding of past climate events, are subject to interpretation, data selection, resolution, and computer simulations. Moreover, the different methods are based on different types of proxies, which may result in discrepancies between the output data, in particular between climate model simulations and temperature reconstructions (Zhu, Emile-Geay, Hakim, King, & Anchukaitis, 2020). The subjective assessments and methodological uncertainties

¹ The stratosphere is the second lowest part of the atmosphere, situated between the troposphere (lower) and the mesosphere (upper) at ca. 15 to 50 km altitude.

associated with the geoscientific datasets tend to be overlooked in archaeological research, which carries a risk of uncritically adopting geoscientific interpretations without critical evaluation (cf. Degroot et al., 2021).

2.1 Volcanic induced climate forcing. Some basic issues

Major explosive events, so-called Plinian-size² eruptions, emit large quantities of sulphur dioxide into the stratosphere where it is oxidised to sulphuric acid and creates a persistent aerosol veil (Oppenheimer, 2011, pp. 53-61; Robock, 2000). Depending on eruption characteristics and geographical location, aerosol veils have the potential to cause global effects on climate as stratospheric circulations cause considerable spatial spread. This is particularly true for near-equatorial eruptions, which spread globally on both hemispheres. Recent research, however, suggests that volcanic events constrained to the Northern Hemisphere may cause greater extratropical climate forcing in proportion to the amount of sulphur injected, due to the confinement of aerosols to a single hemisphere (Toohey et al., 2019).

Stratospheric aerosol veils scatter and absorb incoming solar radiation, ultimately influencing the tropospheric temperature development and potentially affecting the Earth's total heat budget for a number of years (Oppenheimer, 2011, pp. 60-66; Robock, 2000, p. 194). Post-eruption cooling of global summer surface temperatures is a common consequence, as the amount of sunlight reaching the biosphere is consequently reduced, but due to the physical nature of the particles, aerosol veils also have the potential to cause climate warming (Oppenheimer, 2011, p. 62). Volcanic fallout consists of gases and particles of different shapes, sizes and chemical compositions, which all cause different effects on radiation. Furthermore, the components accumulate and drop out of the stratosphere at different rates, leading to climate effects changing over time. In general, larger particles are not only less effective in scattering the sunlight, but also have a shorter stratospheric lifespan since they are gravitating towards the troposphere faster than lighter particles. Heavier particles therefore have shorter temporal effects. The aerosol veil has a stratospheric lifetime of approximately 1 to 3 years, and is eventually reaching the troposphere, from where the volcanic aerosols are quickly deposited to the ground by rainfalls and weather (Robock, 2000). The aerosol veil will gradually thin/decrease to consist of smaller particles (Oppenheimer, 2011, p. 61). As the volcanic dust veil reflects the incoming solar radiation, it causes

² Plinian eruptions are named after the historical eruption of Mount Vesuvius in AD 79 and its chronicler Pliny the Younger, but is not an accurate designation of the magnitude of the events (Oppenheimer, 2011, p. 17). It is nevertheless commonly used in volcanic terminology to characterize major explosive eruptions of a Volcanic Explosivity Index (VEI) of 4 or higher, of which 8 is the maximum value (eg. Bryan et al., 2010; Houghton et al., 2013; Newhall & Self, 1982).

considerable optical effects such as the illusion of a darkened sun, dimmed stars and moon, but also spectacular sunsets and twilights.

The dynamics of Earth's climate system contribute to considerable regional variability, meaning that a mean global cooling may include spatial and temporal pockets of strong heating as well as severe cooling. The aerosol veil is, therefore, conditioned by the time of the eruption, as latitudinal and seasonal variations in the tropopause³ affect the required eruption intensity necessary for the plume to reach the stratosphere (Oppenheimer, 2011, p. 74). Atmospheric circulation changes throughout the year, influencing the spread of the volcanic dust veil as well as surface humidity, temperature and weather. Of particular importance are major circulation phenomena, such as the El Niño Southern oscillation and the North Atlantic oscillation, both of which have the potential to dampen or amplify the climate impact of volcanic eruptions. A recent model study by Matthew Toohey et al. (2019, p. 104) simulates that a Northern Hemisphere winter-time eruption would result in a prolonged stratospheric aerosol lifetime, compared to a summer-time eruption at same latitude and with equal injection height and sulphur dioxide intensity. A winter-time Northern Hemisphere extratropical event would have an aerosol lifetime only slightly shorter than a tropical eruption with equal injection heights.

In short, there is not a simple linear relationship between the magnitude of an eruption and the subsequent climatic consequences. Although the amount of sulphur emission is important for volcanic induced climate forcing, the sulphur load itself is controlled by several physical and chemical parameters, which remain only partially understood (Oppenheimer, 2011, pp. 69-71). Fundamental are temperature, pressure, and melt composition during the eruption. Furthermore, since extreme yields of sulphur dioxide lead to the formation of larger particles in the stratosphere, the climate response does not scale in a simple way neither to eruption size nor sulphuric load (Oppenheimer, 2011, p. 71).

The long history of volcanism can be traced from ice-cores, and in recent years, considerable research efforts have been made into developing high-resolution chronologies (eg. Sigl et al., 2015). The primary evidence consists of layers of sulphuric acid, although tephra charts are sometimes also identified. Synchronised ice-core evidence from different locations, preferably Antarctica and Greenland, allows for calculations of an approximate latitude and magnitude of eruptions (eg. Sigl et al., 2015; Toohey, Krüger, Sigl, Stordal, & Svensen, 2016). Furthermore, the chemical composition of tephra serves as 'fingerprint

³ The tropopause is the boundary between the troposphere and the stratosphere.

evidence', as volcanoes around the globe have different chemical signatures. Where tephra is found it contributes to an identification of the geographical location of past volcanic eruptions.

The temperature effect is derived from other proxies. Tree-ring series constitute the primary evidence for past climate reconstructions, since tree-rings represent a widely distributed and easily accessible archive of annually resolved climate proxies (Luckman, 2013, p. 459). Maximum latewood⁴ density (MXD) is of particular importance to identifying past cooling events, because the development of latewood is susceptible to cold and wet summers which result in poorly-defined and lighter rings (Luckman, 2013, p. 463; Toohey et al., 2016, p. 7). In addition to physical measures of tree-ring characteristics, increasing research attention has been directed towards stable isotope analysis over the past 20 years (Luckman, 2013, p. 461). Carbon isotope variations in tree-rings are believed to be driven by solar radiation, thus providing a precise record of annual cycles and anomalies (Helama et al., 2018, p. 1). Nevertheless, tree growth is influenced by several non-climatic factors as well, such as tree-to-tree competition, which causes considerable local variability. Moreover, the rings are subject to physiological memory within the trees which affects the climate signals, although this is a more distinct feature for ring width than MXD (Lücke, Hegerl, Schurer, & Wilson, 2019). Scientific reliability is achieved through correlation between large number of proxies of geographically distributed tree-ring series, as it is believed that only climate affects terrestrial growth over large spatial scales (Helama et al., 2017; Luckman, 2013, p. 459). Furthermore, trees growing at the outmost range of their habitats, such as latitudinal and altitudinal treelines, are more sensitive to climate variations than trees growing in interior forests or lower altitudes, which are more sensitive to moisture (cf. Helama et al., 2018).

2.2 The 1815 Tambora eruption

The 1815 Tambora eruption on the island of Sumbawa in Indonesia is the largest recorded eruption in historical times. It caused tens of thousands of casualties in the near vicinity of the volcano, but also had a significant global outreach (Oppenheimer, 2003, 2011). The event is well documented, although exact estimations of the magnitude of the eruption vary (Oppenheimer, 2003, pp. 242-243; J. Smith, 2007, p. 28). The Tambora eruption is often compared to the AD 536/540 events, thus shaping our interpretations of the possible climatic and societal impacts (eg. Baillie, 1994, p. 214; L. B. Larsen et al., 2008, p. 4; Løken, 2020, p. 286; Price & Gräslund, 2015, p. 112). Both catastrophes caused immediate widespread cooling throughout the Northern Hemisphere and have therefore been related to agrarian failure, famine and epidemics. The Tambora event not only provides insights into societal consequences of volcanic induced

⁴ Latewood is made by a thickening of the cell walls at the end of the growing season (Luckman, 2013, p. 459).

climate response, but also serves to illustrate the complexity and spatial and temporal variability of the climate system. Furthermore, the event shows the importance of socio-political contextualisation of the affected societies, as the societal impact differed within both Europe and North America.

Northern Hemisphere cooling following the aftermath of Tambora persisted throughout 1815-1817, resulting in crop failure, famine and epidemics on both sides of the North Atlantic (Bjørnstad, 2012, pp. 109-110; Brázdil et al., 2016; D'Arrigo et al., 2013; Oppenheimer, 2003; J. Smith, 2007). The summer of 1816, 'the year without summer', was the coldest for generations and one of the coldest for the past six centuries at the Northern Hemisphere, resulting in what has been labelled "the last great subsistence crisis in the Western world" (Brázdil et al., 2016, p. 1362; D'Arrigo et al., 2013, pp. 3-5; Oppenheimer, 2003, pp. 244-247, 251; 2011, pp. 295-319).

In the summer of 1815, the optical effects of the eruption's dust veil were observed in Europe as spectacular sunsets and twilights (Oppenheimer, 2003, p. 244; J. Smith, 2007, p. 29). Records from the modern-day Czech Republic note cold temperatures, frequent rain and incidents of frost in May, followed by a windy and rainy summer (Brázdil et al., 2016, p. 1366). Some of the year's rye crop was infested with rust, all of the hay rotted at higher altitudes, and summer gave way for a dry, cold autumn. The subsequent spring of 1816 was cold and dry, which delayed the spring sowing until the middle of May. Cold and rainy weather then dominated most of the summer, involving dense fogs and damaging thunderstorms, which caused the grain to saturate, potatoes to rot, and made it difficult to work on the fields (Brázdil et al., 2016, p. 1367). Rising water levels, floods and landslides are reported throughout the period 1815-17, of which some are considered major incidents.

A 'dry fog' was observed in north-eastern USA in spring and summer 1816, which has been identified as a stratospheric sulphate aerosol veil, as neither wind nor rain could disperse it (Oppenheimer, 2003, p. 244). Mild and stormy winters seem to have happened across parts of Europe, and the unusually late spring documented in Czech records manifested itself on other parts of the continent as well. The following summer stands out as exceptionally cold. Reconstructions suggest that the summer temperature in western and central Europe may have been 1-2°C cooler than the average for the period 1810-1819 (Oppenheimer, 2003, p. 245). It must be taken into consideration that the period in question is known to have been unusually cold in the first place, which is believed to have been caused by an unidentified eruption in 1809 (Brázdil et al., 2016, p. 1362; Timmreck et al., in review). The 1816 temperatures were up to 3°C cooler than temperature averages for 1951-1970 (Oppenheimer, 2003, pp. 242, 245, 254-256). Extreme weather, including frost and abnormally heavy summertime rainfalls, was

reported throughout 1816 in particular in parts of north-western and central Europe and north-eastern America. The province of Québec experienced snowfalls in June 1816. Heavy rainfalls and flooding inundated arable land in Holland and inland France (Oppenheimer, 2003, p. 251).

The cold and wet weather prevailed well into 1817 in western Europe and northern America. The worsened environmental conditions in the aftermath of the Tambora eruption caused agrarian failure, resulting in inflated grain prices (Brázdil et al., 2016, p. 1368; Oppenheimer, 2003, pp. 251-252). While killing frosts had devastating effects on the main crops in New England, poor yields were reported as far south as North Carolina. Due to a lack of fodder, many livestock died in New England in the winter of 1816-17. Famine is reported throughout the affected countries, as are incidents of social unrest and riots, and the crisis may also have influenced the financial depression in subsequent years. Families in Wales are reported to have travelled long distances as refugees, begging for food (Oppenheimer, 2003, p. 251). Many farmers fell into debt (Brázdil et al., 2016, p. 1368). Numerous outbreaks of diseases such as dysentery and typhus, which swept through Europe, have also been seen as a direct consequence of the climatic impact of the Tambora eruption (Oppenheimer, 2003, pp. 250, 253).

2.2.1 SOCIAL IMPACT

There were, however, considerable social factors at play which strengthened the societal impact of the disaster. The Tambora event occurred during a period of social and economic distress in the aftermath of the French Revolutionary and Napoleonic wars, after which high unemployment rates, poverty and malnutrition followed (Oppenheimer, 2003, p. 253; 2011, pp. 312-319). Long-lasting warfare, social unrest and years of low summer temperatures had already imposed considerable challenges on society, thus enhancing societal vulnerability to unforeseen events. Rather than being the cause itself, it may be argued that the climate cooling of 1815-17 represented a catalyst for an existing crisis. North-eastern USA was probably susceptible to crop failure, as farming was taking place in what have been characterised as climatologically marginal lands (Oppenheimer, 2003, p. 250). Furthermore, the north-eastern USA experienced increasing competition from the American Midwest and central Canada, putting farming under pressure. Due to a ban on grain export, sufficient resources and low population density, Canada appears to have avoided severe societal consequences (Oppenheimer, 2003, p. 250). The cold years between 1815-1817 were hard in the modern-day Czech Republic, but were not considered to be as devastating as Late Medieval and 18th-century incidents of famine and starvation (Brázdil et al., 2016, p. 1371). Considerable temporal and spatial variability in societal responses to climate change is evident throughout the affected countries, and governmental disaster management capabilities may have been a defining factor (Oppenheimer, 2011, p. 317).

The agrarian crisis was, to some degree, also related to farming strategies. Failed potato harvests were reported across central and western Europe (Brázdil et al., 2016, p. 1367; Oppenheimer, 2003, p. 251). Grain prices have been used as proxy for harvest outcomes, and demonstrate a doubling of costs between 1815 and 1817 in Europe and North America (Oppenheimer, 2003, pp. 251-252). However, different types of cereals responded differently to the new environmental conditions. Czech records have been compiled and presented by Rudolf Brázdil et al. (2016, figure 7) and demonstrate more than a fourfold increase in rye and barley prices between 1813 and 1817, and a tripling in prices for wheat. However, records show that fluctuations in oat prices were more stable than for other grains and that farmers experienced a good oat yield in 1816. Wheat, rye, and barley seem to have been particularly affected by the cold and wet weather, whereas oats may have been more resilient to changed conditions. However, this situation does not apply to all geographic regions, since failed oat harvests are known from Ireland (Oppenheimer, 2003, p. 251).

Differences in agrarian outcomes may to some extent be due to differences in farming strategies and local climate conditions. However, it is also important to consider the spatial spread of the aerosol veil. A drastic drop of summer temperatures was experienced in parts of north-eastern America and central and north-western Europe, whereas parts of eastern Europe appear to have been less affected. Climate reconstruction models suggest normal or even warmer weather in 1816 than the previous year (D'Arrigo et al., 2013, p. 5; Neumann, 1990). North-western America also seems to have been less affected in 1816 (Oppenheimer, 2003, p. 247). While Czech farmers experienced crop failure and inflated grain prices, good crop yields, which allowed for surplus grain export, were reported from Danish, Russian and Polish areas (Brázdil et al., 2016, p. 1367; Neumann, 1990, p. 105).

2.2.2 TAMBORA AND NORWAY

There is little evidence for major consequences of the Tambora eruption in Norway. Compared to western and central Europe, climate reconstructions suggest less climatic impact on Scandinavia (D'Arrigo et al., 2013, figure 3). Evidence for slight cooling is present in records from Denmark and middle Norway, whereas areas around the Baltic Sea seem to have experienced normal or even slightly warmer weather (D'Arrigo et al., 2013, pp. 5-6, figure 3; Neumann, 1990).

Furthermore, the historical record from Norway bears little evidence of disaster and stands in marked contrast to the reports from western and central Europe. In similar ways to the rest of Europe, Norway experienced considerable economic difficulties during and after the Napoleonic wars. The difficulties were

enhanced by wartime British blockades and several years with poor yields in parts of the country in the period 1780-1815 (Dyrvik & Feldbæk, 1996, pp. 50-59, 122, 176-191; Gjerdåker, 2002, pp. 20-22; Neumann, 1990). Farmers experienced particular hardships, and the 'black year' of 1812 is documented as having been cold and harsh, resulting in crop failure in Norway, Sweden and Finland (Bjørnstad, 2012, pp. 107-108; Dyrvik & Feldbæk, 1996, p. 52; Lundstad, 2004, pp. 136, 172, 197; Neumann, 1990, pp. 101-108). Famine was avoided in Sweden and Finland due to grain import, while Norway experienced a major crisis and so-called bread riots because of the British blockade (Bjørnstad, 2012, p. 107; Neumann, 1990, p. 104). Records of severe frost, which caused pigs to die in the summer pastures, are known from the Åker farm in Lake Mjøsa region. The farm nevertheless appears to have successfully avoided a profound crisis, since the farmer still managed to provide supplies for the army (Lundstad, 2004, p. 136).

Thus, Norway experienced similar societal challenges as its European counterparts, caused by vulnerable conditions following enhanced climate cooling. However, no major epidemics are reported from Norway in the aftermath of the Tambora eruption. On the contrary, in spite of economic and agrarian difficulties, the country experienced considerable population growth between 1815-1825 (Dyrvik & Feldbæk, 1996, pp. 192-201; Gjerdåker, 2002, pp. 18-20). Importantly, a drastic reduction in the mortality rates is evident from 1815 to 1816, a trend which continued throughout subsequent years (Neumann, 1990, pp. 103-104, table IV). Reduced infant mortality and increased birth rates resulted in a near-doubling of the population size within 50 years. Although the reasons for this population growth are contested, it may be due to a combination of several social factors such as the introduction of vaccines, improved public health, changes in agrarian strategies during the wartime years, and a return to breastfeeding (Dyrvik & Feldbæk, 1996, pp. 192-201). The Norwegian mortality rates have been described as the lowest in contemporary Europe, perhaps even globally (Dyrvik & Feldbæk, 1996, p. 197; Gjerdåker, 2002, pp. 18-20), and are in contrast to increased mortality rates in other parts of central and western Europe (cf. Oppenheimer, 2011, p. 317).

Moreover, there is little evidence for widespread crop failures in the years following 1815 and the overall record does not reflect a major agrarian crisis at the time (cf. Dyrvik & Feldbæk, 1996, p. 52). Northern Norway experienced poor yields in 1815, while eastern Norway seems to have had slightly lower agrarian output than normal in 1816 (Dyrvik & Feldbæk, 1996, p. 52). Spatial differences may also be noted, as crop yields seem to have remained unaffected in western and middle Norway throughout the entire period 1809-1830. However, social unrest broke out in eastern Norway in 1818, in part due to poor yields, but also as a response to other factors such as increased taxation and deflation (Dyrvik & Feldbæk, 1996, pp. 183-185). The overall record does not reflect a major agrarian crisis at the time (cf. Dyrvik & Feldbæk, 1996, p. 52).

2.2.3 TAMBORA AND ÅKER

Local records, particularly the Åker farm diaries in Lake Mjøsa region, provide further documentation of the effects of the Tambora eruption. In order to reconstruct the climate development of the area from 1749 to 1835, the Åker records have been compiled and systemized by Elin Lundstad (2004). Her analysis suggests low summer temperatures in 1815 and 1816, with reported incidents of frost in 1815. The two years may have been the third and second coldest between the years 1800-1835. The cooling seems to have been less profound than the 'black year' of 1812. Furthermore, 1815 and 1816 follow a number of cold summers from the middle 18th century and onwards, and do not stand out in a longer historical perspective (Lundstad, 2004, pp. 123, 149, 180, 189, figure 8.4 and table 9.1). However, another characteristic of the summer of 1816 is not the cooling itself, but the range and presence of weather anomalies, including great variations in temperatures, incidents of drought, storms, floods, cold and heat. High winter and summer precipitation is reported at Åker for 1815-1817, but 1816 specifically experienced heavy spring and autumn floods which resulted in a rather dry and cold summer (Lundstad, 2004, p. 138). The conditions eventually threatened crops, but agrarian failure still seems to have been avoided.

The Åker records are interesting, since they suggest noticeable difficulties for agriculture in the aftermath of the Tambora eruption, expressed through extreme weather phenomena; ranging from cooling to heat, high precipitation and draught – all within one and the same summer of 1816. The Åker records for 1815 and 1817 detail similar incidents, although not to the same extremes as during 1816. Agrarian failure nevertheless seems to have been avoided, which is consistent with the overall historical narrative (cf. Dyrvik & Feldbæk, 1996; Gjerdåker, 2002). High levels of precipitation, such as those documented in 1815-1817, were characteristic for much of the years between 1811-1820, but this decade is still considered drier than the late 18th century (Lundstad, 2004, pp. 125, 138, 180, 186, figure 8.8, 8.9, table 9.1 and 9.8). Incidentally, the summer of 1812 stands out in Scandinavian 19th century history as one of crisis and famine, and was described as "the year without summer" by the farmer at Åker (Lundstad, 2004, p. 136, author's translation)⁵. Frequent floods and storms are also recurring elements in early 19th century weather records from the farm (Lundstad, 2004, pp. 177, 197, table 8.17, 8.18 and 9.10).

⁵ «Aaret uden Somer».

2.2.4 LESSONS FROM TAMBORA

The historical record details considerable social difficulties in parts of Europe and North America in the aftermath of the Tambora eruption, and serves to illustrate the complexities associated with climate change and the spatial outreach of volcanic eruptions. Regional climate variability is evident, suggesting that the societal consequences may differ accordingly. Furthermore, even if climate cooling is documented for different European areas, evidence for agrarian failure and famine in one part of Europe cannot automatically be applied to neighbouring regions. Local environmental and societal conditions may still have caused markedly different situations, as is illustrated by the case of Scandinavia and western Europe. Both regions experienced significant changes in temperature and precipitation, but only the latter experienced widespread agrarian failure. The mechanisms behind the two different outcome scenarios of the climate downturn are not yet fully understood, although the drastic reduction in mortality rates in Norway from 1815 and onwards does suggest that social factors made a significant contribution to enhanced societal resilience.

Despite limited consequences in Norway, the Tambora eruption example can not be used as an argument against the suggestion that the 6th century cooling may have been of profound consequences for Scandinavian Iron Age societies. Since socio-political, cultural, and farming conditions were quite different, the early 19th century analogy is therefore not directly applicable to an Iron Age context. The 'black year' of 1812 clearly demonstrates that Scandinavia very well could experience widespread crop failure due to a cooling event. A reinforcing factor in 1812 was the political circumstances at the time, which lead to different consequences in Norway and Sweden. Thus, the two examples serve to illustrate the necessity of analysing past environmental events within a wider historical and cultural context, in which the consequences are not understood as directly related to issues such as eruption magnitude, but depends on a variety of factors embedded within both the human and environmental domains.

Consequently, a profound understanding of the consequences of the AD 536/540 events is dependent on a combined assessment of climatic evidence, societal context and the character of the affected societies. As will be discussed in the following chapter, the climatic impact of the AD 536/540 events surpassed that of the Tambora eruption.

2.3 The 6th century cooling

The AD 536 volcanic eruption event was first recognised by Richard B. Stothers and Micael R. Rampino (1983). The identification was based on indirect atmospheric observations in written Mediterranean

sources, which led the researchers to the conclusion that a distant volcanic eruption must have taken place in AD 536. Stothers and Rampino (1983) furthermore argued that the eruption may have been the most explosive in recorded history. Four contemporary chroniclers and historians, Prokopios, John Lydus, Zachariah of Mytilene and John of Ephesus⁶, all recorded similar observations of a darkened sun, lasting for one year or a year and a half, causing poor fruit harvests and “... distress ... among men ... from the evil things” (Zachariah of Mytilene, as referred in Stothers & Rampino, 1983, p. 6363). Stothers and Rampino (1983, p. 6363) identified the phenomenon as a volcanic aerosol cloud, suggesting it may have been caused by a major tropical eruption at Rabaul in Papua New Guinea.

Another contemporary observation is known from Cassiodorus, then prefect of Italy, who described the phenomenon in similar terms (Arjava, 2005, pp. 79-80). A letter in his collection reports of famine in northern Italy in AD 536, while Cassiodorus himself mentioned widespread agrarian failure in AD 537. Some areas, however, seem to have been less affected, as Cassiodorus instructed that supplies be brought from Istria, where the harvest had been better, to Ravenna. There is also evidence for the dust veil reaching well beyond the Mediterranean, as ancient Chinese records mention reduced sky visibility in AD 536 (Gräslund, 2007, p. 104; Oppenheimer, 2011, p. 256). These observations were followed by incidents of summer frost and snow in AD 536-539, including reports of crop failure and famine.

2.3.1 THE GEOSCIENTIFIC EVIDENCE

The idea of a major volcanic aerosol cloud could be supported by the presence of sulphate in the Greenland ice-cores, which suggested evidence for a major eruption sometimes around the middle 6th century (Stothers & Rampino, 1983, p. 6369). Stothers and Rampino’s interpretations have since been coupled with dendrochronological data (Baillie, 1994). In general, the tree-ring record displayed a relatively consistent pattern across the Northern Hemisphere. Of importance are compilations of tree-ring evidence from European oak, Fennoscandian pine and western US bristlecone pine and foxtail pine, all indicating notable growth reduction between AD 536-546. The results indicated considerable cooling in both Europe and North America, which by far surpassed the tree-ring data associated with the 1815 Tambora eruption. According to Michael G. L. Baillie (1994, p. 124), in terms of spatial reach and duration, the Tambora eruption had more limited climatic consequences compared to the AD 536 event. Baillie furthermore pointed out evidence for a two-stage response in the tree-ring chronologies, around AD 536 and 540, questioning whether only a single event was involved. However, Baillie (1994, p. 215) also

⁶ The works of John of Ephesus are mainly missing. However, some of his works, including the description of the AD536 event, have been reproduced or quoted by later writers, such as the 12th century bishop Michael the Syrian. A similar version which has also been attributed to John of Ephesus, was copied by an anonymous Syrian monk (Arjava, 2005, pp. 78-79; Stothers & Rampino, 1983, p. 6362).

questioned the Greenland ice-core evidence for a major eruption in the mid-6th century, as a re-dating of the sulphate layer moved the date decades prior to AD 536. The reasons behind the AD 536 dust veil was therefore unclear, leading Baillie (1994, p. 216) to suggest additional explanations, such as an interstellar cloud or asteroid impact – a perspective further elaborated in his popular book *Exodus to Arthur* (Baillie, 1999).

Revised ice-core chronologies strengthened the volcanic eruption hypothesis (L. B. Larsen et al., 2008), leading Baillie (2008) to withdraw the comet argument. Sulphuric acid in the Greenland ice cores, dated to AD 533-534 ± 2, supported the idea of an extensive aerosol veil around AD 536. The acidic depositions were 40% greater than those for the 1815 Tambora eruption. The data was compared with Antarctic ice core evidence, in particular a layer of sulphate deposits dated to AD 542 ± 17. Although not as conclusive as the Greenland evidence, the presence of more or less contemporary sulphuric depositions in both hemispheres led to the conclusion that the AD 536 event must have been caused by a near-equatorial eruption (L. B. Larsen et al., 2008). Furthermore, the findings were coupled with dendrochronological evidence which suggested a protracted and severe short-term Northern Hemisphere cold period lasting until AD 550. L. B. Larsen et al. (2008) assessed the cooling as unparalleled during the last two millennia, even surpassing the climate downturn in the aftermath of the Tambora eruption.

However, discrepancies between the revised ice core chronologies and dendrochronological record led Baillie (2008) to question the interpretations of L. B. Larsen et al. (2008), hence putting forward an alternative explanation. Firstly, the identification of the AD 533-534 ± 2 layer as the AD 536 event contradicted previous interpretations of a two-stage environmental event, as suggested by tree-ring chronologies (cf. Baillie, 1994, p. 215). Moreover, L. B. Larsen et al. (2008) had identified another sulphate peak in the Greenland ice-cores, dated to AD 529 ± 2, thus being somewhat older than the AD 533-534 ± 2 layer. Moreover, the AD 529 ± 2 depositions seemed to surpass those of AD 533-534 ± 2 but could not be coupled with data from Antarctic ice cores. These observations led L. B. Larsen et al. (2008) to suggest a Northern Hemisphere origin of the AD 529 ± 2 depositions, possibly the mid-6th century Plinian eruption at Haruna in Japan. Baillie (2008) furthermore pointed out that a sequence of 6th century eruptions, identified in the ice core chronologies, was systematically followed by an interval of about 7 years before manifesting in the tree-rings in the North American bristlecone pines. Baillie therefore suggested that the dates should be moved accordingly, leading him to line up the AD 529 ± 2 sulphate layer with the AD 536 event. Consequently, the AD 533-534 ± 2 layer had to reflect the AD 540-541 frost ring occurrences, thus acting as a reinforcing climate catalyst for the AD 536-550 environmental downturn. By rearranging the ice core and tree-ring chronology, Baillie consequently identified the AD 536 event as caused by a Northern Hemisphere eruption. Accordingly, the AD 540 event had to be near equatorial in origin.

New high-resolution sulphur measurements from Greenland and Antarctica ice cores have improved dating accuracy, leading Michael Sigl et al. (2015) to identify a total of 283 individual eruptions over the course of the last 2500 years. Distinctive age markers for known historical events were used to constrain the chronologies. The revised ice core chronologies confirmed the timing of two major eruptions around AD 536 and 540. Five of the eruptions exceeded the sulphate loading from the 1815 Tambora eruption, among them AD 540, followed by clear post-volcanic responses in tree-growth in Germany, the Alps, Siberia, and north-western USA. Multiple tree-ring reconstructions suggest that AD 536 was the coldest single year during the last two millennia, while 536-545 was the coldest decade of the same period (Sigl et al., 2015). In AD 536, Europe may have witnessed a decline of 1.6-2.5°C in mean summer temperatures, depending on the reconstruction methods used, when compared to the previous 30 year average. The European summer temperatures of AD 541 may have decreased by 1.4-2.7°C (Sigl et al., 2015). Sigl et al. (2015) arrived at similar conclusions as L. B. Larsen et al. (2008), arguing that cold temperatures prevailed across the Northern Hemisphere until around AD 550.

Consistency between the ice core records, tree-ring chronologies, geochemical analysis of tephra from the Greenland ice cores, and historical observations support Baillie's hypothesis of a Northern Hemisphere origin of the AD 536 eruption, probably located between 46-56 degrees latitude in North America (Sigl et al., 2015; Toohey et al., 2016, p. 10). However, the chemical fingerprint may be of a combined volcanic signal. In other words, the aerosol veil may have been caused by more than one eruption, thus enhancing the climate impact. The second eruption, in 539 or 540, is identified in both Antarctica and Greenland ice-cores, suggesting a near-equatorial origin. Climate model simulations indicate a best agreement for the AD 540 eruption around 15 degrees Northern Hemisphere latitude, which would be consistent with Lake Ilopango in El Salvador and El Chichón in Mexico. A massive eruption at Ilopango, labelled the Terra Blanca Joven (TBJ) event, has been identified around the middle 1st millennium AD (Kutterolf, Freundt, & Pérez, 2008). The eruption was initially dated to AD 429 ± 107, but later analysis of carbonized timber buried by pyroclastic flow deposits suggested a possible death date for the tree to AD 535 (Dull et al., 2010). However, the authors stressed that a plateau in the calibration curve caused considerable uncertainties regarding the results, meaning that the eruption could in fact have happened anytime between AD 440 and 550.⁷ Combining all evidence, the TBJ event might instead be related to the AD 540/541 climate downturn rather than AD 536 (Newfield, 2018, pp. 464-467). Richard Dull et al. (2019) later revised their interpretations and identified the TBJ event as the source of the 539/540 mystery eruption. However, the exact timing of the eruption remains controversial. A recent paper refutes any

⁷ See further comments on the Migration Period plateau in chapter 6.4.1.

connection to the 6th century cooling, as it is at odds with the archaeological remains found in relation to the TBJ deposits (V. C. Smith et al., 2020). The study suggests that AD 431 ± 2 is a more likely date for the TBJ eruption, which, accordingly, would be more consistent with the archaeological data.

The case of the TBJ event not only clearly illustrates the many source-critical aspects associated with dating prehistoric volcanic eruptions, but also their respective climate impacts. The estimated stratospheric sulphuric load varies according to available methods and data. Based on analysis of Meso-American marine and lake core samples, Dull et al. (2010) first calculated a maximum output of a massive 160 Tg for TBJ, although admitting that the precise load could not be derived from their data. Based on their calculations, they nevertheless considered an up to 40% larger discharge compared to Tambora to be feasible, as implied by Greenland ice core data (cf. L. B. Larsen et al., 2008). Dull et al. (2010) operated with 53-58 Tg for Tambora, which would result in approximately 74-81 Tg for TBJ. In their later paper, Dull et al. (2019) estimated a total load between 9-90 Tg. However, uncertainties are emphasised by the fact that the event is 15% smaller than Tambora in the Antarctic ice core (L. B. Larsen et al., 2008, p. 4). By using published ice core volcanic sulphate deposition data from both the Antarctica and Greenland, Toohey et al. (2016, p. 4) estimated a global stratospheric sulphur dioxide injection of approximately 30 and 50 Tg for the 536 and 540 events. When applying the same method and ice-core data on the 1815 Tambora eruption, Toohey et al. (2016, p. 4) estimated a load of 50 Tg sulphur dioxide, which is consistent with other estimates. Due to the revised dating, Victoria C. Smith et al. (2020) compare the TBJ event to older sulphuric layers in the Greenland ice-cores and are down to only 14 Tg.

There are inconsistencies between the tree-ring and ice core data, as the exceptional cooling indicated by the former does not stand out equally as strong in the latter. According to Baillie (1994, p. 214), the tree-ring evidence implies that the Tambora eruption had severe, but rather temporally and spatially limited climatic consequences, in contrast to the aftermath of AD 536 and subsequent years. Direct comparisons of tree ring chronologies from the same areas show fewer effects following AD 1815 than AD 536 and subsequent years, leading Baillie (1994, p. 214) to conclude that “[t]hese observations, given the significance afforded Tambora by volcanologists, implies that Tambora may be a poor role model for the likely effects of an environmentally effective dust-veil event of the AD 536 variety”. Consequently, estimates of climate impact magnitudes differ depending on the source of evidence (Toohey et al., 2016, p. 2).

In order to bridge these discrepancies, Toohey et al. (2016) reconstructed the radiative forcing of the two events by using a coupled aerosol-climate model, constrained by ice-core evidence and historical

accounts. Based on the contemporary written accounts of the AD 536 dust veil, a test run was set with an assumed eruption date for the 1st of March, while a similar run was set for AD 540 with eruption dates in January and July. The results were then used in a 15-year long Earth system model simulation to estimate long-term climatic effects and spatial anomalies. Their analysis suggests a significant Northern Hemisphere temperature decline following both eruptions, with a maximum mean cooling of -2°C after the 540 eruption, compared to pre-industrial conditions, and a mean decadal temperature drop of $-0,7^{\circ}\text{C}$. Furthermore, the simulations suggest considerable spatial and seasonal variability. The climate cooling seems to have been more profound over land masses in central and southern Europe and around the Barents Sea (Toohey et al., 2016, p. 7). Nevertheless, the cooling is assumed to have had a larger impact on areas with marginal agriculture, such as Scandinavia, the Alps, and around the Baltic Sea. In these areas the temperature decline would represent a larger portion of the annual heat budget, thus increasingly affecting the accumulated temperatures needed for cultivated cereals to reach maturity (Toohey et al., 2016, pp. 8-9). Furthermore, extended ice sea covers would probably be an important factor for prolonging the short term climate effects into decadal cooling, thus being a reinforcing factor for the northernmost parts of Europe (Toohey et al., 2016, p. 10). Consequently, the absolute effect on agrarian productivity would be lower around the Mediterranean, which according to the authors would be in accordance with the historical records (with reference to the thorough review given by Arjava, 2005).

Simulations of aerosol optical depth (AOD)⁸ for AD 536 is also consistent with the written accounts of a darkened sun and reduced solar intensity (Toohey et al., 2016, p. 6). Estimations suggest that the AD 536/540 dual event would result in a Northern Hemisphere decadal AOD 1.5 times larger than the combined effects of the 1809/1815 events. The exceptional characteristic of the 536/540 events are, according to Toohey et al. (2016, p. 6), "... not the magnitude or latitudinal structure of either eruption individually, but rather the temporal proximity of two events with strong forcing in the Northern Hemisphere mid and high latitudes".

Ulf Büntgen et al. (2016) used compilations of numerous tree-ring chronologies from the Alps and Russian Altai to reconstruct the mean summer temperature over the past two millennia. They concluded that a triple event in AD 536, 540 and 547 (with reference to Sigl et al., 2015), resulted in an unprecedented long-lasting cooling of the Northern Hemisphere. The decade following AD 540 was, respectively, the coldest and second coldest in the Altai and Alpine reconstructions. However, the cooling, in part sustained

⁸ AOD is a measure of the aerosol absorption of sun radiance, i.e. how much direct sunlight is prevented from reaching the ground.

by an exceptional solar minimum and increased sea-ice extensions, seems to have lasted well beyond the AD 536-550 cold period (cf. L. B. Larsen et al., 2008; Sigl et al., 2015; Steinhilber, Beer, & Fröhlich, 2009). The solar minimum contributed to a significant middle 6th century drop in solar irradiance, reinforced well into the 7th century (Büntgen et al., 2016, p. 233). A drop in solar irradiance has also been documented for the time around the 1815 Tambora eruption, but was far less pronounced (Steinhilber et al., 2009, figure 2). Recurring low summer temperatures and several incidents of severe decadal cooling, lasting until the 660s, stood out in the overall record. The cold phase, nicknamed the Late Antique Little Ice Age (LALIA), might exceed any other long-term cooling during the last two millennia, considering both the magnitude and rate of change (Büntgen et al., 2016, p. 234).

The hypothesis has received some critique, as the tree-ring evidence for a prolonged cold period until the 660s is limited (Helama et al., 2017). A recent study involving climate model simulation also conclude that the cooling event can be understood as multidecadal, but probably not lasting for over a century (van Dijk, Jungclaus, Lorenz, Timmreck, & Krüger, in review). The LALIA hypothesis seems to be well supported by the Alpine and Altai records, but is only identifiable in a restricted number of other regions across the Northern Hemisphere. It is also worth noting that the Altai record display a much more significant maximum cooling (>4°C cooling w.r.t. 1961-90) than the Alpine record (>2°C cooling w.r.t. 1961-90), which illustrates considerable regional variation. Samuli Helama et al. (2017) therefore argue that the sustained cooling in the aftermath of AD 536 appears to be limited to the 570s at the latest. In their reply, Büntgen et al. (2017) acknowledge that the LALIA may not have been uniform across the Eurasian continent, but stress possible reinforcing factors such as ocean, sea-ice and atmosphere dynamics, which possibly prolonged the effect of volcanically-forced climate cooling in certain areas. Another contributing factor may be an unattributed eruption in AD 626, probably resulting in prolonged summer cooling.

Timothy P. Newfield (2018, pp. 453-459) stresses the variations among tree-ring chronologies and analyses. Climate cooling is clearly demonstrated in several temperature reconstruction series, but there are also differences between them. The Alpine and overall Northern Hemisphere series suggest sustained summer cooling, while the Scandinavian record is less conclusive, including considerable year-to-year variability. Newfield's observations is consistent with the results from the climate simulations of Tooley et al. (2016, pp. 7-8), indicating less climate impact in northern Europe compared to the Mediterranean and Middle East. As is the case with the TBJ event and reconstructed eruption scenario, the results derived from tree ring chronologies vary depending on the data at hand.

Helama et al. (2018) point out that temperature reduction plays an important role for agricultural production at high altitudes and latitudes but argue that it is only a secondary factor in central and southern Europe, where crop yields are constrained by solar radiation rather than temperature. Based on irradiance proxies obtained from stable carbon isotope ratios in tree rings, it has been suggested that the volcanic aerosol veil lead to reduced photosynthesis, causing lower agricultural outputs even in warmer regions.⁹ The data was obtained from subfossilised and living pines near the timberline in Northern Scandinavia. The area is less prone to draught, meaning that the tree ring ratios are believed to be well-suited for extracting irradiance proxies (Helama et al., 2018, p. 2). Results indicate strong negative irradiance anomalies for several summers following AD 536, in general lasting until the 570s, with a particularly substantial drop in AD 541-544. The findings are interpreted as indicative of reduced photosynthesis, due to a dry fog event such as a volcanic dust veil. In their view, temperature effects are subordinate to the reduced sunlight, at least at lower latitudes with higher resilience to temperature anomalies such as the Mediterranean. The results nevertheless overlap with indications of cold summer temperatures and suggest that the dust veil acted as a reinforcing agent for decadal cooling (Helama et al., 2018, p. 7). Reduced photosynthesis may be in accordance with records of failed crops in written Mediterranean sources, in particular the Eastern Empire, including several incidents of famine during the period AD 525-549 (with reference to McCormick et al., 2012). However, the cited work by Michael McCormick et al. (2012) has organised the historical records in intervals of 25 years, making it difficult to assess whether there is indeed a direct link between the reported famines and the AD 536/540 double event.¹⁰

2.3.2 HOW COLD WAS IT?

In other words, the interpretation of the 6th-century cooling event is not as straightforward as one may have expected in the first place. Interpretations and conclusions vary, depending not only on the available data and methods used, but also the spatial resolutions employed in the respective studies. However, most studies agree on the broader perspective of the 6th-century cooling as being exceptional for the last two thousand years, both in terms of the degree of the cooling itself and its duration. Levels of uncertainty increase in relation to increased spatial resolution, as the proxy data becomes more limited, but also because the climate system itself can cause considerable variations on local scales. It is therefore not possible from the present state of research to pinpoint the exact climate effect in each region.

⁹ However, a recent study on solar geoengineering, published after this chapter was written, concludes that aerosol veils may be beneficial for crops, as the scattered sunlight is better suited for piercing through densely cultivated species (Fan et al., 2021).

¹⁰ For further discussions on the study, see Chapter 3.3.2.

However, distinct patterns can be outlined that contribute to overall estimations on the degree and duration of the cooling.

Figure 2.1: Data from Christiansen and Ljungqvist (2012). The reference period has been changed from 1880-1960 to 1961-1990 (+0.23°C). The average temperature cooling for AD 536-550 is -1.7°C.

Figure 2.2: Data from Büntgen et al. (2011), based on Alpine conifers. The reference period has been changed from 1864-2006 to 1961-1990 (-0.2°C). The average temperature cooling for AD 536-550 is -2.1°C.

In Figure 2.1 and Figure 2.2, I have presented two extracts for AD 450-660 drawn from continuous temperature reconstructions for the last two millennia, made available by Büntgen et al. (2011) and B. Christiansen and F. C. Ljungqvist (2012). The numbers given in Figure 2.1 are based on multi-proxy reconstructions from the entire extratropical (30-90° N) Northern Hemisphere, including both summer and winter temperatures (Christiansen & Ljungqvist, 2012). As such, the temperature reconstruction has

expressive value for the Northern Hemisphere at whole and marks the average annual temperature deviations throughout this area. The dataset from Büntgen et al. (2011) is identical to the one used in the much-cited Büntgen et al. (2016) and is based on Alpine conifer data.¹¹ As it is solely based on tree-ring analysis, it reflects the mean temperature during the summer season. However, the Alpine record is spatially limited, and the reconstructions are not necessarily representative of other parts of Europe. The Alpine record is also built on fewer proxies and is therefore more susceptible to single results. When compared directly, both models nonetheless display shared distinct patterns.

Annual temperature fluctuations of ± 0.5 - 1°C between consecutive years are evident in both diagrams, which reflects regular inter-annual temperature variations. The deviations are somewhat higher in the Alpine record, which may be due to proxy size. Higher variations can also be expected on local scales, while the Northern Hemisphere reconstruction reflects more stable overall temperature developments. Both diagrams display unprecedented and rapid cooling around AD 536, with a temperature drop of 2.5°C from one year to next for the entire Northern Hemisphere, and minus 2.3°C between AD 534-537 in the Alps. AD 536 is the second coldest year in the Northern Hemisphere dataset, with an average cooling of minus 2.4°C compared to the 1961-90 standard period (the coldest recorded year is AD 1642 at minus 2.9°C below average). Cooling occurs more gradually in the Alps, reaching minus 2.4°C in AD 537 and a maximum cooling of minus 2.9°C in AD 545. The maximum level of cooling in the Alpine record is similar to that identified in Scandinavian proxies, although there are considerable differences concerning inter-annual variations (cf. Newfield, 2018, Fig. 32.2).

The average cooling for AD 536-550 is minus 1.7°C in the Northern Hemisphere, and minus 2.1°C in the Alps. The Alps experience a second cooling period around AD 600, with a maximum cooling of minus 2.7°C . A similar event is visible in the Altai record, which led Büntgen et al. (2016) to suggest a prolonged Northern Hemisphere cooling lasting well into the seventh century AD. However, no similar cooling event is identifiable in the overall Northern Hemisphere record, which, on the contrary, indicates rising temperatures (see also the discussion on the LALIA in Chapter 2.3.1). The AD 600 cooling might therefore have been of a more regional character. The differences between the two diagrams (Figure 2.1 and Figure 2.2) highlight the dissimilarities that are often found between shifting climatic conditions at different spatial scales.

¹¹ A temperature reconstruction for Scandinavia is published in Büntgen and Tegel (2011) and Newfield (2018), but the proxies are not available for download.

The climate simulation models in Toohey et al. (2016) suggest less average summer cooling for AD 536 in southern Norway than eastern Scandinavia, Russia and southern Europe. However, one must consider that the models are generalised and at low spatial resolution, with potential for considerable differences at local scales. In addition, the AD 540 event seems to have had a more profound impact on northern and eastern Europe than AD 536 (Toohey et al., 2016, Fig. 3). One must therefore consider that climate conditions in Scandinavia may have changed considerably throughout the cooling event.

In Figure 2.1 and Figure 2.2, the maximum cooling during AD 536-550 ranges between approximately minus 2 to minus 3°C below the 1961-90 average, including an average rate for the entire period at approximately minus 2°C. Thus, for southern Norway, the annual temperatures probably reached an approximate level of minus 2°C sometimes during the AD 536-550 period, with minus 3°C representing a possible worst-case scenario in certain areas. A minus 2°C scenario may have been a recurrent event, which is also indicated by published Scandinavian proxies (Büntgen & Tegel, 2011, Fig. 1; Newfield, 2018, Fig. 32.2).

2.3.3 EPIDEMIC ERGOTISM

Epidemic ergotism, a disease caused by the ergot fungus *Claviceps purpurea* that parasites more than 400 grass species, including forage grasses and cultivated cereals (Negård et al., 2015, p. 1432), may have reinforced the effect of climate cooling (Bondeson & Bondesson, 2014). The *Claviceps purpurea* fungus thrives in cold and wet weather, particularly among rye. Rye is more susceptible to ergot, as it is wind-pollinated and not self-pollinating as other grains (Alm & Elvevåg, 2013, p. 21; Bjørnstad, 2012, p. 25; 2014, p. 87). During the Middle Ages, epidemic ergotism was a frequent but unfortunately poorly understood phenomenon (Alm & Elvevåg, 2013, p. 15). Ergot is highly contagious if digested, and can result in gangrene, muscle contraction, and strong hallucinations, often with lethal consequences. Mortality rates as high as 40% have been documented in 19th-century contexts (Bondeson & Bondesson, 2014, p. 62). Most European episodes of mass poisoning were due to rye infestation, and its prevalence in Scandinavia is usually understood in relation to the spread of rye cultivation. Several references to symptoms of ergotism are present in the medieval sagas, and the disease was probably already well-known during the Late Iron Age (Alm & Elvevåg, 2013, pp. 21-23, 28).

Ergotism can potentially affect livestock and wild deer as well. Ergot is also known to have infected cultivated pastures and caused gangrenous ergotism among sheep in Norway, although in a limited number (Torleiv Løken, Ulvund, & Våg, 1979). Cold, wet, and stormy weather aggravates the effect of the poisoning. Several incidents among elk and roe deer have also been reported from the coastal regions of

southeastern and northwestern Norway and elk seem to be especially susceptible to poisoning (Handeland & Vikren, 2005). In this specific study, no grain production existed in the region where most of the deer were found, which indicates that the animals must have been infected by wild grasses. Cold and wet conditions appear to once more have enabled the spread of ergot.

Lennart Bondeson and Tobias Bondesson (2014) assess the conditions during the 6th-century cooling as ideal for the spread of ergot, and attribute a suggested demographic decline during the cooling event to increased levels of ergotism. Surviving an ergot infection does not lead to immunity to the disease. On the contrary, repeated exposures increase the sensitivity to the poison, thus causing long-term consequences for public health (Bondeson & Bondesson, 2014, p. 63). Bondeson and Bondesson (2014) also point out that toxins pass on into the milk of infected livestock, thus both directly and indirectly affecting the farming communities. Children and teenagers who consume more food per unit of body weight due to growth are particularly susceptible to infection. Thus, epidemic ergotism has the potential to affect both vulnerable and younger segments of society.

The main challenge concerning prehistoric episodes of epidemic ergotism is the general absence of physical evidence, with the exception of a few documented cases. Ergot has been identified in 6th century oat grains found at the Iron Age village at Forsand in Rogaland (Løken, 2001, p. 17; 2020, p. 285). The finds of ergot on oats are particularly interesting, as the species is not considered particularly prone to fungal infections, and is well adapted to harsh, and cold climates (cf. Chapter 6.3 below). Several grains also showed traits of having been harvested before the grains reached maturity, which may indicate a causal relationship with the 6th century cooling. Similar finds have also been made on the islands of Gotland and Bornholm, on Jutland, and in south-western Sweden, but which are of various age and context (Bondeson & Bondesson, 2014, p. 62). However, the finds nonetheless attest to the presence of the fungus in Iron Age Scandinavia, although the proposed link to the 6th century cooling may still be tentative.

The proposed link between epidemic ergotism and depopulation also rests on the assumption that there was increased humidity, which cannot be argued categorically since tree-ring proxies indicate low humidity levels in Europe towards the end of the Migration Period (Büntgen et al., 2011, p. 581).¹² Although regional variability may have been significant, the actual conditions during the 6th century in

¹² A recently submitted paper utilising climate simulations concludes that Northern Hemisphere precipitation may have been reduced with up to 0.2 mm per day (w.r.t. AD 1-1850) in the aftermath of the AD 536 and 540 eruptions (van Dijk et al., in review).

Scandinavia are still somewhat unclear. As with temperature variations, differences in humidity levels may equally be expected within this region. The wet coastal areas of western Norway, where the Forsand site is located, would have been more susceptible to ergot than the drier areas of eastern Norway.

Another factor concerns crop types. Apart from certain parts of southern Scandinavia, the limited extent of rye cultivation up to the Late Iron Age contradicts suggestions that ergotism represented a profound societal challenge at the time. However, the finds of ergot infected oats at Forsand demonstrates that the fungus may affect other crop types as well. Only 2% of grains used for bread need to be contaminated to cause community-wide ergotism (Bondeson & Bondesson, 2014, p. 62). Ergot may consequently have contributed to enhanced agrarian difficulties during a prolonged cooling, especially when considering that ergotism also has the potential of affecting livestock and wild deer. Depending on crop types and weather conditions, ergot may also have contributed to regional variability in societal impact from the cooling event.

2.3.4 THE JUSTINIANIC PLAGUE

The intimate relationship between climate cooling, famine, and epidemics in a number of well documented historical cases has led several researchers within both the humanities and geosciences to propose a connection between the AD 536/540 double event and the Justinianic Plague (eg. Büntgen et al., 2016; Gräslund & Price, 2012; Helama et al., 2018; Iversen, 2013, 2016; Oppenheimer, 2011, pp. 257-260; Sigl et al., 2015; Stathakopoulos, 2007). The Justinianic Plague was bubonic and caused by a biovar of the bacteria *Yersinia Pestis*, thus being related to the Late Medieval Black Death (Drancourt et al., 2004; Little, 2007; Ziegler, 2014). The Justinianic Plague broke out in the Egyptian port city of Pelusium in AD 541, and quickly spread throughout the Eastern Roman Empire (Little, 2007; Stathakopoulos, 2007). Numerous short-lived and localised plague outbreaks were reported until the middle 8th century. The plague struck several regions repeatedly at six to 20 year intervals, with a recorded total of 18 outbreaks from AD 541-750. As the first documented outbreak of *Yersinia Pestis* it is sometimes referred to as the 'First Pandemic' (Ziegler, 2014, p. 263), although several similar incidents are documented as far back as 5000 years ago (Little, 2007, p. 4; Rasmussen et al., 2015). Thus, the Black Death is understood as the 'Second Pandemic', whereas a modern 'Third Pandemic' ended sometimes during the mid-20th century (Ziegler, 2014, p. 260).

Although certain climate conditions have been linked to plague outbreaks in the past, a direct causal connection has thus far been difficult to prove. However, the contemporary presence of significant cooling and written evidence for famine and plague is indeed suggestive of a link (Sigl et al., 2015, p. 6).

Besides the importance of agrarian failure, Helama et al. (2018) argue that reduced solar radiation would result in lower Vitamin D levels, thus negatively affecting population health and increasing vulnerability to diseases.

Up until recently, contemporary written accounts represented the primary evidence. Details concerning the spread and intensity of past epidemics have therefore been limited to the spread of literacy, most importantly the presence of governmental and/or ecclesiastical structures in the Post-Roman world. According to historical records, the Justinianic Plague may have reached as far as Ireland (Dooley, 2007). However, the written records are not conclusive, and may indeed describe a broader range of disease outbreaks than just bubonic plague (Maddicott, 2007). Nevertheless, several archaeological studies have suggested that the disease reached as far north as the present-day Scandinavian countries (Gräslund, 1973; Helgen, 1977; Price & Gräslund, 2015; Seger, 1982; Solheim & Iversen, 2019). However, the assumption of a spread of the plague to Scandinavia is more or less based on a general decline in the number of archaeological sites and burials during the 6th century, and a general assumption that a bubonic plague, like the Black Plague, would have affected all of the Eurasian continent.

Although the available written and archaeological evidence may be ambiguous, aDNA analyses of human skeletal remains have proven the spread of the disease beyond the Alps, more specifically at several sites in France, southern Germany, and from evidence of the 6th-century cemetery at Edix Hill in England (Drancourt et al., 2004; Harbeck et al., 2013; Keller et al., 2019; Mordechai et al., 2019; Wagner et al., 2014). Pending confirmation, it is plausible that the plague may have reached beyond the borders of the former Roman Empire. Whether the plague outbreak had any major long-term impacts is currently subject to considerable debate (cf. Maddicott, 2007, pp. 212-214; Mordechai et al., 2019; Sessa, 2019). Documented, identified case numbers of *Yersinia Pestis* in 6th to 8th century human remains are still low, and mass/multiple burials, which are indicative of particularly high mortality rates, do not appear to have been a distinct feature of the period.

Based on historical accounts, it is frequently claimed that the plague caused the deaths of more than a third of the European population (for instance Harbeck et al., 2013; Wagner et al., 2014). However, this claim is not readily supported by physical and textual evidence (Sessa, 2019, pp. 234-237). Procopius' contemporary account from Constantinople is of particular importance in this regard, but is heavily coloured by his contempt for Justinian and the royal family. To Procopius, the plague plays a dramatic part in demonstrating the demonic rule of the emperor, and the godforsaken destiny of his subordinates (Cameron, 2005). Procopius' narrative was influenced by distinct stylistic and thematic frames that shaped

how events were recounted, in this case modelled upon Thucydides' description of the early antique epidemic in Athens. In their thorough critique of the maximalist approach, Lee Mordechai et al. (2019) have compared evidence from a wide range of historical, archaeological, paleo-botanical, and aDNA data, and conclude that the evidence fails to support claims of widespread disruptive mortality (see also Sessa, 2019, pp. 234-244).

In addition, the large death tolls ascribed to the Justinianic Plague often rest on comparisons with the Black Death, from which more textual and physical evidence is available (cf. Mordechai et al., 2019, p. 5; Sessa, 2019, pp., note 102). However, the two plague variants are not directly related, but share a common origin, and may therefore have had different attributes. Genomes isolated from late antique remains have no known descendants, meaning that it probably became extinct, as did many other strains of *Yersinia Pestis* (Mordechai et al., 2019, p. 6). This is in contrast to the Black Death variant, which is closely related to modern surviving strains of *Yersinia Pestis*, thus opening up for more direct knowledge on the attributes of the medieval plague. Whether the late antique biovar was equally lethal as the late medieval one remains uncertain.

John Maddicott (2007) regards the consequences the Justinianic Plague as rather short-lived, in particular for the decentralised societies of Northern Europe, as populations appear to have recovered quickly. Nevertheless, the plague would still have been experienced as horrific and apocalyptic by those who lived through it (Maddicott, 2007, p. 214). As such, the plague may still have had a considerable effect on society, in particular in psychological terms. In combination with climate cooling and the possibility of agrarian difficulties, it is also plausible that the plague had cultural and economic consequences. However, based on present evidence, it is heavily contested whether the mortality rates were comparable to those of the Black Death. As such, the levels of socio-economic and political consequences remain uncertain. Although it may have reached Scandinavia, the plague should perhaps not be given too much expressive force for the overall societal development at present state.

2.4 Discussion

The increasing amount of high-resolution climate proxies and climate modelling has allowed for a better understanding of the importance of explosive volcanic eruptions for the global climatic development, which, in turn, enables new insights into human-environmental interaction and the role of climate change in past societal developments. There is, however, a risk that increasing precision levels in geoscientific datasets and climate modelling may downplay the many contributing variables and uncertainties associated with the results. As stated by John Moreland (2018, p. 99, note 20), an apparent objectivity-

through-precision tends to camouflage the interpretative processes behind it, as exemplified by Baillie's (2008) reinterpretation of the Greenland ice-cores, and Dull et al.'s (2019; 2010) studies on the TBJ event in Meso-America. Baillie's conclusions were not founded on new proxies or re-calibrations of previous results, but instead on a critical assessment and rearrangement of published data.

The different calculations of eruption magnitude and climate impact should, in similar ways, be treated with caution, as the results vary according to the methods used and available data. As illustrated by the 1815 Tambora eruption, volcanic induced climate forcing is associated with considerable spatial diversity. A mean global climate cooling involves pockets of temperature anomalies, including heat and severe cold. Although it would increase agrarian vulnerability, climate cooling is not synonymous with failing crops, as seen in the example of Scandinavia in 1816. The underlying mechanisms are complex, and as such the climatic and societal consequences cannot be reduced to eruption magnitude. Seasonality and location are important factors, as are eruption type and injection height. External factors, in particular solar intensity, may reinforce or dampen the climate impact. Furthermore, social aspects such as economy, farming and subsistence strategies, public health, as well as stability or social unrest – i.e. the very socio-political context – influence how, and if, a climate crisis develops.

According to general consensus, the AD 536/540 double event stands out in a long-term climate perspective, since it even surpasses the climate outreach of the 1809/1815 events. The tree-ring evidence illustrates the exceptionality of the 6th-century cold period. There is, nevertheless, some disagreement regarding the duration of the climate cooling. Most researchers seem to agree on the notion that an exceptional cooling lasted at least until the 570s, while Büntgen et al. (2016) argue for a sustained summer cooling lasting well into the AD 660s, possibly reinforced by a third eruption in AD 547. The prolonged effects of the climate downturn may, nevertheless, be of regional rather than global character, as the tree-ring evidence is not fully conclusive. Helama et al. (2018) argue that the cooling itself was not the decisive factor, instead emphasising the consequences of reduced sun radiance due to the aerosol veil for photosynthesis and terrestrial growth, for which the solar minimum may also have played a considerable part. In this perspective, agrarian failure would be an equally important factor around the Mediterranean as in Northern Europe.

Although the 6th-century climate cooling may have been of more profound and spatially extensive character compared to the early 19th-century climate crisis, the simulations undertaken by Tooney et al. (2016) nevertheless display patterns of regional differences in climatic responses. The cooling seems to have been most significant in southern and central Europe, whereas the temperature decrease may have

been somewhat lower in Scandinavia. Newfield (2018) has also pointed out that the dendrochronological record is less conclusive regarding sustained climate cooling in Scandinavia when compared to the Alps and overall Northern Hemisphere time-series. This observation does not imply that cooling was less consequential for Scandinavian Iron Age societies compared to areas further south, as a slight decrease would still make up a larger portion of the annual heat budget, thus having the potential to severely affect the growing season. But, as seen in the Tambora event example, summer cooling and bad weather is not synonymous with agrarian failure since local environmental and social circumstances will affect possible outcomes. Furthermore, subsistence strategies may incorporate a wider range of categories than just agriculture, meaning that agrarian failure is not synonymous with societal failure. In order to thoroughly assess the consequences of the AD 536/540 events, more attention must be directed towards the archaeological record and the analyses of long-term cultural trajectories.

The possible social consequences of a climate downturn may have been reinforced by widespread bubonic plague and epidemic ergotism. The connection between environmental disasters, famine and epidemics seems to be a recurrent phenomenon throughout history and may equally apply to the 6th century climate cooling and the Justinianic Plague. However, there are several source-critical issues to consider regarding the extent and severity of the pandemic, which at present create substantial uncertainties regarding the plague's societal impact. Although a spread of the disease to Scandinavia is plausible, major consequences are still subject to substantial debate. Considerably more research on the plague impact factor is needed before firm conclusions can be made concerning its significance. This need for more research also applies to ergotism, although the evidence from Forsand strongly suggests that it may have been a crucial factor at least in the coastal areas of western Norway.

2.5 Chapter conclusion

As demonstrated in this chapter, considerable source-critical issues must be considered concerning the 6th-century cooling and its consequences. Important contextual factors are regionality, duration, and the interpretative processes behind geoscientific results. No linear relationship exists between eruption magnitude and the degree of climate forcing, nor on the degree of social impact. Multiple environmental and cultural factors are of importance to situational developments. Thus, the evidence needs to be contextualised, both in geoscientific and socio-cultural terms. In summary:

- Significant variations can be expected along both spatial and temporal scales
- The proposed significance of the Justinianic Plague remains highly contested and uncertain
- Whether or not the cooling had considerable societal impact must be analysed for each specific area or society in question

However, two important conclusion can also be reached:

- The cooling is likely to have reached around minus 2°C below the 1961-90 average in southern Norway during the AD 536-550 period, with minus 3°C representing a possible worst-case scenario in certain areas
- Secondary effects of the cooling, such as epidemic ergotism, might have reinforced a possible famine

3 THE CRISIS NARRATIVE IN SCANDINAVIAN IRON AGE ARCHAEOLOGY¹³

In the following chapter, I will discuss how crises have been discussed in Scandinavian Iron Age archaeology, with particular emphasis on the Norwegian discourse. The aim is to disentangle the underlying premises for the debates, and to identify main differences in interpretation, approaches, and choices of archaeological proxies.

However, the terminology itself is rarely defined in the literature, and the term ‘crisis’ is more commonly used as a colloquial reference rather than a defined interpretation of past conditions. The term ‘crisis’ is often associated with social unrest and warfare, but crisis may also be used to refer to a dramatic end of something, for instance the end of an era (Koselleck, 2006). A crisis, then, may simply represent a radical transformation. In Norwegian archaeology, discussions of the 6th-century crisis concern the character of change, whether it represents a continuation of Early Iron Age dynamics or something altogether different.

As will be demonstrated, debates surrounding the Fimbulwinter hypothesis have persisted for over a century since the Swedish palynologist Johan Rutger Sernander’s (1910) suggestion of a climate forced demise of Bronze Age civilisation. Both Sernander (1910) and Price and Gräslund (2015) propose a connection between a sudden prehistoric temperature decrease and changes in the archaeological record, and links are drawn to the Norse myths of the *Fimbulwinter* and *Ragnarok*. Although the interpretations have developed in step with new methods and proxies, the main arguments for and against the crisis narrative have nonetheless broadly remained consistent. To some extent, this consistency serves to illustrate how ideas and interpretations are recycled. One of the main challenges lies in the difficulties in developing a coherent approach, which can move beyond mere concurrency in selected datasets. The Fimbulwinter hypothesis has considerable potential to advance our understanding of the Early to Late Iron Age transition. However, its potential is hampered by the absence of clear analytical frameworks capable of substantiating the claim of widespread agricultural failure and population decline, leading to allegations of determinism and climate reductionism. At the same, critics of the crisis narrative often advocate multicausal frameworks that nonetheless are vaguely defined, and in practice often remain restricted to the social sphere (eg. Gudesen, 1980; Magnus & Myhre, 1976; Myhre,

¹³ An earlier version of this chapter has been published as a peer-reviewed article (Gundersen, 2019).

2002; Näsman, 2012). Despite considerable focus on climate in recent research, *de facto* human-environmental perspectives have thus far not developed within Scandinavian Iron Age archaeology.

3.1 The Fimbulwinter in early research

Sernander (1910) was the first to suggest that the Norse myths of the Fimbulwinter may have been related to climate change and actual prehistoric events. His pioneering works within paleo-botanical studies of bog deposits led him to identify a rapid climate deterioration at the transition from the Bronze Age to the Iron Age, followed by a long-term cooling in the Pre-Roman Iron Age. In this, he saw the breakdown of Bronze Age civilisation. The identification of climate change was a novel discovery for its time, as contemporary researchers considered climate to be stable and of little instrumental value for societal development (cf. Hassan, 2016, p. 39). According to Sernander, the rapid cooling was unparalleled in postglacial times and further characterized by a significantly wetter and colder climate, leading to higher lake levels and marsh and heath growth. Few archaeological finds and paleo-botanical evidence for reforestation reflected depopulation and agricultural decline, which may have caused mass migrations in the following centuries (Nordhagen, 1933, pp. 219-224; Sernander, 1910). The crisis was understood as a profound watershed moment in prehistory, thus heavily influencing the eschatological beliefs of the time.

Sernander's hypothesis had a significant influence on Norwegian prehistoric narratives (Holmsen & Straume, 1972, pp. 32-34). Although remaining inconclusive on the matter, Shetelig (1925, pp. 115-120) discussed whether the cooling caused societal decline and mass migrations in southern Norway, as well as a total depopulation of the northern parts of the country. However, Sernander's interpretations were also criticized for advocating near-apocalyptic scenarios which failed to take the long-term trajectories of the archaeological record into full account (Brøgger, 1925, p. 136; 1933, p. 28; Nordhagen, 1933, pp. 220-222, 233). In his influential work on the agricultural development in Norway, Hougen (1947, pp. 77, 104-105) argued for considerable spatial complexity and dismissed the idea of an all-encompassing societal crisis, and regarded it as an outdated interpretative framework. However, the general idea of climate-induced social change persisted, and Bjørn Hougen (1947) suggested that the cold period affected Scandinavian agriculture and farming techniques. Accordingly, climate deterioration resulted in indoor stalling of livestock in wintertime, which caused a need for fodder harvesting and storing. In this, Hougen (1947, p. 105) saw the initial abandonment of nomadic lifestyle and the establishment of the farm as a firm social and economic factor in Scandinavian prehistory – as the very foundation of Iron Age society.

Sernander's hypothesis was also challenged on the basis of dating the cooling event to the Pre-Roman Iron Age, as the absence of adequate dating techniques caused considerable uncertainties in this regard

(Solheim & Iversen, 2019, p. 430). The implementation of radiocarbon dating and increasing availability of archaeological and paleo-botanical datasets have since contributed to a more nuanced assessment of Pre-Roman Iron Age farming and environmental conditions (Gräslund, 2007, pp. 93-94; Hagen, 1967, pp. 162-163; Magnus & Myhre, 1976, pp. 215-217; Myhre, 2002, pp. 100-101; Solberg, 2003, pp. 50-51). A recent critique emphasizes the long-term cultural trajectories in the 1st millennium BC and argues against the notion of climate change as a driving force behind changing farming strategies (Pedersen & Widgren, 2011, pp. 48-49; Widgren, 2013, pp. 130-131). The climate deterioration appears to have been more gradual and not as sudden as previously assumed. Furthermore, the implementation of stalling and fodder harvesting follows a line of long-term agricultural innovation which, in a European perspective, pre-dates the Pre-Roman Iron Age cold period. The development seems to represent an intensification of livestock keeping and of the milk economy, including more effective use of cattle manure for infield cultivation (Widgren, 2013, p. 130). Gräslund (2007, p. 94) argues that the overall data suggest a Pre-Roman Iron Age settlement expansion, rather than decline. Although influential at its time, Sernander's hypothesis is mostly regarded as obsolete in modern research (Gräslund, 2007, pp. 93-94; Myhre, 2002, pp. 99-101; Pedersen & Widgren, 2011, pp. 48-49; Solberg, 2003, pp. 50-51; Widgren, 2013, pp. 130-131).

In spite of becoming a research historical footnote, Sernander's (1910) hypothesis still remains interesting, as it constitutes an important parallel to the current climate discourse in Scandinavian Iron Age archaeology (cf. Gräslund, 2007, pp. 93-94; Solheim & Iversen, 2019, p. 430). As with the modern Fimbulwinter hypothesis (cf. Chapter 2.3.1 and 3.3), it was initiated by a breakthrough in scientific methods, which generated new types of proxies and explanations for profound changes in the archaeological record. Furthermore, in terms of crisis and decline, climate change was considered as a major driver for societal change. The suggested causal link between climate and society was novel for its time, and challenged contemporary assumptions of a stable environment (see also Chapter 4). However, similar to other grand narratives, Sernander's interpretations were soon challenged by the complexity of the archaeological record, and the absence of a coherent analytical framework that could substantiate his claims of widespread famine and cultural collapse.

Comparatively less attention is directed towards the Pre-Roman Iron Age climate record in current archaeological research, but the general idea of a causal link between climate change and societal change has been firmly revitalized in recent years, due to the identification of the 6th-century cold period (cf. Chapter 2.3). However, the current discourse is firmly entrenched in a century-long debate on the character and importance of the Early to Late Iron Age transition, amongst which climate is merely the

latest in a long line of crisis hypotheses.¹⁴ In the following chapters, I will explore the crisis narrative in Norwegian Iron Age archaeology in order to disentangle the premises of the current Fimbulwinter hypothesis.

3.2 Norwegian archaeology and the 6th-century crisis

In this chapter, I will discuss the main outlines of the debate on the 6th-century transition in a research historical perspective. By doing so, I wish to demonstrate how the idea of crisis initially struggled with contrasting regional and temporal patterns in the archaeological record, and thus encountered difficulties with substantiating the suggested causal factors within a coherent analytical framework. This is not only reminiscent of the debate concerning Sernander's climatic explanations (Chapter 3.1), but is something which also continues to characterise the current debate (Chapter 3.3). Regarding the 6th-century transition, different explanations were repeatedly proposed, such as agrarian failure, trade disruptions, migrations, warfare, plague, and climate change, until possible contributing factors were combined under a vaguely defined multicausal framework which potentially could explain the ambiguity of the archaeological record. From the 1970s onwards, the suggestion of a 6th-century crisis was increasingly met with criticism, since more researchers advocated for patterns of continuity and social transformations founded in long-term socio-political developments.

3.2.1 A CENTURY-LONG DEBATE BEGINS

As early as 1906, the 5th to 8th centuries were recognized by Gabriel Gustafson (1906, pp. 67-96) as an important transitional period in Scandinavian prehistory, since this time frame encompasses several changes in craft and design that would later come to define Viking Age material culture.¹⁵ These changes were understood as particularly significant for the latter half of this period, which coincides with the current definition for the Merovingian Period. An important trait was also a general decrease of finds, which is in contrast to the richer archaeological complexes of the previous centuries (Gudesen, 1980, p. 11).

Important changes in the archaeological record, such as a reduction in numbers of finds, ceramics, changes to burial customs, ornamental style and weaponry, were recognized through numerous typological and chronological studies (Brøgger, 1925; Bøe, 1931; Gjessing, 1934; Grieg, 1918, 1920, 1923;

¹⁴ For a parallel debate in Swedish archaeology, see Näsman (1988a; 2009, p. 107; 2012)

¹⁵ Gustafson termed the 5th to 8th centuries as Migration Period and part of the Early Iron Age, see also Oluf Rygh (1999 [1885])

Hougen, 1936; Shetelig, 1912, 1925). While emphasizing continuity, G. Gustafson (1906, pp. 67-68) interpreted the changes in light of the continental geopolitical upheaval at the time, which resulted in cultural isolation, trade disruption, and considerable innovation and creativity in Scandinavian craft and design.

Gustafson's notion of cultural isolation was soon challenged by several studies. A characteristic feature of the Merovingian Period was the somewhat duplex nature of the archaeological material – characterized by local and regional distinctiveness on one side, and continental, Anglo-Saxon and East Scandinavian impulses on the other (Brøgger, 1917; 1925, pp. 212-217; Gjessing, 1934; Grieg, 1923; Hougen, 1936; Shetelig, 1925); a perspective that has recently been re-explored by Ingunn M. Røstad (2016). The contemporary ethnocentric perspectives played a rather marginal part in early Norwegian Migration Period and Merovingian Period research, as regional differences and supra-regional distributional patterns across modern borderlines challenged the contemporary nationalistic sentiments (Røstad, 2016, pp. 9-14).

Haakon Shetelig (1925, pp. 162-165), for instance, pointed out strong Migration Period cultural impulses from areas in modern day Germany, France, and England. A gradual shift towards western impulses in the later part of the period was, accordingly, reflected by the emergence of strong political entities in western Norway. Frankish-Merovingian impulses were evident in western Norway in the Merovingian Period as well, while Anglo-Saxon, south German and Langobardic impulses characterized eastern Norway and Sweden (Brøgger, 1925, p. 216; Shetelig, 1925, pp. 174-177).

Several researchers pointed out the rich 6th-century finds at Åker in the Lake Mjøsa region and the emergence of monumental burial mounds in eastern Norway (Brøgger, 1917, 1937; Gjessing, 1934; Grieg, 1918; Hagen, 1950; Shetelig, 1925). The so-called 'Åker-complex' was understood as an early state formation under influence from the Vendel dynasties in middle Sweden, thus reflecting a shift in the power balance from western to eastern Norway.

Shetelig's (1912, 1925) thorough typological and chronological studies of the Iron Age material represent a pivotal moment in the early research history of modern archaeology, and introduced the very concept of a 'Merovingian Period'¹⁶ to Norwegian archaeology. Shetelig (1925, pp. 173-177) pointed out that

¹⁶ Shetelig (1925, p. 173) set the transition date to AD 600, but which is now more commonly set around the middle 6th century (see for instance Axboe, 1999; E. Mikkelsen, 1973; Näsman, 2012)

cultural changes in the transition to the Merovingian Period not only represented a major development of Iron Age societies, but also a fundamental break with previous traditions and practices. His interpretations were highly influential and outlined the future premises for Merovingian Period research in Norwegian archaeology (Gudesen, 1980, pp. 11-16). The transition from the Migration Period to the Merovingian Period would also come to define the very transition from the Early to the Late Iron Age (Slomann, 1956, p. 64). Shetelig's hypothesis marked the starting point for a long-lasting debate that can roughly be divided in two interpretative frameworks; *crisis* or *a change of practice*.

Although important changes in the archaeological record were recognized, the main interpretative framework was, however, based on an essential notion of cultural and societal continuity throughout prehistory. This notion was, according to Lars Erik Gjerpe (2014; 2017, pp. 36-45) and Lars Pilø (2005, pp. 9-63), a characteristic feature for Norwegian archaeology in the Interwar Period and emerged from the 19th-century struggle for political and cultural independence (see also M. D. Amundsen & Fredriksen, 2014, p. 83; Grønnesby, 2019, pp. 31-40; Grønnesby & Heen-Pettersen, 2015, pp. 171-174). It furthermore developed into a distinct retrogressive method which sought to reconstruct prehistoric cultural traits on the basis of known historical conditions, resulting in ideas of structural continuity from modern and medieval farms, and reaching as far back in time to the initial colonization and cultivation. Early interpretations of the 6th-century transition must therefore be viewed against the contemporary historical and political background. Gjerpe focuses in particular on the works of Anton W. Brøgger (1925), but the basic notion of social and cultural continuity is also recognisable in Shetelig's (1925) narrative. The new cultural traits at the beginning of the Merovingian Period were, by Shetelig (1925, pp. 173-177), understood as a matter of new impulses and a change of practice. The hiatus in the archaeological record, particularly in western Norway, was neither understood as signs of crisis *per se*, but predominantly seen as a reflection of shifting power-balances and the emergence of stronger dynasties in eastern Norway.

To some extent, Shetelig's assessment of the Merovingian Period diverges from his discussion of Sernander's hypothesis (see Chapter 3.1). This is possibly due to the contemporary debate on when a proper Norse culture actually began. G. Gustafson (1906, p. 59, authors translation) argued that "True civilisation begins with Iron Age"¹⁷, whereas the Stone Age and Bronze Age were described as 'foreign'. This notion is also visible in Shetelig's (cf. 1925, pp. 119-120) writings, but he furthermore assessed the Pre-Roman Iron Age to share more parallels with the Bronze Age than the rest of the Iron Age. Finds are described as scattered and incoherent, and fundamentally different from later Iron Age material culture. 'Civilisation' is understood as an emerging concept during the first centuries AD and under the influence

¹⁷ "Først med jernalderen begynner den egentlige civilisation"

of the expanding Roman Empire. Shetelig (1925, p. 120) identified a fundamental break at the transition from the Pre-Roman to Roman Iron Age, which was of greater importance for the societal development in prehistory than the introduction of iron itself. Social and cultural continuity was, in essence, more of a defining aspect for the 1st millennium AD than prehistory in general. This notion was probably also central to how the Merovingian Period was assessed.

3.2.2 THE EMERGENCE OF CRISIS

While emphasizing continuity from the Early to the Late Iron Age, early researchers mainly interpreted the 6th century transition in light of the socio-political upheaval in Europe in the 4th to 5th centuries (Brøgger, 1917; Gjessing, 1934; Grieg, 1918; G. Gustafson, 1906; Hougen, 1936). Although Shetelig's writings are consistent with the research tradition of his time, his hypothesis of a fundamental break with Early Iron Age custom (Shetelig, 1925, pp. 173-177) nevertheless contested the notion of cultural stability. His observations are early indicators for future directions of the more crisis-oriented ideas that were to follow, which suggested demographic, ecologic or epidemiologic explanations (Brøgger, 1940; Helgen, 1977; Løken, 1988; Myhre, 1979; Møllerop, 1958; Petersen, 1954; Slomann, 1956). Brøgger (1940) was the first researcher to explicitly use the term 'crisis' to describe the widespread changes around the mid-1st millennium AD in the archaeological record.

The gradual shift in scope and interpretation was influenced by the increasing number of settlement studies during the first half of 20th century. The southern and south-western parts of the country in particular generated considerable evidence for settlement and agricultural expansion in the 4th and 5th centuries, followed by signs of abandonment and decline in the 6th and 7th centuries (cf. Kallhovd & Stylegar, 2014; Myhre, 1979, 1980; Myhre, 1982). Importantly, few traces of settlement continuity were identified. Other parts of Norway were less systematically investigated. Few, if any, Migration and Merovingian Period house remains had been documented in eastern Norway and the settlement development of the region remained unclear (Gjerpe 2016:40, 2017:31). All in all, the notion of crisis was, primarily, based on settlement data from southern Norway.

It should however be stressed that the idea of crisis was not understood in terms of collapse of Iron Age societies. On the contrary, crisis was assessed as an extremity which put the existing society under immense pressure. The disagreement was, in other words, not about cultural continuity in itself, but instead concerned whether or not a crisis could be detected in the archaeological record. Wencke Slomann (1956), for instance, recognised a major break in material culture in the transition to the Merovingian Period, emphasizing a significant decline in the number of finds and settlement sites.

However, abandoned farmsteads were not understood in terms of depopulation *per se*, but as a contraction of people and farms towards the traditional main settlement areas. Although a break in material culture was identifiable, the fundamental notion was nevertheless of societal continuity.

3.2.3 AN AGRICULTURAL CRISIS?

Several studies, especially in the post-war period, highlighted the Migration Period settlement expansion, believing that it led to overpopulation and subsequently to migration and the abandonment of non-favourable lands (e.g. Brøgger, 1940; Petersen, 1954). Farming was assessed as extensive in character and based on husbandry, which would eventually lead to overexploitation of the limited amount of cultivable land. Consequently, this would result in a shift to intensive farming techniques based on crop production.

Still, the even distribution of abandoned farms in south-western Norway, located in both central and marginal agricultural areas, led some scholars to a different conclusion, instead suggesting that the Justinianic Plague (see Chapter 2.3.4) must have been the main, or at least a contributing, cause to the decline, as it was more likely to affect all segments of society (Gudesen, 1980; Helgen, 1977; Magnus & Myhre, 1976, p. 405; Møllerop, 1958). Epidemic explanations are recurrent in the archaeological discourse up to this day (Bergstøl, 2008, pp. 199-200; Iversen, 2016; Solheim & Iversen, 2019).

Soil deterioration could still be an important factor, as fertilizing was believed to have been limited (Magnus & Myhre, 1976, pp. 403-406). However, later studies showed the importance of intensive cultivation techniques as early as the first centuries AD, involving systems of infield, outfield and mixed farming (Myhre, 1979, 1980, 1982). According to these studies, the extent of the 6th-century crisis could not be attributed to a limited farming strategy based on husbandry. However, as later excavations at Forsandmoen in southwest Norway would prove, intensive farming may also have contributed to society's vulnerability (Løken, 1988). The excavations provided evidence for soil deterioration due to long-term overexploitation.

Agricultural decline was not as evident in eastern Norway. Hougen (1947) identified a significant Merovingian Period agricultural expansion at summer farms in the lower mountain areas, which is testament to the continued importance of extensive farming and husbandry. The expansion was nevertheless understood as a response to the agricultural crisis suggested by Brøgger (1940). However, few excavations had been conducted at the time, and the study was therefore based on artefact studies and distributional patterns. A later study of select sites provided evidence for agricultural intensification

around AD 200-400, followed by decline and final abandonment around AD 800 (Pedersen, 1990), in parts mirroring the results from south-western Norway.

Due to the low number of settlement excavations, the pattern remained unclear in eastern Norway until the 1980s, when machine-assisted topsoil stripping was introduced (Gjerpe, 2016; Østmo, 1991). Recent excavations reveal the early existence of a mixed farming economy, involving systematic use of fertilizers, plaggen soil, fallowing, and rotational farming (Gjerpe, 2013; Gundersen, 2016d; Mjærum, 2012, 2020). A mixed farming economy is believed to have enhanced agricultural robustness and production, as it allows for a better integration between pastoral and arable farming, but also contributes to enhanced soil quality through more effective use of animal manure. These studies also support the view of an agricultural decline around the middle of the 1st millennium AD, but the present evidence seems to display a gradual and complex process that cannot be attributed to the AD 536 event alone (Gjerpe, 2013; Gundersen, 2016a).

3.2.4 TEMPORAL AND SPATIAL VARIABILITY

The concept of crisis was problematic for a few important reasons. Firstly, early studies of the 6th-century transition were characterized by limited archaeological data. Most studies in the interwar period were predominantly concerned with collected artefacts. Few studies incorporated a wider range of archaeological features, leading to simplified and generalized interpretations (Gudesen, 1980, p. 14). Furthermore, the idea of settlement decline was based on studies of limited geographical scope. The results from south and south-western Norway could not be supported by similar studies of other parts of the country. The evidence for a 6th-century crisis was not as prominent in eastern Norway, which was instead characterised by a more ambiguous pattern, involving varying reflections of continuity and crisis (Gudesen, 1980, pp. 141-143).

Growing archaeological datasets, regional studies, new methods and the recognition of considerable complexity in the archaeological record resulted in several critical reviews from the 1970s and onwards (Gudesen, 1980; Johansen, 1972; E. Mikkelsen, 1973). According to Arne Johansen (1972), the notion of a 6th-century crisis rested on aligning significant archaeological features with suitable dates in prehistory, thus causing a circular reasoning. This is particularly true for finds and sites which were not easily datable, and instead dated via precisely dated historical events. Due to the regional patterns of the archaeological

record, Egil Mikkelsen (1973) argued that the transition between the Early and Late Iron Age should be set to AD 550 in eastern Norway, AD 575 in middle- and northern Norway and AD 600 in western Norway.¹⁸

The 6th-century crisis could be regarded as a regional crisis in southern and western Norway (cf. Helgen, 1977; Løken, 1988), whereas other parts of the country seemed less prone to overexploitation (Myhre, 2002, pp. 170-179). This was particularly true for northern Norway, where the 6th century displayed little evidence for crisis or stagnation (Jørgensen, 1988; Vinsrygg, 1979). In other words, the notion of a 6th-century crisis was readily challenged by regional studies which displayed considerable spatial and temporal variability (a similar conclusion could also be reached at a Scandinavian level, cf. Näsman, 1988a, 1988b).

3.2.5 THE END OF CRISIS?

The growing awareness of the complexity in the archaeological record called for an explanation that combined a wide range of factors, such as plague, social unrest, warfare, soil deterioration, economic decline, and trade disruption as well as climate change (Gudesen, 1980; Magnus & Myhre, 1976; Myhre, 2002, 2015). These factors may have had different impacts on both regional and local scales, depending on the socio-cultural contexts of different areas.

The major societal changes of the 6th century were attributed to the emergence of new powerful dynastical elites, new ideologies and political reorganization, followed by a transformation of the cultural landscape. Accordingly, the lack of Merovingian Period settlements was seen not as a consequence of depopulation, but as a result of new societal and agricultural strategies (Myhre, 2002, pp. 180-213; Skre, 1998, p. 216). Later excavations of Merovingian Period settlements seem to support the idea of changing settlement patterns. Settlement continuity throughout the 6th century has indeed been documented at several sites (Bjørndal, 2016; Lund, 2008; J. Martens, 2007; Pilø, 2005), although in a lower number compared to the number of Early Iron Age settlements. Marginal and smaller farms appear to have been abandoned, whereas Late Iron Age farms are moved closer to historical settlements. However, the idea of widespread settlement abandonment may require further revision. Early interpretations of a 6th-century crisis were predominantly based on settlement surveys and excavations in southern Norway, amongst which Sosteli in Agder (Figure 3.1) has been particularly important. The excavation results suggested that the farm was abandoned at the end of the Migration Period (Hagen, 1951). However, later revisions of archival data provided contrasting results, indicating that the farm may have been in continued use up

¹⁸ Similar ideas have also been discussed by Slomann (1956, pp. 78-79)

until the 10th century (Jessen & Stylegar, 2012). The example of Sosteli demonstrates the challenges related to the older settlement record, as new methods and analyses may provide different answers and results than previous studies.

Figure 3.1: Excavated Iron Age farm building at Sosteli in Agder. Photo: Unknown, Museum of Cultural History (Cf.9506).

Myhre (2002, pp. 170-189; 2015, pp. 249-250) recognized the 6th century as a major transitional period, but concluded that the evidence for a crisis were scarce and incoherent. Agricultural crisis was certainly a factor in some areas, like Forsandmoen in the southwest (cf. Løken, 1988), but could not be applied to the country as a whole. On the contrary, the temporal and spatial complexity of the archaeological record suggested a gradual and asynchronous development, rather than single causes and events (Myhre, 2002, pp. 187-188; 2015, p. 250). Myhre (2002, p. 173) particularly focused on the archaeological record and palynological evidence from middle and northern Norway, which mirrored traits of continuity. Similar perspectives were also raised concerning Vestfold in eastern Norway (Myhre, 2002, p. 174; 2015).

The simultaneous emergence of monumental burial mounds and relatively low number of other graves reflected, according to Myhre (2002, pp. 182-189), profound changes in social status and juridical rights. Graves were seen as the privilege of free peasants, whereas low numbers or absence of graves close to

farms would indicate the presence of tenants or thralls (similar interpretations were also put forward by Skre (1998, pp. 44-56, 198-212)). In this Myhre saw evidence for increasing social and economic differentiation in society, which enabled a fundamental restructuring of settlement patterns and subsistence strategies. He concluded: "The idea of a 6th century crisis is about to become research history"¹⁹ (Myhre, 2002, p. 179, authors translation).

3.2.6 BACK TO START

Although few researchers would disagree on the importance of new dynastical structures and societal reorganisation in the Merovingian Period, one might argue that Myhre (2002, 2015) offered little explanation as to why change happened in the first place. Although Myhre argued that regionality would indicate multicausality, he directed less attention towards developing an analytical framework that could explain the temporal and spatial patterns or the importance of individual factors. Social change was understood in political and economic terms, as a process of increasing power accumulation within a small number of ruling dynasties, ultimately resulting in the petty kingdoms of the Viking era. Environmental factors, soil depletion, plague, crisis, and hazards were credited with little real explanatory force.

Myhre's narrative has also been criticized as neo-evolutionary, since continuity between different societal 'stages' of structural complexity are considered as fundamental to the prehistoric development (Grønnesby, 2019, pp. 44-45; Grønnesby & Heen-Pettersen, 2015, pp. 172-173). Patterns of discontinuity were understood as changes of practice and political reorganisation due to changing impulses and circumstances. The fundamental notion of continuity throughout prehistory, as outlined in early retrogressive archaeology, was thus developed further as an analytical model for assessing Iron Age social structure. Major changes in the archaeological record would, consequently, be interpreted as ongoing social processes towards increasing hierarchisation and social complexity.

Although Myhre emphasized societal continuity, it would nevertheless be an oversimplification to suggest that he failed to recognize settlement discontinuity (cf. Gjerpe, 2014, p. 65). His early works in particular both identified and emphasized breaks in settlement patterns (Magnus & Myhre, 1976; Myhre, 1979, 1982). Myhre's (2002, pp. 170-189; 2015, pp. 249-250) later critique of crisis-oriented hypotheses was not expressed within an explicit evolutionary framework, but instead empirical and source-critical. The disruptive patterns were not understood as profoundly different from continuity, but rather as parts of a necessary reorganisation that enabled further progress.

¹⁹ «Hypotesen om en krisetid mellom folkevandringstid og merovingertid er i ferd med å bli forskningshistorie»

Similar syntheses have also been put forward by other influential Scandinavian researchers. Herschend (2009, pp. 389-411) has described the changes towards the end of the Migration Period as almost revolutionary in character; not in terms of popular uprisings, but due to internal strife among different factions within the ruling class. Increasing stagnation, social crisis, and unrest resulted in great need of reform. Likely explanations are found in a collapsing world economy in the wake of the fall of the Western Roman Empire. According to Herschend (2009, p. 403), it made the symbolic investments of the traditional elites impossible, thus resulting in a loss of ideological legitimacy. This development was accompanied by changes in world view, warfare and social organization, which may have been influenced by the Hunnic warrior ideology of the 5th century (cf. Hedeager, 2011), and resulted in new dynastical and regional structures. In other words, the driving forces were first and foremost understood in economic terms (see also Herschend, 1980; Herschend, 1988). Particular focus has been placed on long-term dynamics, but progress has not necessarily been understood in directional terms. Herschend (2009, pp. 399-407) explains regional and local differences as a result of the resilience of older power structures and habitual patterns. The synthesis complements Myhre's (2002, 2015) interpretations, but also mirrors early retrogressive assessments of the 6th-century transition, as a phase of continuity and influenced by geopolitical events (cf. Chapter 3.2.1). Skre (1998) offers a similar interpretation but more strongly emphasises settlement continuity. Skre outlines a process of increasing dependency on wealthy landowners, resulting in a decreasing number of free peasants and the emergence of large dynastical estates. Thus, there is a development of growing social complexity and stratification that transcends the 6th-century transition, in which disruptive patterns in the archaeological record is briefly explained in relation to changing practices during the Merovingian Period. However, Skre (2019) have since revised his previous conclusions, and now credits the 6th-century transition with far greater importance for the development of Scandinavian Iron Age societies, including the development of ruler sites and political institutions.

As I have discussed in these chapters, there is little real disagreement on the elements of 6th-century change. While the patterns were recognised early on, the following debates concerned how it should be understood: as a reflection of crisis and social distress, or cultural innovation and a change of practice. However, even crisis-oriented hypotheses were still structured around a general notion of cultural and societal continuity, and the disagreement was therefore not profound. In fact, depending on perspective, one may argue that there is no real contradiction between interpretations of crisis and a change of practice in the first place. However, regardless of chosen perspective, the main challenge has been to construct causal explanations that could account for the complexity of the archaeological record. A multicausal framework has sometimes been called for, but analytical frameworks have still predominantly

focused on the social sphere, which makes it more difficult to define why exactly the 6th century stands out as a pivotal era. Because of this, interpretations still suffer from similar challenges as a century earlier. Multicausality remains vaguely defined and is not yet embedded in a coherent analytical framework that adequately considers the interaction, importance, and inter-dependency between human and environmental systems. To move forward, environmental factors must not only be taken into consideration, but also become firmly integrated in the analytical frameworks and given instrumental value.

3.3 The Fimbulwinter discourse

There has been a noticeable increase in archaeological literature over the last two decades which emphasise the role of climatic and environmental factors for past societal change. More focus is directed towards hazards and climate crises in connection to incidents of collapse of complex societies. In Scandinavia, the 6th-century cooling has gained considerable attention and represents a new environmental turn for Iron Age archaeology. This offers new possibilities to advance our understanding of the Iron Age dynamics, if embedded in a coherent framework that bridges social and environmental factors. However, the general absence of coherent methodology and analytical frameworks creates a risk of being unable to solve the same underlying problems which have 'plagued' 6th-century research so far. The Fimbulwinter discourse has mostly followed the same recurring patterns as similar debates over the past century (cf. Chapter 3.1 and 3.2). Regionality is for instance sometimes acknowledged, but is still not particularly well explained or understood. As with previous debates, critics tend to emphasise the long-term trajectories, whereas advocates have a similar tendency to focus on selected finds or assemblages, or emphasise the profound character of the 6th-century socio-political changes. In this chapter, I will discuss the many facets of the Fimbulwinter discourse, to disentangle the basic challenges and possibilities embedded in the idea of climate-induced social change during the 6th century.

3.3.1 INTRODUCTION

Stothers and Rampino's (1983) initial identification of the AD 536 event in written historical sources did not gain any immediate traction in the Humanities, until their interpretation was linked to dendrochronological records a decade later (see Chapter 2.3.1). The findings initiated a debate among classicists regarding the consequences for Late Antique society, which by some has been considered as a historical milestone, marking the beginning of the end for Antiquity (cf. Arjava, 2005, p. 74; McCormick et al., 2012; Moreland, 2018, p. 97; Sessa, 2019). The Justinianic Plague is particularly important in this respect, and is often believed to be related to the cooling event (see Chapter 2.3.4). As for Scandinavia, the issue was first discussed by Klavs Randsborg (1997), who saw an interesting concurrency between the

AD 536 event, the outbreak of the Justinianic plague and major archaeological changes at the transition to the Merovingian Period. However, his observations received little attention and played no part in the subsequent discourse. Interest only increased after Morten Axboe (1999, 2001) raised similar ideas, developed seemingly independently of Randsborg. Axboe's analyses combined the study of the numerous hoards containing gold bracteates in the early 6th century with evidence from tree-ring chronologies and the Norse myths of the Fimbulwinter and Ragnarok²⁰, and Axboe interpreted the hoards as sacrificial investments in times of crisis and social distress.

However, the lack of good internal chronologies for the gold hoards raises questions as to whether there is an actual increase towards the middle 6th century, or if hoarding may have ceased more gradually (Nielsen, 2005, p. 269). Karen Højlund Nielsen (2005, p. 278; 2006, p. 45) nevertheless considers the AD 536 event as a contributing factor to the political and cultural changes in Denmark in the 6th century, but which were only of temporary and limited character. Both Axboe and Nielsen are predominantly concerned with socio-psychological aspects of the climate crisis, such as distress caused by considerable optical illusions (see Chapter 2.1), and reject the idea of a societal collapse *per se*.

The idea of a 6th-century Fimbulwinter was mainly developed by Gräslund in his influential 2007 article, which laid the foundation for considerable interest on the AD 536 event among Scandinavian archaeologists. Gräslund (2007) elaborates on Axboe's ideas by compiling a wide range of archaeological, paleo-botanical, mythological, and historical sources in his analysis, but also by building on a previous hypothesis on the possible effect of the Justinianic Plague for 6th-century settlement disruption (Gräslund, 1973). Through detailed analysis of the Norse myths on Ragnarok and the Fimbulwinter – and the Finnish Kalevala – Gräslund identified tales of prolonged winters, cold summers, darkened sun and moon, and treacherous weather as optical and climatic effects of a volcanic aerosol veil. Gräslund furthermore suggests that the climate crisis not only affected Scandinavian Iron Age societies in eschatological terms, but also had a severe impact on society as a whole, and constituted one of the main driving forces behind the 6th-century transition. This initial hypothesis is further developed into a coherent synthesis in cooperation with Price (Gräslund & Price, 2012; Price & Gräslund, 2015), which eventually influenced several recent publications in the Nordic and Baltic countries (eg. M. D. Amundsen & Fredriksen, 2014; Arrhenius, 2013; Fredriksen et al., 2014; Iversen, 2013, 2016; Løken, 2020; Löwenborg, 2012b; Rødsrud, 2016; Skre, 2019; Solheim & Iversen, 2019; Stamnes, 2016; Tvauri, 2014; Zachrisson, 2011). It is important to note that few, if any, of these publications thoroughly discuss the geoscientific evidence for the

²⁰ A possible connection between the Ragnarok and the AD 536 event was also raised by Baillie (1999), but interpreted as a mnemonic remnant of a meteoritic impact.

cooling, and instead often rely on the interpretations provided by Gräslund and Price (2007; 2012; 2015), or the main conclusions in frequently cited geoscientific studies (eg. Büntgen et al., 2016; Toohey et al., 2016).

Following Axboe (1999, 2001), Gräslund and Price (Gräslund & Price, 2012; Price & Gräslund, 2015) hypothesise that the Norse and Finnish myths not only represent a collective memory of a short-term climate deterioration in the mid-6th century, but also of depopulation, distress and profound societal crisis. Price and Gräslund (2015) suggest, in reference to Dull et al. (2010), that the Fimbulwinter may have been caused by a massive tropical volcanic eruption at Lake Ilopango in El Salvador that, according to the authors, surpassed the total effect of Mount Vesuvius in AD 79, Krakatau in 1883, Mount St. Helens in 1980, Pinatubo in 1991 and Tambora in 1815. Of central importance to their claim is evidence for widespread deforestation, rising lake levels, growing marshes and heaths and agricultural decline throughout Scandinavia (cf. Berglund, 2003; Dörfler et al., 2012; Widgren, 2013). The low margins of agricultural resilience led, accordingly, to widespread famine and demographic recession – possibly reinforced by the Justinianic plague – leading them to suggest societal collapse and a population decrease of up to 50% in Norway, Sweden, and possibly Finland (Gräslund & Price, 2012, p. 440; Price & Gräslund, 2015, p. 127). A main argument is that Scandinavia, with its lower margins of agricultural resilience, would experience critical conditions during a cooling event. In Norway, the hypothesis has been most strongly advocated by Frode Iversen (2013, 2016), but has also been considered important by Trond Løken (2020) in his study of the Iron Age village at Forsand in south-west Norway, and by Skre (2019) as a contributing factor to the development of the dynastical power structures in the Early Merovingian Period.

3.3.2 JUST ANOTHER ‘GREAT DISASTER’ THEORY?

At first glance, the main characteristics of the Fimbulwinter hypothesis share a striking resemblance with Sernander’s (1910) hypothesis of a Pre-Roman Iron Age Fimbulwinter (see Chapter 3.1). In both narratives, rapid and unprecedented climate deterioration initiated a long-term cooling that resulted in increased humidity, agricultural decline, reforestation, and eventually population decline and societal crisis. It is, therefore, not surprising that the hypothesis of a 6th-century climate crisis has been assessed as a recycling of ‘old ideas’ on the importance of climate change for cultural change (Näsman, 2012, p. 5). The idea of a 6th-century climate crisis has, for instance, been viewed as ‘just another “Great Disaster” theory’ by historian Chris Wickham (2005, pp. 548-549 and note 50). Does the idea of a 6th-century Fimbulwinter have anything new to offer?

Differences in temporal resolution between the archaeological and geoscientific datasets are central challenges (Kristoffersen & Røstad, 2020). Archaeological chronologies are rarely at decadal resolutions, and are therefore not directly comparable to the annual precision provided in past climate reconstructions. This creates some uncertainties for the discussion of causal relationships. However, the discussion on chronological resolution is not decisive, as concurrency does not equal causation. Chronology is an important tool, but not an analytical framework in itself. To gap the divide between concurrency and causation, one must first attempt to understand the character of both the environmental and human datasets.

A main challenge with the interpretations put forward by Price and Gräslund (2015) is the absence of adequate levels of source criticism regarding the geoscientific data, leading them to adopt certain scientific figures without proper contextualisation or discussion. The maximum estimate of 160 Tg sulphur dioxide for the Lake Ilopango event (Dull et al., 2010) is for instance used to support the claim that the cooling must have been critical. The direct comparison to other known eruptions is used to substantiate their interpretations. However, as discussed in Chapter 2.1, there exists no direct one-to-one relationship between eruption magnitude and the spatial and temporal characteristics of the aerosol veil, let alone its temperature effect. Admittedly, some reservations are made (Price & Gräslund, 2015, p. 113), but not fully considered. Consequently, the many uncertainties regarding the eruption, both concerning the dating and eruption magnitude, are overlooked. The importance of this is illustrated by the later revision provided by Dull et al. (2019), but also the criticism published by V. C. Smith et al. (2020) which questions the very connection between the Lake Ilopango event and the 6th-century cooling. Although we can be certain that a cooling did take place (cf. Chapter 2.3.1 and 2.3.2), its exact attributes are a matter of interpretation and data selection, and the geoscientific conclusions should therefore not be treated as objective and fixed values. In order to avoid interpretation biases, the methodological challenges, and the 'spatiotemporal heterogeneity' of past climate change, must be taken into account (Degroot et al., 2021).

The use of geoscientific evidence in the archaeological literature is reminiscent of what Mike Hulme (2011) refers to as an "epistemological slippage", in which interpretations and conclusions are transferred from one academic domain to the other without adequate theoretical or analytical justification. It can also be understood as a kind of climate reductionism, since climate is isolated as the primary determinant for otherwise complex entities (Hulme, 2011, p. 253). Moreland (2018) convincingly demonstrates the deterministic perspectives prominent in several recent publications on the 6th-century cooling. The predictive authority of the geosciences, an apparent 'objectivity-through precision', opens up to uncritical use of data and interpretations, thus influencing our understanding of historical events (Moreland, 2018, pp. 99-100). The fields of geosciences can be easily related to as providers of 'hard' facts, high-resolution

datasets, and simulations, which, however, tend to camouflage the interpretative process behind it. The general absence of thorough analytical frameworks within Scandinavian Iron Age archaeology in the assessment of the role of climate in societal change, creates a certain risk of confusing concurrency with causation. Thus, the mechanisms of social change and adaptation remain poorly understood, leading to conclusions that are not adequately substantiated. For instance, Price and Gräslund's (2015, p. 127) suggestion of a halving of the population in present-day Norway and Sweden is not founded in a coherent methodology or analysis, but instead predominantly derived from the use of analogies, and through a general impression of overall trends in the archaeological and paleo-botanical datasets.

The use of analogies is particularly important for the crisis narrative, as textual evidence from around the Northern Hemisphere, in particular the Mediterranean and Post-Roman world, are used to substantiate claims of profound impact on the more marginal agricultural landscapes of Scandinavia (cf. Gräslund, 2007, pp. 101-106; Løken, 2020, pp. 286-288; Price & Gräslund, 2015, pp. 109-114). However, the use of analogies risk at becoming a highly selective search for examples that support the narrative. For example, in Løken's (2020, pp. 286-288) study, parallels are drawn as far afield as to the lowland Maya at the Yucatan, without making any attempt at demonstrating how, and why, the example is relevant to Scandinavian conditions, and in apparent unawareness of the fact that the lowland Maya may have been far more directly impacted by one of the eruptions than distant Europe (cf. Chapters 2.3.1, 5.3.2 and 5.4). Thus, the use of analogies may lead to a confirmation bias, rather than presenting a method for substantiating the interpretations of the Scandinavian trajectories.

Peter N. Peregrine (2020a) offers a more statistical approach, in which a social change index is compared to evidence for temperature change throughout the Northern Hemisphere, including examples from both southern Scandinavia and the lowland Mayas. His study suggests considerable differences in disaster impact after AD 536, which may be understood in terms of political robustness and character (Peregrine, 2020b). Despite Peregrine's deliberate distancing from using worldwide examples as mere analogies, and taking spatial patterns of cooling events into consideration, this study does not offer a coherent explanation for why temperature change should be considered as the main driver for identifiable social trajectories in the first place. No analytical tools are offered which would substantiate claims as to why climate cooling would have critically affected so highly diverse societies. As pointed out by Peregrine himself, the results do not support a presumed predictable pattern between climate change and social change, and which may suggest more complex causal relations (Peregrine, 2020a, p. 5). A statistical approach has also been employed by Steinar Solheim and Iversen (2019), who identified a Late Iron Age decline in the number of radiocarbon dates from archaeological sites in the country of Vestfold in Norway, which is used as proxy evidence for a considerable social impact from the 6th-century cooling

event. However, as with the study of Peregrine (2020a), a clear causal link is not substantiated, thus reducing the method to a mere question of concurrency (see further discussions on this area of study in Chapter 9.4).

In consequence, Moreland's (2018) criticism is understandable and remains valid, as it highlights some of the fundamental challenges with the current hypotheses. By and large we are talking about major events in the archaeological and geoscientific record taking place simultaneously, resulting in somewhat deterministic explanations that climate change must have been the main contributing cause (Degroot et al., 2021, p. 541; Gundersen, 2019, p. 110).

The current critique of the Fimbulwinter hypothesis not only concerns epistemological and methodological issues, but also the very character of the archaeological and historical datasets. Antti Arjava (2005) presents a thorough review of the Mediterranean historical sources that have been used to support the crisis narrative, but claims that little evidence for profound change is given, which may suggest that historical implications were rather limited. Arjava (2005) acknowledges the contemporary observations of a 'dust veil' and a darkened sun (see Chapter 2.3), but equally remarks that several other contemporary sources paid no attention to the phenomenon at all, although other remarkable events such as earthquakes, draughts, floods, plague, a comet, and a short solar eclipse are mentioned. He therefore questions the view that the event can be understood as a hallmark moment in Mediterranean history (Arjava, 2005, p. 84). Food shortages were a recurrent phenomenon throughout Antiquity, and the AD 536 event does not stand out as particularly evocative in the bigger picture (Arjava, 2005, pp. 92-93).

At first hand, Arjava's interpretations appears to be contested by later research, as his analysis is largely restricted to 6th-century sources. McCormick et al. (2012) instead employ a long-term perspective on the climatic and societal development in the Mediterranean during 100 BC-AD800, and identify a significant increase in famines and several incidents of extreme cold in written eastern Mediterranean sources during the first half of the 6th century that, in part, is attributed to the cooling event. However, it should be stressed that similar results could not be obtained for the western Mediterranean, although a few incidents of extreme cold have been reported. Only one incident of famine in the western Mediterranean is mentioned in their record, compared to eight incidents in the eastern Mediterranean (McCormick et al., 2012, p. 182, figure 6). The number of recorded famines, except for AD 525-549 in the eastern Mediterranean, remains rather stable throughout the 4th to 8th centuries (McCormick et al., 2012, p. 182, figure 6). Their analysis is, therefore, not directly contradicting Arjava's (2005) conclusions, as he emphasised the regularity and non-exceptionality of famines in the Greco-Roman world. Moreover, since

their data is organised in intervals of 25 years, it is less evident whether the recorded famines occurred before, during or after the cold phase.

McCormick et al. (2012, pp. 198, 202-203) suggest that the cooling led to a series of push-and-pull effects extending well beyond the eastern Roman borders, ultimately destabilising the economic and political structure of the empire. As such, climate conditions are attributed with considerable explanatory strength, eventually leading them to infer that the 6th century cooling was of greater significance for the decline of the Eastern Roman Empire than had been previously assumed. The rise in number of famines also led McCormick et al. to suggest a possible connection between the Justinianic Plague and nutritional difficulties. However, their narrative has been criticised for having a distinct eco-deterministic framework, where imperial expansion and contraction are explained by specific environmental circumstances and with little consideration of the social, economic and political dynamics of the Empire, or for the character of the textual evidence used as proxy data (Moreland, 2018, p. 97; Sessa, 2019, see also Degroot et al., 2021).

Criticism has also been raised against the mythological components of the Fimbulwinter hypothesis. In a recent paper, Mathias Nordvig and Felix Riede (2018) discuss the problems with combining 13th-century literary evidence with 6th-century archaeological records, and conclude that it cannot be decided whether the Norse myths of Ragnarok and the Fimbulwinter reflect actual past experiences, passed on as mnemonic mythological remains, or are instead entirely fictional dramas with Christian overtones. Furthermore, Nordvig and Riede point out several fundamental characteristics of the myths that seem to have more in common with the 10th-century Icelandic volcanic landscape, including the 934-940 Eldgjá eruption, than the attributes of the 6th-century cooling. Especially the Ragnarok sequences are characterised with imagery of fire, chaos, and crumbling mountains, whereas the details relating to the cooling event are inconsequential and minute, and may reflect phenomena experienced in a volcanic landscape (Nordvig & Riede, 2018, p. 317). However, a possible link to the 6th century cannot be categorically ruled out but is nonetheless viewed as less convincing than the 10th-century alternative. There is also the possibility that older myths may have been reshaped and adapted in face of new realities and experiences (Gräslund, 2007, p. 118), but this does not rule out the source-critical challenges when applying mythological accounts onto historical and archaeological events. On the contrary, a combined influence, of which both are related to the attributes of volcanic eruptions, makes it even more difficult to use the myths as points of reference for actual events. Baillie's (1999) interpretation of Ragnarok as resembling a meteoritic impact also demonstrates the ambiguity of the Norse myths, and the difficulties in attributing them with any direct historical relevance.

Concerning the Scandinavian archaeological record, Ulf Näsman (2012, p. 14) denounces the climate crisis perspective as inadequate for explaining the character and complexity of socio-cultural change in 6th-century Scandinavia. Näsman, in this particular case, is commenting on the work of Daniel Löwenborg (2012b), but the text can easily be read as a critique of the climate narrative as a whole (cf. Price & Gräslund, 2015, pp. 118-119). Löwenborg (2012b) analyses traits of discontinuity in settlement and burial sites in the Mälaren Valley area in Sweden in the context of socio-political theory, with particular reference to 'The Shock Doctrine' by Naomi Klein (2007), but also the medieval Black Death. In reference to how crisis and disasters have been exploited by competing groups of society, Löwenborg makes extensive use of analogies to support his interpretative framework. According to Löwenborg (2012b), the climate crisis was used by the elite as a catalyst for social stratification, through capitalising on the shock and social unrest caused by famine and decline. Fundamental for Näsman's critique are the many source-critical problems associated with pollen data and chronology, and finally the difficulties in assessing settlement and societal (dis)continuity from fragmented and spatially distributed archaeological data. Näsman (2012, p. 6) explicitly states that he sees no reason to revise previous conclusions (with reference to Näsman, 1988a, 1988b), consequently situating the current debate within well-established positions.

Näsman (2012, p. 14) nevertheless acknowledges the idea of a possible population decline, to which climate cooling may have been a contributing cause. His main argument is aimed against monocausal explanations, i.e. climate change as a single prime mover for societal change, and Näsman stresses the importance of complex models which incorporate local, regional and superregional perspectives. However, as with previous crisis critiques (cf. Chapter 3.2), the element of multicausality is only vaguely defined, and restricted to the social sphere. Change is predominantly viewed as a matter of cultural orientation, or due to necessary intensified resource exploitation. Even his assessment of the agrarian history of Denmark is preoccupied with economic, organisational, and practical measures (Näsman, 2009). Almost no references are made to climatic conditions, despite being fundamental to any form of cultivation. Thus, environmental factors are not attributed with any real instrumental value, and the debate has the characteristic traits of being at an intellectual standstill. In his reply, Löwenborg (2012a) very briefly touches upon these fundamental challenges to the Fimbulwinter discourse by suggesting that resilience theory may represent a way forward (with reference to Gunderson & Holling, 2002; Redman, 2005). Although I will not go into details on resilience theory in this chapter (see Chapter 5 for further presentation), I want to briefly point out that resilience theory is explicitly aimed at constructing a coherent model for human-environmental interaction, in which cultural and political trends are understood as incorporated and channelled through social responses to crisis. However, a human-environmental path has not yet been fully explored in relation to the 6th century in Scandinavia, and the debate continues to revolve around the old dichotomy between crisis and a change of practice.

The general lack of environmental perspectives is noticeable also in Herschend (2009). He recognizes the explanatory force of the AD 536 event but makes a strong point in arguing that stagnation is a long-term phenomenon that overrides the temporary effects of climate crisis. Herschend rejects neither catastrophe nor ongoing changes in human practice, as he considers these more or less apparent oppositions as two sides of the same coin (Herschend, 2009, p. 288 and note 234). The environmental crisis is not understood to be without consequences for Iron Age society, but he argues that the main reasons and driving forces behind societal change must be analysed within a social and economic framework. Thus, as in Myhre (2002, 2015) and Näsman (2012), the environment remains somewhat detached from Herschend's interpretative framework. There is no disagreement on the climate event itself. The 6th-century cooling itself remains a widely used point of reference, but its role and impact are not yet fully understood.

An interesting case study is the Helgö cult site in the Lake Mälaren area, middle Sweden, which changes character towards the end of the Migration Period (Arrhenius, 2013). The comprehensive Migration Period casting of bronze artefacts came to an end, and rituals changed from outdoor sacrifices to indoor rituals in a large hall. Furthermore, cemeteries are established, indicating the presence of permanently settled inhabitants. Birgit Arrhenius (2013) interprets the changes in light of the Fimbulwinter hypothesis, but stresses that the crisis may have been short-lived, as the Merovingian Period is a flourishing period at Helgö. Arrhenius nevertheless regards the climate cooling as a memorable disaster and suggests that the new practice of using bread as burial gifts may infer failing crops and famine, and reflect an increased importance of bread.

As in previous debates (cf. Chapter 3.1 and 3.2), regional and local variations in the archaeological record are a recurrent argument in criticism of the Fimbulwinter hypothesis. In Sweden, it is highly debated whether the suggested crisis struck all parts of the country with the same force (Pedersen & Widgren, 2011, p. 61). Regionality is, however, also recognised as a key element for understanding the impact of the 6th-century climate crisis. Price and Gräslund (2015, p. 119) argue for a considerable socio-cultural impact but reject the notion of the climate event as total explanatory factor. Their interpretative framework can be characterised as an assessment of the climate crisis as a *catalyst* for human change, rather than the *cause* itself. Thus, Price and Gräslund aim to bridge climate perspectives with the criticisms raised against previous suggestions of a societal crisis. Accordingly, the social transformations followed a long-term trajectory that began a considerable time prior to AD 536, but it is pointed out that this earlier onset does not mitigate against the idea of the climate crisis having a profound impact. Many of the arguments made against the Fimbulwinter hypothesis are, in the words of Price and Gräslund (2015, p. 119), "... essentially a matter of degree and emphasis". In his initial paper, Gräslund (2007, p.

112) briefly discusses aspects of regionality within Scandinavia, which may suggest that differences in subsistence strategies caused varying levels of vulnerability to cooling. Unfortunately, this aspect of the Fimbulwinter hypothesis is currently under-explored, but represents an essential research question when attempting to assess the impact of climate cooling on society: firstly, how substantial was the dependency on agriculture in the first place, and secondly, what are the agrarian thresholds for the areas in question? To move forward, a more coherent analytical framework must be developed which moves beyond mere concurrency. Consequently, to discuss agricultural vulnerability to climate cooling becomes of substantial importance to understanding the human-environmental dynamics in play (Widgren, 2013).

3.3.3 AGRICULTURAL VULNERABILITY

The idea of population decline rests heavily on the paleo-botanical evidence for reforestation and fallowing, although it should be stressed that several of the cited studies are of considerable age (cf. the referred studies in Berglund, 2003, p. 9; Gräslund, 2007, p. 110; Gräslund & Price, 2012, p. 431; Tvauri, 2014, pp. 35-36). As Näsman (2012, pp. 12-13) points out, the pollen records are associated with varying degrees of uncertainty, as pollen cores first and foremost reflect local past vegetation covers and often are imprecisely dated (see also Chapter 6.2 for a discussion on the pollen records). However, Price and Gräslund (2015, p. 115) argue that clear support for reforestation has also been provided by recent studies (with reference to Dörfler et al., 2012; see also Tvauri, 2014, pp. 35-36). The interpretations are further strengthened by correlating results across Scandinavia and central Europe. However, important local and regional diversity are reflected in the pollen diagrams, in particular in examples of increased human influence on the landscapes, for instance in central Uppland in Sweden and coastal Vestfold in Norway (Høeg, 2004; Myhre, 2015, pp. 103-108; Pedersen & Widgren, 2011, p. 61).

Mats Widgren (2013) stresses the importance of long-term perspectives and agricultural vulnerability as key components to understanding the different levels of societal impact across Europe, thus criticizing eco-deterministic frameworks in past disaster studies. By drawing on Näsman (1988a, 2012) and Herschend (2009), Widgren argues that the 6th-century crisis was not a sudden crisis, but continued an ongoing process which originated in the 3rd and 4th centuries. By stressing the social aspects of environmental crisis, he regards the 6th-century cooling as a catalyst rather than the cause itself. Evidence for considerable settlement and agricultural expansion in the Roman Iron Age and Migration Period is important, since landscape exploitation may have intensified beyond sustainable levels. According to Ellen Anne Pedersen and Widgren (2011, pp. 61-62), the subsequent decline is particularly evident in the areas of Sweden which experienced the greatest expansion. In their view, the most probable explanation lies in shifting power balances that affected surplus production and settlement density. For Danish areas, Näsman (2009, p. 107) explains the changes as means of streamlining the agricultural production, in order

to increase the output and meet the increasing need for resources. The introduction of the infield/outfield system made extensive farming practices of the preceding periods redundant. There is, in other words, little disagreement on the process of widespread landscape reorganisation in Scandinavia around the mid-1st millennia AD, although the causal explanations vary considerably.

It has been pointed out that middle and northern Scandinavia had lower margins of agricultural resilience, since these regions are situated along the liminal zone for crop production in Europe, and therefore at greater vulnerability to climate cooling (Gräslund, 2007, p. 115; Price & Gräslund, 2015, p. 127; Toohey et al., 2016). Stamnes (2016) explores agricultural vulnerability in relation to the 6th-century cooling in northern Trøndelag, middle Norway, by using geostatistical modelling and analysis. By reducing the average temperature by -1 °C and -3,5 °C (w.r.t. 1961-90), he concluded that even small changes in the average summer temperature may have had large effects on crop production (Stamnes, 2016). His results are interesting, considering Myhre's (2002, p. 173) reference to middle Norway as one of a few regions displaying clear evidence for continuity throughout the 6th-century transition. It has, however, been argued that the agricultural data from middle Norway is limited and not conclusive (Ystgaard, 2014, p. 286). Whether it reflects a crisis, or not, is therefore contested.

Bondeson and Bondesson (2014) place particular emphasis on the possible importance of epidemic ergotism (Chapter 2.3.3), by comparing ergotism to the bubonic plague in the context of mortality rates. Bondeson and Bondesson also argue that some passages in the Norse myths of the Fimbulwinter may reflect distant memories of epidemic ergotism.²¹ The general preconditions for food poisoning by ergot – ideal weather, the fungus itself, and vulnerable foodstuffs – all coexisted in Scandinavia in the mid-6th century. Ergot is closely related to environmental conditions, as it is affected by temperature, humidity, and geology, and might therefore have contributed to the regional and local differences in the aftermath of AD 536 (Bondeson & Bondesson, 2014, p. 65). For instance, the differences in precipitation levels between western and eastern Norway are considerable (cf. Chapter 6.5.1), which is likely to affect the spread of ergot. The cooling event itself may also have contributed to different regional patterns of agricultural vulnerability to ergotism, as it seems to have caused drier conditions in parts of Europe (Chapter 2.3.3). Thus, the epidemic effect can be expected to have varied considerably from place to place. The importance of ergotism can, however, be debated, as rye crops only seem to have played a minor part in Early Iron Age agriculture in Scandinavia, with the possible exception of southern Scandinavia, and rye only became more prevalent in the Late Iron Age (Myhre, 2002, pp. 137-143, 314-

²¹ 'On unsown acres the ears will grow, all ill grow better' and '...wolf age ere the world crumbles...', both from *Völuspá* (as cited in Bondeson & Bondesson, 2014, p. 64, based on the Icelandic Codex Regius). Accordingly, the wolf is understood as a symbolic embodiment of ergotism in ancient times.

326; Pedersen & Widgren, 2011; Robinson, Mikkelsen, & Malmros, 2009). Ergot also affects other cereal types, but it is far less common. The scarcity of data on prehistoric ergot adds to the uncertainties concerning the importance of ergotism, although it cannot be ruled out as a possible contributing factor to the societal impact of the cooling event. It is also important that ergot can affect livestock and wildlife (Chapter 2.3.3). However, considering that patterns of regionality can be expected, without access to high-resolution climate reconstructions for Scandinavia, and more direct evidence for widespread presence of ergot, it is difficult to assess its importance.

However, societal dependency on crops is rarely analysed, nor how different farming strategies would affect agricultural vulnerability to climate change. Cereals have different requirements and are thus not affected equally by climate change. A mixed farming economy, in which a closer interaction between pastoral and arable is achieved, is believed to have been gradually introduced during the 1st millennia BC, and increased in importance during the Iron Age (Mjærø, 2020; Myhre, 2002, pp. 137-141; Pedersen & Widgren, 2011, pp. 46-47). The development led to more emphasis on fodder harvesting for livestock keeping, but also resulted in more efficient resource exploitation (Myhre, 2002, p. 199; Näsman, 2009, p. 107; Pedersen & Widgren, 2011, pp. 68-70). The importance of livestock versus crops is difficult to identify from the archaeological record alone, but large livestock dependency is likely to have decreased societal susceptibility to climate change and weather phenomena, whereas mainly crop producing farms would be highly vulnerable. Leaves and unripened grains can be cut green and used for animal fodder (Gjerpe, 2017, pp. 200-201; Sveinsson & Hermannsson, 2017, p. 9). A society based more on outfield- and marine resources, and less on crop production, would equally be less affected by crop failure than agrarian-dependent communities, as it is also suggested by Gräslund (2007, p. 112) concerning northern Norway, and by Markku Oinonen et al. (2020) for the Levänluhta people of western Finland. Agrarian failure is, therefore, not synonymous with societal collapse, if other means of subsistence are present and utilised. When assessing the possible societal consequences of climate change, it is of vital importance to employ a broader approach to subsistence strategies.

3.3.4 SETTLEMENT REORGANISATION

Evidence for settlement reorganisation across Scandinavia is a recurrent subject of debate regarding the Early to Late Iron Age transition (Herschend, 2009; Myhre, 2002; Näsman, 2012; Price & Gräslund, 2015). Once again, the disagreement is not on the phenomenon itself but on how it should be understood.

Of great importance are the numerous settlement sites in Norway and Sweden that have been uncovered by machine-assisted topsoil stripping during the last decades, resulting in a new empirical body which had

not been previously studied in this context (Gräslund & Price, 2012, p. 432; Iversen, 2013; Price & Gräslund, 2015, p. 118). In the following text, I aim to discuss some of the main overall patterns, and how these relate to the Fimbulwinter discourse.

Attention has been directed to the evidence for large-scale reorganisation at the end of the Migration Period documented in the Uppland area of middle Sweden (Göthberg, 2007; Göthberg & Sundkvist, 2017). The settlements are reorganized around the best land in locales which would later become historical farm plots, creating larger settlements and production units. Both Löwenborg (2012b) and Zachrisson (2011, 2017) argue for a redefinition of property rights in the aftermath of the AD 536 event, which resulted in the accumulation of land within a small number of powerful families. Similar ideas have been brought forward in a study of abandoned Early Iron Age settlements in Rogaland in south-west Norway, where Late Iron Age graves seem to be used as markers for property rights (B. I. Dahl, 2016).

The development in Uppland is closely associated with the emergence of a monumentalised landscape around the Late Iron Age magnate complex at Gamla Uppsala (Ljungkvist & Frölund, 2015; Pedersen & Widgren, 2011, p. 61). However, the process has been described as a gradual transformation between the 4th and the 7th centuries, with the 5th and 6th centuries being the most decisive (Göthberg & Sundkvist, 2017; Ljungkvist & Frölund, 2015). The late 6th century represents a period of high dynamic activity, including large investments in monumental burials and constructions. Discovery of several Late Iron Age houses and farm units are interesting, especially when seen in contrast to older settlement records from the area. Hans Göthberg and Anneli Sundkvist (2017, p. 23) explain the discrepancy between the older and newer record in relation to choice of archaeological methods and changes in Iron Age architecture. The three-aisled longhouses cease to be the dominating building type, and are increasingly replaced by more varied and smaller houses where the walls carried the full weight of the roof. Hearths are less frequently identified, whereas artefact finds in the top-soil become more common. Thus, Late Iron Age houses can be more difficult to find, especially if metal detecting is not systematically employed prior to top-soil stripping. Architectural changes show that stalling and other functions were separated from the dwelling-house, and relocated to specialised buildings (Pedersen & Widgren, 2011, p. 69). Whereas Early Iron Age settlements were scattered in the terrain, and characterised by a certain level of mobility, the Late Iron Age is defined by higher settlement concentrations in the vicinity to the monumental burial mounds at Gamla Uppsala. The broad socio-economic changes evident at Gamla Uppsala are perhaps best explained in light of the emergence of powerful dynasties, who exercised their power through a visual reorganisation of the landscape (Ljungkvist & Frölund, 2015).

As in Uppland in Sweden, the reorganisation of the settlement landscape in Rogaland also seems to be less clear cut than previously assumed (cf. Myhre, 1979, 1980, 1982), since new settlement data suggest a gradual process of radical reorganization of the cultural landscape that lasts well into the Viking Age (cf. Bjørdal, 2016). As with Gamla Uppsala, more recent excavations have resulted in a considerable increase in Late Iron Age settlements. The largest group of the newly discovered settlements has occupation phases in the Merovingian Period, but only a few sites show continuity throughout the 6th century. Viking Age farmsteads are rarely found on the same sites as Early Iron Age settlements, and there seems to be a change in settlement layout between the Early and the Late Iron Age. Thus, a major reorganisation of the landscape appears to have taken place gradually and over a considerable timespan. However, patterns of crisis are more evident at the Forsand complex in Rogaland, where a large village complex was abandoned around the mid-6th century AD (Løken, 2020).

A long-term process also seems to have occurred in Denmark. According to Nielsen (2005, 2006), this process can be detected as considerable mobility in settlement structure in Denmark from the Migration Period to the Merovingian Period, since many old settlements were abandoned and new ones established. At Funen, villages appear to have been reorganized sometime around AD 600, when the settlement pattern changes from dynamic and conglomerate farm-structures into fixed village formations (Hansen, 2016). As with Uppland in Sweden, there is a considerable increase in metal detector finds from the Late Iron Age and Middle Ages. The 3rd to 6th century is a period of population growth and innovation, including the introduction of rye, thus mirroring the evidence for settlement expansion in Norway and Sweden around the same time (Myhre, 2002, pp. 127-159; Pedersen & Widgren, 2011, p. 56). The structure established around AD 600 constitutes the main settlement outline maintained up to the 19th century, which is reminiscent of similar conclusions reached for the Borre area in coastal Vestfold in Norway (Myhre, 2015, p. 105). In this, Jesper Hansen (2016, p. 23) identifies a development comparable to the one documented in Uppland.

Nielsen (2005, 2006) points out that there is a slight decrease in the number of Danish sites, but also considerable regional variation and little evidence for an overarching decline. The process is enforced during the following centuries and reaches a climax at the transition to the Viking Age, which might indicate that climate change is not the major driving force behind the process. Nielsen (2006, p. 41) defines the period from the beginning of the Migration Period to the end of the Viking Age as one long transition. However, the 6th century is attributed with significant importance in this matter, as it marks a watershed moment in the overall development towards the Viking Age society. Others have traced the roots of Late Iron Age societal structure back to the Late Roman Iron Age, when important changes in

settlement organisation point towards the emergence of property rights and increasing social stratification and societal reorganisation (Hedeager, 1992, pp. 226-228; Herschend, 2009, p. 393).

A large number of excavations in southern and eastern Norway have also resulted in new insights into the settlement and agricultural history of the region (eg. Gjerpe, 2010; Gundersen, 2016e; Helliksen, 1997; Skre, 1998). At first glance, the evidence seems to strengthen the idea of settlement abandonment in the 6th century. In reference to the Swedish settlement record, Iversen (2013, 2016) suggests that climate crisis, plague and depopulation led to large scale division of farmland into smaller production units, due to a lack of farm labourers that could maintain production levels at the larger estates. Surviving estates would, however, benefit from the crisis and give way for new dynastical structures in the Merovingian Period. Accordingly, the climate crisis therefore resulted in both new powerful elites and a large group of independent peasants. Iversen's interpretations are based on a quantitative analysis of excavated settlement sites and toponomy, which indicates a significant shift in the 6th century. However, the hypothesis has been thoroughly criticized for its distinct retrogressive framework and methodology, thereby downplaying important long-term political, cultural, and structural trajectories pre-dating the crisis (M. D. Amundsen & Fredriksen, 2014, p. 83; Gjerpe, 2014; 2017, pp. 45-47). There is also an absence of comprehensive settlement data from southern and eastern Norway, dated to the Late Iron Age, which can be used to support the idea of estate division and smaller production units.

It may also be questioned whether the settlement development in eastern Norway follows the same pattern over the whole area, or displays traits of regionality (which would be in accordance with Gudesen, 1980). Recent excavations of agricultural and settlement sites in the Gudbrandsdalen valley might, for example, support the notion of settlement reorganisation, due to a combination of environmental and cultural causes (cf. Gundersen, 2016a). The Lake Mjøsa region, on the other hand, has traditionally been viewed in terms of stability and prosperity in the 6th century (Brøgger, 1917; Hagen, 1950; Røstad, 2020; Shetelig, 1925; Solberg, 2003, p. 198), which seems to be supported by settlement excavations around the lake (cf. Loktu & Hovd, 2014; Pilø, 2005).²² Although large-scale abandonment is evident in southern and eastern Norway through quantitative analysis (Iversen, 2013), in-depth studies display several regional characteristics, adding complexity to the overall development.

Gjerpe's (2017, pp. 191-204, 222) recent assessment of the settlement data from eastern Norway arrives at similar conclusions. He emphasizes the complexity of the archaeological record and the importance of

²² See chapter 8 and 9 for further discussions on the settlement data in Gudbrandsdalen valley and Lake Mjøsa region

long-term perspectives, as important development traits appear to start prior to the 6th century. Accordingly, the settlement reorganisation began as early as the 5th century and reflects a gradual development of permanent farmsteads, as opposed to the more collective and mobile character of the settlement structure in the Early Iron Age. His interpretations are supported by recent excavations in middle Norway, which indicate a break in settlement patterns (Grønnesby & Heen-Pettersen, 2015). According to the study, the farm as a permanently located social, political and economic entity, is first established in the Late Iron Age (see also Grønnesby, 2019). The interpretations contest previous notions on settlement continuity in middle Norway, as suggested by Myhre (2002, p. 173), and are reminiscent of the processes documented for Funen and Uppland.

Gjerpe (2017) argues that the process is a consequence of increasing competition for cultivable lands and culminates in a firm consolidation of farm boundaries and property and hereditary rights in the Late Iron Age. The end of Early Iron Age settlement structure is therefore understood as a consequence of ongoing social processes, but he furthermore suggests that the 6th-century cooling may have influenced the Late Iron Age turn of events (Gjerpe, 2017, pp. 194-200). By drawing on Löwenborg (2012b) and analogies to the late Medieval *Black Death*, Gjerpe suggests that a power vacuum in the aftermath of the crisis may have opened up opportunities for upstarts and surviving members of the old elite. Abandoned and unclaimed land could be acquired, possibly through force, as former collective and social principles diminished due to societal collapse. In other words, lawless conditions enabled an even greater accumulation of land divided between few, but powerful, families. The climate crisis is, consequently, attributed with a considerable explanatory force for understanding how society developed throughout the Late Iron Age, but Gjerpe nevertheless points out that the main causes are to be found in the choice of agricultural strategies of the Late Roman Iron Age and Migration Period.

An interesting case study from the mountain summer farm Kalvebeitet in Western Norway suggests that the site may have been abandoned in response to the 6th-century climate crisis, but the burning and clearing of the site is interpreted as a planned and organised process (M. D. Amundsen & Fredriksen, 2014). The organised abandonment of Kalvebeitet raises questions concerning how the AD 536 event was experienced by contemporary society, whether as a sudden or gradual decline, but also touches on the connection between psychological distress and human behaviour during times of crisis. It may, however, be debated whether the site was abandoned due to climate change or a Migration Period stagnation, as outlined by Herschend (2009), since the available radiocarbon dates have rather large inaccuracies (cf. M. D. Amundsen & Fredriksen, 2014, p. 85).

As demonstrated in this short review of the settlement record, significant societal reorganisation is evident throughout Scandinavia, but the causal relation to the 6th-century cooling remains disputed. Several researchers have highlighted the long-term trajectories of the era, which seem to support the idea that the process originated earlier than the 6th century, in some cases perhaps as early as the Late Roman Iron Age. However, the 6th-century cooling is rarely ruled out as a contributing factor, as the development seems to have been reinforced during the Early to the Late Iron Age transition. As will be discussed in the next chapter, this narrative is recognisable also in a number of other archaeological studies.

3.3.5 A LONG-TERM TRANSITION

Important changes have been documented around the mid-6th century in a wide array of archaeological categories, such as pottery, dress code, weaponry and food practice, although the evidence may suggest a more gradual process as opposed to a sudden and disruptive change of events.

Of the four above-mentioned categories, ceramics are often considered as particularly evocative, since ceramic finds do not simply change, but instead almost disappear from the archaeological record. Nevertheless, three recent studies highlight the underlying long-term processes (Fredriksen et al., 2014; Fredriksen, Rødsrud, & Caruso, 2020; Rødsrud, 2016). In south-western Norway, important changes in pottery use and production are evident during the 4th and 5th centuries, including an end to household production. The production of black ware ceramics ceases during the late 5th century, while the production of bucked-shaped pots continues, in combination with metalworking, in highly specialized workshops until the end of the Migration Period (Fredriksen et al., 2014). This implies clear traits of fundamental changes to the use and social significance of pottery production prior to the 6th century, in which social distress during a climate crisis may have been instrumental to the abandonment of the specialised sites, but not the cause for the decline itself. However, a recent study on the specialised production site of Augland in southern Norway has led to a revised dating of its abandonment, which is adjusted from the 6th to the 5th century (Fredriksen et al., 2020). The re-interpretation strengthens the assumption that the process, first and foremost, should be understood in a socio-economic and geo-political perspective.

In eastern Norway, a limited number of ceramics continue to appear in archaeological contexts throughout the 6th century (Rødsrud, 2016). Only few vessels have been found and the ware is both coarser and thicker than earlier designs, reflecting the overall decline in pottery production. The possible impact of AD 536 is anyhow somewhat less evident than in western Norway, although it should be

mentioned that the vessels have also been interpreted as foreign handicraft and not rooted in domestic Migration Period traditions (Bøe, 1931, pp. 234-237; Slomann, 1956, p. 78).

The gradual decline in pottery use and production coincides with overall changes in food technology. Cooking pits, for instance, are extensively used in the Early Iron Age, peaking around the 3rd to 5th centuries, with sporadic use in the Late Iron Age (Bukkemoen, 2016; L. Gustafson, 2005b; Ødegaard, 2019). A quantitative study of cooking pits in eastern Norway displays clear traits of different regional patterns (Gundersen et al., 2020). Compared to the major inland valleys, the use of cooking pits peaks and declines centuries earlier in the coastal region of Vestfold. In Vestfold, the link to the 6th century is almost non-existent, while there is a stronger temporal correlation in the inlands. However, important changes begin to occur as early as during the Early Migration Period, since several specialised cooking pit sites are abandoned. In a parallel process, new types of kitchen utensils and vessels come into use, inferring a move from large open-air rituals and gatherings to indoor feasts associated with the hall and the warrior aristocracy (Bukkemoen, 2016).

Changes to warfare and weaponry stress the profound character of the societal development at the time. Iron Age weapon graves from central Norway testify to changing tactics, from organised and collective fighting styles in the Early Iron Age, towards individualised practices in the Late Iron Age. Ingrid Ystgaard (2014) interprets the changes as expressions of changing loyalties and the increasing professionalization of warfare, favouring more aggressive tactics. Drawing on Herschend (2009), she argues for increasing accumulation of wealth among privileged families during the Roman Iron Age, while the subsequent turbulence of Migration Period Europe seem to pave the way for new leadership ideals, in which territorial control is replaced by hegemonic control. Warfare is, consequently, moved from the battlefields to the halls, reflecting conflict between dynasties rather than peoples or tribes (Herschend, 2009, pp. 369-381). A system of dependencies, developed and sustained by a warrior aristocracy, prevails throughout the turbulent 5th and 6th centuries, and is consolidated as a defining structure of Late Iron Age society (Ystgaard, 2014, p. 305). Although recognising a Migration Period economic and demographic decline, Ystgaard (2014, p. 307) does not conclude on the reasons behind it. She nevertheless points out that the development in the practice of warfare probably predates the crisis and is therefore not caused by it. The crisis is still considered important, but subordinate to the social processes.

Similar conclusions can be reached from Røstad's (2016; 2018) recent study of Migration Period and Merovingian Period brooches and costumes. While the composition and symbology of the female dress display local and regional identities, the warrior-graves reflect affiliation to an overarching multi-ethnic

warrior identity, thus mirroring the reshaping of Germanic identity in Post-Antiquity (cf. Hedeager, 2011). Regional affiliations are also expressed in the graves of the elite. Røstad (2016, pp. 410-423) interprets their symbolism as a political strategy to create a common identity for a mixed retinue, in which the leading families functioned as cultural markers and bearers of collective memory and tradition. Distributional patterns change during the Migration Period, probably reflecting socio-political processes, eventually culminating in the emergence of fewer and more defined regions in the mid-6th century. Røstad (2018) points out that the jewellery and dress display few signs of continuity, including new styles and techniques. However, detailed studies reveal a continuation of tradition and symbolism. For instance, brooches were worn in the same manner. Although style is changing, the symbolic language remained consistent. Røstad's (2018, p. 101) synthesis is, in other words, one of both crisis and continuity, in which new ruling families are (re)established after times of crisis and societal upheaval, meaning that changes and replacements within the elite are camouflaged behind an attempt to maintain ancient traditions.

The importance of the long-term trajectories is pointed out in several detailed studies of selected archaeological features during the last decade, which all share an acknowledgement of the importance of the crisis but do not consider it as the single *primus motor* for the profound material and societal changes at the transition to the Merovingian Period. On the contrary, the main causes are found in the social, political, cultural and economic development of the Early Iron Age. Gjerpe's (2017, p. 197) conclusion on the settlement record serves to illustrate this approach: He defines the end of Early Iron Age society foremost as a *result* of ongoing social processes, but regards the crisis as a transformative force heavily *influencing* the character of Late Iron Age society.

3.4 Chapter conclusion

In this chapter, I have presented and discussed the crisis narrative in Scandinavian Iron Age archaeology to disentangle the premises used to substantiate or invalidate the claims. The crisis narrative rests heavily on settlement and agricultural datasets which, however, display contrasting patterns throughout Scandinavia, but also within respective countries. Several archaeologists emphasise the importance of long-term perspectives when assessing the Iron Age development, as several important processes seem to pre-date the 6th century with considerable margins, as well as continuing to shape society for a long time after. However, there seems to be a general consensus that the 6th century nonetheless represents a pivotal moment, as many of the features which later characterise Viking Age society appear to manifest themselves more clearly during this period. Thus, the Early to Late Iron Age transition remains an intriguing point of reference for Iron Age archaeology, regardless of the explanatory frameworks attributed to it.

However, despite a century-long research history, the discourse is still suffering from the same fundamental issues as earlier, and which was expressed by Sernander's pioneering research on the collapse of Bronze Age society: concurrency versus causation, high-resolution versus low-resolution, spatial and temporal complexity versus grand-narratives, and environmental forces versus social processes. Research appears to be cyclical rather than directional. At present, there is no *de facto* contradiction between these approaches, as it is more a matter of perspective than opposing explanatory frameworks. The challenge remains to bridge a gap between environmental and human datasets, but also between quantitative and qualitative approaches. The chronological issues are not necessarily decisive in this regard, as complementary high resolutions of human and environmental datasets would nevertheless provide little supplementary context on the relationship between them. On the contrary, coherent analytical frameworks are needed which take spatial complexity and long-term trajectories into consideration, as well as enabling the assessment of possible impacts of climate change on Iron Age societies. In other words, social vulnerability and robustness must be employed as analytical tools to provide an interpretative framework in which both environmental change and social processes can be better integrated.

PART II

ANALYTICAL FRAMEWORK

4 COLLAPSOLOGY AND THE ENVIRONMENTAL HUMANITIES

There has been a noticeable increase in archaeological literature during the last two decades which emphasises the role of climatic and environmental factors for past societal change. In particular, much focus is given to hazards and climate crises in connection to incidents of collapse of complex societies. In this chapter, I will give a short review of the development of disaster research in archaeology and how it relates to the overall development in archaeological thinking. This offers an important background for understanding the development of the environmental humanities, but also the growing preoccupation with catastrophes in current research, which forms the epistemological context in which the Fimbulwinter discourse takes place.

4.1 Shifting paradigms

Collapsing civilisations and environmental catastrophes have inspired popular imaginations throughout human history. Myths, such as the destruction of Atlantis or the biblical Great Flood, constitute important parts of the modern historical narrative, influencing numerous fictional works (Middleton, 2017b, pp. 1-11). Within the natural sciences, the sub-field of *geo-mythology* undertakes research that attempts to reveal the real geological events behind myths and legends (Vitaliano, 1968) – an approach that has much in common with the initial geo-historical works by Stothers and Rampino (1983) on the AD 536/540 event (see Chapter 2.3). Dorothy B. Vitaliano (1968), in her foundational work, interpreted the Atlantis myth as reminiscent of the mid-2nd millennium BC volcanic eruption at Thera in the Aegean, an event believed to have had considerable impact on the contemporary Minoan society (Driessen, 2019; Hoffman, 1999).

In early academic scholarship, Edward Gibbon's influential *Decline and fall of the Roman Empire* (1776-1788), is often referred to as a starting point for the preoccupation with collapsing civilisations within the humanities (e.g. Butzer, 2012; Knodell, 2018; Tainter, 2016), which has since been termed as 'collapsology' by Guy D. Middleton (2017a, p. 79). Gibbon held an ethical perspective, analysing the Roman decline in light of moral decay, but was also aware of the socio-political context and historical processes at play (Butzer, 2012; Knodell, 2018).

Attempts to understand societal decline and collapse in analytical terms is, however, a noticeable feature as early as Antiquity, as seen in the works of the 2nd-century BC Greek historian Polybios (1893). Polybios, witnessing the destruction of Carthage at the end of the 3rd Punic war, considered the rising hegemony of

the Roman Empire a result of particular political structures and principles, rather than divine fortune or virtue. The 14th-century Islamic historian Ibn Khaldun, in agreement with Gibbon centuries later, analysed the rise and fall of the Roman Empire in light of moral decay, rebellions and invasions, functioning as an implicit critique of contemporary Islamic society (Butzer, 2012, p. 3632). Polybios and Ibn Khaldun were, however, both exponents of a cyclical worldview, in which all civilisations were destined to undergo growth, maturity, senescence, and death (Tainter, 2016, p. 28). As such, Polybios, whilst witnessing the cementation of Roman world hegemony, could predict that the Roman Empire itself would nevertheless eventually fall. To quote Joseph A. Tainter (2016, p. 29), today's studies of collapse "... have perhaps 3,000 years of literature on our topic. This is a distinguished ancestry, but it also poses a disturbing question: Why, after 3,000 years of effort, do we still have no consensus on what causes collapse?" A multitude of approaches have been put forward just within the last century which, for a large part, have moved crosswise the major epistemological turns in archaeology.

The shifting paradigms in archaeology, such as cultural-historical archaeology, processualism, and post-processualism, can be described as shifting cycles towards either rationalism or romanticism, in which periods of rationalism favour grand narratives, positivism, and generalisation (Kristiansen, 2008). Romanticism, on the other hand, tends to favour historical particularism and local/national perspectives on past societal change. Kristian Kristiansen (2008) argues that periods of rationalistic thinking are initiated and characterized by methodological or theoretical innovations within the natural sciences, leading to an increasing interest in environmental perspectives and, as a result, the quantification and systematisation of data in archaeological research. The innovative phases are nonetheless succeeded by increasing critique from humanistic standpoints, as contextual and local perspectives challenge grand narratives and universal approaches (Kristiansen, 2008). Kristiansen (2014) emphasizes the importance of technological innovation and big data compilations in current research, leading to what he terms the 'Third Science Revolution', representing a new turn towards rationalism. Within the geosciences, an increasing amount of high-precision data and climate simulations, as outlined in Chapter 2, has in fact generated renewed interest in environmental factors among prehistorians. Modern disaster research, however, cannot be categorized easily within a rationalist or romantic framework, as it is characterized by a multitude of approaches drawing on several traditions of scientific thinking. As such, current disaster research might also reflect what Kristiansen (2014) describes as a reformulation of both former processual and post-processual approaches, in turn opening up for a new paradigm bridging between macro and micro perspectives.

While Gibbon (1776-1788) can be defined within a rationalistic tradition, shaped by contemporary enlightenment ideas, certain romantic sentiments are identifiable during the early 19th century when

adventurous explorations drew scientific attention towards the 'rediscovery' of ancient sites and civilisations. Of particular importance was John Lloyd Stephen's journeys to the Mayan heartland of Meso-America. The drawings of his travel companion, Frederick Catherwood, appealed to colonial sensationalism and romanticism, contributing to the widespread fame of Stephen's (1841, 1843) publications. In Indo-China, the contemporary Henri Mouhot, played a similar important role for bringing the Khmer civilisation into public awareness (Middleton, 2017b, p. 299).

The discoveries of major abandoned cities and civilisations fascinated both the popular and scientific audience, but was also coloured by colonial and racial sentiments. The transient Eastern and Meso-American civilisations stood, in contrast to the comparative durability of the Roman Empire and Western Christian civilisation, as proof of Western moral and racial supremacy, thus legitimating colonial ventures; this was defined by Bruce Trigger (1989, pp. 110-145) as an *imperial synthesis*. Influenced by Darwinism and ideas of 'natural selection', global Western hegemony was understood as the result of racial and cultural evolution, justifying both internal class distinction and suppression of inferior peoples. Importantly, Western culture was not the end of history, but the sum of past experiences that would enable further progress. As John Lubbock (1865, pp. 490, 492) stated: "In reality we are but on the threshold of civilisation. Far from showing any indications of having come to an end, the tendency to improvement seems latterly to have proceeded with augmented impetus and accelerated rapidity", which was to be understood as "... the necessary consequence of natural laws". In other words, collapse of foreign civilisations, such as the Maya and Khmer, was understood as a consequence of natural selection, as opposed to 18th-century enlightenment ideas, in which progress was often assessed as continuous, frequently conceptualised in terms of stages, and stimulated by adaptation to the environment (Trigger, 2006, p. 101). Nevertheless, future optimism and ideas of cultural evolution disconnected the concept of 'collapse' from the Western self-narrative. Confidence was put into the industrial revolution and science. The West was seen as a new empire which would, by the help of knowledge and technological innovation, assure continual growth, and transcend possible future difficulties and decay (Butzer, 2012, p. 3632; Trigger, 2006, pp. 175-176).

According to Patricia McAnany and Norman Yoffee (2010b, p. 14), colonial sentiments continue to influence modern collapsology. Accordingly, there is a tendency to assign labels like collapse and failure to former civilisations of colonized peoples, while Western prehistory is understood as one of continuity. In fact, the political and urban structure of Europe has changed several times, and continuity must, at best, be understood in cultural terms (cf. McNeill, 2010, p. 362). When assessing the lowland classic Maya there is a tendency to discuss it in terms of collapse, as various city-states were indeed abandoned,

although Maya culture, as well as Meso-American urbanisation, prevailed until colonial times (cf. McAnany & Negrón, 2010).

Cultural evolution would soon be challenged by even more nationalistic and racial sentiments, fuelled by increasing dissatisfaction, socio-political struggles, and less confidence in the concept of 'progress' (Trigger, 2006, pp. 211-235). New ideas emphasized cultural particularity, attempting to bridge social class distinction by creating notions of national identities. The concept of 'culture' became an important interpretative tool, in particular within the so-called *kulturkreislehre*, as assemblies of archaeological artefacts were directly related to cultural entities.²³ Accordingly, each culture followed their own historical trajectories, but adopted new ideas through a process of more or less random cultural diffusion. As such, innovation and decline could occur due to particular environmental and historical circumstances, in which migration and direct contact with other cultural groups would be instrumental. Consequently, loss of contact with an innovative centre could cause cultural stagnation.

Environmental aspects, such as past climate change, were integrated in Scandinavian prehistoric research as early as the mid-19th century (Trigger, 2006, pp. 131-137; Van de Noort, 2013, p. 21). In the inter-war period, climate change was heavily debated among Scandinavian prehistorians as a possible causal link for the demise of Bronze Age society (see Chapter 3.1), thus defining the climate as a possible destructive agent that could generate societal collapse. However, the concept of climate change was still controversial around the early 20th century (Hassan, 2016, p. 39) and the integration of cultural and environmental research was not equally appreciated outside Scandinavia, thus making it a hallmark of Scandinavian archaeology for decades. The diffusionist, migratory, and cultural-historical perspectives in early 20th century Europe gave little room for environmental perspectives. Nevertheless, increasing interest in how settlements related to their environmental settings gradually introduced new approaches, leading up to functionalist and environmentalist frameworks in the post-war period (Trigger, 2006, p. 137; Van de Noort, 2013, p. 21).

4.2 Collapse and processual archaeology

From the 1960s and onwards, within the rising paradigm of so-called 'new archaeology' or 'processual archaeology', evolutionary and rationalistic perspectives once more came to define human change, in

²³ The idea of material assemblages as directly linked to cultural complexes was, however, not an entirely new phenomenon by the early 20th century. For instance, in the mid-19th century, the Norwegian historian Peter A. Munch (1852, pp. 4-6) interpreted stone tools as reminiscent of Sámi peoples, bronze tools as Celtic and iron tools as Germanic.

terms of stages, from less complex lithic cultures towards complex civilisations (Trigger, 2006, pp. 386-418). Causality was often analysed within frameworks of economic, ecologic, or technologic determinism, in other words, as adaptational strategies in face of changing preconditions. Lewis R. Binford (1972, p. 106), being the far most influential scholar within the new paradigm, defined evolutionary processes as "... those which operate between a living system and its environmental field. They may result in modification of the magnitude or complexity of the living system." By doing so, he understood change in terms of ecological dynamics, in which social systems responded to changing circumstances, including the interrelationship with other social systems. Consequently, when assessing cultures as ecosystems, adaptation was more or less understood as functional, aiming at maintaining or achieving a state of equilibrium and stability. In this, change was considered continuous and progressive. As a consequence, more interest was put into the development of social complexity, rather than processes of decline and collapse (cf. Tainter, 1988, p. 3).

Examples of societal decline, and returns to less complex organisations, contradicted the general assumption of societal evolution. Glenn Schwartz (2006) consider the increasing focus, in the 80s and onwards, on collapse in early complex societies as indirect critiques of processualism and evolutionary models. Collapsing civilisations were, in fact, recognised as an epistemological challenge within the processual paradigm, as stated by Colin Renfrew (1978, p. 203): "For processual archaeologists, sudden change, or discontinuous change, remains a problem". Renfrew (1978) addressed the problem by turning to mathematical theory, by suggesting that a sudden change of behaviour could occur due to a gradual build-up of continuous change. The process would ultimately release abrupt change, without any sudden alterations in the forces acting upon it, due to cost-benefit ratios. Over time, investments would exceed the expected profitable outcomes, hence causing stagnation and possible collapse.

Based on a mathematical tool called the *cusps catastrophe* (Figure 4.1), the approach was developed into a general systems theory, called *catastrophe theory*, where socio-political organisation is conditioned by the degree of the system's centralisation, cost-to-benefit ratio, and the investment in the legitimisation of the system's authority (Faulseit, 2016, p. 10; Renfrew, 1978). The model consists of separately functioning components, producing feedback loops between different levels in a hierarchical manner (Faulseit, 2016, pp. 9-10). Importantly, the individual but interdependent institutions functions as control mechanisms, thus contributing to maintain an equilibrium state or political resilience for the total system. However, according to Renfrew (1978), the system becomes unstable if the investments in the socio-political organisation, such as centralisation, hierarchisation, and specialisation, outweighs the benefits of maintaining it. Decreasing financial margins and stagnation make the system unstable, as the benefits of the system are outweighed by the costs of maintaining it. When the development reaches a critical point

in the 'cusp', society faces a rapid decline or collapse. Whether the further development is one of continuity or discontinuity depends on the value of the 'splitting factor', understood as lack of investments or fundamental changes in habit or thought (Renfrew, 1978, pp. 208, 210). Renfrew's model offers a framework for understanding societal change without any external factors working upon it, but the lack of input factors is also one of the model's weaknesses. Society is modelled as an isolated unit, following its own logic and dynamics independent of changing circumstances.

Figure 4.1: The cusp catastrophe model (Renfrew, 1978, figure 2).

Renfrew's approach was criticised for relying upon idealised socio-political systems functioning in a kind of near-equilibrium state (Cowgill, 1988, p. 253; Eisenstadt, 1988, pp. 237-238; Yoffee, 1988, pp. 9-11). In line with this way of thinking, vulnerability is created when the ability to maintain equilibrium is reduced. Thus, the mechanisms of catastrophe theory have much in common with what has been termed *engineering resilience*, which Crawford S. Holling and Lance H. Gunderson (2002, pp. 27-30; Holling, 1996) criticised for constructing ideas of an idealised and stable state of systemic existence during which maximum cost-benefit ratios can be maintained (see further discussions in Chapter 5.2.1). It also involves a certain deterministic idea of how societies develop and devolve in discrete stages, as well as suggesting that collapse is an inevitable outcome of socio-political evolution (Faulseit, 2016, p. 11). As George Cowgill (1988, p. 253) pointed out, while stressing the importance of internal socio-political conflicts in stratified

societies, "... most states *don't* work very well." He furthermore criticised the complexity of systemic models, which creates a sense of objectivity out of what can be understood as mere possible linkages. From an anthropological point of view, Anthony Oliver-Smith (1996, p. 321), nonetheless seeing potential in catastrophe theory, criticised Renfrew (1978) for ignoring the inherence of hazards to socio-environmental systems, thereby neglecting ecological factors when assessing human systems. Environmentalism had, in fact, lost much of its explanatory force during the 1970s, as increasing recognition of cross-cultural variation set aside ideas of universal generalisations (Trigger, 2006, p. 440; Van de Noort, 2013, p. 23). Scientific interest was put into developing systemic theories, in which subsistence strategies and socio-political and cultural structures were emphasized. External factors, such as environmental change, natural disasters, or even human migrations, were considered less important.

Increasing critique of systemic and generalised approaches led to the development of a post-processual paradigm, favouring synchronic analyses of individual societies and their historical particularities (Schwartz, 2006). Modern collapsology, as a prehistoric field of research in its own right, developed during the late 1980s and 1990s, and owes much to the works of Yoffee and Cowgill (1988) and Tainter (1988) (cf. Fauseit, 2016; Middleton, 2017a, p. 79). These early studies paid considerable attention to sophisticated and complex societies, such as the Minoans, imperial Rome, the lowland classic Mayans, the Egyptian 'old kingdom', the Mycenaeans, Mesopotamia, and so on, subjects that still attract significant scientific interest within this field of research (cf. Cunningham & Driessen, 2017; Fauseit, 2016; Hassan, 2016; McAnany & Yoffee, 2010c; Middleton, 2017b).

4.3 Paradigms lost

It has been argued that the prevailing focus within the post-processual paradigm on non-economic aspects, such as symbology and agency, offered environmental processes or events little importance when assessing cultural change (Van de Noort, 2013, pp. 23-24). This might, in part, be true when studying Yoffee and Cowgill's (1988) volume. Yoffee and Cowgill, nonetheless having cross-disciplinary aims, picked contributors entirely from the humanities and social sciences. In most of the articles, ecology, or environmental factors, is offered little explanatory force. However, although historical particularism was a defining feature of many studies, it might be misleading to identify modern collapsology as an entirely post-processual construct. Tainter (1988), for instance, understood societal collapse foremost as a product of economy. Accordingly, society was defined as a problem-solving organisation, maintained and developed in order to meet specific circumstances and challenges. Nevertheless, increasing socio-political complexity required considerable investments, ultimately reaching a point of declining marginal results. As such, further investments would increase vulnerability to collapse,

as diminishing reserves would reduce the ability to counter potentially stressful situations, like warfare or failing crops. In this, Tainter (1988, pp. 194-198) did not assess collapse as a state of anarchy or chaos, but rather as a return to a normal level of lower complexity. By restoring the marginal return on organizational investment to a more favourable level, collapse could be understood as an economising process of rapid character, moving society from one structurally stable level to another. His synthesis is reminiscent of evolutionary thinking, but in the reverse direction, as an adaptation to changing circumstances due to cost-to-benefit ratios. Tainter's approach was, in other words, not that different from Renfrew's (1978). Both authors assess collapse as a long-term process provoked by the system itself, in which wealth accumulation plays a fundamental part.

When assessing the demise of lowland classic Maya city-states, Tainter (1988, pp. 169-178) argued that ecological limitations caused productivity fluctuations, spiralling off a destructive economic and socio-political trajectory. This approach has much in common with Patrick Culbert (1988) in Yoffee and Cowgill's volume (1988), who considered the Maya collapse as a consequence of demographic-ecological stress due to agricultural intensification and overextension. However, even though overexploitation was an integrated part of their synthesis, the environment was not considered a precondition for human change in its own right, but rather as a stage for human action, creating possibilities and limitations. Environmental disasters were in particular considered to be of limited importance. Tainter (1988, p. 54), when assessing the Thera eruption and the decline of the late 2nd millennium BC Minoan civilisation, quite frankly dismissed the importance of volcanic cataclysms by stating "The Cretans of ca. 1500 B.C. most likely stopped to watch the eruption of Thera, made whatever preparations were called for, and when it was all over went about their business." In general, Tainter (1988, p. 53) assessed catastrophe explanations as too simple to accommodate for the complexity of human societies and the process of collapse. Consequently, the ecological limitations of the Maya lowland was first and foremost understood in economic terms. Culbert (1988, p. 100) did not consider that all collapses were ecologically derived either, but stated that they were more often rooted in political and administrative aspects. Other researchers were even more critical to an environmental approach. Cowgill (1988, pp. 266-268), for instance, questioned the slow development of the lowland classic Maya demise and the prevailing low population density during subsequent centuries. Accordingly, explanations should be assessed within a political and economic framework in which changing trade-routes might have been decisive, a perspective further explored by McAnany and Negrón (2010). Payson Sheets (1999, 2012), on the other hand, sees environmental factors, such as over-exploitation and cataclysmic volcanism, as important prerequisites for changing trade routes. Collapsing lowland city-states would accordingly open up possibilities for competing groups further north.

What is clear from this short review, however, is that modern disaster research cannot be easily defined within a rationalistic or romantic framework; a combination of economic, political-historical, and environmental perspectives are utilized in different ways by different authors, reflecting a fragmentation of the classic processual and post-processual paradigms. The combination of environmental perspectives and collapsology, as in the case of Sheets (1999, 2012), may serve to illustrate this argument. Another interesting perspective is brought forward by McCormick et al. (2012), in which migratory explanations, reminiscent of inter-war cultural-historical perspectives, are combined with an environmental framework. In essence, climate change and degradation is understood as a primary driver for migrations. Environmental perspectives and ideas of migrations and collapse would, in a traditional research historical perspective, be understood as inherent in different scientific traditions, namely rationalism and romanticism (Kristiansen, 2008, 2014; Trigger, 2006). However, as I have endeavoured to demonstrate in the preceding pages, the divide is not always that clear. Environmental perspectives were prominent in Scandinavian inter-war research, nonetheless categorized within a cultural-historical and romantic framework. Furthermore, environmentalism was less recognized within late processual thinking, opening up for more systemic and economic approaches to 'collapse' (cf. Renfrew, 1978; Tainter, 1988). As such, one could argue that environmental approaches and notions of collapse transcend the major epistemological turns in archaeology.

4.4 The environmental humanities

The gradual blend of environmental and social perspectives has become more prominent during the last several decades, with increasing focus and theorisation on human-environmental interaction. The attempt to synthesize the many tensions and conflicts playing out in the interaction between the environmental and social spheres characterise what is often termed the *environmental humanities* (cf. Riede, 2015, p. 13). American anthropological and sociological disaster research have been important in this recent turn, in which an increasing focus on societal vulnerability to hazards has been pivotal (Furedi, 2007, p. 484; Oliver-Smith, 1996, p. 304). Hazard-disaster research originated in the social sciences around the mid-20th century, later on influencing several disciplines within both the natural and social sciences (cf. García-Acosta, 2002; Sheets, 2012, p. 43). In the 1970s and 1980s vulnerability was beginning to be analysed in political-economic, social organisational, and ecological perspectives, rather than just as a matter of practical measures, such as deforestation (Oliver-Smith, 1996, p. 314; 2002, p. 27), thus diverging from the theoretical turn in archaeology at the time (cf. Chapter 4.2). As such, environmental disasters were increasingly understood as rooted in society, not as something happening outside a passive and receiving society, thus opening up for the development of a more cohesive human-environmental approach. Important to this discussion is the definition of vulnerability as a construct of both human and environmental systems, in which the processual life of one domain contribute to the vulnerability and

resilience of the other (Oliver-Smith, 2002, p. 39). In other words, a dualistic understanding of nature and culture is criticised, as nature and culture are not to be understood as separated entities, but mutually dependent and influential. Human life and disasters are neither nature nor culture, but embedded in both. The concept of vulnerability thus differs from previous environmentalist approaches, likely reflecting the inheritance of disaster research in the social sciences (see Chapter 5.3 for further discussions).

Within ecology, vulnerability has been incorporated as an important analytical tool for understanding ecosystem dynamics, in turn constituting a central prerequisite for resilience theory. Resilience is understood in two different ways: as resistance to disturbance, and as the amount of disturbance that can be absorbed before the system changes its structure (Holling, 1996, see chapter 5.2.1 for further discussions). Resilience theory has been further developed into holistic models for human-environmental interaction, the most common being the 'adaptive cycle model' (Holling & Gunderson, 2002, see chapter 5.2.2 for further discussions). As such, although being related analytical concepts, vulnerability and resilience have been developed within different scientific traditions (cf. Holling, 1996; Oliver-Smith, 1996). The scope of resilience and vulnerability is also somewhat different, as resilience in particular is directed towards issues of social learning and disaster mitigation. It can be understood as the capabilities and capacities of a given society or group to respond adequately to a situation of danger. Vulnerability, on the other hand, describes the susceptibility and predisposition to suffer harm, damage, or disaster (Oliver-Smith, Alcántara-Ayala, Burton, & Lavell, 2017, p. 472). In certain ways, one might define resilience not as an equilibrium or state of existence, but as a constant adaptational process inherent in changing features of vulnerability and risk. Both concepts interact dialectically with each other and address the underlying causes of disasters, and the questions of adaptation and recovery (Oliver-Smith, 2015, pp. 547-548; Oliver-Smith et al., 2017, p. 472). The introduction of vulnerability and resilience as analytical tools within the social sciences has been defined by Oliver-Smith (2015, p. 547) as a paradigmatic change.

Resilience theory, in particular, has been influential within archaeology in the 2000s (Bradtmöller, Grimm, & Riel-Salvatore, 2017; Redman, 2005), while disaster anthropology has been mostly preoccupied with social vulnerability (Oliver-Smith, 2015, p. 547). The recent focus on resilience theory in archaeology represents, according to Faulseit (2016), a gradual shift from collapse studies towards a focus on societal resilience, which in turn has led to an increasing interest in understanding the process of adaptation and recovery (e.g. Torrence, 2016, 2019). Resilience theory has, however, been criticised both for a lack of clear definition and for leaving little room for social complexity and human agency by forcing human action into predictable patterns preconditioned by environmental factors (Butzer, 2012, p. 3633; Middleton, 2017a, p. 92; Rashidian, 2021).

During the 2000s, there has been a steady increase in human-environmental studies, of which a considerable percentage is preoccupied with 'catastrophes' (Degroot et al., 2021, p. 542). The growing scientific interest for disasters and environmental perspectives might be explained in light of modern challenges concerning global warming, ecology and sustainability (Holling, Gunderson, & Ludwig, 2002; McAnany & Yoffee, 2010b, pp. 6-7; Oliver-Smith, 1996; Oliver-Smith & Hoffman, 2002; Tainter, 2016, p. 29). In other words, current societal difficulties and policymaking not only influence scientific priorities, but can also colour how we interpret past disasters and societal transformations. This is well exemplified with cultural geographer Diamond's (2005) popular book *Collapse: how societies choose to fail or succeed*, in which environmental degradation and climate change is assessed as primary movers for societal failures, i.e. as an 'ecocide' due to overpopulation, deforestation and overexploitation, explicitly functioning as a 'warning' for the contemporary global society. Although there is an increasing awareness of environmental factors within archaeology, Diamond has nevertheless been criticised for constructing more or less apocalyptic scenarios that downplay important traits of cultural resilience (McAnany & Yoffee, 2010a, 2010b; McNeill, 2010; Middleton, 2017a, pp. 80-82; see also Diamond 2010). For instance, McAnany and Yoffee (2010b, p. 7) do not question environmental factors themselves, but the human ability, in pre-industrial times, to destroy the environment and bring down their own societies (sustainability among native populations is nonetheless a much debated issue, see Hames, 2007).

Several archaeological and anthropological studies are preoccupied with developing methodical and theoretical frameworks which might be applicable to contemporary environmental challenges or issue correctives to modern society (Butzer, 2012; Knodell, 2018; Oliver-Smith, 1996, 2016; Oliver-Smith et al., 2017; Oliver-Smith & Hoffman, 2002; Riede, 2015; Riede & Sheets, 2020; Van de Noort, 2013). As such, modern sustainability issues are, in essence, a *raison d'être* for the environmental humanities. In spite of clear-cut intentions and increasing scientific interest, the influence of the environmental humanities, and the paleoenvironmental humanities in particular, remains marginal in modern policy-making (Oliver-Smith, 2016; Oliver-Smith et al., 2017; Riede, 2016, p. 3; Van de Noort, 2013, p. 2). Three factors seem decisive: first, pre-industrial and industrial societies have different characteristics, thus experiencing different levels and types of vulnerability and resilience to hazards (Chester, Duncan, & Sangster, 2012); second, the magnitude and scale of the modern global society, which has no parallels throughout human existence, seem to render experiences from the past irrelevant to the modern overpopulated world (Van de Noort, 2013, p. 3); and third, neoliberal policies, models of development and huge imbalances in power continue to privilege economic growth over sustainability, reducing disaster risk management to technological measures and emergency management, rather than risk-reduction through socio-economic analyses of causations and effects (Oliver-Smith, 2016; Oliver-Smith et al., 2017).

In addition, no clear-cut theoretical paradigm is readily identifiable. 'Collapse' can be understood in several ways: as a fragmentation of states into smaller political units; as the partial abandonment or complete desertion of urban centres; the loss of centralizing functions; the breakdown of economic systems; or as the failure of civilizational ideologies (Schwartz, 2006, p. 6). However, as pointed out by Shmuel Eisenstadt (1988, p. 242), collapse rarely involves a total disappearance of a group or cultural traditions – a feature that makes the very idea of collapse somewhat intangible. On the contrary, collapse and reorganisation can be understood as a continuous process of societal reconstruction and adaptation, meaning that the boundary between them becomes difficult to define. Rather than oppositions, regeneration and collapse can be understood as related phenomenon.

The concept of collapse opens up for a multitude of approaches, often given different designations, such as *palaeo-social volcanology* (Riede, 2015), *crisis archaeology* (Driessen, 2017), *collapsology* (Middleton, 2017a), or the more neutral *history of climate and society* (HCS) (Degroot et al., 2021). The different approaches are developed within somewhat different scientific traditions, but mutually influential. The explanations vary. Invasions are not as commonly referred to as before, but other external variables such as climate change are frequently used, in particular cases resulting in agrarian failure (Schwartz, 2006, p. 6). Internal variables, such as overexploitation and economic decline, may cause an ideological failure leading people to abandon their faith in the governing system. Another factor can be tension between traditional kinship structures and increasing centralization and social stratification. The various approaches and theoretical frameworks are accompanied by great diversity in terminology and definitions (Middleton, 2017a; Oliver-Smith, 2002; Tainter, 2016, p. 24). The lack of coherence is challenging, as it makes it difficult to compare the different case studies and develop a common theoretical basis for understanding human-environmental interaction. Collapse, for instance, can be understood as both a long-term (Storey & Storey, 2016) and short-term process (Tainter, 1988), although the former would be conceived by most people as counter-intuitive (Middleton, 2017a, pp. 85-87). Tainter (1988, p. 4) views collapse as a political process, in which society experiences a rapid and significant loss of an established level of socio-political complexity. Driessen (2017) argues that societal collapse ideally implies a complete eradication of existing social, political, and material structures. McAnany and Yoffee (2010b), on the other hand, question the very notion of collapse, not just by stressing cultural resilience, but by also pointing at certain colonial notions when assessing non-Western prehistory (cf. Chapter 4.1).

4.5 Chapter conclusion

Since Gibbon's days, collapsology and environmental archaeology have gone through a rapid development, in part transgressing the major epistemological turns in archaeology. Beginning in the 1980s there has been an increasing trend towards developing more coherent analytical frameworks for understanding societal collapse which, from the 1990s and onwards, have been frequently combined with environmental perspectives. This later turn of events is difficult to separate from the contemporaneous public preoccupation with the dangers posed by environmental and climatic deterioration. In many ways, threats of ecocide and climate change function as a *raison d'être* for the environmental humanities, a field which is now attempting to provide methodologies and knowledge that may contribute to modern disaster mitigation. However, modern archaeological disaster research is characterised by a multitude of definitions and approaches and a lack of stringent methodology, causing considerable confusion about how societal collapse should be approached and understood. This development may be related to an ongoing process of deconstructing former paradigms, as argued by Kristiansen (2014), which may result in more holistic approaches that have the potential to bridge not only macro and micro levels of analysis, but also environmental and human perspectives on prehistory. As such, the process represents considerable potential for scientific renewal. However, there is also a certain risk that modern environmental concerns influence our perception of the past, as the need to provide lessons for modern societies favours catastrophic explanations of prehistoric events. The Fimbulwinter discourse has developed independently alongside the overall discussions in prehistoric disaster research, and has so far not interacted with it in any substantial way. On the contrary, the novel approaches on human-environmental interaction during the last two decades have not generated any immediate interest in Scandinavian Iron Age research. In many ways, the Fimbulwinter hypothesis has little in common with the environmental humanities, as no coherent analytical framework for understanding the climatic impact has so far been put forward (cf. Chapter 3.3). This represents a considerable challenge for assessing the impact of dust veil events on the societal development of the time, but also considerable opportunities for moving the debate forward from the current state of research.

5 THEORISING DISASTERS. KEY CONCEPTS OF HUMAN-ENVIRONMENTAL INTERACTION

In a recent publication, Thomas Hylland Eriksen (2016) discusses the conflicts caused by modern globalisation, environmental degradation, and neoliberal capitalism. Societies and cultures change at different paces, causing social tensions along different spatial and temporal scales. Fundamental for his narrative is the ability to understand the disjunctures between speed and slowness, and change and continuity, in order to grasp the conflicts arising from accelerating globalisation. However, his observations could just as well be applied to the study of prehistoric societies. A main concern for prehistorians is the attempt to understand past social processes, how society develops, by analysing innovation and tradition in a long-term perspective. Globalisation, environmental degradation, and neoliberal capitalism, although profoundly modern conceptualisations are, nevertheless, in their basic form, more or less modern versions of perpetual mechanisms. Human impact on the environment is by no means a modern phenomenon, as witnessed by the extinction of megafauna, domestication of plants and animals, and the presence of anthropogenic soils – the archaeosphere – throughout Earth’s ice-free land surfaces (Edgeworth et al., 2015; L. Stephens et al., 2019). The prehistoric inheritance of the archaeosphere challenges the conceptual divide between the past and the present as fundamentally different, as the human ecological footprint and ability to alter their environment is not exclusively modern. It is all about scale and magnitude. The three categories – human interaction, environmental impact, and economy – are interrelated in Eriksen’s (2016) narrative, reflecting the same general tension between universality and particularity, between global and local. Being interdisciplinary in character, the environmental humanities attempt to bridge the processes in the human and environmental spheres by assessing them as mutually instrumental (Chapter 4.4). From this perspective, disasters are often viewed as possible causal agents for societal and cultural change rather than just destructive environmental events. Particular emphasis has been put on the analytical concepts of resilience and vulnerability, which are complementary, but nonetheless developed within somewhat different schools of thought.

In this chapter, I aim at exploring resilience and vulnerability in order to present an analytical framework in which the temporal and spatial patterns of the 6th-century transition in Scandinavian archaeology can be understood. An important prerequisite is the basic notion of interdependence in human-environmental systems (Oliver-Smith & Hoffman, 2002). Human and environmental systems are mutually instrumental, as events and processes in one domain affect conditions within the other. In other words, natural disasters are conditioned by both cultural and environmental factors, but, importantly, emerge as such in the moment they *appear within a social system* and affect *someone*. Although rooted in environmental processes, natural disasters are consequently understood as social in character.

Understanding human and societal development is largely about understanding its pace and dynamics, and the interaction between social and environmental systems. For instance, Eriksen (2016) draws on the works of the anthropologist Bateson, whose cross-disciplinary studies on ‘patterns that connect’ within the fields of psychology, biology, and philosophy are important for organization studies (Zundel, 2014). Eriksen’s (2016, p. 9) emphasis on the necessity to understand the pace and character of change and continuity has much in common with resilience theory, which will be further outlined in Chapter 5.2 below. In short, resilience theory aims at developing holistic models for understanding human-environmental interaction. More specifically, it seeks to meet the political and public demands for analytical tools which could enable a sustainable future (Holling, Gunderson, & Ludwig, 2002). Resilience theory is also frequently applied to prehistoric contexts in order to assess the dynamics of human-environmental interaction in the past (Chapter 5.2.3).

A key feature in resilience theory is interdependency between human and environmental systems, which is interwoven with the concept of vulnerability and how it is created. Although environmental degradation may be a global phenomenon, vulnerability to disaster is nevertheless contextual and local since degrees of vulnerability depend on the character of each individual society (see Chapter 5.3 below). Thus, the often-considered opposition between universality and particularity in prehistoric research (cf. Kristiansen, 2008), which is also expressed through the Fimbulwinter discourse (Chapter 3.3), can be broken down. Instead of contrasting, the perspectives can be understood as complementary.

However, disaster and crisis are not neutral concepts, and the growing interest for climate and disaster studies in archaeology in the 2000s risk being coloured by modern political sentiments and societal challenges. The recognition of profound environmental challenges for modern society has not only generated considerable research interest in environmental events in prehistory. It has also contributed to a profoundly different view concerning how human-environmental interaction is to be understood, as exemplified by the recognition of humanity’s ability to alter its environment even in prehistoric times. The recent environmental turn in archaeology offers novel insights to past socio-cultural developments, but also includes a certain risk of interpretative biases that potentially shape our perception of the past. In order to avoid these caveats, the concepts themselves must be disentangled and put into an epistemological context – one in which the Anthropocene becomes fundamental.

5.1 Crisis and disaster in the Anthropocene

Concepts, and how we define and use them, are closely related to the current socio-political situation. In other words, concepts reflect how we understand and perceive our present state and the world around us (Jordheim, 2017, p. 17; Koselleck, 2017 [1985], p. 25). Key concepts, such as crisis, progress, and humanity, thus define our interpretation of the past, present, and future. The scientific terminologies that are applied to prehistoric settings are not just tools for describing or understanding the features in question, but in essence function as interpretations of past events through a modern lens.

However, the very definitions change throughout history. The word 'crisis', which is thoroughly embedded in both our understanding of the 6th-century transition (see Chapter 3.3) and environmental hazards (see Chapter 2), has for instance lost much of its initial meaning and is now applied to almost any given situation of uncertainty and stress, resulting in a dramatic increase in the use of the word during the 20th century (Koselleck, 2006). Being Greek in origin, the term described stark alternatives in the spheres of law, politics, medicine, and theology; between right and wrong, life, or death, hence demanding immediate decision-making. The modern use of the word developed during the late 18th century, in particular the decades around the French revolution, when it was increasingly used as a metaphor for describing current political and social situations. As such, 'crisis' entered the historical-philosophical narrative and came to be a basic interpretative tool for social and political history – a conceptual innovation that Koselleck (2017 [1985], pp. 26-27) attributed to Jean-Jacques Rousseau (2010 [1762]). In other words, 'crisis' can be understood as a key concept for how we conceptualize the world around us, influencing how we understand time itself. The term came to mean the end to something, as an epochal change. How 'crisis' is manifested through time can nevertheless be understood in different ways, as being processual, recurrent, or even apocalyptic. The conceptualisation was symptomatic for how the past and the future was now understood. From being assessed, in pre-modern times, as closely integrated, past and future came to be interpreted as something different and divided (Kverndokk, 2017, pp. 34-35). 'Crisis' and 'progress' can be understood as interrelated terminologies, in which 'crisis' paves way for a future substantially different from the past (Jordheim, 2017).

The modern use is multi-layered, ambiguous and omnipresent, which Koselleck (2006, 2017 [1985]) understood as symptomatic for a current 'crisis' not yet fully understood, but probably influenced by the modern shift from future optimism towards pessimism. Eriksen (2016), analysing the modern sentiments from the viewpoint of social-anthropology, describes a situation of chronic crises driven by fundamental contradictions in the global system, between the universal and local, but also between modernity and tradition. Basically, the basic idea of improvement, development, and confidence in the future are

challenged by conceptions of stagnation, doubt, and resistance to change (Eriksen, 2016, p. vii). Accordingly, it is a sustained and global state of crisis, accelerating during the 20th century, but nevertheless perceived, understood, and responded to locally (Eriksen, 2016, p. 8). Eriksen’s narrative is reminiscent of Koselleck’s assessment of the conceptual history of ‘crisis’, and offers a socio-cultural framework in which the current use of ‘crisis’ might be contextualized.

Figure 5.1: The use of the phrases ‘crisis’, ‘climate’, and ‘disaster’ in books written in English from 1650 to 2019, in percentage of the total volume per year, set with a 5 year smoothing average. Retrieved from Google Books N-Gram Viewer, 30.03.2021 (Michel et al., 2011).²⁴

Firmly integrated in the modern sentiments and discourses concerning ‘crisis’ is the increasing notion of a lasting human footprint on our physical surroundings, ultimately influencing research both within the humanities and natural sciences. Figure 5.1 visualises the use of the words ‘crisis’, ‘disaster’, and ‘climate’ in English books from 1650-2019. The data is retrieved from Google Books N-Gram Viewer, consisting of a database of over 5 million digitised books, drawn from over 40 university libraries around the world (Michel et al., 2011). It illustrates not only an increasing scientific preoccupation with notions of crisis during the second half of the 20th century, but also disasters and environmental issues (see also Degroot et al., 2021, pp., Figure 2). The profound human impact on the environment, in terms of pollution, consumption, and exploitation, has led geologists to discuss whether we have reached a new geological

²⁴

https://books.google.com/ngrams/graph?content=crisis%2Cclimate%2Cdisaster&year_start=1650&year_end=2019&case_insensitive=on&corpus=26&smoothing=5&direct_url=t4%3B%2Ccrisis%3B%2Cc0%3B%2Cs0%3B%3Bcrisis%3B%2Cc0%3B%3Bcrisis%3B%2Cc0%3B%3BCRISIS%3B%2Cc0%3B.t4%3B%2Cclimate%3B%2Cc0%3B%2Cs0%3B%3Bclimate%3B%2Cc0%3B%3Bclimate%3B%2Cc0%3B%3BCLIMATE%3B%2Cc0%3B.t4%3B%2Cdisaster%3B%2Cc0%3B%2Cs0%3B%3Bdisaster%3B%2Cc0%3B%3Bdisaster%3B%2Cc0%3B%3BDISASTER%3B%2Cc0

era: the age of Anthropocene, thus classifying humankind as a geological agent (cf. Crutzen, 2002; Crutzen & Stoermer, 2000; Waters et al., 2018; Zalasiewicz, Williams, Steffen, & Crutzen, 2010)²⁵.

‘Crisis’, in itself, is a temporal concept, as it implies something happening before and after (Kverndokk, 2017, p. 34). In the modern age, crisis is more or less understood as permanent, but also existential (Jordheim, 2017, pp. 20-21). In current public debates is the term ‘climate’ so closely entangled with ‘crisis’ that it is hard to distinguish between the two (Kverndokk, 2017). ‘Climate’ is, just like ‘crisis’, omnipresent in the public debate.

Figure 5.2 The use of the combined phrase ‘climate crisis’ in books written in English from 1650 to 2019, in percentage of the total volume per year, set with a 5 year smoothing average. Retrieved from Google Books N-Gram Viewer, 30.03.2021 (Michel et al., 2011).²⁶

The combined term ‘climate crisis’ appeared in scientific papers for the first time during the 1970s, but became more common during the 1990s (Kverndokk, 2017, p. 34). In the 2000s it has metaphorically skyrocketed (Figure 5.2). The idea of disaster has gone through a similar, but more gradual historical development. Environmental disasters were traditionally understood as acts of supernatural or divine

²⁵ The conceptualisation of humankind as a geological agent is, however, not a recent one. The Russian geologist and geochemist Vernadsky (2007 [1926], Kindle-position 3285) stated as early as the 1920s that “... civilized Man breaks the established terrestrial balance. With the civilization of *Homo sapiens*, a new geological power has appeared, the significance of which in the geochemical history of all elements is growing. We will see that it is only one fact of a great, general, historically new phenomenon.”

²⁶

https://books.google.com/ngrams/graph?content=climate+crisis&year_start=1650&year_end=2019&case_insensitive=on&corpus=26&smoothing=5&direct_url=t4%3B%2Cclimate%20crisis%3B%2Cc0%3B%2Cs0%3B%3Bclimate%20crisis%3B%2Cc0%3B%3Bclimate%20crisis%3B%2Cc0%3B%3Bclimate%20crisis%3B%2Cc0%3B%3BCLIMATE%20CRISIS%3B%2Cc0%3B%3Bclimate%20crisis%3B%2Cc0%3B%2Cs1%3B%3Bclimate%20crisis%3B%2Cc0%3B%3Bclimate%20crisis%3B%2Cc0%3B%3BCLIMATE%20CRISIS%3B%2Cc0

powers (Furedi, 2007, p. 483; Kverndokk, 2015, p. 23), but enlightenment ideas ultimately opened up for scientific explanations. Kverndokk (2015, p. 14) writes that the disastrous 1755 earthquake in Lisbon represents a watershed moment, as the idea of divine presence in nature and human life was seriously questioned. Thus, the opposition between human and nature became more evident (Oliver-Smith, 2002, pp. 30-32). Enlightenment secularism led to an important shift in which catastrophes were increasingly seen as *Acts of Nature*, rather than *Acts of God* (Furedi, 2007, p. 483). Disasters, as interruptions of order, were perceived as at odds with the human world, despite being generated by the normal functioning of the same global social system (Oliver-Smith, 2002, p. 31; Oliver-Smith et al., 2017, p. 470). As such, nature was understood as something to be acted upon, subjugated to control and use, although domestication of nature also creates vulnerability to hazards. In recent times, however, catastrophes are increasingly understood as *Acts of Men and Women* – a shift probably influenced by the fear of technological disasters and anthropogenic climate change (cf. Furedi, 2007; Kverndokk, 2015, pp. 221-223, see also Oliver-Smith 1996, p. 307).

In the Anthropocene, the concept of ‘climate crisis’ has more or less turned into *the Crisis* with capital ‘C’, embracing every aspect of human life, consequently shaping our understanding of past, present, and future. On one side, the modern debates on climate change have brought to light new scientific perspectives on human-environmental interaction, in which natural disasters are viewed as inherent to human systems, rather than mere unpredictable events (Oliver-Smith, 1996, p. 304). It also influences how we relate to cultural heritage, and assess our social responsibility as scientists (Solli, 2011). On the other hand, equally important for past disaster studies is how the present ultimately becomes an interpretative tool for understanding the past, rather than the other way around (Kverndokk, 2017, p. 35). In this perspective, prehistory not only loses its significance for understanding the present, but is at risk of creating confirmation bias in topical scientific and socio-political narratives.

The Anthropocene can be understood as a process of ‘discursive catastrophisation’ (Ophir, 2010). It is a socially constructed experience, situated in the public and governmental discourses of society, through which an objective status is obtained, leading up to a state of emergency and preparedness. The notion of crisis may be rooted in real or imaginary threats, but it becomes a collective bias through the social discourse. As such, it is a totalising process, shaping the collective consciousness, and is at risk of becoming a permanent state of crisis due to a lack of ability – or interest – in solving it. The process is reminiscent of the permanent and global crisis in Eriksen’s (2016) narrative, maintained through the dynamics of globalisation, but also in the public environmental discourse, through an almost fetishisation of disasters in popular culture and news media (cf. Ekström & Kverndokk, 2015; Kverndokk, 2015). The significant growth in disaster literature in archaeology during the last decades (cf. Chapter 4), and the role

attributed to catastrophes for social change, is difficult to separate from the contemporaneous public and popular preoccupation with crisis and disasters (cf. Holling, Gunderson, & Ludwig, 2002; McAnany & Yoffee, 2010b, pp. 6-7; Oliver-Smith, 1996; Oliver-Smith & Hoffman, 2002; Riede & Sheets, 2020; Tainter, 2016, p. 29). Thus, the Anthropocene, in the process of becoming a modern key concept, influences our understanding of past, present, and future.

In the age of Anthropocene and global climate change, a certain interpretative hegemony is often attributed to the natural sciences in the scientific and public discourses as providers of “hard” facts, high-resolution datasets, and simulations that can be easily related to (Hulme, 2011). Climate models are often given considerable explanatory force for how future social processes and human action will play out, thus downplaying the importance of human behaviour and culture for understanding societal dynamics. As discussed in Chapter 3.3.2, this can result in the uncritical use of geoscientific interpretations in archaeological studies, derived from the notion that the climate must have been the cause, rather than employing a stringent method that could substantiate it. In this, as stated by Moreland (2018), there is a certain element of neo-determinism. The lack of a coherent methodology often makes the use of analogies important for the interpretations, whether it be the medieval Black Death (cf. Chapter 2.3.4), the 1815 Tambora eruption (cf. Chapter 2.2), or other historical, archaeological, and contemporary examples of possible major disaster impacts (Chapter 3.3.2). Although analogies can be powerful tools for visualising the possible outcome of similar scenarios, it does, however, come with a risk of under-communicating the need to contextualise the specific circumstances in question. As concluded in Chapter 2.2.4, similar scenarios might still result in different outcomes, depending on the combined effect of human and environmental factors.

Thus, the Anthropocene, and the current scientific preoccupation with crisis and disasters, is accompanied with certain epistemological pitfalls that need to be acknowledged. However, the solution lies not in rejecting the explanatory force of environmental factors as such, in order to return to mere socio-economic explanations of past societal change (as exemplified by Renfrew, 1978; Tainter, 1988). It is through contextualising, and combining, human and environmental factors that more substantiated interpretations can be achieved. Nonetheless, integrating human and geoscientific sciences remains a profound challenge, both in terms of epistemology and types of datasets, and is not solved by mere interdisciplinary work (Riede et al., 2020). Causality cannot be derived from data alone, as the intricacy of both human and environmental systems complicates any direct relationship between events and effects. It requires methods and interpretative frameworks that transcend the epistemological and practical boundaries of profoundly different academic disciplines (cf. Degroot et al., 2021). It goes without saying that these issues cannot be solved within the limits of this thesis. Anyhow, a first important step for

Scandinavian Iron Age archaeology lies in developing frameworks that allow for a more systematic and analytic approach to the issue of the 6th-century transition in place of the mere use of analogy and uncritical use of geoscientific results. As will be discussed in the forthcoming chapters, the concepts of resilience and vulnerability provide analytical tools in which temporal and spatial patterns can be better understood.

5.2 The resilient community

Resilience theory has been much debated in international archaeology during the last two decades, and owes much to the works of Gunderson and Holling (2002). Drawing on biology and organisational psychology, the interaction between society and the environment is conceptualised in a long-term perspective, emphasizing the processes leading up to radical change (Redman, 2005). As such, resilience theory attempts to separate itself from deterministic approaches to human-environmental interaction, as the root causes for the character of change are sought in social dynamics predating a disaster onset, and not in the disaster itself. Compared to traditional studies of past societal collapses, resilience theory offers contrasting perspectives on how radical change is understood (Allcock, 2017; Bradtmöller et al., 2017). Disasters are not understood as game-changers in their own right, but rather as extreme events accelerating the inherent mechanisms of society. By emphasising the adaptive capacities of socio-cultural systems, radical change is understood as means of maintaining systemic properties and its integrity in face of disruptive agents – as opposed to ideas of structural disintegration and collapse. Resilience theory also differs from 1970s-style systems theory, like catastrophe theory (Renfrew, 1978), as both change and stability is considered continuous, but never as a defining aspect of society. On the contrary, human practice and social change is understood as constantly moving in between the two extremes in a learning process defined as an adaptive cycle (Redman, 2005). However, a common critique against systemic thinking lies in the difficulties in dealing with the unpredictability of both our physical surroundings and human behaviour, which tends to cause discrepancies between the subject of study and the applied model. This is very much also the case with resilience theory, which will be further outlined below. In this chapter, I will explore and discuss resilience theory in order to highlight its potential for past disaster studies. I will also discuss some of the limitations inherent to the theory, in particular some defining aspects of the *adaptive cycle model*.

5.2.1 TWO DEFINITIONS OF RESILIENCE

The definition of resilience varies, which has direct implications for how it is applied in social theory. It has traditionally been understood in two different ways, defined as both *ecosystem resilience* and *engineering resilience* (Holling, 1996; Holling & Gunderson, 2002). The former is drawn from ecology and biological

sciences, while the latter is rooted in environmental sciences and is influenced by physics and engineering. The two definitions of resilience focus on different attributes of change, adaptation, and persistence, in part reflecting the use of the term within different scientific traditions. The environmental sciences follow a more traditional understanding, concentrating on stability near an equilibrium and resistance to disturbance, while in ecology change is understood as a way of achieving stability (Holling, 1996, p. 33). In other words, engineering resilience focuses on the ability to maintain *efficiency of function*, while ecosystem resilience focuses on maintaining *existence of function*. Consequently, the latter approach involves multiple possible futures in the face of disruption, as adaptation is understood as a key component for maintaining structural properties. The former approach, being one of the foundations for economic theory, aims at maintaining an idealized state of existence, able to absorb disturbance and quickly restore the desired condition, which is quite similar to the basic principles employed in late processual catastrophe theory in archaeology (Chapter 4.2). According to Holling (1996, p. 33), the two definitions have very different consequences for how change and complexity is evaluated and understood. Engineering resilience has been criticised for asserting that natural systems can be controlled and attributed with predictable consequences (Holling & Gunderson, 2002, pp. 27-31). Nature, however, is not constant or balanced. On the contrary, ecosystems are constantly in flux with the environmental factors which act upon them, meaning that resilience is not infinite but always moving in between change and stability, thus opening up opportunities for species diversity.

In turn, large-scale change, for instance due to large-scale environmental disruptions, will ultimately replace one system with another. Holling and Gunderson (2002, p. 32) argue that resilience is not an ideal in itself as it can be the enemy of adaptive change. Successful resilience, in other words, may cause conservatism that creates vulnerability over time. Their argument is exemplified by the case of the Soviet Union, described, as for a time, as an immensely resilient dictatorship of bureaucracy, but proving to be maladaptive and therefore vulnerable in a long-term perspective. Diamond's (2005) assessment of the Norse medieval settlements on Greenland, in which he describes an agricultural society able to persist for centuries at the very edge of the agrarian productivity zone, closely resembles Holling and Gunderson's argument. According to Diamond, their successful adaptation to a harsh climate turned into cultural conservatism, thus increasing their vulnerability to changing environmental conditions in the Late Middle Ages. Holling and Gunderson (2002) argue for a shift from a static view of resilience towards a dynamical perspective. Thus, engineering resilience, being the ideal of many modern societies, in fact increases human vulnerability to environmental change.

The two definitions resemble how resilience is employed in the archaeological literature, often understood as *political resilience* and *cultural resilience* (Faulseit, 2016, p. 7; McAnany & Yoffee, 2010b, p.

10). The first is the ability to maintain or quickly restore desirable conditions, which relates to engineering resilience. Related to ecosystem resilience, the other approach emphasises the ability, when experiencing major disruptions and loss of socio-political complexity, to maintain long-term cultural continuity by adaptation and transformation. Rather than mutually exclusive, the two definitions can be understood as complementary as they relate to both the different aspects of the social sphere and the different attributes of human practice and organisation (McAnany & Yoffee, 2010b, p. 10). The distinction allows for a more nuanced understanding of concepts such as crisis, collapse, and disaster, as even during incidents of political and societal disintegration, cultural identity and characteristics can still be maintained through human practice (cf. Middleton, 2017a, pp. 79, 86).

In essence, social and political institutions follow different trajectories during societal transformations (Faulseit, 2016, p. 7). Political structures engage in the need for balancing different economic and political measures, constantly renegotiating the internal power-balance and interests of state. For that reason, the political structures are characterised by the leaders' necessity to employ short-term strategies, countering disruptions to the ideal state of the governing apparatus. The social institutions, on the other hand, are more closely related to the cultural traditions that are developed and maintained throughout generations, thus engaging in long-term strategies intended to reinforce the social contract between individuals and groups. In other words, human behaviour and tradition is considered more robust than overarching political and ideological structures.

However, political and cultural resilience strategies might also be incompatible as social strategies, and therefore mutually destabilizing, as they have different aims and scopes (Faulseit, 2016, pp. 7-16). Short-term measures, whether rooted in cultural or political strategies, might have unintended long-term consequences. Long-term strategies, on the other hand, might cause profound conservatism, thus increasing vulnerability during times of changing environmental conditions (as outlined by Holling & Gunderson, 2002, p. 32). As a consequence, political and cultural resilience have different attributes and trajectories but are nonetheless mutually influential and inter-dependent. The relationship between the two is consequently best analysed in long-term perspectives, meaning that political and cultural resilience involves important temporal parameters not always sufficiently explored within the field of anthropology. Moreover, Ronald Faulseit (2016, p. 8) points to examples of when cultural resilience has played important roles for societal regeneration. Thus, as it is conditioned by numerous case-specific variables and contextual parameters, the interaction between political and cultural resilience is complex, proving it difficult to model or operationalise (cf. Faulseit, 2016, pp. 8-16). The diversity inherent in unique historical trajectories represents a pivotal challenge for any grand narrative or systemic model, but can, according to Faulseit (2016, pp. 16-19), be overcome by the adaptive cycle model.

5.2.2 THE ADAPTIVE CYCLE MODEL

Hollings' (1996) ideas about ecosystem resilience has been further developed into an integrated theory, addressing current global societal and environmental change (Holling, Gunderson, & Ludwig, 2002). The aim of Holling, Gunderson, and Ludwig (2002, pp. 7-10) is formulated as a way of achieving a scientific and interdisciplinary model for modern sustainability policies, by combining economy, ecology, social aspects and evolutionary change into one coherent analytical framework. In this way, resilience theory aims at bridging the natural and social sciences (Holling, Gunderson, & Ludwig, 2002, p. 5). Their theory offer a framework for analysing the interplay between change and persistence across different hierarchical scales, which allow for adaptive evolution within both social and natural systems.

Figure 5.3: The adaptive cycle model. Short arrows: slow and time-consuming processes. Long arrows: rapid processes. Illustration by Ingvild Tinglum Bøckman. Modified from Holling and Gunderson (2002).

The framework is visualised through the adaptive cycle model (Figure 5.3). It has two important characteristics. First, change is inevitable and episodic, and not continuous or chaotic. Second, the system is not defined by a state of equilibrium, as it is a moving target in between stability and transformation. The cycle is constituted along three dimensions: potential for energy/capital accumulation, connectedness/interdependency between the entities, and resilience/vulnerability of the system (Holling & Gunderson, 2002). Neither of them are constant, but increase and decrease according to the shifting

properties of the cycle. The cycle moves along four different sequential stages. These are reorganisation, exploitation, conservation, and release. Although being cyclic, the system does not repeat itself in exact manners, as changing circumstances and innovations alter the system's characteristics over time.

The speed of the process varies, as the move from exploitation to conservation can be quite tedious, while it speeds up from conservation to release, and onwards to reorganisation. While the release phase can be understood as the end of a system characteristic, reorganisation represents the beginning of an altered state of the system. The model aims at describing how resources in an ecosystem are exploited by different species in a competitive cycle towards increasing dominance and decreasing diversity. Over time, the cycle results in conservation, less flexibility, and increasing vulnerability to disturbance, which ultimately opens up for a creative destruction of the system. The system is regenerated through a process of innovation and experimentation. According to Holling and Gunderson (2002), the model can also be applied to human systems, in which the trajectory from exploitation to conservation would represent increasing control, stagnation, hierarchisation, and monopolisation.

The adaptive cycle operates at every level in society as nested relations and dependencies (Holling, Gunderson, & Peterson, 2002). Every level communicates information or resources to the other levels. As long as the connection between the levels are maintained, internal changes and transformation at each level may occur without the whole system losing its integrity. As such, the model is applicable to several levels in the human sphere, from the human agents constituting sections of society to society itself, and society as part of supra-regional environmental and social systems (Solich & Bradtmöller, 2017).

Importantly, the overarching structure has a stabilising effect on the individual cycles as it provides a kind of memory that allows for recovery within similar structural properties when change occurs. Charles Redman (2005, p. 73) exemplifies this with family structure. As he points out, although families might disintegrate because of divorce, the moral and cultural ties of society would nonetheless be instrumental for how the families reconstitute themselves. However, when transformations in individual cycles become overconnected, it might influence and destabilize the overall system as well. For instance, financial difficulties in several sections of society would affect society as a whole.

The mechanisms inherent in the system are the same for every part of the hierarchy. In the following, based on the work of Holling and Gunderson (2002), I will further outline some basic features of the model, in particular the different properties associated with the four sequential stages in the adaptive

cycle. These properties are important for understanding stagnation and radical change in a long-term perspective, furthermore how vulnerability to hazards is influenced by overall societal trajectories.

Being an innovative phase, reorganisation represents a state of opportunity and high potential for change, but with it comes also unpredictability and danger of crisis. In this, it opens up the possibility for multiple development paths ('reform'). It also represents both continuity and innovation, as reorganisation makes possible the introduction of new elements, as well as the retention of surviving elements from the former system and their continued participation in the new cycle. The character of the destruction process during the release phase is vital for the ensuing development. In human systems, a disintegration of the structural properties in society might result in revolutionary change ('revolt'), in which one political and ideological system is replaced by another. However, as pointed out by Eisenstadt (1988, p. 242), a complete disintegration is rare, even throughout profound political upheavals, as some degree of structural functionality is often preserved from one regime to another. Even the 1917 Russian Revolution, perhaps the most profound societal upheaval of modern times, rested, in part, on mobilisation and radicalisation of existing state organisations (Rowney, 2005). In other words, unless one population is replaced by another, some degree of structural and cultural continuity is to be expected.

During the reorganisation and exploitation phases diversity is high and connectedness is low, meaning that the system is not fully integrated or set (Holling & Gunderson, 2002, p. 41). Competition is high and over time some elements gradually become more dominant. In the process, they gain 'founding rights' over remaining capital, in turn increasingly shaping the development of the entire system. The potential is reduced during the exploitation phase, as the limits of change are contracted. However, resilience remains high as the system is characterised by diversity and entrepreneurship. The situation makes possible experiments that otherwise would be out-competed.

As competition moves the cycle in the direction of increasing dominance by a few species, both monopolisation and predictability become more evident. The need for cooperation creates clusters of mutually supportive activities and organisations. In the process, connectedness and internal control increase. Higher production is achieved through efficiency, interaction, and by adapting the system to the surroundings. The loop from exploitation to conservation maximises production and accumulation, while release to reorganisation maximises invention and re-assortment (Holling & Gunderson, 2002, p. 47). These processes cannot be maximised simultaneously, but follow each other sequentially, meaning that the model embraces growth and stability in the former, and change and variety in the latter.

While the system becomes more interdependent, population numbers and production levels are usually high. However, over time, the system becomes overconnected, conservative, and rigid. The margins decrease and the system stagnates. Nonetheless, the exploitation to conservation loop is rather slow and takes a considerably longer time to develop compared to the rather fast pace of release, reorganisation, and exploitation. The productive potential is high, as the system is both efficient and accumulative, but the ability to change and adapt to shifting circumstances is low. As a consequence, the rigidity of the system creates increasing vulnerability to disturbance. Even minor events might trigger large consequences. In corporative economic theory, this is the phase in which reorganisation, outsourcing, and downsizing might be imminent in an attempt to harvest the accumulated resources in the system. In social theory, it can be understood as a revolutionary phase during which the need for systemic change is perceived as unavoidable and necessary for societal renewal.

Radical and rapid change is, nonetheless, not a predestined outcome, at least not within set time frames. The system might prevail for considerable time, as it is self-supportive and in control of the available resources. Consequently, although vulnerability is high during conservation, the system is in need of some kind of disturbance to trigger systemic change, whether it is changing environmental preconditions or some kind of major external event that breaks down the established balance. In social systems warfare, invasions, subsistence failure, disasters, or riots might constitute destructive triggers. The argument presented here is that disasters are not preconditioned to generate major systemic change. It depends instead on the systemic circumstances present at the time. This is not to say that major disruptions are without consequence for a system situated in stages of high resilience, but rather that the system in such a state is better suited for absorbing disturbance and retaining its structure. The reasons for systemic collapse are not so much in the character of the destructive event itself, but in the internal dynamics that, over time, create vulnerability.

However, the theoretical basis for resilience theory, in particular concerning ecosystem stress (cf. Scheffer, Westley, Brock, & Holmgren, 2002), share many similarities with the economic principles of catastrophe theory (cf. Chapter 4.2). Resilience theory nonetheless differs from 1970s-style systems theory in that it emphasises both stability and transformation (Redman, 2005, p. 72). A basic feature is how the system constantly relates to disturbance. Furthermore, destabilising forces are important to maintain diversity, flexibility, and opportunity. As Holling and Gunderson (2002, p. 32) points out, resilience is not a fixed quantity that defines a system, or, as such, an ideal in itself, but rather that it can be the enemy of adaptive change. Creative destruction is required for maintaining adaptability and system regeneration, and, thus, be able to secure the existence of the system in spite of changing

preconditions. The goal of the system is not to preserve its temporal or spatial characteristics, but to maintain the very existence of its functionality.

Because of its rigidity, the adaptive cycle model struggles with some of the same basic weaknesses as catastrophe theory (cf. Chapter 4.2), as the complexity of social systems is often difficult to take into full account in an idealised model. This is further complicated by the fragmented nature of the archaeological record. As will be discussed in the next chapter, this had led to some debate on how the adaptive cycle should be implemented in archaeological research. Particular problems arise when attempting to relate the structural properties of the adaptive cycles to archaeological complexes, as the political and economic structures of prehistory are often an unknown factor and are more prone to change than present-day fixed nation states and political organisations.

5.2.3 RESILIENCE THEORY AND ARCHAEOLOGY

Owing much to the works of Redman (2005), resilience theory was picked up early on in archaeology and soon generated a huge body of literature on the subject, including a special issue of *Quaternary International* (446) in 2017. In this chapter, I do not intend to give a full review of resilience theory in archaeology but rather discuss some possibilities and limitations concerning its implementation in current research. Marcel Bradtmöller et al. (2017) distinguish between two main approaches: operationalisation and conceptualisation. Conceptualisation can be defined as analogous, which means that the cycle is used as a metaphor for explaining successive events observable in the archaeological record.

Operationalisation, on the other hand, means that the adaptive cycle is used as an analytical tool for directly identifying distinct patterns in archaeological datasets. In addition, there are less theorised frameworks, using resilience instead as a concept for discussing cultural persistence in times of major disturbance (eg. McAnany & Yoffee, 2010b; Middleton, 2017a, pp. 91-94).

Several studies have used the adaptive cycle model to create analogies to established chronological datasets, functioning as a tool for understanding system dynamics and the process of change in a long-term perspective (Bradtmöller et al., 2017; Freeman, Hard, & Mauldin, 2017). Often considered an important theoretical innovation for the discipline, this is by far the most common application of resilience theory.

The idealised properties of the model have some limitations when it comes to contextualisation, as evidence might be forced into a predictable pattern at the expense of historical particularities.

Furthermore, as opposed to a more common-sense understanding of resilience, it has been questioned whether a generalised schematic, like the adaptive cycle model, has much to offer (Middleton, 2017a, pp. 92-94). A comparative case study by Eva Svensson et al. (2012) serves to illustrate some of these concerns. Their study attempts to apply the adaptive cycle model on five rural medieval settlements in Sweden and Norway, by using potential, connectedness, and remembering as analytical concepts. Their study suggests that accumulated knowledge and experience were decisive for the peasants' ability to adapt to changing circumstances, thus constituting the most important factor for the communities' level of resilience. However, their final remark is somewhat intriguing as they stated that resilience theory had "... helped us to look at the investigated rural settlements in more analytical ways, but we would probably have reached the same conclusions in other ways as well" (E. Svensson et al., 2012, p. 104). Elnaz Rashidian (2021) reports on similar concerns after experiencing that resilience theory added little value to her research project, thus becoming an unnecessary add-on.

However, it might be unjust to dismiss resilience theory on such grounds completely. As a single-level analysis, the study of E. Svensson et al. (2012) is limited to the adaptational strategies documented at the sites in question. Furthermore, the temporal scope of the study was situated within a well-known historical and medieval framework, in which archaeological results are easier contextualised and synthesised, and therefore often less theory-driven. An application of resilience theory might have quite contrasting results in a firm prehistoric setting, even when restricted in similar fashion to site-level analysis (eg. Cascalheira, Bicho, Manne, & Horta, 2017). When societal characteristics and developments are not predefined, synthesising is more dependent on theoretical and anthropological analogies. Nonetheless, the study still exemplifies some limitations of the application of the resilience theory on archaeological features, namely the lack of a proper methodology. To move beyond mere generalisations, the structural properties of the model need to be combined with some kind of measurability (Bradtmöller et al., 2017, p. 4).

There are also some challenges concerning the evolutionary sequences of the cycle itself. Because of the unpredictable character of the model, the adaptive cycle model was not meant to be understood as a fixed theory for systemic change, but more as a metaphor for understanding internal dynamics, events, and causes (Holling & Gunderson, 2002, p. 33). In order to develop a framework that has generality, one has to operate with properties that transcend the case-specific variables and uncertainties. However, the character of change is not given but rather dependent on the circumstances and systemic dynamics at play. As pointed out by Redman (2005, p. 73), some societies do not necessarily go through all phases of the cycle, or at an equal pace. The sequential stages might be of greater or lesser duration depending on the related contextual properties and external stress factors. Furthermore, resilience is not a single

variable, but varies according to the type, exposure to, and intensity of the stress factors (Solich & Bradtmöller, 2017, p. 111). Society might prove resilient towards certain types of disturbance but vulnerable towards others. In general, short-term major disturbances might prove less dangerous to society over time compared to a sustained crisis. Warfare, migrations, natural disasters, and drought might affect society in fundamentally different ways, depending on the specific developments of the stress factors and the character of society. The impact value, but also the complexity of the processes, are difficult to model, as contingency in itself is fundamental for how situations develop in each specific case. Therefore, the adaptive cycle model does not offer an explanation on societal change *per se*. To be able to disentangle and analyse case-specific past societal change, the model needs to be combined with a contextual approach analysing the specific drivers and variables affecting the course of action (Freeman et al., 2017).

The main challenge which remains is to establish a valid system for measuring and assessing resilience in prehistoric societies. Bradtmöller et al. (2017) argue that we need to set up resilience indices for different types of societies and standardise the way resilience theory is applied. In this, Bradtmöller et al. (2017) calls for a more stringent operationalising of the adaptive cycle model, as opposed to traditional conceptualisations. A few attempts have been made to use connectedness as an analytical tool for studying human-environmental and human-human relationships by identifying behavioural and demographic shifts in deep-time perspectives (Freeman et al., 2017; Solich & Bradtmöller, 2017). Relevant topics may include social relations, long-distance networks, social stratification, cultural expressions, demographics, and land-use strategies, whereby indices of population growth and increasing cooperation, interaction, and interdependence can be understood as a societal development towards system conservatism.

Martin Solich and Bradtmöller (2017) stress the need to define connectedness specifically for each case and each level of the panarchy, all the way from group level to supra-regional entities. However, a stringent operationalisation requires high-resolution datasets, which are more often the exception rather than the rule in archaeology. Dating-precision, quality, and comprehensiveness of the archaeological records are all of critical importance. Defining micro-level and short-term adaptive cycles might be particularly challenging, as is finding datasets that have similar resolution and quality on all required analytical levels. Samantha Allcock (2017) therefore turns to two temporal scales for the Cappadocia region of Turkey, the meso (decadal-centennial) and macro (centennial-millennial), in which she defines four main macro-level cycles from the Neolithic up to Ottoman times. By comparing broad-scale settlement trends with climatic and environmental data, she uses the adaptive cycle to synthesise long-term developments of the region. Her study demonstrates the potential of conceptualising the cycle in a

deep-time perspective, but might also serve to illustrate the limitations of the adaptive cycle as a stringent method. Her dataset is compiled from three different survey projects, which are associated with contrasting methodological issues of site visibility and investigator bias (Allcock, 2017, p. 68). For instance, a scientific preoccupation with urban sites has caused a certain degree of disproportionate documentation, affecting for instance the ratio of urban versus minor rural sites. Later anthropogenic activities also constitute a considerable source-critical factor, especially when it comes to Byzantine and medieval sites. These sites are often buried underneath modern townships, resulting in a considerable underrepresentation in the archaeological datasets (Allcock, 2017, p. 71). Consequently, the site count data becomes problematic when compared to the relative high numbers of middle Bronze Age, Hellenistic, and Roman sites. However, what is important is how the different chronological periods are associated with different occupational strategies and settlement types. These variables constitute important premises for Allcock's study, but would be difficult to model and measure in a strict operational approach. The source-critical issues are important, as they more often would be the rule rather than the exception in archaeological datasets.

Operationalising the cycle would also have to handle some fundamental issues when it comes to defining the very systems in question, a topic that I find rarely discussed in resilience theory papers. If operationalising means defining measurable parameters, the character and reach of the systemic properties needs to be addressed. Landscape formations, such as the Cappadocian region, constitute physical boundaries appropriate for data systematisation but need not reflect neither political nor cultural entities. Fauseit (2016, p. 16) argues that adaptive cycles are best applied to institutional structures and not various components of physical scale. However, household, site, and group levels might be possible to define in an archaeological setting, but the process becomes more difficult when moving up to overarching political and societal structures of varying extent, durability, and significance. It becomes even more difficult in prehistoric settings, where the socio-political structure of past societies is often unknown. How, in an undefined socio-political context, do we set the boundaries of regional and supra-regional entities? Cultural expressions, as opposed to political structures, might be easier to define in archaeological datasets, but are nonetheless not fixed entities as they often vary considerably along spatial and temporal scales. Considering the many challenges associated with the method, one might ask whether a stringent operationalisation, as opposed to a mere general conceptualisation, would add much to the analysis. In itself, the concept is difficult to model on a given society. As Eisenstadt (1988) pointed out in his critique of catastrophe theory, populations are not equally distributed within different social systems, but are in part overlapping and influencing each other, not just vertically in a hierarchical manner (as in resilience theory) but also horizontally. As such, human agency is difficult to operationalise in a strict and predictive model. In line with the intentions of Gunderson and Holling (2002, p. 33), the adaptive cycle model has more to offer as a metaphor and an analogy to system dynamics, as a way of

understanding and conceptualising adaptational processes, change, and reorganisation, in contrast to being employed as an explanatory model on a given archaeological context.

Resilience theory and the adaptive cycle model have nonetheless contributed important insights to the understanding of past societal dynamics and human-environmental interaction. In particular, using connectedness as an analytical tool has proven to be a valuable approach for assessing the development of social networks and land-use strategies (Freeman et al., 2017; Solich & Bradtmöller, 2017). However, the concept of connectedness addresses first and foremost the internal dynamics and the process towards increasing accumulation and interdependence, and less on the specific preconditions that generate societal vulnerability to disturbance. In this, there are certain basic similarities with the analytical properties of engineering resilience and catastrophe theory, as societal vulnerability is first and foremost understood as a cost-benefit ratio with little external force acting upon it.

As Fauseit (2016, p. 16) points out, systemic models, like the adaptive cycle model, appear first and foremost to address *how* societies evolve, rather than *why*. When it comes to past disaster studies, causation remains a fundamental issue, in particular if one aims to address the significance of environmental factors for societal change. By some means, expressions of connectedness, such as economic stagnation and increasing hierarchisation, serve to explain a socio-cultural setting in which vulnerability is allowed to develop. However, this is only a part of the greater picture and is therefore limited as a causal explanation. Alone it is insufficient for explaining why system conservatism ultimately develops into a process of rapid and radical change. Given that resilience must be understood in multivariable terms, the explanations must consequently be sought in case-specific circumstances and preconditions. A contextual approach to past disaster studies requires a strong emphasis on how resilience is constituted in a given society, or, more explicitly, how vulnerability to different types of disturbance is created and maintained. In order to do so, the concept of societal vulnerability must be analysed on its own terms, and attention must be given to how it is intrinsically linked to the social construction of disasters.

5.3 The vulnerable society

Disasters are often understood in terms of immediate and cataclysmic events in which the focus often lies on the destruction itself. The attention paid to dramatic circumstances tends to favour interpretations that over-emphasise its role in and importance to social change, also labelled 'then it was destroyed by the volcano' school of history, at the expense of more complex and long-term explanations (Gräslund & Price, 2012, pp. 428-429). Cataclysmic interpretations have made their mark on the Fimbulwinter

discourse as well (Chapter 3.3), but are even more prominent in the geoscientific literature where direct links are often drawn between environmental events and major turns in world history (for instance Büntgen et al., 2020; Büntgen et al., 2016; McConnell et al., 2020). However, disasters are all-encompassing and multidimensional, simultaneously affecting social, biological, political, and economic aspects, but also occurring at the interface of society, technology, and the environment (Oliver-Smith, 1996, 2002). Thus, disasters are not just singular events with defined beginnings and ends, but are rooted in long-term social and environmental dynamics that create the very possibility for hazards to develop. To a certain degree, catastrophes signal the failure of society to adapt to certain features of its naturally- and socially-constructed environments in a sustainable fashion.

Being fundamentally destructive, disasters put society into stark relief by revealing conflicts and diverging interests between groups and individuals – matters otherwise veiled behind practice, tradition, and symbology. In some ways society and culture become unclothed, as windows of opportunities are opened in which society is renegotiated and redefined (Hoffman, 1999, p. 310; Oliver-Smith, 2015). Thus, disasters are firmly associated with societal change, but not necessarily as game-changers in their own right. By setting a critical stage that motivates for social action, power arrangements can be altered to bring forth underlying and subdued impulses, thus influencing society in radical new directions. However, a crisis can also result in a reinforced political system entrenched in traditional ways, or accelerate social, political, and economic processes already underway (Hoffman, 1999, p. 311; Oliver-Smith, 1996). In other words, the outcome of disasters is not given. The process of change can also be gradual and partial, which stands somewhat in contrast to the immediate character of the disaster itself. Several factors are instrumental, such as the magnitude and character of destruction as well as the socio-political dynamics and character of the affected societies. Fundamental is the concept of vulnerability and how it is constructed through human practice and social organisation (Oliver-Smith, 2015). This aspect is crucial for understanding the mechanisms that cause different levels of impact along spatial, temporal, and social scales, thus contributing to a variety of responses and consequences in the aftermath of destruction. In this chapter, I will outline the social and multidimensional aspects of disaster and discuss the potential of vulnerability as an analytical tool for understanding societal impact and human responses.

5.3.1 THE SOCIAL CHARACTER OF DISASTERS

In the field of psychology, the concept of control is considered fundamental for human welfare, perception, and self-preservation (Jind, 1998). During disastrous circumstances, whether it is on a personal or communal level, a sense of loss of control can be experienced as traumatic and pave the way for changes in behaviour and cognition. Consequently, it becomes important to regain a sense of control of your personal environment, either by direct action on your own initiative, or, if it fails, by submitting to

authorities, to the circumstances, or to the overall development. In this process, a sense of rational meaning and causal explanation becomes more important; the harm one is experiencing becomes justified, or blame is projected either on forces out of your control or on other people. In this process, one questions former beliefs and conditions. Thus, crisis creates the conditions for radical change, both at individual and communal levels. Structural properties that upheld previous arrangements and practices are broken down, and the development becomes more influenced by dominant or emerging powerful social constellations who are able to seize the initiative (Oliver-Smith, 2002, 2015). A recent and well-documented example is the Indian Ocean Tsunami event of 2004, which heavily shaped the worldview and cognitive perception of the local crisis-stricken population (Hastrup, 2008). The world was perceived as more unpredictable and their environment as dangerous. The traumatic experiences and breakdown of local fishing communities also paved the way for societal changes initiated by powerful economical groups that invalidated previous arrangements between locals and governmental institutions (Klein, 2007). Thus, the situation became firmly entrenched in the ongoing neoliberal economic development to which the local fishing communities were no longer able to resist.

Susannah Hoffman (1999) argues that the character and scope of disasters, as well as population and cultural complexity and background, are important variables for understanding both smaller and bigger socio-cultural changes, including the duration of the changes. Important is also whether the whole of society, or specific social layers and groups, are affected, as well as to what degree subsistence resources and material culture are damaged. Hoffman (1999, p. 308) also distinguishes between deep structure and surface structure, the former defined as the invisible rules of human behaviour and perception — in other words, the deep structural principles of society. Surface structure, on the other hand, is understood as cultural and social expressions, such as habits, practices, and ceremonies. Accordingly, surface structure is seen as more prone to transform, but nevertheless organized by deep structure, which is more resistant to change. Drawing on Marcel Mauss (1995 [1924]), she assesses the deep organizing principles of society as rooted in the exchange systems, such as the kinship system, the economic system, or language. By applying these premises to disasters, she argues that deep structural change occurs when one of the exchange systems are sufficiently affected (Hoffman, 1999, pp. 308-309). Deep structural changes are enduring and significant, while minor disruptions to the organizing principles of society would result in mere superficial modifications. Her assessment of deep structure and surface structure is reminiscent of resilience thinking, in particular how change is understood as happening at different paces at different structural levels (Chapter 5.2.2).

However, disasters do not just *happen*. They may be caused by human actions, such as warfare or technology, or environmental hazards, but nonetheless occur at the interface between human and

natural systems (Oliver-Smith & Hoffman, 2002). The social factor, such as social structure and the character of human interaction with the environment, is significant for the course of development. In other words, the conjunction of a human population and a potential destructive agent does not inevitably produce a disaster. Whether it develops into a disaster depends on the total ecological system, including natural, modified, and constructed features (Oliver-Smith & Hoffman, 2002, p. 3). Disasters emerge as such in the moment they appear within a social system, when they affect *someone*. Consequently, a major physical event, such as an explosive volcanic eruption, is not understood as a disaster unless it represents a danger to society. Whether a disaster is rooted in technological, environmental, or social issues, the human mechanisms involved in face of an extreme situation is nonetheless quite similar (Oliver-Smith, 2002, p. 25). The concept of disaster is all about how it is perceived and experienced by humans, and less about the morphology and development of the event itself. Consequently, disasters are profoundly social in character. They are not to be understood as something unpredictable and extreme happening outside society, but something happening *in* society. As socially constructed and experienced, disasters generate a multitude of explanations and interpretations depending on the sets of circumstances involved for each particular group and individual (Oliver-Smith & Hoffman, 2002). Disasters, no matter the magnitude, extent, and persistence, are first and foremost experienced at a local and individual level (cf. Eriksen, 2016), and expressed through a cultural lens of collective memory, belief, myths, and human behaviour (Oliver-Smith, 2015, pp. 548, 551). Conflicting accounts can be found alongside social distinctions, such as class, gender, ethnicity, age and profession, but also across the geographical landscape, thus challenging common cultural values and belief systems (Oliver-Smith, 2002, pp. 25-26; Oliver-Smith & Hoffman, 2002). During the process of destruction, recovery and reconstruction, are contradicting notions expressed, such as cooperation and conflict, and continuity and change.

The key factor for understanding the development of destructive agents, and their societal impact, is embedded in the concept of vulnerability. Vulnerability is often defined as the "... characteristics of a person or group in terms of their capacity to anticipate, cope with, resist, and recover from the impact of a natural hazard" (Oliver-Smith, 2002, p. 28, with references), in other words as 'susceptibility to harm' (Torrence, 2019, p. 259). An important premise for this approach is the assessment of disasters as processes, rather than events, as it is conditioned by factors in the past and the present, but also affects future conditions and course of actions (Oliver-Smith, 2002; Oliver-Smith & Hoffman, 2002, p. 12; Torrence, 2019, p. 258). A disaster develops in the context of a historically produced pattern of vulnerability, in which social, material or environmental damage becomes unavoidable (Oliver-Smith, 2002, p. 28; Oliver-Smith & Hoffman, 2002, p. 3).

5.3.2 THE MULTIDIMENSIONALITY OF DISASTERS

In line with the discussion above, vulnerability is rooted in structural mechanisms in society which can, at varying degrees, be managed and changed, but also influenced by risk drivers like population growth, migration, distributional systems, land-use patterns, infrastructure, environmental degradation, and poverty (Oliver-Smith et al., 2017, p. 471). Vulnerability is consequently not understood as a singular value that can be measured and precisely defined, but varies according to different types of threats and circumstances. Certain aspects of society can prove resilient in face of one type of hazard, but highly susceptible to another. The level of vulnerability can also change over time as successful short-term measures can generate long-term unforeseen consequences, especially if the physical environment is altered by human practice or climate change. Successful adaptations to certain environmental factors also have the potential of creating vulnerability to other potential threats. Vulnerability must consequently be understood as contextual and studied in relation to the human-environmental system in which it takes place.

The growing interest within anthropology for current ecological and climatic threats is often coupled with attempts to influence modern policymaking, in particular in the field of disaster risk reduction, which, however, tends to be somewhat more focused on technocratic rather than socio-cultural perspectives, thus being at risk of downplaying the root causes and societal processes that generate vulnerable conditions (Oliver-Smith, 2016). Effort is therefore put into developing analytical frameworks for systemising and disentangling the social mechanisms that create vulnerability to hazards (Oliver-Smith et al., 2017, p. 471). By focusing on risk drivers, root cause analysis (Figure 5.4) approaches disasters as systemic processes unfolding over time, in particular by addressing the policies and practices that influence the development. The gradual build-up of structural and behavioural patterns results in a specific set of unsafe conditions which constitute levels of vulnerability when exposed to hazards and danger. Disaster risk is not only dependent on society's predisposed vulnerability, but also on the character of hazards (technological, natural or socio-natural), and on society's exposure to hazards, i.e. the danger of physical damage on elements required for livelihood and social well-being. However, there can be no disaster without a triggering physical event, whether technological, environmental, or socio-natural. Societal resilience, in terms of capabilities and capacities, may help to overcome hazards and reduce disaster impact through matters like emergency management, legislations, and policy-making (Oliver-Smith et al., 2017, p. 472). Disaster risk research in applied anthropology aims at enhancing societal resilience through models like root cause analysis, but resilience, as an analytical tool alongside vulnerability, is somewhat less emphasized and developed in this perspective.

Figure 5.4: A schematic representation of the social construction of risk and disaster. E: Exposure, V: Vulnerability, H: Hazards, N: Natural, T: Technological, SN: Socio-natural, DR: Disaster risk (from Oliver-Smith et al., 2017, figure 1, license number 5043540431415)²⁷.

Nonetheless, important for disaster risk research is how vulnerability and disaster impact are rooted in several social domains, like ideology, economy, and demography, but also in the environmental sphere, like ecology. Whether a situation, event, or process becomes destructive depends on a variety of societal, cultural, and environmental preconditions, in essence the very nature and character of human-environmental interaction. Consequently, vulnerability can also be differentiated along social axes, meaning that different groups in society are exposed to different levels of risk and disaster impact. In this way a coherent human-environmental approach differs substantially from eco-determinism, as collapse or crisis are not to be understood as unavoidable consequences of environmental degradation or cataclysmic events. The underlying research questions are *why* some destructive agents turn into disasters for society and others not, and for *whom*. In other words, vulnerability expresses the multidimensionality of disasters by focusing on the totality of human-environmental interaction (Oliver-Smith, 2002, p. 28). This approach opens up for a multitude of potential outcomes, highlighting the complexity of social systems and human responses when confronted with substantial risk.

²⁷ <https://s100.copyright.com/CustomAdmin/PLF.jsp?ref=13ef330b-573c-4c28-bcfa-2fd5d43b1fd2>

Despite having great potential for anthropological research and public disaster mitigation, the method would prove more difficult to employ on prehistoric societies. The archaeological record differs considerably from the anthropological in terms of temporal resolution, types of proxies, and data quality. For instance, Oliver-Smith et al. (2017) emphasises the importance of political agendas and economic interests and the need to systemise processes and chains of events that are not directly empirically observable, but can instead be identified through the actual conditions they generate. This causes certain methodological challenges in disaster anthropology, requiring considerable interpretative efforts and the use of extensive information, which can become even more problematic for a fragmented and incomplete archaeological record with low resolution. However, root cause analysis still provides useful principles that can be built upon in archaeological disaster research, including how disaster development and societal vulnerability should be understood. Important is the premise that disasters are multidimensional, influenced by both human and environmental domains, but that they also operate simultaneously at different temporal, spatial, and social scales, thus creating the potential for considerable diversity in the aftermath of destruction.

Figure 5.5: Schematic representation of the spatial and temporal dimensions of volcanic eruptions (from Riede, 2019, figure 1, license CC BY-NC-ND 4.0)²⁸.

The spatiality and temporality of disasters, and how they affect vulnerability, resilience, and recovery in prehistoric societies, have been emphasised by researchers like Riede (2019), Sheets (1999, 2012), and Robin Torrence (2016, 2019), each highlighting mobility as a key factor for societal survival. Riede (2014,

²⁸ <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-nd/4.0/deed.en>

2019) pays particular attention to the physical attributes of volcanic eruptions (Figure 5.5) and attempts to develop a systematic approach that draws on both volcanology and disaster risk research. Fluoride poisoning of water, respiratory health impact, and digestive and dental problems due to hard and sharp volcanic particles all constitute major and direct physical consequences of volcanism (Riede, 2019). Destruction and burial of vegetation under tephra fallout also causes major challenges for humans, livestock, and wildlife. As such, explosive volcanism represents a major threat for any human society within proximal and medial distance from the eruption site regardless of socio-cultural particularities (cf. Riede, 2019). Numerous factors add to the level and character of vulnerability, such as subsistence strategies, demography, social networks, and resource competition. Despite the difficulties, the direct physical effects of volcanic events are often rather short-term; Torrence (2016) highlights examples of societal persistence at Papua New Guinea, where sites were often reoccupied after a short period of abandonment. Exchange networks and social relations are ascribed with considerable importance for societal continuity by not only making possible refuging for the small and mobile populations in question, but also by providing opportunities for cultural innovation.

Thus, mobility, as a temporal measurement, or as a cultural phenomenon in itself, can be understood as a key factor for societal survival during disruptive events. However, migration is also associated with considerable difficulty as it is affected by conditions outside the refugees' control and influence, consequently rendering them vulnerable to exploitation. Access to possible refugee areas depends on the character and relationship to neighbouring groups and their ability (and interest) in aiding support. Refugees are in a vulnerable position and are often capitalized on as disenfranchised groups are the easiest to ignore in times of stress or emergency by those in positions of authority (Sheets, 2012, p. 50; Torrence, 2016, p. 13). Furthermore, without access to the means and resources necessary for communal feasts, trade, and maintaining social networks, leading families can experience difficulties in holding on to their rank and status within their own communities. It should also be taken into consideration that critical situations often increase resource competition, and cause conflicts between previously friendly groups. Even highly mobile and egalitarian hunter-gatherer societies might face considerable difficulties when exposed to major environmental events, in some cases involving permanent abandonment of the affected regions (Riede, Oetelaar, & VanderHoek, 2017).

Sheets (1999, 2012) puts a particular emphasis on the social attributes of disasters when comparing small and complex prehistoric Meso-American societies, and found social complexity, political organisation, and inter-societal conflicts important for disaster development when exposed to explosive volcanism. He found the egalitarian villagers of Arenal area in Costa Rica, with low population density, high levels of mobility, and a broad subsistence strategy, more resilient than the stratified and urbanized Meso-

American city-states. The city-states were characterised by complex redistributive economies and intensive maize-based agricultural systems, relying on long-distance trade-networks, centralised authority, and markets. The densely populated, specialised, and top-down economic and administrative system were thus vulnerable if major events caused disruptions in the societal infrastructure. Accordingly, the TBJ event (see Chapter 2.3.1), and global climate cooling in subsequent years, weakened the lowland Maya city-states and contributed to increased warfare and resource competition. The demise was, nonetheless, not a quick one. The final collapse happened in the 9th century, after centuries of accelerating warfare, deforestation, overpopulation, soil deterioration, and nutrition difficulties.

In an interesting observation, Sheets (2012, p. 56) notices that the Maya architectural apex occurred during the late 7th and early 8th century, in what could easily be described as a golden age of monumental construction and artistic achievements. This would normally contradict the notion of societal crisis on the verge of collapse. However, the assessment of the Maya crisis is also a question of perspective. When considering land-use, nutrition, subsistence strategies, and population health, Sheets points out that the apex occurred two centuries earlier. The development after the 6th century is characterised by decreasing stature among both commoners and elites, a development attributed to exacerbated malnutrition. Thus, the narrative is one of both resilience and vulnerability, as societal persistence gradually gave way for patterns of vulnerability that in the long run threatened their existence. The example illustrates well the many variables in play as vulnerability is a process unfolding and changing over time, depending on the character of the society in question.

Much of the vulnerability literature in current archaeology is preoccupied with the direct impact of major environmental events, in which mobility often becomes a necessary measure for societal survival (Riede, 2016, 2019; Sheets, 1999, 2012; Torrence, 2016, 2019). There are nonetheless certain basic differences concerning volcanic fallout and climate change that affect how human responses may develop. In 6th-century Scandinavia, the consequences of distant explosive eruptions would not be experienced as a direct and immediate physical danger, but more in terms of a gradual and vaguely defined change in temperature, weather, and solar radiation, in which human responses would be less characterised by abrupt action and alertness. Hemispheric climate change also has the potential of affecting vast areas for a considerable number of years, thus potentially limiting the number of unaffected territories in which refuting might be a possibility. In this, there is a distinct risk of an accelerating destabilising situation in which migration is understood more in terms of conflict than adaptation. Climate change, if critically affecting subsistence strategies, is likely to increase resource competition within and in-between groups, contributing to conflict, migrations, and probably warfare.

However, migration has also been described as fostering resilience against climate change (Degroot et al., 2021, p. 546). Mobility should not just be understood in terms of refuging and as a response to crisis, but also as a social practice in its own right. The concept of multi-locality aims at bridging the presumed binary opposition between permanent residency and mobility, and describes a social practice of regular absence and presence at several households, reflecting rootedness in more than one place (G. Wood, Hilti, Kramer, & Schier, 2015). Although mainly associated with late modernity, the concept is not confined to a particular part of the world and has several historical precursors. It resembles the multi-residential lifestyle often suggested for the ruler and the warrior aristocracy of the Scandinavian Iron Age, in which sites like Åker functioned as one of several ruler sites (cf. Røstad, 2020, p. 25). In this perspective, multi-locality would mainly be understood in terms of exercising hegemonic control over large territories, but the concept also includes certain social capacities and possibilities that can be utilised during times of societal stress. For north-west Africa, mobility and migration networks have been described as important for climate adaptation in face of global warming, not in terms of refuging but as a provider of knowledge, resources, and cooperation opportunities through the diaspora networks (Scheffran, Marmer, & Sow, 2012). The examples are not directly comparable, but the latter nonetheless illustrates how social capital, generated through human mobility, represents possibilities for disaster mitigation. Mobility was not only a feature for the ruling elite, but also characterised mid-1st-millennia Europe in general. Both Gjerpe (2017) and Geir Grønnesby (2019) argue for a mobile settlement pattern in the Early Iron Age that becomes only gradually replaced by permanent farmsteads, in particular during the Late Iron Age. Marie Amundsen and Per D. Fredriksen (2014) discuss the concept of a decentralised farm structure in relation to a wider socio-economic framework in which outfield resource exploitation, directed towards long-distance trade and exchange, was an important underlying mechanism. The Roman Iron Age and Migration Period in particular, but also to a certain degree the Merovingian Period, is often described in terms of extensive mobility and close interaction between the Germanic tribes and ruling elites in the form of migrations, warfare, refuging, hostage exchange, gift exchange, alliances, and political cooperation, interactions which seem to have included Scandinavian nobilities, and, with it considerable knowledge of the outside world (cf. Gundersen, 2010b; Hedeager & Tvarnø, 2001, pp. 267-280; Herschend, 2009, pp. 377-381; Iversen, 2019, pp. 249-250; Skre, 2019, pp. 227-228). In this context, there existed considerable social capital that could be utilised in times of social and economic crisis, either by means of aggressive warfare for resources, cultural innovation, or through enforced cooperation and exchange of foodstuffs. Thus, mobility in 6th-century Scandinavia can be understood in terms of both resilience and conflict, depending on the socio-political context and how it evolves during a perceived crisis.

When taking the multidimensional character of disasters into consideration, it becomes evident that single variables would not only prove inadequate for assessing the societal consequences, but that the

attributes and instrumental values of the variables themselves would also vary according to circumstances and the resulting chains of events. As discussed in relation to the concept of mobility, it cannot be understood in terms of either vulnerability or resilience. It must be assessed within a broader political context, one in which the character and robustness of social relations and networks are important factors.

This underpins the importance of not only analysing disasters in relation to the societies and geo-political situations in which they emerge, but also approaching them in line with the spatial and temporal attributes of the environmental events. This requires approaches that move beyond mere environmental or socio-economic perspectives to disasters, if one aims to understand the social dynamics that may be caused or influenced by them.

A considerable challenge for archaeology remains the character of the archaeological record itself. Fragmented, and often with low temporal resolution, it rarely allows for detailed studies of the chains of events and obscures how crisis affects different segments of society. Consequently, the level of analysis is usually kept to society at whole, or within broad social or cultural categories. However, human-environmental approaches to disasters have nonetheless proved fruitful in a number of archaeological studies by opening up for considerable diversity in our understanding of disaster impact and human responses.

5.3.3 VULNERABILITY, RESILIENCE AND ADAPTATION

Although vulnerability offers important insights to disaster studies, the concept might still have a somewhat limited scope. For example, vulnerability studies in anthropology tend to focus on the immediate preface, presence, and consequences for disaster development, and less on the long-term socio-cultural processes pre-dating or post-dating the catastrophe (Torrence, 2019, p. 259). What happens after incidents of societal disintegration – the process of regeneration and reorganisation – has traditionally been a neglected topic in past disaster research (Schwartz, 2006, p. 3), albeit increasingly emphasised in a number of recent publications (Faulseit, 2016, p. 19).

As outlined in Chapter 5.2.2, societal defragmentation and radical change is rarely totalising, and therefore is not to be understood as an end-point to a given social trajectory. In order to understand past disasters, pasts, presents, and futures need to be integrated into the analysis. Furthermore, important for understanding causes and effects is the disentangling of ongoing social processes from the direct consequences of major disruptions, and, as such, separating causation from correlation (Torrence, 2019,

p. 258). Thus, deep-time perspectives are required, which can be provided by using resilience theory as a conceptual framework for interpreting the process of change and the social construction of vulnerability (cf. Chapter 5.2.3).

As analytical tools, vulnerability and resilience have different qualities. Riede et al. (2017, p. 25) understand vulnerability in terms of 'limits to adaptation', whilst resilience can be understood as coterminous with adaptability. As vulnerability is a negative characteristic of society, the term might be less suited for analysing situations that do not develop into stages of critical danger in which disaster is avoided (Torrence, 2019, p. 259). For a better understanding of long-term processes like adaptation and recovery, which seem to be more common throughout prehistory than societal collapse (Middleton, 2017a, pp. 79, 88; Torrence, 2019, p. 260), more effort should perhaps be put into studying the mechanisms of social memory, learning, and innovation. Vulnerability is usually assessed after a disaster or crisis takes place, in which the outcome is already given. On the other hand, resilience and adaptation are insufficient for assessing a disaster development, and, as such, are also insufficient as tools for understanding the character of crisis – and the character of change. Thus, a coherent human-environmental framework requires an implementation of a variety of mutually-complementary and reinforcing analytical concepts.

Torrence (2019) structures vulnerability, resilience, and adaptation along a timeline of pasts, presents, and futures, in which vulnerability represents the immediate impact of a disaster onset, i.e. the present. Resilience is understood as rooted in the past, as the ability of social groups to respond to and recover from a disaster. The third aspect, adaptation, is associated with the future, in terms of innovations and changes resulting from the experience of the disaster. As such, adaptation is the process of becoming resilient, as accumulated experiences and knowledge, eventually enclosing the process in a cyclic manner reminiscent of Resilience Theory. In this way Torrence (2019) aims at bridging resilience and vulnerability into one coherent framework that moves beyond the disaster itself, but nonetheless recognises its social inheritance and interaction with long-term social dynamics. She follows up by listing a number of key variables associated with social, political, and productivity robustness, which in varying degrees affect societal vulnerability, resilience, and ability to adapt. Although vulnerability should not be understood merely in short-term perspectives, as it is rooted in deep-time social mechanisms and structures (Oliver-Smith et al., 2017), her approach offers an interesting framework for how root causes can be structured and analysed in a prehistoric context. In the following, I will build on this approach in an attempt to disentangle how societal vulnerability and resilience might have been constituted in a Scandinavian Iron Age context.

5.4 Towards a human-environmental approach to the 6th century transition

The Fimbulwinter discourse reflects a growing interest in environmental factors in Scandinavian archaeology. However, less effort has, so far, been put into developing analytical frameworks that allow for a more coherent approach to the possible causal relations between climate change and societal change (Chapter 3.3.2). In Chapters 5.2 and 5.3, I have discussed the social inheritance of crisis and disaster in relation to the concepts of vulnerability, resilience, and adaptation, all of which will be utilised as analytical tools in the present thesis. The three concepts are complementary, but each offers different perspectives on the temporal and social attributes of disruptive events. Resilience theory emphasises the long-term social dynamics that, in general, create vulnerable conditions, while root cause analysis targets the specific mechanisms and practices that influence disaster development and impact. Adaptation is associated with the reconstruction phase and the process of building future resilience. When combined, the three concepts offer an analytical framework through which disaster impact, human responses, and the overall societal development can be better understood along both temporal and spatial scales (Torrence, 2019). Thus, three basic principles become important for the analysis:

- Utilising long-term perspectives
- Identifying risk drivers
- Contingency

As a starting point, disasters are recognised as case-specific. Different types of disturbances are associated with different types of risk, depending on the circumstances and societal character. Society might prove more resilient to certain types of hazards than others, meaning that vulnerability is not a single variable that can be measured and precisely defined in a predictive manner. In other words, the 6th-century cooling should not be addressed as one uniform event for the whole of Iron Age Scandinavia, but must be analysed in light of the environmental and social preconditions within each area or society in question. Thus, regionality and long-term perspectives must be emphasised in order to disentangle the practices and structures constructing vulnerability to hazards in the first place, and for identifying patterns that indicate possible adaptational strategies.

DOMAINS	CATEGORIES	VARIABLES
POLITICAL	Conflicts	Within group, between groups, migrations
	Networks	Distance, competitive/friendly, intermarriage, mobility
	Communication	Networks, technology
	Decision-making	Household/tribal/state level, thing/assemblies
	Demography	Population size, structure, public health, disease load
	Ideology	Ties to land/places, belief systems guiding behaviour
	Knowledge	Tradition/innovation, oral/written, familiarity with hazards
	Social structure	Egalitarian/hierarchical
	Power arrangements	Centralized/decentralized
ECONOMIC	Trade	Distance, resources, necessities/luxury
	Resource allocation	Centralized authority
	Craft	Specialized, household
	Settlement structure	Scattered/clustered, architectural robustness
	Ownership	Collective/private/centralized/local
	Storage	Capacity, conservations methods, climatic preconditions, access to preservatives
	Self-subsistence	Level of self-sufficiency/trade dependency/surplus production
	Mercantilism	Professional/semi-professional (seasonal)/barter, trading posts
ENVIRONMENTAL	Agricultural strategies	Specialized/diverse, intensive/extensive
	Land-use patterns	Erosion, degradation, salination, over-extension, deforestation
	Infrastructure	Roads, navigable waters/rivers, storage capacity, means of transport, ports
	Topography	Landscape characteristics, floods, landslides, marginal/productive
	Climate	Temperature, precipitation, annual variability, climate change, weather, precipitation, seasonality
	Access to resources	Terrestrial/wildlife composition, systemized/individual exploitation, access to additional resources
	Pastoralism	Specialized/diverse, intensive/extensive, outfields
	Seasonality	Growing degree days, seasonal subsistence strategies

Table 5.1: Key variables for assessing societal vulnerability and resilience in Iron Age Scandinavia. The table is a reworked and extended version of Gundersen (2019, Table 1), and builds on the principles outlined in Oliver-Smith et al. (2017), Riede (2019), and Torrence (2019).

Table 5.1 suggests a number of variables that might be useful when discussing societal vulnerability and resilience in a Scandinavian Iron Age context as part of a root cause analysis that is structured around widely defined political, economic, and environmental domains. The latter domain is made up of both the naturally-and socially-constructed environment as the two often overlap. However, as changes within one domain affect the others, the different factors are intertwined, interdependent, and mutually instrumental. Some factors could very well be positioned within a different domain, or be separated to constitute another one. In other words, the table is a means to structure the different variables that might have come into play, and not meant to be understood as a stringent categorisation of how robustness is constituted in a given society. Table 5.1 builds in particular on the works of Torrence (2019, Table 1), but is more directed towards the human-environmental context of Iron Age Scandinavia and the attempts to sum up the variables discussed in Chapters 5.2 and 5.3.

When it comes to disasters, much focus lies instinctively on infrastructure damage and economic consequences as they concern the immediate effects and destruction that must often be promptly dealt with. However, the political domain is of equal importance as it not only relates to social capital and the ability to utilise it in times of stress and disturbance (Peregrine, 2020b), but also to factors that can enhance or reduce the difficulties, such as population size, public health, networks, communication, and public relations. Torrence (2019, p. 261) underpins the value of collective memory and familiarity with similar events as important for society's adaptational capacity, which is understood as closely related to the ideological sphere and behavioural patterns. Repeated exposures can contribute to enhanced robustness by, for instance, building experience on how to respond to recurring hazards or by motivating the development of subsistence and land-use strategies better adapted to the environmental dangers. Also important are power arrangements and the process of decision-making, as it designates society's ability to mobilise and act upon unexpected events. Societal organisation is often considered fundamental for disaster mitigation and response (Torrence, 2019, p. 260). As pointed out by Sheets (1999, 2012), stratified and redistributive societies can be understood as more vulnerable to catastrophes due to a lack of efficient decision-making and dependency on specialised production, storage, and well-functioning infrastructure. Small-scale, mobile, and egalitarian groups are considered more able to adapt rapidly to changing circumstances as decisions are made on a household-level. On the other hand, pre-state societies are usually lacking in large-scale organisational and economic capacities, which in modern societies can prove important for disaster mitigation and reconstruction. Still, centralised and interconnected modes of production and political authority would be highly vulnerable if society at whole was affected and the systems of exchange broke down. As such, the question of vulnerability in stratified societies depends on the type of hazard in question, its effect, duration, and impact values, and not just the issue of social complexity in itself. The character and magnitude of the event is therefore of vital importance.

IMPACT VECTOR KM	PROXIMAL <50	MEDIAL 50-500	DISTAL 500-1000	ULTRA-DISTAL >1000
TEPHRA FALL	X	X	X	X
PYROCLASTIC FLOWS	X	X		
GASES	X	X	X	
LAHARS	X	X		
FLOODS	X	X	X	
EARTHQUAKES	X	X		
TSUNAMIS	X	X	X	
DUST VEILS	X	X	X	X

Table 5.2: A schematic representation of possible impact vectors systemised along spatial scales (modified from Riede, 2019).

Riede (2019, Table 2) has systemised the effect of volcanic eruptions along temporal and spatial scales, in order to create a framework for assessing the consequences for prehistoric societies (see also Figure 5.5). The damaging effects vary according to eruption type, magnitude, and distance. In order to clarify, impact vectors associated with explosive eruptions are simplified and modified in Table 5.2. Within immediate distance, gases, tephra, and pyroclastic flows constitute serious threats to ecosystems and terrestrial life. For instance, the 1815 Tambora eruption caused immense devastation on the islands of Sumbawa and Lombok, with over 71 000 people dying during or in the aftermath of the eruption (Oppenheimer, 2003). Earthquakes, tsunamis, and floods represent considerable threats at proximal and medial distances, but can also be experienced at distal range. However, the direct physical effects are of limited durability, and might be overcome by society after some time. At distal and ultra-distal proximity the direct consequences are less detectable as the spatial reach of tephra, pyroclastic flows, and gases are limited. The event might still affect society in ways that are more indirect and probably experienced with minor, if any, knowledge about the cause itself. Depending on numerous variables (as discussed in Chapter 2), dust veils may spread globally and affect temperatures, precipitation, weather, and solar radiation, which might prove persistent and long-term. The optical illusions caused by the aerosol veil alone might generate stress and anxiety, as is discussed by Axbøe (2001). Consequently, the way it affects productivity, health, belief-systems, and ecosystems is quite different from proximal areas, but might nevertheless be equally catastrophic for those who experience it.

Most studies dealing with paleo-social volcanology assess societies within the immediate and medial range from the eruption sites (Riede, 2019; Sheets, 2012; Torrence, 2016), and are therefore mostly concerned with the direct physical effects of the event. For instance, Torrence (2019) lists architectural robustness as a key variable for societal vulnerability, while Riede (2019) raises important issues regarding fluoride poisoning and tephra as a dental abrasive. Mobility, social networks, and stable foreign relations are therefore frequently discussed as means of disaster mitigation as the area would, for some time, be

uninhabitable. However, when analysing the impact of the 6th-century volcanic events on Scandinavian societies, we are at a distal to ultra-distal range from the eruption sites, meaning that direct physical effects are literally non-existent. Consequently, the effect on Iron Age Scandinavia must be assessed by using other parameters than, for instance, the Meso-Americas (cf. the discussion on the use of analogies in Chapter 3.3.2).

Furthermore, the consequences might take time to unfold. At the same time, the temporal attributes of volcanic dust veils allow time to prepare, but can also reduce societal alertness. Without proper knowledge about the causes behind the observed phenomenon, or a lack of experience with similar events, the gradual temporal build-up might contribute to enhanced societal vulnerability. Farmers experiencing unusually cold summers are likely to recognise the danger it represents for the upcoming harvest, and consequently have some time to respond through practical measures or offerings and rituals (as suggested by Axboe, 2001). The first response can mitigate some of the consequences by utilising alternative resources, while the latter has the potential to reinforce a crisis development.

The spatial outreach of eruptions is extensive and hemispherical, thereby reducing the number of possible unaffected refugee areas. As outlined in Chapter 2, the climate impact might differ greatly not only from region to region, but also within regions. Serious consequences in one area might affect another in a push-and-pull effect, as social unrest, trade disruptions, and increased conflict might affect groups and societies otherwise less impacted by the event itself (as suggested by McCormick et al., 2012). Similar challenges are also to be found at proximal and medial distance (as discussed by Sheets, 2012; Torrence, 2016). If crisis unfolds, the extensive spatial outreach of volcanic dust veils might enhance the risk of conflicts.

IMPACT TYPES	EFFECT	PHYSICAL IMPACT	SOCIAL IMPACT
TEMPERATURE CHANGE	Cooling/warming	Crop failure, ergotism	Famine, epidemics
PRECIPITATION	Floods/draught	Infrastructure damage, crop failure, ergotism, rotten hay	Famine, epidemics, reduced exchange and communication
EXTREME WEATHER PHENOMENON	Summer frost, storms, floods	Reduced agrarian productivity, infrastructure damage	Unrest, reduced exchange and communication
REDUCED IRRADIATION	Photosynthesis	Reduced terrestrial growth	Reduced public health
OPTICAL ILLUSIONS	Belief systems		Unrest, anxiety

Table 5.3: Possible consequences of globally distributed volcanic dust veils in prehistoric agrarian societies.

Drawing on the discussions in Chapter 2 and 5.3, Table 5.3 lists a number of possible consequences of volcanic dust veils, structured around temperature change, precipitation, extreme weather phenomenon, reduced irradiation, and optical illusions (such as a darkened sun and blood-red sunsets). The possible societal impacts concern issues like reduced agrarian productivity, infrastructure, and public health, but more aspects must be considered, as dust veils might generate other difficulties as well. For instance, reduced photosynthesis and terrestrial growth (as discussed by Helama et al., 2018) might, in a worst-case scenario, affect both husbandry and wildlife due to diminishing food resources. Cold and wet weather also favours the spread of ergot (Chapter 2.3.3). Thus, aerosol dust veils have the potential to impact outfield exploitation in addition to cultivation, potentially reducing the possibility of compensating for poor harvests with increased hunting and trapping or pastoral farming. It is a factor that might be of more importance during sustained cooling, compared to short-term climate variations, as the impact on animal populations would be gradually developing over time. However, the effect on animal fodder is largely under-researched and the role that can be attributed to it is unclear.

Infrastructure damage, on the other hand, might be of less crucial importance in prehistoric than modern societies as roads, communication lines, transport etc. would be less developed. However, floods and landslides can pose a considerable threat to buildings, fields, and grasslands as well, resulting in profound damage. In Scandinavia, the 1789 extreme flood event is perhaps the best-known from historical times as it devastated large parts of eastern and southern Norway, in particular the Gudbrandsdalen valley (Gundersen, 2016b; Sommerfeldt, 1972). However, floods and landslides only rarely reach such dimensions in Scandinavia (cf. Roald, 2013). Conditioned greatly by topography and weather, it is more of a factor in certain regions and vulnerable areas than for Scandinavia at whole, thus adding to the spatial complexity.

By and large, the threats against society are primarily associated with subsistence and nutrition, which, in turn, might contribute to reduced public health, social unrest, migrations, and conflicts. Thus, in a wider perspective, a volcanic dust veil event would have the potential to affect the whole spectrum of political, environmental, and economic domains in Scandinavian Iron Age societies. However, whether it would develop into a full-fledged crisis depends on the character of the individual categories, in particular those related to subsistence strategies, their relationship, and the magnitude and duration of the event. Important in understanding crises is identifying possible risk drivers by exploring the variables in Table 5.1. In resilience theory, high levels of connectedness within society, as expressed through a specialised, interdependent, and highly efficient means of production, is associated with considerable rigidity in the social system and high levels of vulnerability to disturbance (Chapter 5.2.2). The modes of production are therefore of importance, as is how they relate to each other.

Not all of these aspects can be thoroughly analysed within the scope of this thesis, but diagnostic results can be obtained by focusing on certain key variables. For a dust veil event and pre-modern societies, particular vulnerability is associated with cultivation and the risk of crop failure. The farming landscape in Scandinavia is diversified, in terms of both climatic and geographical preconditions, but also farming practice, which consequently has the potential of being affected in different ways by climate change. Of importance are land-use strategies and the local thresholds for cultivation. Farming situated close to the minimum temperature requirements for cultivation have smaller margins to rely on and are therefore more vulnerable to bad weather and climate deterioration. This also depends on cereal types as different species are associated with different temperature and precipitation requirements (cf. Chapter 6.4.1). Also of importance is the level of dependency on agriculture and the level of specialised production. A narrow subsistence strategy, in particular those made up of a limited selection of farming outputs, would be a considerable risk driver in the face of climate change. Thus, subsistence exploitation needs to be analysed in a regional or local perspective since resource availability, environmental preconditions, and subsistence strategies might differ significantly from place to place. Finally, the magnitude and duration of the climate event itself represent crucial variables. In consequence, the following parameters can be understood as possible risk drivers for Scandinavian Iron Age contexts:

- High dependency to farming outputs
- Specialised production
- Expansive cultivation (low temperature margins)
- Temperature-demanding cereal types
- Significant and sustained climate change

Familiarity with similar events must also be brought under consideration. The processes of learning, innovation, and adaptation, as outlined in resilience theory, constitute important parameters when discussing levels of societal vulnerability. Equally, analysis needs to be extended well beyond the dust veil event itself in order to assess the character of change and how it may relate to the climate downturn. In other words, the impact of the dust veil event must be approached through a deep-time perspective that both pre-dates and post-dates the event, in which the social, political, and economic trajectories are incorporated.

5.5 Chapter conclusion

During the last decades, we have witnessed a significant increase in disaster literature in the humanities, in which environmental factors have gained growing importance as causal explanations for societal crises, collapse, and human innovations throughout prehistory. This development is closely related to the growing scientific awareness of the Anthropocene, which gradually breaks down the traditional dichotomy between culture and nature. With it, there is an enforced recognition of the mutual dependency and instrumentality between humans and environmental systems. In turn, this opens up for the development of new analytical frameworks which help to explore the interactions between the two, thus offering novel insights into the socio-cultural trajectories of past societies. However, the often-catastrophic scenarios accompanying the current scientific and public debates on the Anthropocene risk heavily influencing the interpretative frameworks in archaeology by enforcing catastrophe thinking, the consequence of which is that major environmental events in prehistory are increasingly understood in terms of societal crisis and collapse. As discussed in relation to the Fimbulwinter discourse in Chapter 3.3, and collapsology in Chapter 4, such claims can be well founded but often lack a clear identification of the causal mechanisms that would substantiate it, thus increasing the risk of interpretative biases. It becomes crucial, therefore, for any study of past disasters and climate change to develop analytical frameworks that allow for coherent human-environmental approaches, able to bridge between concurrency and causation. Understanding the multidimensional character of disasters, as well as the affected societies, becomes an important prerequisite for past disaster studies.

Disasters, regardless of technological, social, or environmental origins, are highly complex phenomena, rooted in both environmental and human domains and, therefore, conditioned by numerous variables, often with unpredictable outcomes. Environmental events can therefore not be approached as single variables affecting all societies in similar ways. Depending on the character of the events, the affected societies, and their respective interaction within the environmental spheres, disaster developments and consequences can vary considerably along spatiotemporal scales, thus potentially affecting even similar societies in very different ways. Therefore, when addressing the possible societal impact of the 6th-century cooling in Scandinavia, contingency becomes fundamental, as well as the chosen level of analysis. Local and regional characteristics are crucial variables, potentially contributing to different outcomes throughout Scandinavia.

The possible impact of the 6th-century cooling on Scandinavian societies will be approached by exploring the concepts of vulnerability, resilience, and adaptation. In particular, vulnerability will be employed as a tool for analysing the possible effects on agricultural productivity and subsistence robustness in an

attempt to identify a causal link between the climate event and changes in the archaeological record.

Building on resilience theory and root cause analysis, the following premises will be implemented in the forthcoming analysis:

- Contingency
- Local and regional scales
- Long-term perspectives
- Identifying risk drivers

The identification of variables causing societal vulnerability to climate change is fundamental, as are the human practices that might reflect adaptational strategies to changing environmental preconditions. In the next chapter, I will attempt to implement these principles into a coherent method that can be utilised on the scientific and archaeological records which have been made available through archaeological excavations.

6 METHODS, DATA SELECTION, AND SOURCE-CRITICISM

I have outlined in the previous chapter the basic principles of the analytical framework for this thesis, focusing on the concepts of vulnerability, resilience, and adaptation. In this chapter, I will build on these concepts in order to develop a coherent method in which the possible impact of the 6th-century cooling in Scandinavia can be analysed. My aim is to disentangle the mechanisms that may have created vulnerability to climate change, which requires a long-term perspective on subsistence strategies. Of importance will also be identifying adaptational strategies that reflect the capacity of Iron Age societies to cope with disruptive events.

The main challenge with the Fimbulwinter hypothesis is the issue of causality. The hypothesis might best be described as inductive, i.e. derived from observations of archaeological phenomena that more or less coincide in time with an identified 6th-century climate cooling (cf. Chapter 3.3.2). Dagomar Degroot et al. (2021) outlines a number of key methodological problems often found in past disaster studies, of which a selection bias towards crisis and collapse is a recurrent phenomenon. The basic challenge is identifying the causal mechanisms at play, which is sometimes attempted through an excessive focus on large spatiotemporal scales. To a certain degree, this is also the case with the Fimbulwinter discourse, in which big data compilations are frequently employed to strengthen the idea of societal crisis by identifying major socio-cultural changes around the 6th century (Iversen, 2013; Löwenborg, 2012b; Peregrine, 2020a; Price & Gräslund, 2015; Solheim & Iversen, 2019). However, as demonstrated in a recent study of excavated cooking pits in eastern Norway (Gundersen et al., 2020), there is a need to contextualise even big data as thorough examinations can reveal significant regional patterns otherwise concealed behind overall trends.

Quantitative analysis can be a powerful tool for identifying patterns of social change, but often suffers from what has been defined as the ‘McNamara fallacy’ and the ‘streetlight effect’ (Degroot et al., 2021, p. 541). The terms are used to describe statistical studies where unquantifiable data is ignored, or incomplete (but easily accessible) quantitative datasets are employed, often without sufficient source-critical considerations regarding how the datasets may be biased, thus potentially creating misleading results. This is often accompanied with insufficient attention to statistical uncertainties, or the chronological resolution of the involved proxies. Moreover, there is a tendency towards uncritical use of historical primary sources, which are taken out of context and treated as proxy data, or mere textual illustrations to support the overall narrative. Thus, prehistoric studies risk uncritically imprinting the crisis

narrative of the Anthropocene onto past societies rather than producing new insights into human responses to environmental change (cf. Chapter 5.1).

However, these fallacies are not necessarily ruled out by employing a qualitative approach, as even in-depth archaeological studies often struggle with low-resolution datasets of varying quality. The selection bias towards crisis and collapse is not an exclusive phenomenon for quantitative studies either. Consequently, the problem is not big data and quantitative approaches in itself; the true challenge lies in data selection and the uncritical use of analysis results in the overall interpretations.

There are several good reasons for believing that profound climate change could have had an effect on Iron Age societies, in particular northern and middle Scandinavia, where the length of the growing season is considerably shorter than for instance the Mediterranean. However, as discussed in Chapter 2, crop failure is not an inevitable outcome of hemispherical aerosol veils, not even in areas which are marginal in climatic and agricultural terms. As stressed in Chapter 5, environmental events must be contextualised rather than treated as uniform disasters with predictable outcomes. For one to be able to substantiate how, and why, the cooling had an effect, a consistent methodology is required which transcends mere concurrencies in geoscientific and archaeological datasets. A causal approach requires the identification of both decisive variables and the mechanisms that link the variables to adaptive behaviour (Dincauze, 2000, p. 78). The key analytical question becomes: *how vulnerable were Iron Age societies to climate change?*

Therefore, the archaeological record in general, and in particular the character of subsistence strategies, must be put in the forefront of investigation. In other words, a deductive approach is required, one in which the Fimbulwinter hypothesis is tested up against archaeological proxies in accordance with defined analytical criteria. First of all, how dependent were Iron Age societies on agriculture, and, not to forget, what kind of agricultural strategies were utilised? It must be substantiated that farming was of crucial importance for society, and that the farming strategies were indeed vulnerable to climate change. Important parameters include manuring, livestock keeping, wildlife exploitation, grain types, growth requirements, crop diversity, and, finally, levels of risk for crop failure in periods of reduced summer temperatures.

Secondly, if subsistence difficulties can be substantiated, do we have evidence for adaptation? It is to be expected that widespread crop failure would lead to changes in food strategies whereby alternative resources would increase in importance, at least for some time. Adaptational strategies may involve more

robust grain species, intensified pastoralism, or increased importance of outfield resources, such as terrestrial or aquatic wildlife.

By systemising scientific datasets from archaeological excavations, my aim is to analyse Iron Age vulnerability by employing a two-stage approach utilising different spatial scales, consisting of one macro-level statistical analysis, and micro-level case studies focusing on selected landscape formations. This combination allows for the effective use of the potential of big data while simultaneously allowing for the study of the possible effects of climate change at local scales through in-depth studies.

The statistical approach will be conducted on excavated settlement and agricultural sites within two research areas, and it aims at clarifying the character and development of Iron Age farming and subsistence strategies. In line with the concept of resilience, adaptive change must be studied in a long-term perspective and include a wide range of archaeological proxies. Data from settlement, agricultural, and trapping sites from all of the Iron Age within two designated research areas will therefore be analysed in the study. By doing so, possible risk drivers for Iron Age vulnerability to climate change can be identified and contribute to an assessment of subsistence robustness.

The case studies will make use of the excavation data from two minor landscape formations, one from each research area, and study them in relation to topographical and climatic datasets in a GIS landscape analysis. In addition to climatic and topographical data, the analysis will make use of vegetation history, and descriptive datasets, such as archaeological assessments and interpretations of the excavated sites. This approach aims at assessing the possible impact of colder climates on agricultural outputs by simulating growth requirements in GIS. Topographical and climatic factors, such as soil conditions, risk of floods and erosion, precipitation, and mean temperatures, provide an environmental context for the archaeological evidence in which agricultural vulnerability can be further explored.

Comparing two different areas, at both micro and macro levels, allows for a discussion of differences and similarities in subsistence robustness, resource exploitation, and social vulnerability, and how these factors relate to adaptation and recovery.

In the following sub-chapters, I will further outline the structure, datasets, premises, and source-critical issues of the forthcoming analyses.

6.1 Temporal, spatial, and contextual delimitation

The analysis will be focused on archaeological datasets from Gudbrandsdalen valley and Lake Mjøsa region in former Oppland, Hedmark, and Akershus counties (now part of Innlandet and Viken counties)²⁹. The Lake Mjøsa region is usually defined as the areas bordering the lake or situated in the immediate vicinity (R. Dahl, Nashoug, & Nystuen, 2017, p. 12). Included in the present study are Eidsvoll, Hurdal, Vestre Toten, Østre Toten, Gjøvik, Ringsaker, Hamar, Løten, and Stange municipalities, all within the Lake Mjøsa region, while Gudbrandsdalen valley comprises Lillehammer, Øyer, Gausdal, Ringebru, Sør-Fron, Nord-Fron, Sel, Vågå, Lom, Skjåk, Lesja, and Dovre municipalities (Figure 6.1). Lillehammer borders both regions and defines the transition between the two, and is, as such, neither a valley nor a lake district. As most excavated sites in the area have been conducted on the northern part, Lillehammer is, in this context, included in Gudbrandsdalen valley.

These two research areas have been chosen with several reasons in mind. As neighbouring regions, similar climatic conditions are present, but the two landscapes comprise different topographical qualities and natural resources. The Gudbrandsdalen valley is Norway's largest valley, stretching from Lake Mjøsa in the south to the high mountain region in the north and west, thus forming a landscape of great contrast and diversity. Most of Gudbrandsdalen valley belongs to the 'valley and mountain countryside' (Figure 6.2), where pastures and livestock have traditionally been emphasised (Puschmann, Reid, Fjellstad, Hofsten, & Dramstad, 2004, pp. 53-55). In contrast, Lake Mjøsa region is situated around Norway's largest lake, just south of the major inland valleys of Gudbrandsdalen and Østerdalen. The northern and southern part are dominated by extensive flat landscapes termed the 'lowland countryside', which is understood as one of the country's most important and productive farming landscapes (R. Dahl et al., 2017; Puschmann et al., 2004, pp. 47-49). Thus, similarities in climatic conditions, but differences in resources and topography, offer an excellent starting point for discussing societal vulnerability and human responses to climate change.

²⁹ From 2020, the Norwegian municipal and regional borders have been reorganised, and several administrative units are now merged together. However, as my work was initiated prior to 2020, and my database therefore organised according to the former borders, I have decided to relate to the former municipal system in my thesis. As the former administrative units were smaller, employing them also allows for higher geographical precision in the text.

Figure 6.1: Map over the two research areas, Lake Mjøsa region and Gudbrandsdalen valley, and their affiliated former counties and municipalities (prior to 2020). Lake Mjøsa lies at the intersection between the three former counties of Hedmark, Oppland, and Akershus, now parts of Innlandet and Viken counties. Illustration by author.

Figure 6.2: Agricultural regions in south-eastern Norway (Puschmann et al., 2004). Source: NIBIO. Illustration by author.

During the last four decades, several excavations have been conducted in both regions. Particular attention has been paid to Fron in middle Gudbrandsdalen and Hedmarken³⁰ in the north-eastern part of Lake Mjøsa region, where excavations have made available an essential part of the settlement and agricultural datasets which will be used as proxy data in the present thesis (Gundersen, 2016e; Pilø, 2005; Rødsrud & Mjærum, 2020). Fron makes up 51% of the Gudbrandsdalen sites, while Hedmarken accounts for 46% of the Lake Mjøsa sites. The two areas are also among some of the most important agricultural landscapes within each region. Fron and Hedmarken will therefore be subject to in-depth case studies, while the statistical analysis will include excavation datasets from the entirety of the two regions.

All excavated settlement and agricultural sites dated to the Iron Age which were available as finished reports as of 1.1.2020 are included in this study. The term 'settlement sites' is used in a broad sense, and includes all sites where settlement traces have been documented, such as cooking-pits, fireplaces, houses, postholes, and debris layers. 'Agricultural sites' are understood as sites involving cultivated layers and/or clearance cairns. All available paleoenvironmental, osteological, and radiocarbon datasets from these sites are quantified and compiled in the thesis database.

To supplement the evidence from the settlement sites on outfield exploitation, well-documented hunting and trapping sites form a third site category for analysis. However, to mitigate the impact of a number of investigation biases, the study area has been extended to include all excavated trapping sites from Akershus, Oppland, and Hedmark. Only a few trapping sites have been excavated in the near vicinity of Lake Mjøsa, while large numbers have been investigated in Gudbrandsdalen valley. Although this is an interesting aspect concerning resource availability and exploitation in the two research areas, it creates a certain spatial imbalance in the dataset, even within Gudbrandsdalen valley. Large-scale systematic investigations have been conducted around the melting snow patches in the northern part of the region within recent years (Pilø et al., 2018), thus providing significantly more C14-proxies than from the lowland trapping sites in other parts of the valley. By including a larger geographical territory in the analysis, an improved statistical selection can be achieved.

³⁰ Not to be confused with former Hedmark county. Hedmarken is a landscape formation covering Ringsaker, Hamar, Stange, and Løten municipalities, which through several administrative reorganisations first gave its name to entire Hedmark county in 1919 (Thorsnæs, 2021).

6.1.1 THE DATABASES

Two databases have been developed for analysis: one for settlement and agricultural data, and the other for hunting and trapping sites.

Figure 6.3: Number of annually excavated settlement and agricultural sites in Lake Mjøsa region and Gudbrandsdalen valley during 1979-2018. Based on the records in the thesis database.

The settlement and agricultural database consists of archaeological, osteological, radiocarbon, paleobotanical, and micro-morphological datasets, made available through archaeological excavations within the two research areas (Figure 6.3). The excavations have been conducted by the Museum of Cultural History or the respective county administration. Up until 2012, the county administrations had limited access to conduct archaeological excavations and most excavations prior to this date were therefore managed by the Museum of Cultural History. In order to simplify and streamline the decision-making process in cultural heritage management, the county administrations were given an extended mandate in 2012 to excavate, under their own initiative, minor sites discovered during surveys. From that year on, there is a steady increase in the number of excavations conducted by the county administrations, of which a significant number concerns small sites with less than five archaeological features (Figure 6.4). These sites mostly include cooking pits. At sites with <5 archaeological features excavated from 2012 to 2018, 36 out of 43 sites (84%) only include cooking pits, compared to mere 12 out of 42 sites (29%) with

≥5 archaeological features.³¹ At the same time, the ratio between small-scale excavations and larger excavations has increased in the favour of the former. Thus, the increase in excavated small sites adds significantly to the percentage of cooking pits in the overall Iron Age record.

Figure 6.4: Number of archaeological features documented per excavated site with reference to executive institutions.

The main figures from the settlement and agriculture database are presented in Table 6.1. Considerably more sites have been excavated in Lake Mjøsa region than Gudbrandsdalen valley, which creates a certain imbalance in the dataset. The ratio between the two regions is approximately 4:1. However, many of the Lake Mjøsa sites were investigated several decades ago and a large proportion of these involve rather few scientific analyses, especially when it comes to radiocarbon dating. Gudbrandsdalen valley, on the other hand, has had much of its archaeological investigations undertaken throughout the 2000s and several of the sites are consequently well-documented, often including a wide range of scientific analyses. As shown in Table 6.2, the rate of scientific analyses per investigated site is therefore higher in Gudbrandsdalen valley. While the quantitative dataset is considerably larger from the area around Lake Mjøsa, the

³¹ The numbers for sites excavated in 1979-2011 are 71% for small sites and 33% for larger sites

Gudbrandsdalen dataset offers, in general, more information per site. In total, the Lake Mjøsa region nonetheless includes more data.

CATEGORY	TOTAL	LAKE MJØSA REGION	GUDBRANDSDALEN VALLEY
EXCAVATED SITES	212	173	39
CONTEXTS	494	387	107
RADIOCARBON DATES	1216	945	271
OSTEOLOGICAL ANALYSIS	60	42	18
MACRO-BOTANICAL ANALYSIS	78	47	31
POLLEN ANALYSIS	40	22	18
MICRO-MORPHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS	17	8	9
BUILDINGS	46	33	13
SETTLEMENT SITES	166	142	24
AGRICULTURAL SITES	28	18	10
SETTLEMENT/AGRICULTURAL SITES	18	13	5

Table 6.1: Main figures from the settlement and agricultural database.

‘Context’ is the main structural feature of the database, and connects all the datasets to each other. Context is defined as a set of archaeological features that share common characteristics, such as cooking pits and clearance cairns, delimited from other similar features by a continuous span of C14-dates. In other words, context is understood as a defined activity, or related set of activities, within a certain amount of time on each archaeological site. Houses, debris layers, and agricultural layers always constitute individual contexts as they can be separated from the rest as an overall construction or defined stratigraphic layer. As archaeological sites often involve data from a long period of time, the approach allows for the sorting of information according to phase and type of activity and the exportation of relevant datasets to a GIS analysis.

CATEGORY	LAKE MJØSA REGION	GUDBRANDSDALEN VALLEY
RADIOCARBON	5,4	6,9
OSTEOLOGICAL	0,2	0,5
MACRO-BOTANICAL	0,3	0,8
POLLEN	0,1	0,5
MICRO-MORPHOLOGICAL	<0,1	0,2

Table 6.2: Rate of scientific analyses conducted per excavated site.

The outfield database consists of radiocarbon dates from hunting and trapping sites in the lowlands and mountain regions (eg. T. Amundsen, 2007; Barth, 1996; Gundersen, 2016c; Jacobsen & Larsen, 1992; Nesje et al., 2011; Pilø et al., 2018; Post-Melbye & Bergstøl, 2020). By and large, the lowland and low-mountain contexts are made up of pitfalls used for elk or reindeer trapping. The high mountains include a large number of artefacts used during reindeer hunting, retrieved through extensive snow patch surveys. The dates are systemised as ‘terminus post quem’ (TPQ), ‘terminus ante quem’ (TAQ), ‘construction elements’, and ‘artefacts’³² (Table 6.3). Preserved construction elements are rarely recovered from the pitfalls, meaning that several excavated pits are only indirectly dated through radiocarbon analysis of organic matter predating (TPQ) or postdating (TAQ) the constructions (cf. Bergstøl, 2015b, pp. 53-54; Gundersen, 2016c, p. 225). However, TPQ and TAQ dates become a source-critical factor when large datasets are compiled and analysed as one since the dates are not directly related to the targeted activity. By separating the radiocarbon dates according to context, misrepresentations in the overall dataset can be avoided.

COUNTY	TOTAL	TERMINUS POST QUEM	CONSTRUCTION ELEMENTS	ARTEFACTS	TERMINUS ANTE QUEM	N/A
OPPLAND	198	16	59	105	15	3
HEDMARK	125	44	27		44	10
AKERSHUS	8				3	5
TOTAL	331	60	86	105	62	18

Table 6.3: Number of C14-dates in the outfields database.

6.1.2 GEOSCIENTIFIC DATASETS

The climate experiences considerable year-to-year variability and change over time. So-called standard periods – or climate normals – are therefore usually defined, which make comparisons between historical, present day, and future projections of climate change possible (WMO, 2017). Based on measured weather records, the standard periods are defined by the mean temperature sum and amount of precipitation during the given period. Pre-industrial records are not suitable, as precise and geographically distributed proxies are preferred. The weather records for 1961-90 and 1971-2000 are often used as the data is accessible worldwide and with high precision. When it comes to the 6th-century cooling, 1961-90 is frequently used as a point of reference in high impact geoscientific papers (i.e. Büntgen et al., 2016; Sigl et al., 2015), as well as in Stamnes’ (2016) simulations of crop failure probability for middle Norway. For direct comparison, the 1961-90 period is employed in this study as well.

³² Only artefacts directly associated with hunting is included in the study (arrows, scaring sticks, cut antler, and a bow).

Local weather data for 1961-90 from the research areas are accessible from the Norwegian Meteorological Institute (MET)³³. Topographical datasets are available from the Geological Survey of Norway (NGU)³⁴, while the Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research (NIBIO)³⁵ offers several datasets combining topographical, climatic, and agricultural proxies (Table 6.4). The data are subsequently processed and mapped in ArcGIS 10.7.1.

TYPE	AREA	SOURCE	ACCESS DATE
SOIL QUALITY [JORDKVALITET]	Hedmark, Oppland, Akershus, Østfold, and Buskerud counties	NIBIO	20. May 2020
SEDIMENTS 1:50 000 [LØSMASSEKART]	Sør-Fron, Nord-Fron, Hamar, Stange, and Ringsaker municipalities	NGU	18. May 2020
CULTIVATION CLASS (BARLEY) [DYRKINGSKLASSEKART FOR BYGG]	Hedmark and Oppland counties	NIBIO ³⁶	04. February 2021
MARINE LIMIT [MARIN GRENSE]	Hedmark and Oppland counties	NGU	25. May 2020
TEMPERATURES [DØGNNORMALER 1961-90]	Norway	MET	26. January 2021
PRECIPITATION [MÅNEDSNORMALER 1961-90]	Norway	MET	26. January 2021
GROWING SEASON MAP (ASCII) [VEKSTSESONG 1961-90]	Norway (from the NCCS report 'Climate in Norway 2100')	MET ³⁷	11. May 2020
AGRARIAN LANDSCAPES [LANDSKAP - JORDBRUKSREGION]	Norway	NIBIO	12. May 2020
SEDIMENTS 1:250 000 [LØSMASSEKART]	Norway	NGU	11. August 2020
PRECIPITATION MAP (ASCII) [MIDLERE NEDBØR 1961-90]	Norway (from the NCCS report 'Climate in Norway 2100')	MET ³⁸	17. November 2020

Table 6.4: Meteorological and geological datasets used in the thesis, with original Norwegian titles in brackets.

It should be stressed that the datasets for agrarian landscapes, cultivation classes, and soil quality are modelled according to the attributes of modern agricultural practices, and are therefore not directly applicable to prehistoric contexts. For instance, steep terrains are usually assessed as less suitable for modern agricultural machinery than flat landscapes (Puschmann et al., 2004, p. 54), and are therefore

³³ <https://www.met.no/en/free-meteorological-data/Download-services>

³⁴ <https://www.ngu.no/en/topic/datasets>

³⁵ <https://kilden.nibio.no>

³⁶ The dataset is not yet made available for download at 'Kilden' and is used by request and special permission from NIBIO.

³⁷ By request.

³⁸ By request.

given lower values in the cultivation class system. Slopes exceeding 33% inclination are deemed 'not suitable' for modern cultivation (Klakegg, 2020). However, an agricultural practice based on manual labour may have made cultivation possible in otherwise inaccessible and rugged terrains. In addition, modern agriculture is often based on irrigation, especially in the dry areas of northern Gudbrandsdalen valley. In any case, the NIBIO cultivation class dataset employed in this study is solely based on precipitation-based cultivation.

Figure 6.5: Post Ice-Age marine limits in southeastern Norway. Source: NGU. Illustration by author.

Another relevant factor is the presence of clay-rich soils. Clay is considered highly nutritious for crops, but was difficult to cultivate with pre-industrial methods. Modern farming techniques allow for the large-scale

cultivation of heavy soils, and clay is therefore assessed as favourable for cultivation in the NIBIO datasets. The dataset might consequently be misleading when applied to a prehistoric context. Nonetheless, the presence of pure clay deposits is limited by the post-Ice Age marine limit, which in eastern Norway is situated at about 190 masl (Figure 6.5) and, therefore, effectively excludes the Gudbrandsdalen valley and most of Lake Mjøsa region. Pockets of freshwater clay are nonetheless found around Lake Mjøsa, but is mixed with gravel, stones, and humus (R. Dahl et al., 2017, pp. 18, 223). It is not as clean as proper marine clay, thus making it easier to cultivate. Pure clay occurrences are more common in Eidsvoll south of the lake. However, Eidsvoll is not subject to a landscape case study in which the cultivation class system is utilised. The clay factor is therefore of little source-critical significance in the upcoming analysis.

6.2 The archaeo-botanical data

In the following section, I will discuss source critical factors and limitations concerning the archaeo-botanical record, an understanding of which is vital for how the data is used in this thesis. The identification of prehistoric agriculture relies heavily on the palynologists, as the physical remains in many cases are limited to preserved pollen in geological deposits (Fægri, Kaland, Krzywinski, & Iversen, 1989, p. 1; Hafsten, 1958, p. 52; Høeg & Mikkelsen, 1979, p. 161). The pollen analytical method is, in essence, a technique for reconstructing the past vegetation by means of the pollen grains it produced and demonstrates, in historical detail, the development of both settlement and land-use techniques (Fægri et al., 1989, pp. 1, 175).

Bogs and lakes serve as important historical archives of past vegetation, but pollen analysis is also extensively used on samples from excavated cultivation fields and cultural layers; in recent years it has been increasingly combined with geo-archaeological approaches like micromorphology and soil chemistry (see for instance Gjerpe, 2013; Gundersen, 2016d; Macphail, Cruise, Courty, Crowther, & Linderholm, 2016; Mjærum, 2012; Viklund, Linderholm, & Macphail, 2013).

The assessment of Iron Age agriculture is largely dependent on the archaeo-botanical data (pollen, macrofossils) made available by excavations of agricultural and settlement sites, as few pollen diagrams developed from bog coring exist from locations in the two research areas. Only a few of the excavations within the last decade have incorporated micromorphology and soil chemistry (eg. Gundersen, 2016e), and the results can therefore only be used as a supplement to the archaeo-botanical data at a limited number of sites.

6.2.1 SOURCE CRITICAL CHALLENGES

The laboratory methods of pollen-analysis have changed considerably during the 20th century, and some of the older methods were in many ways already obsolete by the late 1980s (Fægri et al., 1989, p. ix). The size of most pollen grains ranges from 10 to 100 μm and important morphological characteristics can therefore not be detected by the use of standard microscopes – this causes considerable difficulty when it comes to separating cultivated cereals (*Cerealia*) from wild grasses (Behre, 2007, p. 204; Fægri et al., 1989, p. 1). Older pollen analyses are therefore not as reliable as recent ones. The implementation of phase contrast microscopy from the 1950s and onwards represents an important innovation, especially for identifying pollen from cereals. The method has been continuously developed up until present day, but is, according to Karl-Ernst Behre (2007, p. 204), not always employed during the preparation of pollen diagrams.

Pollen analysis has some limitations that should not be underestimated, as it first and foremost provides information about vegetation history, and thereby, through interpretation, about the environmental and cultural context (Dincauze, 2000, pp. 343-362; Fægri et al., 1989, pp. 2, 164-173). Any climatic and societal interpretations are secondary deductions from the vegetational record and depend to an equal extent on empirical data from sources other than the pollen record, such as the archaeological record.

The interpretations are further complicated by a range of events that influence the analytical process, such as pollination ecology, sedimentology, and sampling strategy (Fægri et al., 1989, pp. 2-3). The first category consists of a number of aspects, including flowering, pollen production, and pollen dispersal, and is well-illustrated by the cases of cereals and pine (*Pinus*). Wind transport of cereal pollen is usually quite limited as traditional grains are self-pollinating, meaning that most of the pollen remain within the glumes (Behre, 1981, p. 227; 2007, p. 206; Fægri et al., 1989, pp. 170, 186; Høeg, 1989, p. 375; 2011, p. 114; Høeg & Mikkelsen, 1979, p. 161). Most of the pollen is released during harvesting and threshing, and may therefore be easier to recognise in samples from within or in proximity to prehistoric farmsteads and cultivated fields, rather than nearby wetlands (Behre, 1981, p. 227; 2007, p. 206; Fægri et al., 1989, p. 186). Rye (*Secale*) represents an exception from this rule, as it is wind-pollinated with high pollen productivity and good dispersal capacity. It is therefore among the most reliable indicators of cultivation, but it also means that single finds of rye in bog deposits do not necessarily reflect the farming strategies on site.

This is also the case with a number of weeds which are either self- or insect-pollinated and therefore disperse very little pollen in the air (Fægri et al., 1989, p. 186). For some species, like the plantain (*Plantaginaceae*) and goosefoot types (*Chenopodiaceae*), the wind distribution is reduced by their low height and much of the pollen is dispersed in close proximity to the plants (Høeg, 2011, p. 114). As a consequence, cultivated species and other anthropogenic indicators might be absent in pollen diagrams from bogs and lakes even close to the prehistoric fields, which is by no means synonymous with an absence of agriculture (Behre, 1981, p. 227; Fægri et al., 1989, pp. 182-190).

The limited pollen dispersal of some of the most important anthropogenic indicators stands in stark contrast to species like pine and birch (*Betula*), which produce a great amount of pollen. Pollen from pine can be distributed over great distances and has, in some cases, been documented in great quantities in the pollen diagrams as far away as the Svalbard archipelago, despite the fact that trees have never grown there (Høeg, 2011, p. 114). Thus, a majority of the documented pollen grains can be the result of long-distance distribution and do not represent an accurate picture of the past vegetation at site (Dincauze, 2000, p. 345; Hjelle, 2015, p. 247).

However, a newly developed Landscape Reconstruction Algorithm (LRA) makes it possible to separate background pollen from local pollen, and in this way the method contributes to far more precise interpretations (Hjelle, 2015). However, no such analyses have been published for eastern Norway as of the writing of this thesis.

The second category concerns the context in which the pollen is preserved and the changes occurring in that context from the moment of deposition to the moment of sampling. Both changes in environmental conditions and human activity affect the degree of preservation (Fægri et al., 1989, p. 3). Pollen grains can, for instance, be quickly decomposed on unprotected ground and in cultivated fields, especially if the soil contains high pH levels (Hafsten, 1958, pp. 53-54; Høeg, 1989, p. 376; N.-O. Svensson & Regnéll, 2013, p. 130). In general, pollen grains are better preserved in wetlands with low pH values, but the limited pollen dispersal of several cultivated plant indicators means that the pollen records in such cases do not reflect a 1:1 representation of the actual prehistoric vegetation on site. It should also be stressed that the rate of decomposition varies from species to species, depending on the environmental conditions, which can result in distortions in the archaeo-botanical record (N.-O. Svensson & Regnéll, 2013, p. 131). Oak (*Quercus*), aspen (*Populus*), sedge (*Cyperaceae*), willow (*Salix*), sorrel (*Rumex*), and ribwort plantain (*Plantago lanceolata*) are especially prone to decomposition. This is to some degree also the case with cereals, causing difficulties when it comes to subspecies determination.

The third category concerns the methods and sampling strategies employed during fieldwork, procedures during sample preparation and analysis, and, last but certainly not least, the skill and experience of the archaeologists and palynologists involved in the different stages of the process (Behre, 2007, p. 204; Fægri et al., 1989, p. 3). It should also be mentioned that the pollen analytical method is dependent on known equivalents, but as the development in farming methods have changed considerably throughout the ages, modern agricultural landscapes do not resemble the character of prehistoric land use and plant communities. Important changes in the archaeo-botanical record are visible as early as the implementation of the mouldboard plough during the Iron Age and the plaggen technique in the Middle Ages (Behre, 1981, pp. 229, 240; for a discussion concerning earlier C14-dates of plaggen soil, see Mjærum, 2012, p. 121; Myhre, 1979, p. 232). Knut Fægri et al. (1989, p. 186) point out that the use of indicator species might be misleading as it may indicate a modern plant community instead of the extinct one in which the indicator originally grew. Emphasis must therefore be put on a constellation of species and not on single indicators.

When all these factors are summed up, there can be little doubt that pollen diagrams must be treated with a great deal of caution. According to Fægri et al. (1989, p. 3) there is no such thing as a one-to-one relationship between vegetation covers and pollen dispersal and deposition. Nonetheless, pollen is mostly subject to natural processes and is therefore often considered more reliable than macro-botanical remains (cf. Myhre, 1982, p. 212). The strength of pollen analysis lies in the very nature of the pollen itself. Pollen is produced in great quantities and makes up a uniform group of proxies, thus making comparisons between different sites possible.

In comparison, the indicative power of macro-botanical remains is restricted to the local vegetation and is a direct reflection of human activities (Fægri et al., 1989, pp. 1-3). The occurrence of macrofossils is more or less accidental, or, as when found within the household, has been subject to more or less non-random selections when deposited. Seeds and other plant remains are conditioned by their use in consumption and food production and are therefore not an accurate measure of species composition in the fields (Dincauze, 2000, p. 28; Myhre, 1982, p. 212). For instance, oats are often associated with animal fodder rather than human consumption and may therefore be less common in household deposits than barley, rye, and wheat, but still have constituted a considerable part of crop cultivation. Preservation conditions might also vary considerably between contexts. They are easily destroyed and their low frequencies make it impossible to compare the numbers between different sites, but the find of a macrofossil is still a fairly certain indicator that the species was cultivated or consumed in or near the site at the time of the deposition. While nothing can be concluded from its absence, it is still a valuable supplement to pollen

analysis and can be used to strengthen the interpretation of the anthropogenic indicators in the pollen diagrams (Behre, 2007, pp. 205-2015).

6.2.2 ANTHROPOGENIC INDICATORS

A number of different plants have traditionally been understood as 'anthropogenic indicators', a collective term meaning cultivated plants and weeds favoured by agriculture (Danielsen, 1970, p. 117; Hjelle, 2015). Human cultivation represents an important intervention in the landscape, causing significant changes in the composition of the flora that is easily detected in the pollen records. Deforestation, clearances, pastures, and crop fields favour a number of weeds that were previously unknown in the area or had limited distribution. Some of the species may be sparsely represented in the pollen diagrams but still serve as important anthropogenic indicators (Fægri et al., 1989, p. 170). Charcoal dust derived from the burning of wood and other plant material is also used as a positive indicator of agricultural activity, such as initial clearances, manuring, and re-cultivation after fallowing (Fægri et al., 1989, p. 183; Høeg, 2011, p. 114).

The species are often divided into primary and secondary indicators (Bakka & Kaland, 1971, p. 24; Behre, 1981; 2007, p. 206; Høeg, 1989, p. 376; 2011, p. 115). Primary indicators are understood as direct evidence for agriculture, while secondary indicators only indirectly suggest human activity and cultivation (Behre, 1981, pp. 226-228). Direct evidence is understood as species introduced by humans which are also dependent on human activity for reproduction (*anthropochores*). Secondary indicators mostly consist of native plants (*apophytes*) that occur naturally in small habitats but are favoured by human activity, namely agriculture (Behre, 2007, p. 206). The identification of secondary indicators is therefore dependent on a number of factors, including the character of the natural flora and environmental conditions. A wide range of indicators is usually required when it comes to identifying the presence and character of agriculture from secondary indicators alone. Species like, for instance, absinthe (*Artemisia*), goosefoot and sorrel thrive in coastal areas and should not be attributed to agriculture alone in such areas (Bakka & Kaland, 1971, p. 24; Danielsen, 1970, p. 118).

Naturally, the most important primary indicators are the cereals themselves, in particular rye, wheat (*Triticum*), barley (*Hordeum*), and oats (*Avena*), and cultivated plants like flax (*Linum usitatissimum*) and hop/hemp (*Cannabis/Humulus*). Hop and hemp are not easily distinguished from one another in a pollen analysis and are therefore often treated as one category. Rye is readily distinguishable from other species, while wheat, barley, and oats in most cases can be differentiated from wild grasses with the aid of phase contrast microscopy (Behre, 1981, p. 226). There is, however, some difficulty when it comes to separating

wheat and oats from wild species, resulting in uncertainties in regards to the identification of single grains in the pollen diagrams (Behre, 2007, p. 204).

Most secondary indicators are associated with both arable and pastoral farming, but a few are mainly understood as indicators of crop fields (Behre, 1981, p. 233). This is the case for species such as sheep's sorrel (*Rumex acetosella*), knotweed (*Polygonum/persicaria*), common bistort (*Polygonum bistorta*), common knotgrass (*Polygonum aviculare*), and purging flax (*Linum catharticum*), which Lisbeth Prøsch-Danielsen (1993, p. 242) regards as reflecting weeds in arable fields or fallow lands. Sheep's sorrel is, however, understood by other researchers as a strong indicator of pastures as well (Bakka & Kaland, 1971; Behre, 1981; Danielsen, 1970; Hafsten, 1958; Høeg, 2011). Wild buckwheat (*Fallopia convolvulus*), german knotweed (*Schlerantus annuus*), cornflower (*Centaurea cyanus*), buckwheat (*Fagopyrum*), and broad bean (*Vicia faba*) are also associated with pastoral farming but can be present in periods of fallowing as well (Behre, 1981, p. 233).

However, as Behre (1981, p. 228) points out, the practice of creating sharp divisions between areas devoted to arable and pastoral farming is a relatively new practice in Europe and stands in contrast to the traditional farming practices of rotational systems and fallowing. Recent excavations in Vestfold in Norway have also shown the close connection between pasturing and grain cultivation in a rotational system as early as the Pre-Roman Iron Age (Gjerpe, 2013, pp. 17-19; Mjærum, 2012; N.-O. Svensson & Regnéll, 2013). In other words, evidence for pastoral indicators does not exclude the presence of arable farming in itself – and vice versa. Farming methods play an equally important role as the anthropogenic species are associated with different levels of resilience to soil cultivation. An Iron Age cultivation technique based on the use of ards, mattocks, and shovels favours perennial species, among them pastoral indicators like grass (*Gramineae*), broadleaf plantain (*Plantago major*), and ribwort plantain (Behre, 1981, p. 229; Dincauze, 2000, pp. 394-396). However, the implementation of the mouldboard plough during the Iron Age caused changes in the biotope, favouring instead therophyte (annual) species.

Ribwort and broadleaf plantain are, by most researchers, understood as important anthropogenic indicators but are variously associated with arable farming, pastures, and fallowing (Bakka & Kaland, 1971, p. 23; Behre, 1981; Danielsen, 1970; Hafsten, 1958, p. 55; Høeg, 1989, pp. 375-376; 2011, p. 115; Høeg & Mikkelsen, 1979, p. 161; Høgestøl & Prøsch-Danielsen, 2006, p. 25; Prøsch-Danielsen, 1993). Behre (1981, p. 229; 2007) is particularly critical of the use of ribwort plantain as a primary indicator and stresses its significant role in recolonizing abandoned cultivated lands, thus being a strong indicator of fallowing. Of importance is the interpretation of the apophytes in a wider botanical context. For instance,

high values of ribwort plantain, broadleaf plantain, sorrel, grasses, buttercup (*Ranunculaceae*), and heather (*Calluna vulgaris*) would suggest the presence of pastures (Behre, 1981, p. 241).

6.2.3 MAIN INDICATORS OF PASTORAL FARMING

The great variability in the ways that different palynologists assess the species highlights the subjective and human factor associated with the interpretative process (Behre, 1981, p. 237). One must also bear in mind that several species are native plants and that small quantities do not necessarily indicate farming (Behre, 2007, p. 206; Høeg & Mikkelsen, 1979, p. 161). Differences aside, there seems to be a general consensus on certain species associated with pastoral farming. Table 6.5 is based on the assessments made by Behre (1981), which is still in use as a focal point of reference in contemporary research (eg. Hjelle, 2015; N.-O. Svensson & Regnéll, 2013), and further supplemented with the assessments made by Bakka and Kaland (1971), Danielsen (1970), Fægri et al. (1989), Hafsten (1958), Høeg (2011), Høeg and Mikkelsen (1979), Høgestøl and Prøsch-Danielsen (2006) and Prøsch-Danielsen (1993).

LATIN NAME	COMMON NAME	ASSOCIATED WITH
<i>Rumex acetosella</i>	Sheep's sorrel	Cropfields, fallows, pastures (rare), outfield pastures
<i>Plantago major</i>	Broadleaf plantain	Cropfields (rare), fallows, pastures, outfield pastures
<i>Plantago media</i>	Hoary plantain	Cropfields (rare), fallows, pastures, outfield pastures
<i>Ranunculaceae</i>	Buttercup family	Cropfields (rare), fallows, pastures, outfield pastures
<i>Poaceae</i>	Grass	Cropfields, fallows, pastures, outfield pastures
<i>Cyperaceae</i>	Sedges	Fallows, pastures, outfield pastures
<i>Rumex acetosa</i>	Sorrel	Fallows, pastures, outfield pastures
<i>Umbelliferae</i>	Parsley	Fallows, pastures, outfield pastures
<i>Plantago lanceolata</i>	Ribwort plantain	Fallows, pastures, outfield pastures (rare)
<i>Jasione/Campanula</i>	Bellflower	Fallows, pastures (rare), outfield pastures
<i>Artemisia</i>	Absinthe	Fallows, outfield pastures
<i>Succisa pratensis</i>	Devil's-bit	Pastures, outfield pastures
<i>Calluna vulgaris</i>	Heather	Outfield pastures
<i>Juniperus communis</i>	Common juniper	Outfield pastures
<i>Melampyrum</i>	Cow wheat	Outfield pastures

Table 6.5: Anthropogenic indicators mainly associated with pastoral farming.

LATIN NAME	COMMON NAME	LATIN NAME	COMMON NAME
<i>Compositae</i>	Sunflower	<i>Polygonum bistorta</i>	Common bistort
<i>Cruciferae</i>	Mustards/crucifiers/cabbage	<i>Polygonum aviculare</i>	Common knotgrass
<i>Trifolium repens</i>	White clover	<i>Linum catharticum</i>	Purging flax
<i>Caryophyllaceae</i>	Carnation	<i>Convolvulus arvensis</i>	Field bindweed
<i>Urtica</i>	Nettle	<i>Vicia faba</i>	Broad bean
<i>Polygonum/Persicaria</i>	Knotweed	<i>Fagopyrum</i>	Buckwheat
<i>Spergula arvensis</i>	Corn spurry	<i>Centaurea cyanus</i>	Cornflower
<i>Chenopodiaceae</i>	Goosefoot	<i>Schlerantus annuus</i>	German knotweed
<i>Fallopia convolvulus</i>	Wild buckwheat	<i>Lychnis/Agrostemma-type</i>	Ragged-robin/corncockles

Table 6.6: Non-specific anthropogenic indicators.

A few of the species in Table 6.5, like broadleaf plantain, hoary plantain (*Plantago media*), buttercup, grasses, and sheep's sorrel *can* occur in crop fields but are mainly associated with pastures. In the pollen diagrams, sorrel (*Rumex acetosa*) and sheep's sorrel are often designated under the common term of *Rumex*, and are therefore not distinguishable in the source material.

Several more species are considered strong anthropogenic indicators but appear, in a varying extent, within a broad spectre of cultural landscapes, including cropfields, fallows, and pastures (Table 6.6). Although they can be good indicators of human activity, they are more or less non-specific with regard to farming practices and are therefore less useful in a study of subsistence strategies unless studied in relation to a wider range of main indicators.

6.2.4 ANIMAL MANURE

Pollen and macro-botanical samples from settlement and agricultural sites may also contain types of proxies other than botanical remains, providing further information on farming practices. Charred dung has, in a few instances, been identified among macrofossils and can sometimes be identified at species level (Moltsen, 2016). Dung testifies to livestock keeping, either as direct evidence for livestock presence at the respective sites, or more indirectly as remains of manure handling. Thus, dung becomes a useful proxy that may help to identify specific farming techniques, such as the manuring of permanent cropfields or rotational farming. The use of manure can also be identified through soil micro-morphology, which may include supplementary data on composition and origin, such as settlement and/or byre waste, but only occasionally at the species level (eg. Macphail et al., 2016; Viklund et al., 2013). However, the low number of soil micro-morphological analyses from excavations in Gudbrandsdalen valley and Lake Mjøsa limits the amount of data provided by this method (cf. Table 6.2).

Indirect evidence for livestock and manure can also be provided by the occasional occurrences of eggs from intestinal worms in paleo-botanical samples. Parasitic infections were rather common among humans and livestock in Europe until the mid-20th century, but are now more common in tropical and subtropical areas (Brooker & Pullan, 2013; Roepstorff & Pearman, 2005; Søre et al., 2018). The most common species belong to the *Trichuris* and *Ascaris* genera. Their eggs are deposited in faeces and therefore mostly found in cesspits and latrines (Brinkkemper & van Haaster, 2012), but can also be found in manured contexts or pastures (Moltsen, 2005, 2016). The eggs can survive for a considerable time in well-preserved contexts (Brinkkemper & van Haaster, 2012). Eggs from *Ascaris* have, for instance, been recovered from Palaeolithic contexts (Gonçalves, Araújo, & Ferreira, 2003). Before infecting a new host, the eggs require certain temperatures and levels of humidity in external environments to embryonate

(Brooker & Pullan, 2013). The eggs are therefore usually transmitted through ingestion from the environment, making pastures and manured cropfields an important source of infection (Roepstorff & Pearman, 2005, p. 205).

From Gudbrandsdalen valley there exists several identifications of *Ascaris* in pollen samples from agricultural layers, in some instances in large numbers, but also a few incidents of *Trichuris* (Moltsen, 2016). In general, *Trichuris* is better preserved than *Ascaris* over time and is therefore more often identified in archaeological contexts (Roepstorff & Pearman, 2005, p. 208). The high number of *Ascaris* in Gudbrandsdalen may be due to good preservation conditions provided by flood deposits (Moltsen, 2016).

Most parasites are host-specific and serve as markers of their respective hosts, making it a valuable proxy for studies of past dietary preferences (Søe et al., 2018). For instance, *Parascaris equorum* (*Ascarid*-type) and *Oxyuris equi* are associated with horses, while *Toxocara canis* (*Ascarid*-type) infects canines (Roepstorff & Pearman, 2005, p. 205). However, most species are difficult to separate from each other in the archaeological record. Traditional identification rests on morphological examinations and most species can be defined by microscopy only to the genus level. Closer examinations require DNA-analysis, which has not been conducted on the present material. Nonetheless, *Ascaris* and *Trichuris* appear more often in certain types of species thereby helping to identify the likely hosts.

Trichuris is usually associated with ruminants, canines, and rodents. *Trichuris suis* may infect pigs, but they seem to be more vulnerable to *Ascaris*. *Trichuris* may also infect humans but cannot be easily separated from the types infecting pigs (Roepstorff & Pearman, 2005, p. 208). A Danish study of organic pig herding showed that, if they have not received any medications, 28-33% of the pigs were infected by *Ascaris suum* and 4-13% of *Trichuris suis* (Moltsen, 2005, p. 201, with references). The *Ascaris* genus are mainly associated with pigs and humans and is easily distinguishable from other types of parasites (Roepstorff & Pearman, 2005, p. 205). However, the two *Ascaris* species are so closely related that closer identification is difficult even with DNA analysis (Søe et al., 2018). Cross-species infection is possible, especially between pigs and humans. Incidents of human infections are known from present-day Denmark due to handling of pig manure (Nejsum et al., 2005). *Ascaris* can also infect cattle, but the larvae only mature and produce eggs in humans and pigs (Greenway & McCraw, 1970; Thamsborg, Nejsum, & Mejer, 2013). Thus, identified eggs from *Ascaris* in archaeological contexts testify to the presence of infected humans and/or pigs. In agricultural layers, it most likely reflects handling of pig manure. *Trichuris* may be connected to more species but their presence nonetheless indicates the presence of manure, of which cattle and pigs are possible sources.

6.2.5 ASSESSING ARABLE AND PASTORAL FARMING

The agricultural sites in the thesis database are made up of archaeological contexts in which agricultural layers and/or clearance cairns have been documented (cf. Chapter 6.1). However, assessing farming practices from these two characteristics alone may prove a difficult task. First, farming strategies may have changed over time, meaning that the sites would include evidence from different practices that are not easily distinguished from one another. Clearance cairns do not always occur in relation to cropfields and are consequently found in meadows and pastures alike. Agricultural layers are strong indicators for cultivation, but similar morphological characteristics of the soil may also develop through long-term grazing and manure enrichment, as has been documented for the Fryasletta site in Fron (Macphail et al., 2016. To be further discussed in Chapter 7.2 and 7.8). Documented plough-marks help to distinguish between pastoral and arable layers but, unfortunately, have been documented only in a limited number of cases. In other words, the total body of archaeological and scientific evidence from each specific context must be closely scrutinised before final interpretations can be made of its character, making the archaeo-botanical and micro-morphological evidence of utmost importance.

In line with the discussions in Chapter 6.2, I will use a strict approach to the archaeo-botanical data in which only direct evidence for cultivation (cereals, hop/hemp, and flax) will be considered diagnostic for arable farming. While crop types are of greatest importance, documented plough marks and/or identified cultivated soils through soil micro-morphology will also be put under consideration in the forthcoming evaluations and used as indicators of arable farming. Identified dung can be interpreted as evidence for both grazing livestock and active manuring of cultivated fields and will therefore *not* be treated as conclusive evidence for cropfields in itself.

To help sort out pastoral farming, the secondary anthropogenic indicators in Table 6.5 will be taken into consideration. However, single finds or single species will not be considered diagnostic as the secondary indicators are native species and can occur in a variety of natural and cultural contexts (Chapter 6.2). The identification of pastoral farming therefore requires the presence of more than one indicator, preferably in significant numbers, or be supported by available soil micro-morphological analyses.

6.3 Aspects of crop vulnerability

Different grain species have different requirements for growth, and this variability is essential for understanding Iron Age agricultural vulnerability. Barley, rye, oats, and wheat (including spelt) constitute

the four main types of cereals in both prehistoric and modern Scandinavia. Of these, there are several variants that have been utilised in varying degrees throughout prehistory. The oldest types were naked barley (*Hordeum vulgare nudum*) and different variants of wheat: emmer (*Triticum dicoccum*), einkorn (*Triticum monococcum*), and spelt (*Triticum spelta*) (Myhre, 2002, p. 53). Naked barley was later on replaced by the more robust hulled barley (*Hordeum vulgare*), and emmer and einkorn by common wheat (*Triticum aestivum*). Hulled barley predominated in Iron Age Scandinavia, especially in middle and northern Scandinavia (Bjørnstad, 2012; Pedersen & Widgren, 2011, p. 51; Robinson et al., 2009). Oats were introduced during the 1st millennia BC, while rye arrived only in the 1st millennium AD. Of the four main categories, wheat has the highest temperature requirement, while barley, rye, and oats are less demanding (Frøseth, 2004; Strand, 1984, p. 25). Wheat has traditionally been viewed in favourable terms due to high baking qualities, colour, and taste, whereas rye and oats have often been considered low-status and associated with lower social classes (Bjørnstad, 2014, pp. 87, 98). Barley was clearly favoured in Iron Age farming in present-day Norway, but crop diversity seems to have increased towards the Middle Ages (Bjørnstad, 2012; Myhre, 2002).

As older variants of modern cereals are no longer present, the exact requirements for prehistoric cereal cultivation are difficult to assess. Up until modern times, long-term cultivation led to local adaptation and a multitude of grain variation. Modern industrialised farming has caused most of the older variants to disappear as crops have become more standardised (Strand, 1984, pp. 57-58). Scientific methods and deliberate selections of favourable properties have also led to the development of more robust variants resulting in higher farming outputs. However, the earliest cultivated species were, generally speaking, not that different from modern types, and the basic requirements and qualities remain comparable (Strand, 1984, p. 9).

Cereals can be sowed both in springtime and in autumn as certain variants can hibernate during winter. Winter cereals have several benefits since the farmer is less dependent on the weather during springtime and, since the cereals start to grow at an earlier date, they have a better chance at out-competing weeds. However, not all species are equally adapted to the cold climates in northern and middle Scandinavia and some are therefore not suitable for autumn sowing. In the Iron Age, most grains were sowed in springtime. The exception is winter rye, which was introduced to Scandinavia in the 3rd century AD (Robinson et al., 2009, p. 134). As such, winter rye represents an important innovation to Iron Age agriculture as it allowed for greater diversity in farming strategies. It might also have opened up for an efficient three-stage cultivation system (Bjørnstad, 2012, pp. 100-102). After harvesting barley in the autumn, the fields could be immediately ploughed and sowed with winter rye, allowing for an early harvest the upcoming year. In order to recover, the field was subsequently fallowed after the second

harvest (stage three). The three-stage system is well-known from medieval southern Scandinavia, but the Danish finds suggest it might have been introduced at an earlier stage (Bjørnstad, 2012, p. 100; Robinson et al., 2009). Haakon Foss (1926) was preoccupied with rye cultivation in Norway in historical times and described a similar practice. In order to clear the fields for weeds, fallowing was important after long-term cultivation, which was often followed by sowing of rye in autumn. Furthermore, if left for grasslands, early harvesting of fodder allowed for subsequent rye sowing.

Generally speaking, longer growing periods result in somewhat bigger yields but are more susceptible to bad weather (Frøseth, pers. comm.). Spring cereals can be sowed at both an early or late date, which results in different temperature requirements. It naturally follows that early crops mature at an earlier date than later crops. However, such distinctions are almost impossible to derive from the archaeological record as the utilised species variants are the same. It has nonetheless importance for how we choose to model agricultural vulnerability in a prehistoric setting, in particular when it comes to the required heat budget. In Norway, cereals are still mostly sown in springtime with the exception of rye, which is traditionally sowed in autumn. I will therefore concentrate on spring barley, spring oats, spring wheat, and winter rye in the following text.

	Barley	Oats	Spring wheat	Winter wheat	Winter rye	Winter spelt
Resilience against weeds	Well suited	Well suited	Less suited	Well suited	Well suited	Well suited
Growth during less precipitation	Less suited	Well suited	Well suited	Less suited	Well suited	Well suited
Resilience against diseases	Well suited	Well suited	Less suited	Less suited	Well suited	Well suited
Growth in clay rich soils	Well suited	Well suited	Well suited	Well suited	Well suited	Well suited
Growth in silt rich soils	Well suited	Well suited	Less suited	Less suited	Well suited	Well suited
Growth in sand rich soils	Well suited	Less suited	Less suited	Well suited	Well suited	Well suited
Growth in mixed/poorly structured sediments	Less suited	Well suited	Well suited	Less suited	Well suited	Well suited

Well suited

Suited

Less suited

Table 6.7: Growing conditions for a selection of common grains in modern Norwegian organic farming. Modified from Frøseth (2006).

Some basic geological and biological requirements concerning modern Norwegian organic farming are listed in Table 6.7. General speaking, oats and rye are considered robust species that thrive under difficult

conditions, while barley is a fairly decent all-rounder. Wheat is a particularly vulnerable species, whereas spelt thrives in less nutritious soils and is more robust against diseases and drought. However, more factors need to be added, as will be outlined below.

There are two main types of barley: six-rowed and two-rowed. Six-row barley is more common in middle and northern Scandinavia than two-row barley, as the latter requires more temperatures to mature (Bjørnstad, 2012, p. 18). Barley and oats have traditionally been widely used as animal fodder. Barley can be sowed during both spring and autumn in southern Scandinavia, but only in springtime further north. It is well adapted to a cold Nordic climate and requires around 250-300 mm rainfall, which is more or less equivalent to the average conditions in eastern Norway (Strand, 1984, p. 30). The growing period is quite short, down to a potential of 80 days for early barley (Holtet, 2019). However, as it grows quite fast, it also requires nutritious soils. As such, manuring is often required for barley cultivation (Bjørnstad, 2012; Frøseth, 2004, 2006). Six-row barley was, in the 1920s, cultivated as far north as Alta (70°N). It was also cultivated on Iceland in the Middle Ages, but widespread crop failure occurred during the 13th century because of prolonged cooling, resulting in famine. Ultimately, crop cultivation ceased on the island up to modern times (Bjørnstad, 2012, p. 103).

Oats are a common species in middle and northern Scandinavia, but was of far more importance when horses were widely used for transportation and labour. Oats are, consequently, by and large associated with animal fodder. It has few diseases, is quite nutritious, thrifty, and able to grow in nutrient-poor, harsh, and cold climates (Bjørnstad, 2012, p. 22; Frøseth, 2006). In historical times, barley and oats were often cultivated in the same fields, which increased agricultural robustness towards diseases, bad weather, and annual temperature variations (Bjørnstad, 2012, p. 98). Oats can only be sowed in springtime in Nordic countries.

Rye, like oats, is thrifty and grows in nutrient-poor soils and cold climates, but is susceptible against humid conditions. Rye has poor baking qualities, which are further reduced during periods of increased precipitation. Rye is also highly susceptible to ergot and therefore less suitable for coastal areas (cf. Chapter 2.3.3). As it is resilient towards frost, rye is traditionally sowed in autumn, but is nonetheless vulnerable to snow, which is a regular annual feature in inland areas of middle- and northern Scandinavia. Lasting snow-cover increases the risk for fungal diseases such as snow mould (*fusarium patch*). Thus, rye may be a risky endeavour for high altitude and latitude farming. Still, rye gradually increased in importance in Europe during the 1st millennium AD, in particular eastern Europe, southern Scandinavia, and Finland (Bjørnstad, 2012, p. 100; Robinson et al., 2009). Compared to barley and wheat, it gives better

yields in nutrient-poor areas. The exact time of its introduction to Norway is a matter of some debate, but rye is nonetheless believed to have played only a minor role until the late Middle Ages (Bjørnstad, 2012, p. 100; Myhre, 2002, pp. 143-193, 314).

Wheat has high breadmaking qualities but is also particularly temperature-sensitive. Wheat requires higher temperatures than other species, making it less suitable for a Nordic climate. Systematic selection in the 20th century has improved its temperature requirements, and wheat has therefore only been cultivated in large quantities in Scandinavia in modern times (Bjørnstad, 2012, p. 21; 2014, p. 88). Exclusive as it is, wheat has always been considered high status and associated with the uppermost echelons of society (Bjørnstad, 2012, p. 97). Spelt is less demanding and more suitable for nutrient-poor soils than ordinary wheat (Frøseth, 2004, p. 176). However, as spelt gives lower yields, ordinary wheat is favoured in modern farming. Wheat can be sowed during autumn in middle Scandinavia, meaning that winter wheat has a more northerly distribution than winter barley.

Crop diversity increases agricultural resilience towards crop diseases and pests, and it is therefore recommended that crop fields are alternated with different species from one year to another (Frøseth, 2004). This is particularly important for organic farming as the use of pesticides is restricted. Similar challenges must therefore have been the case for Iron Age farming. A mixed farming strategy, combined with regular fallowing, is also important for soil recovery and preventing soil deterioration (Behre, 1981; Bjørnstad, 2012, pp. 101-102; Frøseth, 2004). According to Randi B. Frøseth (2004, p. 168), oats should only be cultivated every fifth year, and barley and wheat every third year, in a cycle involving pasturing and grass production. If cereals are grown two years in a row on the same field, different species should be cultivated one year to the next. In other words, a single grain strategy would lower farming outputs over time, while a diversified strategy increases agricultural robustness. Mixed crops also enhance agricultural robustness to climate change as the different species respond differently to changes in weather and temperature (Gunnarsdottir & Høeg, 1996, p. 45). Rye is more resilient to cold weather, whereas barley is better adapted to dry summers. Oats require more growing days than barley but have greater tolerance for colder summers and high precipitation.

To sum up, agricultural vulnerability cannot be approached as a single variable but must be explored in close relation to crop types, crop composition, soil conditions, and local climates. Thus, temperature is not the only variable that must be brought under consideration. If combined with snow-rich or humid conditions, even rye cultivation may be a highly vulnerable farming strategy during a cooling event.

6.4 Macro-level analysis

The statistical analysis will be conducted on osteological, radiocarbon, and paleo-botanical datasets made available through archaeological excavations in the Lake Mjøsa region and Gudbrandsdalen valley. By systemising large datasets from a broad set of categories, my approach aims at providing insight into the subsistence strategies within the two research areas, such as grain types, livestock composition, and wildlife exploitation. In order to study changes over time, a chronological resolution will be pursued through modelling of C14-data. By using the 'context' function in the database, the data is arranged according to geographical location and age in order to clarify the following:

- Site development
- Farming practices
- Types of agricultural outputs
- Level of crop diversity
- Level of outfield exploitation

This analysis aims at identifying possible risk drivers in relation to climate cooling, such as temperature-demanding crops, low crop diversity, or narrow subsistence strategies. Of importance is also the identification of possible adaptational strategies, such as more robust crop types and increased pastoral farming and wildlife exploitation. The long-term developments and regional differences between the two areas, which may contribute to a better understanding of societal vulnerability and human responses to the cooling event, are important factors at play. The results lead up to the case studies in which the possible impact of the climate cooling in the two areas will be more closely examined. In the following, I will outline some basic source critical issues inherent in the present datasets, how they are taken into account, and finally how the research goals relate to the structure of the statistical analysis.

6.4.1 DATA REPRESENTATIVENESS

A major source-critical challenge for a quantitative analysis concerns the issue of data representativeness. As stated by Dina Dincauze (2000, p. 27), a quantitative approach needs to draw on large enough proxies to become representative. However, a focus on mere numbers risks downplaying the importance of statistical uncertainties, sampling bias, and putting the character of the dataset itself under close scrutiny (cf. Degroot et al., 2021). Incomplete datasets, or excessive focus on easily available but limited proxies, contribute to partial perspectives and conclusions that are poorly suited for analysing overall societal developments.

Important in this respect are site-formation processes and taphonomy. The term 'taphonomy' was originally used on the formative biological and geological processes and disturbances shaping the paleo-osteological record, but is nowadays more or less interchangeable with site-formation processes, thus describing the processes and human and natural activities that shape the archaeological record (Dawdy, 2006; cf. Dincauze, 2000, pp. 444-467; cf. Pilø, Barrett, et al., 2020; Solli, 1988). Brit Solli (1988, p. 95) compares the source-critical aspects of biofacts with those for artefacts, stressing the need to critically evaluate preservation conditions, the initial deposition, the process of recovery, sampling size, and sampling bias. Thus, the context itself is of importance, representing an archive of information vital for the interpretations of the archaeological sites. Of equal importance is the loss of information, partially caused by differences in preservation conditions and rates of degradation for different types of materials. Furthermore, human waste reaches archaeological deposits through a combination of intentional and unintentional processes, which are further conditioned by degradation caused by human and natural agents (Dincauze, 2000, pp. 445-446). In short, it can be concluded that the archaeological record is by no means equivalent to the past living community, and mere quantified approaches may create a distorted picture of the study object. Archaeological contexts are not snapshots of past conditions and events, but rather the accumulated sum of natural and human processes and disturbances up to the moment of recovery which are further conditioned by methods, sampling strategies, and levels of documentation (Solli, 1988, pp. 94-96).

Quantifications of faunal remains are usually conducted by the choice of three main approaches: number of fragments, weight, and minimum number of individuals, all of which are associated with different types of source-critical challenges (Solli, 1988, pp. 121-127). Of these, the mere quantification of fragments remains the most criticised. Human agency plays a fundamental role in the formation of archaeological deposits through deliberate and accidental selections, influenced by, for instance, butchery practices, craft, and the very character of resource exploitation. This is well-illustrated by the faunal deposits at medieval towns and mountainous mass trapping sites in southern Norway. At the trapping sites, systematic butchery practices and defleshing of the cadavers caused huge amounts of bones to be left behind (Hufthammer, Bratbak, & Indrelid, 2011), resulting in the underrepresentation of bones from wild deer in the urban centres with the exception of large amounts of antler fragments from commercialised comb production (cf. Lie, 1988; E. Mikkelsen, 1994, pp. 142-150). Moreover, large livestock, like cattle (*Bos taurus*), are more likely to be butchered into a high number of pieces than smaller mammals, thus creating more fragments per individual (Solli, 1988, p. 124). Cattle may therefore be overrepresented in archaeological deposits compared to sheep/goat (*Ovis/Capra*) and pig (*Sus scrofa*). Moreover, bones from mammals are more likely to be preserved than those from fish and birds, creating a certain preservation bias towards distinct types of biological remains (Dincauze, 2000, p. 460). Consequently, not much can be concluded from an absence of the two latter categories in an archaeological context, unless in situations

with exceptional preservation conditions. The number of bones vary between species, as well as the robustness of the individual bones against decomposition. These aspects also concern the weight-method, which in addition is affected by the soil conditions in which materials are found. To be able to compare faunal remains at different sites by the use of weight, one would need similar sedimentary conditions at the sites (Solli, 1988, p. 123). Weight would also favour large species, unless the numbers are corrected with regard to the respective species. The third method, minimum number of individuals, is developed in an attempt to overcome the source-critical challenges associated with the first two, but depends on well-preserved, well-sampled, and well-documented contexts in which comparable parts of the animals can be found and assessed in equal manners (Dincauze, 2000, pp. 415-420; Solli, 1988, pp. 125-127).

Figure 6.6: Development in frequency and precision of radiocarbon dating in relation to excavation year, based on 1367 C14-dates from settlement and agricultural sites in Lake Mjøsa region and Gudbrandsdalen valley. Blue and red dots relate to the left axis, whereas the green dots relate to right axis. If conducted over multiple seasons, only the last excavation year is used as point of reference.

Taphonomic biases are of equal importance for the radiocarbon record (Ramsey, 2017, p. 1). Variations in compiled radiocarbon datasets related to the Scandinavian Iron Age have been understood as reflections of demographic developments (Solheim & Iversen, 2019) and shifting labour investments (Herschend,

2009, pp. 20-27), but may also simply reflect investigation bias. Although charred remains are usually preferred for dating purposes, thereby making decomposition a less crucial factor for data representativeness, the dates are not directly related to the magnitude and duration of human occupation in itself, but sampling strategies, research interests, and rate of preservation/disturbance of the archaeological features (Hassan, 2016, p. 40). In addition, charred remains can survive for a considerable amount of time in undisturbed contexts, making it possible that it gets mixed in with later activities and therefore becomes an outlier for the targeted activity. Re-use of older materials, and the age of the respective wood, must also be put into consideration (Wright, 2017, pp. 306-307). Timber used in buildings may, for instance, be of varying age, ranging from perhaps 40 years at minimum and up to several centuries (P. H. Mikkelsen & Bartholin, 2016, pp. 270-272). The type of context chosen for dating purposes is therefore of vital importance. In particular, structural elements are at risk of generating dating results considerably older than the actual use of the site. In any case, all C14-dates are to be understood as *terminus post quem*, as the dated material will always be older, to a greater or lesser extent, than the activity it is associated with (Ramsey, 2009b). Further challenges are provided by the rapid development in archaeological methods, in particular the significant increase in the number of radiocarbon dates conducted per year and per site (Figure 6.6), making it difficult to compare the results from older and more recent excavations. Dealing with sample biases is of vital importance for any study that employ statistical analyses of large radiocarbon datasets. However, the source-critical issues cannot be readily solved by C14 modelling alone (Ramsey, 2017, p. 24). Unless some sort of qualitative or statistical selection is initially made of the available data, the radiocarbon record should not be used as direct proxy for the intensity and duration of human activity.

The method of radiocarbon dating in itself is also important, as it is not a dating technique in its own right but a measurement of isotope ratios that can be used for age estimations (Ramsey, 2009a, p. 337). Radiocarbon is an unstable isotope of carbon that is continuously created in the atmosphere and troposphere and binds with oxygen to create carbon dioxide (R. Wood, 2015, pp. 62-63; Wright, 2017, pp. 304-305). Through photosynthesis, it becomes incorporated into plants and then to the animals through digestion. As long as the animal lives, the amount of radiocarbon remains stable through continuous food ingestion. Upon death, the animal, or plant, stops exchanging carbon with its environment and the radiocarbon starts to decay with a half-life of 5730 years. Thus, an age estimation can be calculated by measuring the amount of radiocarbon left in the organism. All radiocarbon measurements are listed with a statistical probability. Dating precision has improved significantly during the last several decades due to enhanced laboratory procedures and the implementation of accelerator mass spectrometry as standard method; in recent years the margins of error have frequently been below ± 20 years (Figure 6.6). For older excavations the affiliated radiocarbon dates are listed with measurement probabilities as low as ± 160 years, which resulted in great inaccuracies in age determinations. The chronological resolution of older

excavations can therefore be lower than for those conducted more recently, thus adding to the difficulties concerning site comparison.

Figure 6.7: Visualisation of calibration curve IntCal 20 for the 1st millennium AD, by using OxCal v4.4.2 (Ramsey, 2009a; Reimer et al., 2020), with the Migration Period plateau marked in yellow.³⁹ The radiocarbon dates are idealised and set with a 20-year interval and high probability. Illustration by author.

However, the amount of radiocarbon in the atmosphere is not constant. The measurements can therefore only be converted to calendar age by using a calibration curve (R. Wood, 2015, pp. 65-66). The most recent one is IntCal20, developed from mostly dendrochronological proxies (Reimer et al., 2020). Because

³⁹ The plateau is also present in older versions of IntCal.

of the different atmospheric values of radiocarbon in the past, the shape of the curve is not even, but involves several 'wiggles' and plateaus (flatlines), including the Hallstatt plateau around 800-400 BC, whereby one radiocarbon date may correspond to several calendar ages (Rahbek & Rasmussen, 1997; Reimer et al., 2020, p. 735; Wright, 2017, p. 314). Consequently, the Hallstatt plateau has proved problematic for solving important chronological issues around the transition from the Bronze Age to the Iron Age. Even high probability measurements become inaccurate if it borders or falls within it, thus resulting in an unusually wide date range.

A smaller plateau, but of similar importance for the Fimbulwinter discourse, covers most of the period AD 400-550 (Figure 6.7). The calibration curve has similar properties within the plateau, meaning that the calibrated age cannot be precisely defined within its limits. The radiocarbon dates used in Figure 6.7 are idealised and only employed to visualise how measurements that correlate with the plateau result in wide age determinations covering most of the 5th and the early 6th century AD, thus causing low chronological precision and wide date ranges for Migration Period sites (see Guo et al., 2018, pp. 671-672, for a similar problematisation of the plateau). The plateau does not directly affect the Merovingian Period, during which the calibration curve mostly follows a steady development, contributing to higher dating precision. Sites originally belonging to the 5th century may consequently receive dating results that artificially extend the occupation towards the beginning of the Merovingian Period, thus enhancing the impression of widespread site abandonment around this time. It may also create the image of high numbers of contemporaneous sites during the entire Migration Period, hence indicating stable high site density. Moreover, the idealised dates in the model are set with high probability (± 15 years), and the effect of the plateau would increase in line with decreasing measurement probability, potentially extending it to include both the Late Roman Iron Age and the Early Merovingian Period. For older excavations in particular, the Migration Period plateau obscures the chronological development from the Early to the Late Iron Age, which is something that further complicates the source-critical issues related to the crisis hypotheses. It cannot be readily solved, but must nonetheless be taken into account when assessing the temporal attributes of the archaeological record.

6.4.2 SITE REPRESENTATIVENESS

The differences in research history in the two regions have created certain qualitative and quantitative differences concerning their respective archaeological records (cf. Chapter 6.1.1), with more data per site in Gudbrandsdalen valley but a higher total body of data from the Lake Mjøsa region. In general, this is caused by a higher number of older excavations from around the lake, resulting in a lower sampling rate than in the valley. However, the Gudbrandsdalen valley dataset is mostly derived from excavations executed during the last decade, in particular the E6 road construction project in Fron in 2011-2012

(Gundersen, 2016e). This has resulted in several well-documented sites, including a wide array of scientific results, but also in a dataset somewhat restricted in both spatial and temporal terms. The excavated sites are mostly situated in the middle and southern part of the valley, whereas the excavated sites in Lake Mjøsa region are more evenly distributed in the landscape. Moreover, the Fron sites are mostly dated to the Early Iron Age, whereas Late Iron Age evidence is scattered and lacking in defined farmsteads. The E6 zoning plans were limited to a narrow strip in the terrain, mostly located in the valley bottom and lower valley sides, where several Early Iron Age sites were discovered. Fewer excavations have been conducted in the traditional farming heartlands in the middle part of the valley sides, where most burial mounds and Late Iron Age artefact finds have been located (cf. Sæbø, 2020), thus creating a certain bias in the dataset towards what seems to have been an Early Iron Age settlement expansion towards the valley bottom (cf. Gundersen, 2016a; Gundersen, 2016d). Other excavations in the valley have provided important information which help to balance the overall dataset, but the high number of excavations in Fron compared to the rest of the valley still create a distinct investigation bias that must be taken into account. The results from the analysis must therefore be properly contextualised in relation to the spatial and temporal properties of the excavated sites, since a mere quantified approach may create a distorted impression of the changes from the Early to the Late Iron Age. A direct comparison between the two regions can therefore not be done on quantitative data alone, but through coherent interpretations that incorporate the source-critical properties of the archaeological data.

6.4.3 RADIOCARBON PROXIES AND SITE CHRONOLOGIES

Interpretations of site occupation is mainly based on the high number of C14-analyses conducted in relation to the respective excavations, thus making the radiocarbon datasets vital for understanding the long-term trajectories of the archaeological record. However, as discussed in previous chapters, the datasets are associated with source-critical challenges such as outliers, wood age, investigation bias, and uncertainties and inaccuracies regarding the radiocarbon method in itself. Some sort of qualitative and statistical selection is therefore required, which is taken into account by employing a procedure termed 'outlier analysis' (Ramsey, 2009b). Through outlier analysis a number of C14-dates that appear unrelated to the targeted activity are sorted out, whereas the remaining dates are used in kernel density models (KDE) and establishing site chronologies.

Figure 6.8: Number of radiocarbon dates per 'context' in the thesis database.

The age estimations listed in archaeological reports and publications involve different calibration curves, as the C14-analyses have been conducted over a time-span ranging for several decades. To begin with, all available radiocarbon dates are therefore recalibrated in OxCal v4.4.2 by using IntCal20 (Ramsey, 2009a; Reimer et al., 2020). The 2-sigma calibrations are thereafter used as a basis for reinterpreting the age of the respective contexts and sites. However, the number of C14-dates per context varies considerably from site to site. A large number of contexts include only one date, while others contain up to 33 records (Figure 6.8). The fewer the dates, the less reliable the age-identification of the targeted activity becomes, especially if the context represents several events and long-term use. Although a large number of dates may increase reliability, the number of possible outliers is also increased. For instance, some contexts have considerable date ranges, even though the activity or construction in question might have been of limited duration. This is well-illustrated with Grytting I House V in Fron, a longhouse with a probable life-span of approximately 20-100 years (cf. Løken, 2020, pp. 195-206), but with a range of dates as high as 2800 years (Figure 6.9). Clearly, a number of outliers are present that are not related to the actual occupation of the longhouse.

Figure 6.9: Summed probability plot (Ramsey, 2009a) of C14-dates associated with Grytting I House V (context no 333) calibrated with IntCal20 (Reimer et al., 2020).

When working on contextual scales, significant outliers can often be easily identified and sorted out manually. However, when working on large datasets, a more objective and statistical approach is often needed as we can never be really sure whether any particular measurement is an outlier. Following the recommendations of Christopher B. Ramsey (2009b), I have chosen a three-step approach involving Bayesian statistical functions integrated in Oxcal v4.4.2 (Reimer et al., 2020). Initially, significant outliers are manually sorted out. The manual rejection is based on contextual evidence provided by the excavation reports, such as uncertain contexts, stratigraphic attributes, and contextual relations to other archaeological features on site, or if the radiocarbon date diverges considerably from the general age interpretation of the context. This procedure is used on all radiocarbon dates and contexts in the database. Further outliers can be dealt with statistically by using the Outlier_Model in OxCal v4.4.2, using the 'General' command:

```
Outlier_Model("General",T(5),U(0,4),"t");
```

Outlier analysis allows for a statistical approach to age determination and sort out radiocarbon dates that is not related to the study object. The approach is particularly useful when dealing with defined

interrelated activities and constructions, in particular buildings, in order to enhance the chronological precision. The goal is to reduce the possibility of errors due to incorrect measurements, contamination, old wood remains, or sampling strategies. The prior probability that a sample is an outlier can be adjusted in the model and set according to site and sample evaluation. In this particular case, I have set the prior probability to 5%, which is the standard setting in the 'General' command, in order to treat all data in the same manner. Outliers are thereafter removed from the model, which are run a second time with the 'Charcoal' command, with a prior outlier probability of 100%:

```
Outlier_Model("Charcoal",Exp(1,-10,0),U(0,3),"t");
```

The 'Charcoal' command treats all measurements as *terminus post quem* (hence a prior probability of 100%), thus favouring the younger range of the modelled radiocarbon dates. After running the procedure on Grytting I House V, it looks probable that the house was built in the Late Migration Period, and became abandoned during the course of the 6th century (Figure 6.10), which would be in accordance with the interpretations conducted by the excavation team (Villumsen, 2016a). Both commands are run in combination with a one-phased sequence model in OxCal v4.4.2, as the dataset represent a defined, inter-related, and temporally restricted set of activities (establishment, use, and abandonment of a house plot). Multiple phases can be added, if several residential phases can be identified.

The smaller the datasets, the less precise an outlier analysis becomes. On medium datasets (≤ 10) the 'Charcoal' command is sufficient for outlier analysis, as long as one is positive about the representativeness of the younger measurements (which would often be excluded using the 'General' command). On small datasets (≤ 4), outlier analysis adds little to the interpretations and can be ruled out.⁴⁰ For small datasets, and temporally dispersed activities, a sum-plot or multi-plot in OxCal v4.4.2 are sufficient for defining the occupation phase(s).

However, when working upon contexts that have been maintained and used with varying intensity for considerably longer timespans, such as agricultural sites, or compiled sets of diverse settlement traces of varying age, the statistical approach becomes less useful since it favours a statistical average of the total body of measurements. Thus, it would exclude data regarding the earliest and latest occupation phases for that specific context and remove important data from the analysis. The contextual approach in step 1

⁴⁰ In the database are C14-dates included in an outlier analysis marked out, as well as the respective dates that has been excluded in the final sequence model.

is therefore used for detecting outliers among agricultural contexts and diverse activity traces, whereas the statistical analysis in step 2 and 3 represent a useful supplement when assessing defined sequences of human activities, in which it can be determined that the activity would have had a definable beginning and end. This applies, for instance, to buildings, production phases, and craft. In this study, it is mainly employed for the age determination of buildings.

Figure 6.10: Age modelling of Grytting I House V, after running an outlier analysis including the 'General' and 'Charcoal'-commands in OxCal v4.4.2 (cf. Ramsey, 2009b).

Further analysis can thereafter be conducted on the selected radiocarbon dates. In order to analyse overall trends in the archaeological record, KDE analyses in OxCal v4.4.2 (Ramsey, 2017; Reimer et al., 2020) are employed on large compiled datasets, such as agricultural contexts and different types of settlement proxies (a preliminary KDE analysis of cooking pits has been conducted in Gundersen et al., 2020). Summed probability plots are widely used for analysing long-term trends in the archaeological record, but are associated with problems of separating genuine signals from noise caused by fluctuations in the calibration curve, causing sharp troughs and peaks (cf. Figure 6.9) and excessive spreads where there are plateaus in the curve (Michczyński & Michczyńska, 2006; Ramsey, 2017, p. 3). The KDE model is developed to retain underlying signals and remove high frequency noise, thus producing a curve more in

line with the distribution and individual properties of the samples. However, the model itself does not compensate for taphonomic issues, thus making outlier detection important for enhancing the basic qualities of the dataset. Even so, removing outliers does not balance for over-sampling, investigation bias, and the varying frequencies in radiocarbon dating during the last four decades. Radiocarbon datasets do not reflect past human activity in any direct way as they are heavily influenced by the process of recovery, sampling, budgets, and research interests. It is important to remember that the models are mere tools for evaluating the radiocarbon datasets, and not providing final answers in itself.

Figure 6.11: A schematic representation of the principles behind DDA.

In order to make amends for the many biases present in the datasets, KDE is combined with compiled date distributions. The latter is employed as a way of systemising and making use of site chronologies by compiling the data in relation to archaeological periods. The approach is based on thorough examinations of each and every context and associated dates in the thesis database in order to clarify the duration of the respective activities on site, and for the overall site occupation. The assessments are based on stratigraphic sequences, typological evidence, and radiocarbon dates, in which radiocarbon dates constitute the main proxy. The stratigraphic and typological interpretations rely on the observations and conclusions made in the excavation reports. Thus, it becomes possible to treat site chronologies as big data, as different types of activities can be sorted out and analysed in relation to similar finds at other

sites. Following this procedure, each context is given an equal count within each archaeological period, independent from the number of associated radiocarbon dates. Consequently, the approach does not take into account different levels of settlement activity. However, it has the advantage that all sites are given an equal emphasis in the analysis regardless of sampling intensity. This makes possible better comparisons between older and newer excavation results, including those that are only indirectly dated by contextual evidence or typology.

Figure 6.11 visualises how date distributions are compiled to generate overall trends in site chronologies, in the following termed 'date distribution analysis' (DDA). In this example, all sites have been in use over multiple periods, and the total number of records (n) is therefore higher than the actual number of sites. Periods with no evidence for site occupation generates no values, meaning that abandonment phases can be sorted out in the overall statistics. However, as the dates are organised in blocks, the graph becomes somewhat 'delayed'. A context that is abandoned during the course of the Merovingian Period will only appear as such in the subsequent period. To enhance the chronological resolution, each period⁴¹ has therefore been split in two halves, and the dating evidence, to the extent possible, defined as belonging to either the early or later part of the respective period (see chronologies in Chapter 1.3).

From 2012 onwards, there is a certain investigation bias favouring small cooking pit sites (cf. Chapter 6.1.1 and Figure 6.4). These sites are usually of short duration and differs from more complex and larger settlement sites. It is therefore necessary to make some sort of statistical classification of the sites in order to be able to identify different spatial and temporal patterns in their occupation. However, in one out of ten cases site statistics are not complete and lack information regarding the total number of archaeological features. This is particularly the case with older excavations, albeit not exclusively. Among them are important sites such as Åker II, Valum, and Vidarshov excavated between 1992-94 in Hamar (Pilø, 2005), but also the more recent excavations of the Iron Age farmstead at Mo in Øyer. However, they all include well-documented radiocarbon records. In addition, evidence for site continuity/disruption is important for the overall assessments of site development, which adds to the importance of the radiocarbon record for the forthcoming analyses. A distinction is therefore made between small, medium, and large sites based on C14-proxies.

Figure 6.12 demonstrates that the number of archaeological features and C14-dates are statistically related, although not in a one-to-one manner. On average, 1-4 C14-dates correspond to seven

⁴¹ With the exception of the Pre-Roman Iron Age.

archaeological features, while 5-14 dates include 47-63 features. Sites with fifteen or more dates have an average of 167 features. Roughly speaking, there is a ratio between the number of radiocarbon dates and archaeological features somewhere between 1:5 and 1:10. I have therefore used five or more dates to distinguish between smaller sites of likely short-term occupancy, and medium and larger sites with a higher degree of settlement and/or agricultural activity. Fifteen or more dates is used to differentiate between medium and large sites. These divisions are naturally somewhat arbitrary, as the number of documented features is usually dependent on the extent of the investigated area, which, in turn, is quite often conditioned by zoning plans rather than research interests. On the other hand, the categorisation helps to differentiate well-investigated and well-dated sites from others, which is of particular interest when discussing site disruption and continuity.

Figure 6.12: Number of C14 dates (bottom line) per average number of documented features (columns) at archaeological sites. Only Iron Age dates have been included in this overview.

6.4.4 STATISTICAL APPROACH

Common standards for how the data has been systemised and interpreted are required when large datasets are compiled and analysed. As discussed in Chapter 6.4.1, there are considerable source-critical challenges with all kinds of archaeological datasets that challenge direct comparisons between different sites, in particular when it comes to degradable materials heavily conditioned by varying preservation conditions (i.e., the paleo-botanical and faunal records). Of importance is also the level of investigation and sampling bias. In addition, different researchers and laboratories tend to assess and systemize the faunal and paleo-botanical data somewhat differently, making the data less comparable. A mere quantification of identified fragments is nonetheless a common approach, and therefore the least common denominator for most datasets. Poor preservation conditions are a frequent issue for the sites

included in this study, and available scientific analysis have rarely allowed for any other level of identification than total number of fragments per species, which in most cases are rather low. By certain means, the data can be understood as a random selection obtained through similar investigations of sites with comparable preservation conditions.

INSTITUTION	OSTEOLOGICAL DATA	MACRO-BOTANICAL DATA	POLLEN DATA	M. TOPSOIL STRIPPING
MUSEUM OF CULTURAL HISTORY	50	73	40	87%
COUNTY ADMINISTRATION				
OTHER⁴²	10	7		94%
SUM	60	80	40	88%

Table 6.8: Number of database contexts with faunal or archaeo-botanical data in relation to executive institutions. No faunal or archaeo-botanical data has been provided by county excavations.

Table 6.8 demonstrates that most contexts with faunal or archaeo-botanical data have been excavated and sampled by the Museum of Cultural History during mechanical topsoil stripping in agricultural lands, meaning that sampling is likely to have been conducted by similar procedures and under similar circumstances. It also means that the samples have been analysed at a restricted number of laboratories, according to the prevailing framework agreements.

Archaeo-botanical and osteological data are plotted in the database according to the total number of identified fragments in each context, meaning that each identified fragment or seed is counted as one. However, a mere quantified approach would nonetheless be problematic, especially when it comes to faunal remains, as the occurrence of different types of species and bone fragments are heavily conditioned by differences in decomposition rates and human practices such as butchering and waste-management. Decomposition and the human factor are also considerable concerns for macro-botanical remains, in particular those utilised for human or livestock consumption (cf. Chapter 6.2.1). In the present database, three well-investigated sites alone (Åker I, Valum, and Hoffsvangen II) include two thirds of the total number of faunal remains, meaning that it would render all other sites almost irrelevant in a mere quantified data compilation. In other words, quantified comparisons alone would favour a small number of well-preserved, well-documented, and well-sampled sites, thus creating a result not necessarily representative for past conditions. Consequently, direct quantified comparisons between sites would not be of any substantial benefit for the study, unless some precautions are made.

⁴² Research projects conducted by Pilø (2005) and Skjølsvold (1983).

In order to account for some of the most significant biases in the faunal and archaeo-botanical records, a percentage rate is calculated for every species per context. Thus, well-preserved sites with a high number of identified fragments will get the same weight in the overall analysis as other sites with fewer finds. What is important is not the total amount of fragments per species, but the ratio between the species at the individual sites and in the regions at whole.

When combined with DDA (cf. Chapter 6.4.3), it becomes possible to obtain a temporal resolution that can be used for inter-site and inter-regional comparisons of species rates along temporal scales (Figure 6.13). This approach will be used to analyse developments in grain cultivation, livestock composition, and wildlife exploitation in the two research areas. An average rate for each species per period is calculated by adding the individual percentages and dividing them by the number of records. By doing so, some of the issues with site and data representativeness can be mitigated, and allow for changes in subsistence strategies to be analysed in long-term perspectives. Identifying significant changes in species composition and utilisation during the Iron Age is important in order to determine whether distinct species or types of resources have been more emphasised in subsistence strategies over time, in particular after the cooling event. The exact extent to which they have been utilised cannot be determined from the available datasets, and focus must be put on changes in species ratios in the archaeological record over time. In addition, the method will be utilised to study the ratio between pastoral and arable farming in the two regions by employing the criteria for anthropogenic indicators outlined in Chapter 6.2.

The approach nonetheless includes a few drawbacks. First of all, the fewer the finds, the higher the percentage value become for the individual fragments will be, meaning that a single find will receive a 100% count for its respective context. As is the case with mere quantifications, the percentages do not present an accurate picture of past conditions and the results must be closely evaluated against the properties of the basic proxies. Percentage values will nonetheless provide a better overall site representation for analysis than quantifications, as all data are initially treated statistically with respect to the context from which it is derived. The former would be heavily conditioned by investigation biases, whereas the latter makes possible the utilisation of the complete settlement and agricultural records from the two regions, thus improving the spatial and temporal resolution of the dataset. The approach provides a framework in which shifting emphases on certain species can be statistically detected, although not in a direct one-to-one manner.

	PRIA	ERIA	LRIA	EMP	LMP	EMvP	LMvP	EVA	LVA	n=
Site1	20%	35%			50%	60%	45%	55%		6
Site2		30%	10%	30%						3
Site3				50%	58%				80%	3
Site4	10%	20%	30%							3
Site5					10%					1
Site6		45%	25%	5%				35%	10%	5
Site7				100%	40%					2
Site8				25%	37%		19%		25%	4
n=	2	4	3	5	5	1	2	2	3	27
Species 1	15%	33%	22%	42%	39%	60%	32%	45%	38%	100%
Site1	80%	65%			50%	40%	55%	45%		6
Site2		70%	90%	70%						3
Site3				50%	42%				20%	3
Site4	90%	80%	70%							3
Site5					90%					1
Site6		55%	75%	95%				65%	90%	5
Site7				0%	60%					2
Site8				75%	63%		81%		75%	4
n=	2	4	3	5	5	1	2	2	3	27
Species 2	85%	68%	78%	58%	61%	40%	68%	55%	62%	100%

Figure 6.13: An idealised representation of how DDA can be combined with species rates. The individual percentages would be based on calculations for the respective database contexts from each site. The basic date distributions are the same as in Figure 6.11.

Secondly, if a context includes a wide date range covering multiple periods, the results will also show values for the combined periods, thus reducing the overall precision of the results. However, this factor is not exclusive to DDA and applies to any attempt of linking biofacts to radiocarbon evidence and site occupation phases. Nonetheless, the Migration Period calibration plateau (cf. Chapter 6.4.1) represents

an additional source-critical factor for the chronological resolution around the 6th-century transition, as the archaeological evidence may be smeared out across several periods. This has direct consequences for the ability to identify changes in subsistence strategies around the time of the cooling event by causing uncertainty in regards to the representativeness of the results. In order to evaluate whether the DDA results can be considered diagnostic, supplementary analyses are therefore conducted on contexts that can be exclusively dated to before or after the Early to Late Iron Age transition.

6.5 Micro-level analysis

The case studies will be conducted on the landscape formations of Fron in Gudbrandsdalen valley and Hedmarken in the Lake Mjøsa region. These areas are chosen due to the high number of conducted excavations and the agricultural significance attributed to them in their respective regions (cf. Chapter 6.1). Both areas are well-researched, therefore including a considerable number of available archaeological proxies. This analysis will explore the possible effects of climate cooling on crop productions by integrating growth requirements, weather data, archaeological data, and topography in a GIS model, thus elaborating on the results from the statistical analysis. In this way, the method will use vulnerability as an analytical tool by exploring the local environmental preconditions for agriculture, and identifying local thresholds for crop cultivation during different temperature scenarios.

The analysis will follow a three-step approach by studying the potential effect of climate cooling on the:

- Length of the growing season
- Growing degree days
- Local vegetation records

The first two steps utilise the geoscientific datasets listed in Chapter 6.1.2 in GIS modelling, which will be further outlined in Chapter 6.5.1.

Step 3 makes use of pollen diagrams, of which several have been previously published for localities in both Lake Mjøsa region and Gudbrandsdalen valley (Gunnarsdóttir, 1999; Gunnarsdottir & Høeg, 1996; Høeg, 1997, 2011; Pilø, 2005), but none for Fron in particular. In cooperation with palynologist Helge I. Høeg, pollen coring has therefore been initiated at Ulberg in Fron and included in this study. It is particularly targeted at the mid-1st millennium AD and is an important supplement for the archaeological data in the area. For Hedmarken, a couple of pollen diagrams have been published in Pilø (2005), both developed by Høeg. The more informative of the two in regards to the 1st millennium AD has been

reworked by Høeg and is included in this study (with kind permission). In addition, other published pollen diagrams from the two regions are included in the discussions and evaluations. Particular emphasis is put on the anthropogenic indicators and direct evidence for cultivation (cf. Chapter 6.2), including patterns of agrarian expansion, decline, or even outright disruption. The vegetation records are important supplements to the GIS models, as the latter are generalised visualisations that needs to be substantiated by other proxies. In addition, pollen records are first and foremost indicative of the development of local cultivation and do not necessarily reflect overall agrarian trajectories (cf. Chapter 6.2.1). However, coinciding results between GIS modelling and the vegetation records would be mutually reinforcing and indicative of causal chains.

The combined results from step 1-3 will be discussed up against the archaeological records from the two aforementioned areas, in particular site chronologies, settlement patterns, and site evidence of farming activity. In order to supplement the overall synthesis, additional GIS models will be developed for three more areas in other parts of southern Norway and discussed up against published pollen diagrams. In the following text, the input variables and structure of the GIS models will be thoroughly outlined.

6.5.1 GIS MODELLING

To reach maturity, different cereal species have different requirements, including temperature, soil quality, and precipitation (cf. Chapter 6.3). Temperature is usually measured in ‘growing degree days’ (GDD). GDD is the required temperature sum, calculated by multiplying daily average temperatures with the length of the growing season. These numbers can be used in a GIS analysis in order to identify local temperature thresholds for cereal cultivation. The approach has been employed by Stamnes (2016) in his study on the possible effect of the 6th-century cooling on barley cultivation in middle Norway. His study concludes that even a mean temperature reduction of 1°C during the growing season could have been critical in certain areas. The principles behind crop vulnerability modelling, and how it will be employed in a qualitative analysis of the Fron and Hedmarken areas, will be further outlined in this chapter.

As briefly discussed in Chapter 6.3, the exact requirements of prehistoric crops are not known, causing some uncertainty regarding the effect of climate change on Iron Age agricultural productions. In addition, a multitude of local variants existed up to the introduction of modern standardised farming techniques in the 20th century which were adapted to the various local preconditions for crop cultivation (cf. Foss, 1927, p. 31). Modern requirements cannot, therefore, be directly transferred to a prehistoric context. However, the different historical and modern variants are nonetheless believed to have been comparable and shared the same basic characteristics (Strand, 1984, p. 9). The differences between modern and

traditional types mainly concerns yield size, straw length, and straw strength. The exception is modern wheat, which has improved significantly during the 20th century.

	EARLY BARLEY	LATE BARLEY	EARLY OATS	LATE OATS	SPRING WHEAT	WINTER WHEAT	WINTER RYE
MODERN	1250	1330	1300	1380	1460	1480	
TRADITIONAL	1200-1350		1300-1350		1550		1100

Table 6.9: Temperature requirements (GDD) for modern and traditional crops (Foss, 1926, p. 17; Frøseth, 2004, p. 168).

In Table 6.9 I have listed the necessary GDD for traditional and modern cereals, with reference to early 20th-century experimental research in Valdres on traditional crop types (Foss, 1926) and contemporary numbers for organic agriculture in the Oslo fjord area (Frøseth, 2004). The figures for barley and oats are similar, while wheat has become considerably less temperature-demanding.

According to Foss (1926), failing to meet the required temperature sum is by no means directly synonymous with crop failure, but would result in smaller yields and a higher frequency of unripened grains. Unripened grains are unsuited for sowing, and multiple years with low temperatures would thus make it difficult to uphold production. However, unripened grains can still be cut green and used for fodder (Sveinsson & Hermannsson, 2017, p. 9).

The numbers in Table 6.9 serve to illustrate the basic similarities in temperature requirements for modern and traditional cereals. However, GDD is not a fixed value, and the numbers are not adjusted for differences in latitude, precipitation, soil morphology, and solar radiation, all of which affect the required heat budget. In other words, GDD must be calculated for each area in question.

In the following, I have employed the basic approach outlined by Stamnes (2016), but with a few adjustments concerning the length of the growing season. Stamnes defines the growing season from when the temperatures reach 6°C in spring until it goes below 10°C in autumn. However, there is no standardised way of defining the growing season and different criteria have been used in the literature. According to Erling Strand (1984, pp. 22-34), cereals basically start growing as soon as the temperature reaches 0°C in spring. The >0°C threshold is employed by several agriculturalists (Frøseth, 2004; Sveinsson & Hermannsson, 2017; Åssveen & Abrahamsen, 1999). Needless to say, the approach would result in a significantly prolonged growing season compared to Stamnes (2016), but is only based on the temperature requirements for terrestrial growth in itself. When it comes to cereals, a couple of other factors are also of considerable importance. First of all, for the cereals to mature in autumn, a certain

level of temperatures is required for the crops to dry up (Strand, 1984, pp. 20-22). Traditionally, a threshold of 10°C has been considered for autumn, which is also employed by Stamnes (2016). However, tests have shown that lower temperatures might be sufficient — for oats down to 2-5°C (Skjelvåg, pers. comm.). In fact, numerous variables are at play, which makes it difficult to pinpoint an exact temperature requirement.

Furthermore, a >0°C threshold would not take into account the climatic conditions for inland Norway, where snow often covers the fields well into early springtime. In these cases, it does not reflect the actual period for when cultivation is possible. Early sowing also increases the risk of bad weather and frost affecting the crops. In traditional farming, sowing is more likely to be conducted at a later stage in spring, rather than at first possible occasion (Skjelvåg, pers. comm.). It is therefore common to distinguish between the growing season in general, and an active growing season suitable for agriculture (Carter, 1998, p. 162; Strand, 1984, p. 22). The active growing season is conventionally defined as the period during which the temperature and soil moisture conditions are adequate for crop growth, which Timothy R. Carter (1998), for the Nordic countries, defines as when the mean daily air temperatures remain above 5°C. Importantly, this approximates to the time of year with significant growth across a wide range of plant species, including crops. However, being exclusively temperature based, the threshold is somewhat arbitrary, and does not take into account other constraints to the growing season. It is nonetheless a convenient generalised measure that is widely adopted in the Nordic region, including in the climate projections in the NCCS⁴³-report *Climate in Norway 2100* (Hanssen-Bauer et al., 2017, p. 19) which specifically address future crop outputs. The 5°C threshold will also be employed in the present study, which will result in a slightly longer cultivation period than Stamnes (2016).

A GIS-model visualising the length of the growing season in southern Norway is presented in Figure 6.14, and demonstrates considerable differences in plant growth values throughout the area. The outer coastal communities have significantly longer cultivation seasons than the inland mountain valleys of eastern Norway, but considerable differences can also be found within this part of the country. However, temperature is not the only factor in the equation as the required GDD is also conditioned by precipitation, soil morphology, solar irradiance, and latitude (Strand, 1984, pp. 27-29). As visualised in Figure 6.15, there are considerable differences in summer precipitation in southern Norway, but to a certain degree also within eastern Norway. Eastern Norway is considered dry, with an average rainfall between 200-400 mm from June to August. The Gudbrandsdalen valley experiences rainfall as low as <200 mm in the valley bottom.

⁴³ The Norwegian Centre for Climate Services

Figure 6.14: Length of growing season in southern Norway, with reference to the 1961-90 period, defined as the number of days with daily mean temperatures (DMT) $\geq 5^{\circ}\text{C}$. Source: MET, modelled according to the simulations employed in Hanssen-Bauer et al. (2017). Illustration by author.

Figure 6.15: Summer precipitation in southern Norway (June to August), with reference to the 1961-90 period. Source: MET, modelled according to the simulations employed in Hanssen-Bauer et al. (2017). Illustration by author.

When calculating local GDD, latitude and mean annual precipitation are easy to account for. Due to more sun-hours in northern areas during summer-time, the required heat budget decreases with approximately 20 GDD per latitude north of 60°N (Frøseth, 2004; Strand, 1984, p. 27; Åssveen & Abrahamsen, 1999), which means an average decrease of 30 GDD for Fron and 14 GDD for Hedmarken. On the other hand, rainfalls exceeding 250mm from May to August increase the required temperatures with 60-80 GDD per

100mm rainfall for barley, 90-100mm for oats, and 100-110mm for wheat (Frøseth, 2004). In order to enhance the spatial resolution, measured weather data for the standard period of 1961-90 have been downloaded from Fron, Hedmarken, and surrounding areas (Figure 6.16). Further references are made in Chapter 6.1.2. For Hedmarken, the average rainfall from May to August was at the 250mm limit, whereas Fron was down to 220mm (Table 6.10). Precipitation is therefore of little significance for the GDD calculations in these areas.

Figure 6.16: Available weather stations in the vicinity to Fron and Hedmarken. Local weather data used in GDD calculations are depicted in colours. Source: MET. Illustration by author.

The following examples are based on the modern requirements for barley, as barley is widely considered the most common cereal in Iron Age Scandinavia, especially in present-day Norway and Sweden (Chapter 6.3). The differences in temperature requirements for traditional and modern barley are minimal (Table 6.9), and using the modern requirements as a standard value allows for easy comparison with contemporary cultivation, between different regions, and with Stamnes' (2016) results. Table 6.10 lists

the local GDD requirements for Fron and Hedmarken. Fron has more sun-hours than Hedmarken and therefore somewhat lower GDD requirements. The data provided by local weather stations can be used to calculate the length and accumulated temperature sum for the growing season during the reference period of 1961-90.

AREA	BASIC GDD	LATITUDE CORRECTION	MEAN RAINFALL MAY-AUGUST (BELOW 900 MASL)	LOCAL GDD REQUIREMENTS
FRON (61,5°N)	1250-1330	30	220mm	1220-1300
HEDMARKEN (60,7°N)		14	253mm	1238-1318

Table 6.10: Required GDD for modern early and late barley in Fron and Hedmarken, based on averaged meteorological data from local weather stations below 900 masl during 1961-90. Source: MET.

AREA	ACCUMULATED GDD	ACTIVE GROWING SEASON (DAYS)	AVERAGE TEMPERATURE (MAY-AUGUST)
FRON	1706	168	12°C
HEDMARKEN	1675	169	13°C

Table 6.11: Average GDD and length of growing season in Fron and Hedmarken, calculated for an altitude of 200 masl and a mean daily temperature of $\geq 5^{\circ}\text{C}$. Based on averaged local weather data for the period 1961-90. Source: MET.

However, as the temperature decreases with increasing altitude corrections need to be made for different heights. In the troposphere, the temperature drops quite consistently with increasing height at a rate of close to 0.6°C per 100 masl (McIlveen, 1986, pp. 62-65; Strand, 1984, p. 20). Stamnes (2016, with references) uses a lapse rate of 0.64°C . However, wind, humidity, and cloudiness create variations between seasons and geographical locations, and the lapse rate can, in dry areas, be as high as 1°C per 100 masl (McIlveen, 1986, p. 63). Eastern Norway in general and Gudbrandsdalen valley in particular are considered dry, meaning that some local adjustments might be necessary. For that reason, I compared measured weather data from weather stations at different altitudes in Fron and Ringebu, and found that the local lapse rate change during the year, with a lower rate in winter than summer. For the general growing season (April-October), it lies within $0.54\text{-}0.6^{\circ}\text{C}$ per 100 masl, which is quite close to the 0.6°C standard value. In Hedmarken, there is a lack of high-altitude weather stations that could be used for adequate comparison. However, temperature and precipitation do not differ much between the two areas, and I have therefore used a standard lapse rate of 0.6°C per 100 masl for both. The approach is highly generalised, but serves as a way of illustrating temperature conditions at different heights. In Table 6.11, I have made an average calculation for Fron and Hedmarken at an estimated level of 200 masl, which demonstrates that the two areas have comparable climatic conditions during the growing season at corresponding altitudes. However, in Figure 6.17 and Figure 6.18, the calculations are modelled in a GIS terrain model adjusted for every 20 masl. As farming is situated at lower altitudes, Hedmarken mostly experiences a longer growing season than Fron, which demonstrates the potential of modelling agricultural productivity in GIS.

Figure 6.17: GIS-simulations of the length of the growing season in Fron during the 1961-90 period (source: MET). The map is combined with a cultivation class map (source: NIBIO). The dotted black line marks altitudes of 700 masl, which approximately corresponds the maximum extension of the cultivated landscape in this area. Illustration by author.

Figure 6.18: GIS-simulations of the length of the growing season in Hedmarken during the 1961-90 period (source: MET). The map is combined with a cultivation class map (source: NIBIO). The dotted black line marks altitudes of 500 masl, which approximately corresponds the maximum extension of the cultivated landscape in this area. Illustration by author.

The model can be reproduced for any given average temperature decrease or increase, with reference to the 1961-90 average. As the suggested temperature decrease for the period AD 536-550 is not constant, but includes large annual variabilities (Chapter 2.3.2), maps will be produced that illustrate the potential outcome in both areas at temperature reductions of 1, 2, and 3 degrees (Chapter 9). By using local GDD requirements as baseline values, the model can be further developed to visualise the possible effect of temperature change on local agriculture.

Soil morphology and solar radiance are added to the interpretations by making use of cultivation class datasets for early barley from NIBIO, and by supplementary GIS-modelling. By using the ArcGIS HillShade function, solar radiation levels are visualised by simulating the total amount of sun during an extended growing season from April to September, calculated for every fifth day at mid-day (12:00 pm), with values stretching from 0-100%.⁴⁴ Thus, the model does not reflect the total amount of sun for an area but a potential maximum of sun exposure during the most favourable time of the day throughout the summer season. As such, it visualises differences in sun exposure in the landscape and serves to adjust the interpretations made from the GDD model.

LABEL	VALUE	INTERPRETATION
LOW RISK	≥20% margins	Likely to produce good yields
SMALL MARGINS	<20% margins	Vulnerable to weather anomalies. Reduced yields
THRESHOLD VALUES	Local GDD requirements	Susceptible to crop failure. Small yields
HIGH RISK	Temperatures below the required GDD	Unsuitable for crop cultivation

Table 6.12: Main categories used in the GDD models.

The GDD models consist of four categories: ‘high risk’, ‘threshold values’, ‘small margins’, and ‘low risk’ (Table 6.12). The ‘threshold values’ category is a projection of the local GDD calculations in the terrain model, thus visualising the altitudes where the minimum temperature requirements for barley cultivation are met. Within this zone, weather and farming practices, such as sowing time, become of crucial importance, as there are almost no margins to accommodate for unforeseen events, poor planning, or bad weather. Farming within this zone would be susceptible to crop failure, and, as the involved risk would be too high, extensive crop cultivation is not very likely under normal circumstances. ‘High risk’ designates areas with temperatures below the threshold values, meaning that barley is not likely to mature at these altitudes; this category contains, in other words, areas that are unsuitable for crop

⁴⁴ The execution in HillShade has been conducted by Ermias Beyene Tesfamariam, senior engineer for digital documentation at the Museum of Cultural History, and projected in the GDD models by the author.

cultivation. 'Low risk' designates areas with temperature sums 20% or higher than the threshold values, meaning that it has considerable margins to rely on. Barley is likely to mature and produce good yields under most circumstances. In between, 'small margins' designates areas with temperatures up to 20% higher than the threshold values, thus including important margins that can compensate for temperature and weather anomalies, delayed sowing etc., but nonetheless include a certain risk of reduced outputs and even incidents of crop failure due to delayed ripening.

Figure 6.19 and Figure 6.20 display GIS simulations of the threshold values for barley cultivation in Fron and Hedmarken, with reference to the 1961-90 average. The maps demonstrate that current agriculture is situated well within the necessary temperature requirements. In Fron, most cultivable lands lie within 700 masl, while in Hedmarken the maximum extension is at approximately 500 masl. In both areas, the threshold values are situated above what can be described as the main agricultural area. Furthermore, all agricultural lands in Hedmarken are situated within a low-risk zone.

In Fron (Figure 6.19), considerable areas are associated with small temperature margins (<20% to the threshold values). Most fields within this zone are also associated with low or no potential for barley cultivation in the NIBIO classification system due to a combination of steep terrains, late ripening, and risk of drought. Current farming in this zone is consequently made up of grasses. In both areas, fields with medium and high potential for early barley cultivation are mainly situated within a low risk zone with temperature margins $\geq 20\%$ to the threshold values. Furthermore, a considerable number of fields are also situated in the high-risk zone in the lower mountain area, especially at Kvarvet in the south-eastern part. These fields are not deemed suitable for barley cultivation in the NIBIO classification system. The area was characterised by scattered summer pastures and bogs in pre-modern times, and, due to a nationwide effort to cultivate marginal areas, were only cultivated through the use of heavy machinery in the early 20th century (Almås, 2002, pp. 76-78; Gjerdåker, 2002, pp. 266-270).⁴⁵ After initial experiments with rye, the area is now only used for grasses (Øvreliid, 1991, pp. 184-185). Thus, the examples demonstrate the potential of the model as an analytical tool as it reflects current farming conditions within reasonable margins.

⁴⁵ In Norwegian often defined as 'bureisingstiltak'; an effort to establish new farms.

Figure 6.19: GIS-simulation of the required GDD for barley cultivation in Fron, with reference to the 1961-90 average (source: MET), combined with a cultivation class map (source: NIBIO) and simulations of solar radiation (shadowy areas receive little sunlight during mid-day). The dotted black lines mark 700 masl. Illustration by author.

Figure 6.20: GIS-simulation of the required GDD for barley cultivation in Hedmarken, with reference to the 1961-90 average (source: MET), combined with a cultivation class map (source: NIBIO) and simulations of solar radiation (shadowy areas receive little sunlight during mid-day). The dotted black lines mark 500 masl. Illustration by author.

It must nonetheless be stressed that the GDD models are highly generalised and do not take into account highly local differences, or other instrumental factors, such as pre-modern farming techniques, prehistoric cereal growth requirements, or extreme weather phenomena. For example, short incidents of summer frost can be devastating for the crops even if the temperatures reach the required accumulated sum. Consequently, no area can be defined as a 'no-risk zone' as there will always be a certain risk of lowered outputs, or outright crop failure, if short-term and unexpected conditions emerge. Furthermore, restraints caused by topographical factors are difficult to model properly, in particular local ones. It is also important to remember that solar radiation is visualised in the models but do not influence the projected GDD. In Fron, more fields in the south-facing slopes are situated at higher altitudes close to the threshold values, while most farms in the shadowed north-facing slopes are situated at lower altitudes in the low risk zone, which is likely related to differences in sun accumulation. In other words, small margins in north-facing slopes would probably be more critical for agriculture than in the south-facing slopes. Finally, as the exact prehistoric requirements are not known, the models are not to be understood as reproductions of the effect of climate change on Iron Age agriculture in itself, but merely serve to illustrate different thresholds for cereal cultivation between the research areas. Changes in precipitation would also alter the local threshold values, thus producing a different result. However, as no coherent record exist for prehistoric precipitation in the areas in question, I have had to use 1961-90 data as standard values in the GDD models. Whether the 6th-century cooling resulted in moister or drier weather in Scandinavia is a matter of some discussion (see Chapter 2.3.3).

Finally, the results from Fron and Hedmarken are not necessarily applicable to larger areas, or even other parts of eastern Norway. This is well-illustrated by the lower mountain valley of Haverdalen (1050 masl) in northern Gudbrandsdalen, where the cultivation of barley, rye, and oats has been identified during the 1st millennium AD (Høeg, 2011; Stene, 2015), an area which is well above the thresholds for both Fron and Hedmarken. Thus, each area in question needs to be modelled individually in accordance with the constraints of local climates and topography.

By and large, the models contribute to the overall assessments of agricultural vulnerability in selected areas during a period of prolonged cooling. The results from the GDD analysis must be properly contextualised and cannot be understood as an exact reproduction of past or present conditions. Thorough analyses of the exact consequences for each area in question would require detailed multiproxy modelling, which would fall outside the scope and range of this thesis.

6.6 Chapter conclusion

In this chapter, I have outlined a coherent human-environmental framework for assessing the impact of the 6th-century cooling on Iron Age societies, one which incorporates a wide range of archaeological and geoscientific proxies and analyses them at both local and regional scales. By utilising long-term perspectives, possible risk drivers and adaptational strategies may be identified. The approach is separated into one statistical and one in-depth study, in which the former aims at assessing the character of Iron Age subsistence strategies and settlement developments while the latter utilises vulnerability as an analytical tool to examine the potential effect of the cooling event on local agriculture. By doing so, the potential of using big data can be combined with a contextual approach, thereby emphasising the local preconditions and thresholds for agriculture. Although direct causal chains remain difficult to establish, this method offers the possibility of moving beyond mere concurrencies in geoscientific and archaeological datasets, and instead substantiates whether or not a cooling event would have had a severe impact on Iron Age farming societies. Thus, the method allows for spatial diversity in the study of disaster impact, as well as the exploration of human responses to climate change in prehistory. Using this approach, the premises for a suggested climate crisis can be disentangled and studied analytically.

PART III

ANALYSIS

7 REGIONAL CHARACTERISTICS

The environmental preconditions for agriculture form a fundamental part of the analytical framework outlined in Chapters 5 and 6. In this chapter, I will explore some of the main landscape and climate characteristics for the Lake Mjøsa region and Gudbrandsdalen valley, and discuss how these characteristics condition agricultural practices in these areas. I will also draw up some major milestones concerning the research history in the two regions, including sites of particular importance. This serves as a backdrop and point of reference for the analyses and discussions in Chapters 8 and 9, as well as highlighting the basic differences and similarities between the two regions.

7.1. Main landscape formations

The Lake Mjøsa region and the Gudbrandsdalen valley are characterised by several landscape formations which traditionally have affected land use and farming strategies. Although farming has undergone radical changes during the latter half of the 20th century towards a more standardised, mechanised, and specialised practice, topography and landscape still dictate different preconditions for agriculture.

Both regions are dominated by moraine sediments which take on a more continuous and extensive character around the northern part of Lake Mjøsa (Figure 7.1). The thick sediment covers around northern Lake Mjøsa constitute a major part of the *rural lake areas*. The moraine sediments in Gudbrandsdalen valley is more restricted by topographical factors, but thick deposits can be found along the valley sides in both the upper and lower valley districts. The relatively flat and extensive countryside around Lake Mjøsa stands in contrast to the hilly and spatially-restricted terrain of Gudbrandsdalen valley. While several large (by Norwegian standards) crop producing estates are found around the lake, the valley districts are characterised by small and medium size farms which utilise a combination of outfield pastures and cultivated infields (Puschmann et al., 2004). In general, the valley countryside can be understood as marginal and dependent on outfield resources, whereas the rural lake areas include clay- and chalk-rich sediments that have a favourable impact on the crop yields. However, proper marine clay sediments are only found in Eidsvoll at the southern edge of Lake Mjøsa (Figure 7.2).

The valley countryside typically receives very little precipitation and is therefore prone to draught. Cereals need approximately 1/3 mm water per day per mean daily degree $\geq 5^{\circ}\text{C}$ during the growing season, which corresponds to 90 mm per month at 14°C (Strand, 1984, p. 31). Combined with local weather data from Fron and Hedmarken (cf. Chapter 6.5.1), these numbers can be used to highlight some basic climatic differences between the two regions. Accordingly, there was an average need of 301 mm rainfall in Fron

and 317 mm in Hedmarken during the 1961-90 period, representing a shortfall of 81 mm (27%) and 64 mm (20%) respectively. Northern Gudbrandsdalen is even lower on summer precipitation than medial areas of Fron. Water shortfall, especially during May to July, affects yield size (Strand, 1984, p. 31), meaning that Hedmarken is more likely to produce good yields than Fron. As will be further outlined below, the topographical, geological, and climatic factors have been instrumental in the development of the agrarian landscape in the two regions.

Figure 7.1: Main sediment covers in eastern Norway. Source: NGU. Illustration by author.

Figure 7.2: Landscape formations in eastern Norway (Puschmann, 2005). Source: NIBIO. Illustration by author.

7.2. Lake Mjøsa region

7.2.1. LANDSCAPE CHARACTERISTICS

The landscape around northern Mjøsa is characterised by wide-reaching fields, rounded hills, and wide and gentle valleys around lakes and rivers. Clay-rich minerals represent an important element in the local quaternary sediments around the northern and southern part of Lake Mjøsa. In the northern part, agriculture is located on thick moraine sediments on slate bedrock mixed with clay minerals and chalk, which is considered highly favourable for agriculture (R. Dahl et al., 2017, p. 18; Hagen, 1984; Pilø, 2005, pp. 67-78). The amount of stones increases with higher altitudes, meaning that the most productive lands are found in the lower parts of the terrain. The countryside of northern Mjøsa was recognised early on for its agricultural importance and considered highly productive (R. Dahl et al., 2017, pp. 9-12, 16; Hagen,

1984). Most geographical regions are characterised and restrained by topographical factors, whereas the rural lake areas are so heavily cultivated that it has become a defining feature of the landscape (Puschmann, 2005, pp. 39-40).

Figure 7.3: The agrarian landscape of eastern Norway (Puschmann et al., 2004), combined with a soil classification dataset. The dataset visualises the distribution of cultivated fields in the area, but not all areas are covered. Neither the northern part of Lake Randsfjorden (west of Lake Mjøsa) nor Øyer in southern Gudbrandsdalen have been mapped, and the areas have therefore been left blank. Source: NIBIO. Illustration by author.

The central region surrounding the lake is forested and hilly with limited agriculture, while the southern part, in Eidsvoll, widens out once more with a rather flat farming landscape. The Eidsvoll area lies at the northern outskirts of the Romerike plains and share many characteristics with northern Mjøsa, such as wide-stretching and heavily cultivated fields. The soil is made up of marine clay sediments and is considered fertile (Puschmann, 2005, pp. 19-20). The *clay soil areas* stretch downwards to the Oslo fjord

and the main cultivated areas in Vestfold and Østfold. Together with the rural lake areas, it is considered one of the country's most important and productive agricultural landscapes and makes up a significant part of the *lowland countryside* (Figure 7.3).

The lowland countryside is a characteristic feature of the agrarian landscape in eastern and middle Norway and dominates the landscape around the northern part of Lake Mjøsa (Puschmann et al., 2004, pp. 47-49). It is the most cultivated landscape formation in present day Norway and includes the country's largest and most extensive agrarian fields. In eastern Norway, the lowland countryside predominantly lies within a growing season of 160 days or more (cf. Figure 7.4).

Figure 7.4: Length of the growing season, modelled as the number of days with a mean temperature $\geq 5^{\circ}\text{C}$, with reference to the 1961-90 average. Source: MET and NIBIO. Illustration by author.

Today, up 70% of the present fields are utilised for crops, while only 26% are used for grasses. The grass production is typically associated with husbandry, and, as the low percentage of grasses suggests, husbandry plays only a secondary role in the lowland countryside today. However, the current strong emphasis on crops is a recent one and is directly related to changing farming strategies in the 1960s (Almås, 2002, pp. 205-218; Puschmann et al., 2004, p. 48; Selstad & Stensrud, 1991, p. 128). Increasing specialisation, chemical fertilizers, and mechanisation replaced self-sufficiency and mixed farming with fewer species, larger estates, and niche production directed towards a market system. Husbandry had traditionally played a larger role in these areas. Cattle were favoured as they played a particularly important role for grain-producing communities, providing large quantities of manure that could be utilised for soil enrichment and improving crop outputs (Gjerdåker, 2002, p. 55; Lunden, 2002, p. 211; Øye, 2002). As the lowland countryside is extensively cultivated, the prevalence of husbandry is still quite high compared to other agricultural regions and pastoral farming is widespread. Cattle still constitute the highest numbers within present-day husbandry and are often found in cultivated pastures. These cultivated pastures are by and large a modern phenomenon, developed as a means to intensify and streamline modern agriculture, in particular milk production (Almås, 2002, pp. 215-217). A considerable number of sheep are also kept in forested outfield pastures (Puschmann et al., 2004, p. 49).

The forested region is of limited agricultural importance, and forestry is usually the main occupation in these areas (Puschmann et al., 2004, pp. 50-52). Several smaller farms are nonetheless present and often based on a combination of forestry and small-scale agriculture. The soil is typically not very productive and the fields limited by topographical factors such as outcrops and hills. Most farms are rather small and scattered in wide, forested, and hilly terrains, although pockets with favourable agricultural conditions are to be found below the marine limit. Such pockets make up a significant proportion of the agricultural production of the forested region (Puschmann et al., 2004, p. 51). Crops make up about 35%, while grasses cover approximately 60%. Sheep are most common, followed by cattle, in an almost 2:1 ratio. Much of the livestock is situated in cultivated pastures as available grasslands are somewhat limited.

Lake Mjøsa is rich in fish, which has traditionally been utilised by the local communities (Selstad & Stensrud, 1991, pp. 22-31). Vendace has been considered to be of particular importance, but a number of other species are also known, among them trout, carp, burbot, and northern pike. Sigurd Grieg (1958, pp. 92-94), in his assessment of medieval dietary habits, described fish as an important substitute in times of bad harvests. Local fish is generally believed to have made up an important part of local diets around the lake in medieval and historical times, but little is known on exploitation of lake resources in prehistory (Aasen, 2007, p. 147). However, it is worth noting that the thick cultural layers at the Iron Age Åker site

outside Hamar include large numbers of freshwater fish (Perdikaris, 1990), which may suggest that fish was of importance for the local communities (the Åker site will be discussed further below).

According to Gerhard Schøning (1980 [1778], p. 44), medieval Hamar was one of the largest and most distinguished trading towns in Norway at the time. Lake Mjøsa in general, and the Hamar area in particular, is often considered in archaeological literature to have had a favourable position in relation to trade and transport, thus constituting an important basis for the emergence of powerful Iron Age dynasties in the region (cf. Hagen, 1992, p. 13; Mjærum & Rødsrud, 2020; Røstad, 2020, p. 20). Hamar is situated at the intersection between the lake in the west and transport routes to the Østerdalen and Glåmdalen valleys in the east, and perhaps even further to Sweden. The lake itself offers communication with Gudbrandsdalen in the north, and is connected by the Vorma and Glomma river-ways all the way down to the Oslo fjord (Gundersen, 2016a, pp. 320-322).

7.2.2. RESEARCH HISTORY

The Lake Mjøsa region and north-eastern Hedmarken are common points of reference in Norwegian Iron Age research. By and large, this is due to a number of rare and wealthy Merovingian Period stray finds from Åker in Hamar, often referred to as the 'Åker assemblage' (Røstad, 2020). The Åker assemblage stands out in the Scandinavian Iron Age and includes finds with clear parallels to the Vendel complex in middle Sweden, the Frankish empire, and Sutton Hoo in Suffolk, England. It is often referred to as an elite settlement and assembly site of regional importance, comparable to other ruler sites and central places across Scandinavia (cf. Andrén, 2020; Iversen, 2019; J. H. Larsen & Mikkelsen, 1992; Røstad, 2020; Skre, 2019). In discussions on the 6th-century crisis, Åker is emphasised in terms of continuity, power accumulation, and material wealth, alongside other possible ruler sites, like Borre in Vestfold and Raknehaugen at Ullensaker (Myhre, 2002, pp. 173-213; Skre, 2019; Solberg, 2003, p. 198).

Åker was also one of the first inland sites of eastern Norway for the implementation of machine-assisted topsoil stripping in archaeological fieldwork. An attempt was made in 1988-89 during road construction work (Åker I), but a major breakthrough was first achieved with Pilø's (2005) research excavations in 1991-94 (Åker II), which also involved nearby Valum and Vidarshov I. Pilø (2005, pp. 108-113) describes Valum as a wealthy farm including two longhouses of considerable size, measuring approximately 50 metres in length. His excavations uncovered the first identified longhouses through topsoil stripping in the inlands, but he also initiated a number of pollen diagrams from the area. Minor investigations were also done in 1998 and 2015 (Åker III and Åker IV), while a third phase of extensive excavation was conducted in 2016 (Åker V and VI). The report from Åker VI was not completed at the time of this writing, and the

results are therefore not incorporated into this thesis, with the exception of C14-dates.⁴⁶ Åker is considered one continuous major site, but the different fields have been excavated at different times, and with different methods, over the three last decades. For comparison, and practical reasons, it is therefore split up in separate records in the database. The Åker excavations have documented continuous occupation from the Roman Iron Age and onwards, including several buildings, specialised craft, and massive cultural layers with a huge amount of preserved animal bones (Hernæs, 1989a; Perdikaris, 1990; Pilø, 2005). During the 2016 excavations, two gold-foil figures were found, of which one might be related to the remains of a great hall (McGraw, 2017). The results from 2016 strengthen the interpretations made from previous finds and excavations and demonstrate the significance of Åker in Iron Age Scandinavia.

Figure 7.5: Number of annual excavations in the Lake Mjøsa region, based on excavated Iron Age settlement and agricultural sites in the thesis database. 'Other' is made up of research investigations conducted by Ingunn Holm (1989-93) and Lars Pilø (1991-1994).

Another remarkable site was excavated in 1993, 2004, and 2005 at Hov in the Lake Mjøsa part of Lillehammer municipality, where gold-foil figures, a sword, cooking pits, and a large amount of fire steels, among other things, were discovered in and around what was likely a Merovingian Period building (Haraldsen, 1995). The complex is usually interpreted as a cultic site and a probable heathen hof, but no final report or scientific publication exists for the project. I have therefore left it out of the analyses and discussions in this thesis.

⁴⁶ The radiocarbon dates from Åker VI are included in Figure 8.4 and Figure 8.6 in Chapter 8.1

Following the first Åker projects, there has been a steady increase in excavations of settlement and agricultural sites in the Lake Mjøsa region (Figure 7.5). Hedmarken stands out in this context, accounting for 46% of the Lake Mjøsa region sites. Out of 33 identified buildings in the region, 18 are found in Hedmarken. In the south, ten buildings divided between four sites have been found in Eidsvoll alone, while one is found at Bundli IV in Hurdal. Only four have been found in Toten west of the lake, all at the site of Trogstad. Thus, Hedmarken represents a particularly well-researched part of the farming landscape around Lake Mjøsa.

Of particular importance for the southern part of the region is the 1993-96 Gardermoen project at Ullensaker, Nannestad, and Eidsvoll (Helliksen, 1997), and the 2015 Highway 3/25 project in Løten and Elverum in the east (Rødstrud & Mjærum, 2020). The settlement and agricultural sites from Eidsvoll and Løten are incorporated in the thesis database. The Gardermoen project resulted in several settlement sites, including a total of four longhouses at Dønnum I and Dønnum II in addition to several pollen diagrams for the area (Høeg, 1997). Alongside agricultural and settlement sites, and an Iron Age burial site at Skillingstad, the Highway 3/25 project has contributed important data on prehistoric and medieval trapping in the vicinity of the Lake Mjøsa region.

Close to Skillingstad is the burial site of By and Englaug, which was excavated in 1879-81. Irmelin Martens (1965) made a comprehensive study of the artefacts and concluded that none of the burials could be labelled as 'well-furnished', but that the site nonetheless represented a strong element of continuity throughout the Iron Age. The evidence for Migration Period occupation is weak, with the Merovingian Period representing an increase in the number of burials. This, she noted, was in contrast to the inlands as a whole (I. Martens, 1965, p. 67). At Skillingstad, the main phase seems to have been between 400 BC to 600 AD, with most dates around AD 500 (J. J. E. Kile-Vesik, Mjærum, Rødstrud, Linderholm, & Mikkelsen, 2020, p. 95). However, two more cairns are dated to the Merovingian Period. Approximately 60 cairns are located outside the zoning plan and are therefore not excavated. Because of this, there is some uncertainty regarding when the burial site was abandoned. The sites at By-Englaug and Skillingstad share many similarities: both include an unusual large number of burials, mostly consisting of low cairns with modest finds, and both are also associated with continuous long-term use (J. J. E. Kile-Vesik et al., 2020, pp. 96-97). In the Merovingian Period, the graves are found at the outskirts of the main burial grounds (J. J. E. Kile-Vesik et al., 2020, p. 94; I. Martens, 1965, p. 102). According to Martens, the burial site at By-Englaug changes character around the onset of the Merovingian Period, at which point the graves become more scattered throughout the terrain.

A similar study for the western side of Lake Mjøsa has been conducted by Herteig (1955), who analysed the grave finds from the Toten municipalities. Toten includes several well-furnished Roman Iron Age graves, in particular at Gile and Stabu, where Roman bronze imports have been found in two cremation graves (Lund Hansen, 1987, p. 433). The grave at Gile stands out as it includes a full set of weaponry consisting of a sword, two spears, a shield buckle, and parts of a spur. According to Asbjørn Herteig (1955), important changes happened during the 5th century AD, and this time period is characterised by fewer finds and less-furnished burials. The Merovingian Period follows in line with this development, but nonetheless represents a slight increase in the number of finds compared to the preceding period. Stabu stands out in the 7th century, including a helmet fragment akin to similar finds from the Vendel complex in Middle Sweden (Herteig, 1955, p. 125). Only five helmet fragments have been found in Norway, of which three are from around Lake Mjøsa (Røstad, 2020, p. 22). A fourth fragment is found at Gran in Hadeland further west, which can probably be viewed in connection with the finds from around Lake Mjøsa. There is a considerable increase in the number of finds in Toten during the Viking Period, including at the site of Gile.

Several archaeologists have pointed out the continental and Swedish influences in the high status burials from the Merovingian Period from around Lake Mjøsa (Grieg, 1918; Gudesen, 1980, p. 142; Røstad, 2020; Solberg, 2003, pp. 198-201). In particular Frankish, Lombardic, Gotlandic, and Vendel characteristics have been emphasised for the early part of the Merovingian Period, while Danish influences become more evident later on. Compared to valley countryside of eastern Norway, Gudesen (1980, p. 142) has argued that the lowland countryside has a more distinct pattern of social stratification. In her doctoral thesis, Røstad (2016) identifies both regional and overarching multi-ethnic traits in the brooches and dress code of the Merovingian Period elite, which underpins the high level of mutual influence, mobility, and connection between the upper echelons in Germanic societies at the time. Anders Hagen (1992, p. 29) has emphasised the high number of weapon finds at the farms surrounding Åker, which he believed reflected a distinct warrior ideology within the Åker complex.

In contrast to the well-furnished graves stands the agrarian site of Øverbymarka in Gjøvik, situated north of Toten on the western side of Lake Mjøsa. The site has been investigated by Ingunn Holm (1995) during her dissertation research and consists of a large number of clearance cairns. As a part of her study, she initiated pollen bog-coring at the site. Øverbymarka can be described as marginal and restricted by topography, with forested and rocky terrains and large bogs. It was occupied from 800 BC to AD 1700, with pastoral farming being the main activity. There is also some pollen evidence for crops and arable farming beginning in the Middle Ages. Holm's (1995) research has been important for the development of

clearance cairn typology and chronology, but has also contributed with important results on the agricultural development in marginal areas around Lake Mjøsa.

In other words, the Lake Mjøsa region is well researched, both in terms of qualitative site studies and the high number of excavations which provide quantitative datasets for overall analysis. Large-scale and small-scale excavations have been conducted over a period of three decades, ranging from marginal agriculture to the elite milieu at Åker. As such, the archaeological record reflects both everyday farming activities and the overarching geo-political processes of the time.

7.3. Gudbrandsdalen valley

7.3.1. LANDSCAPE CHARACTERISTICS

The Gudbrandsdalen valley is characterised by a diversified landscape that includes pockets of cultivated land amidst large forested areas, steep valley sides, and mountainous terrain (Puschmann, 2005, pp. 47-52). A characteristic feature of this area is the Lågen River, which runs along the valley bottom from Lesja in the north to Lake Mjøsa in the south, with a total length of around 200 km and a waterfall of 480 meters. While the lowland countryside characterises the Lake Mjøsa region, the *valley countryside* dominates the Gudbrandsdalen valley (Figure 7.3). The main settlement landscape can be divided into upper and lower valley areas (Figure 7.2), each offering somewhat different preconditions for agriculture. In particular, the upper valley is connected to the high and low mountain areas and experiences a somewhat harsher and colder climate than the lower countryside, thus increasing the risk for frost during the growing season. The lower valley is connected to Lake Mjøsa to the south and large areas of upland forests to the west and east (Figure 7.2). Southern Gudbrandsdalen is more cultivated than the northern area, and the farms are located on rocky but well-drained moraine deposits well above the post ice-age marine limit. The best agricultural land is situated in Fron, in the central area of the valley (Hiorthøy, 1990 [1785], p. 118; Jacobsen & Larsen, 2005, pp. 44-45; Kleiven, 1979 [1930], pp. 10-11; Schøning, 1980 [1778], p. 106; Sommerfeldt, 1972). The valley is wider in Fron than elsewhere, allowing for somewhat larger farms and fields, and therefore includes a significant proportion of the cultivated lands in the region (Figure 7.3).

The valley countryside constitutes the second most important agricultural landscape within the two research areas, although the number and extent of cultivated fields are heavily restricted by topographical factors (Puschmann et al., 2004, pp. 53-55). Traditionally, barley, winter rye, hemp, and linen were cultivated, as well as, to a lesser extent, oats and summer rye (Sommerfeldt, 1972, p. 10). The

cultivated area stretches from the river valley bottom to the low mountain area, but this is mainly due to 20th century agricultural expansions. The valley bottom is often shaded due to high and narrow valley sides, resulting in somewhat reduced temperatures, early frost, and delayed springs (Gundersen, 2016b, p. 108). Although it is prone to flooding and landslides, the area is nonetheless situated on fertile glaciofluvial sediments (Cannell, 2016). The lower mountains are quite warm during summertime, but the sediment cover is often less continuous and the growing season is significantly shortened by late springs and early autumns (Figure 7.4). Both the lower mountains and valley bottom have therefore traditionally been utilised for grazing and pastoral farming, but in modern times these areas have been extensively cultivated for grass production (Puschmann et al., 2004, p. 53).

Large estates are almost absent in the region, whereas several small and middle size farms are present (Puschmann et al., 2004). However, in medieval and historical times, the Gudbrandsdalen valley included a number of large farms and estates, some of which were associated with the nobility (Hovdhaugen, 1974). Fron in particular was characterised by a number of large farms which were divided into smaller units later on. In addition, a remarkably high number of medieval ecclesiastical buildings has been documented in the area, thus signifying its political and economic importance (Skre, 1988). The traditional farm area is situated on natural terraces along the valley sides. The central areas are more sheltered from the cold mountain winds and frost in the shadowed valley bottoms and are therefore considered the core area for cultivation. Thick moraine sediments consisting of chalk-rich dark sparagmite are often found in the lower and middle parts of the slopes, while less fertile and thinner sediments of light sparagmite are found at higher altitudes (Sommerfeldt, 1972, p. 17). South-facing slopes are especially favourable as they have optimal conditions for solar radiation. The largest farms are to be found in these areas, while smaller and poorer farms traditionally have been situated at higher altitudes and on north-facing slopes (Sommerfeldt, 1972, p. 17; Valen-Sendstad, 1956, pp. 58-62, 65-66). The growing season usually lasts for 110-160 days, depending on altitude, latitude, and the direction and inclination of the valley sides (Figure 7.4). Traditionally, the growing season lasted from April/May to October/November (Sommerfeldt, 1972, p. 10).

Although farming constitutes an important characteristic of the Gudbrandsdalen valley, it is nonetheless restricted by topography and climate. Land available for cultivation is limited. Gudbrandsdalen, and in particular, Fron, is plagued by the frequent occurrence of landslides along the steep valley sides. Often caused by snowmelting in springtime, the tributary rivers swell and gain great speed, leading to erosion and mass-movement. The thick moraine deposits along the valley sides are only rarely kept in place by visible bedrock, meaning that there is little to slow down the landslides until they reach the valley bottom. Agricultural expansion and deforestation increase the risk, as vegetation and roots are usually the only

natural anchors holding the sediments in place. Great floods and landslides have therefore often posed great danger for farming and settlement in Gudbrandsdalen valley (Gundersen, 2016b; Sommerfeldt, 1972).

Figure 7.6: 18th-century irrigation systems in Gudbrandsdalen valley, as depicted in Hiorthøy (1990 [1785]). Reproduced by The Norwegian Museum of Cultural History (NF.10412-003).

Furthermore, the valley experiences low amounts of summer precipitation and is considered dry, especially in the northern regions, which often makes irrigation necessary (Aurtande, 1974; Hiorthøy, 1990 [1785], pp. 51, 118; Sommerfeldt, 1972, pp. 10, 14). Extensive irrigation systems consisting of wooden canals are known from the 18th century, which directed mountain streams towards the fields (Figure 7.6). These large-scale systems were characteristic of the northern part of Gudbrandsdalen valley during the 18th century and allowed for higher agricultural outputs, high enough to allow exportation of grains during favourable years, but similar irrigation systems are not known from prehistoric contexts. According to Hugo Frederik Hiorthøy (1990 [1785], p. 118), similar irrigation systems were not used in Fron. The combination of high mountain sides, south-facing slopes, and low precipitation could therefore lead to draught in hot summers. In prehistoric times, crop cultivation was probably more spatially restricted and yielded significantly lower outputs. Helga Gunnarsdóttir (1999, p. 140) points out that the prehistoric pollen analytical evidence for crops in northern Gudbrandsdalen is quite weak and incoherent, a fact which she attributes to the dry climate.

Forestry is also important, in both the past and the present, and for some it became a primary source of income (Mølmen, 1974; Puschmann et al., 2004). However, numerous hunting and trapping sites also testify to the importance of extensive wildlife exploitation in prehistoric and historical times (Barth, 1996; Gundersen, 2016c; Jacobsen & Larsen, 1992; Pilø et al., 2018). Most sites associated with these activities are found in the mountainous areas, but Iron Age trapping systems have also been documented in the valley bottom. Outfield resources, such as wildlife, iron, and soapstone, are often considered fundamental for prehistoric settlement and power relations in the valley (Gundersen, 2016a; J. H. Larsen, 2007, p. 198; 2016b).

Today, grass production covers 77% of the cultivated land, while crops cover approximately 20%. However, crops are more common in the lower area of the Gudbrandsdalen valley, where grasses and cereals make up approximately 50% each (Puschmann, 2005, p. 48). Due to extensive outfields, husbandry constitutes the backbone of modern-day farming strategies. Cattle are important, but are outnumbered almost 1:3 by sheep. Cattle are mostly held within cultivated pastures close to the farms, but were traditionally kept at summer mountain farms. Sheep graze in the low mountains and hillsides (Puschmann et al., 2004, p. 55). The prevalence of sheep can be understood in light of the vast outfields and hilly terrain, a landscape which normally favours small livestock (cf. Lunden, 2002, p. 219; Myhre, 2002, p. 146).

The mountain region offers vast areas traditionally utilised for summer pastures (Puschmann et al., 2004, pp. 56-58). Summer farms are still a characteristic feature in the lower mountains, but their use reached a peak in the first half of the 19th century before beginning a gradual decline in the subsequent period (Gjerdåker, 2002, p. 62). They were abandoned in large numbers during the latter half of the 20th century in favour of new agricultural principles and cultivated pastures closer to the farms (Almås, 2002, pp. 215-217). However, the use of mountain summer farms is still widespread in Gudbrandsdalen (Gjerdåker, 2002, p. 62; Puschmann et al., 2004).

Regular farms are also abundantly present in the forested lower mountain areas (Puschmann, 2005, p. 48), but have, by and large, been cultivated in modern times in areas previously occupied by bogs and summer pastures. As a measure against high unemployment rates in the early 20th century, several farms were established in marginal areas to improve the national self-sufficiency rates (Almås, 2002, pp. 76-78; Gjerdåker, 2002, pp. 266-270; Mølmen, 1974, p. 158; Øvrelid, 1991, pp. 184-185). After unsuccessful initial attempts with rye, these areas are nowadays predominantly used for grass production and animal husbandry, namely sheep. The number and extent of cultivated fields are rather limited, but the mountain

region has traditionally constituted a very important part of the area's farming strategy (cf. Timberlid, 2015). However, pollen analytical investigations in northern Gudbrandsdalen, in the lower mountain valleys, have provided evidence for high altitude (~800-1000 masl) crop cultivation during the Iron Age (Gunnarsdóttir, 1999, p. 140; Høeg, 2011), thus suggesting that permanent farmsteads might have existed in these areas also in prehistoric times (Stene, 2015).

Gudbrandsdalen is rich in rivers and lakes, and fishing in the Lågen River is mentioned in 19th-century written sources (Hiorthøy, 1990 [1785], pp. 29-32; Schøning, 1980 [1778], pp. 128, 138). Fishing instalments from historical times are known in the southern part of the Lågen River and northern part of the Lake Mjøsa (Aasen, 2007, p. 152). Fishing was considered good in the southernmost areas, particularly in the riverlake Losna in Øyer, but a wide range of species were also found as far north as Harpefoss in Fron. Dried fish was paid as land rent, and vendace was salted and exported out of the valley (Hiorthøy, 1990 [1785]; Kjelland, 2016). The commercial value was nevertheless low, and fishing was mostly directed towards local consumption. The practice of transporting and releasing fish into mountain waters is well known from modern and historical times, but might go all the way back to the Neolithic (Bjørkli, Friis, Mjærum, & Wammer, 2016). While travelling through Gausdal in southern Gudbrandsdalen valley, Schøning (1980 [1778], p. 182) describes a now lost runic stone at the farm Li. The inscription seems to be related to fishing rights, and releasing of fish in Lake Rausjøen, and probably belong to the late 11th century (Aasen, 2007, p. 154, with references). Nonetheless, both the Lågen River and the mountain lakes represent significant sources of subsistence for the Gudbrandsdalen region in both historical and prehistoric times. The river itself must also be understood as an important route of communication and transport in both prehistoric and historical times, as it offers easy access to Lake Mjøsa further south (Gundersen, 2016a, pp. 320-322).

7.3.2. RESEARCH HISTORY

Gudbrandsdalen valley is rich in cultural heritage and archaeological sites, but few excavations have been conducted in farmed areas prior to 2008 (Figure 7.7). Almost no graves have been scientifically investigated, with the exception of Arne Skjølsvold's (1980, 1983) excavations of low mountain graves in Vuludalen and Spranget in 1970, 1979 and 1982. The Vuludalen complex in Fron is highly interesting, as it involves extensive reindeer trapping systems, cooking pits, and a cultural layer, going all the way back to the Pre-Roman Iron Age. It's debated whether it belonged to a semi-sedentary mountainous population, of possible proto-Sami origin, or hunting parties from the local farming communities (Bergstøl, 2008, pp. 139-141, 189-190; Gjerde, 2016, pp. 151-152, 164-165, 208-211; J. H. Larsen, 2016a, pp. 65-66). It is therefore not a farming settlement in a traditional understanding of the term and differs from the other

sites in the project database. It has still been included in the study, however, as it includes archaeological features which are similar to those in the farming area.

Figure 7.7: Number of annual excavations of Iron Age settlement and agricultural sites in Gudbrandsdalen valley, based on records in the thesis database. 'Other' is made up of Skjølsvold's research excavations in Vuludalen in 1979 and 1982, and excavations underneath Ringebu stave church by the Directorate of Cultural Heritage in 1980-81. Harald Jacobsen and Jan Henning Larsen's (2005) excavations at Hundorp in 2002 has been left out, as the project initiated no scientific analysis that could be incorporated in the thesis database.

Up until recent years, the main bulk of archaeological investigations in the valley was indeed conducted in the outfields. Important is the 1986-89 Dokkfløy project in Gausdal in southern Gudbrandsdalen, where a significant number of iron extraction sites and pitfall systems for elk trapping were investigated (Jacobsen & Larsen, 1992; J. H. Larsen, 1991). The Dokkfløy project was also the first to implement machine-assisted topsoil stripping in Gudbrandsdalen valley. A small number of iron extraction sites have also been excavated at Hafjell in Øyer and Furusjøen in Fron. Airborne laser detection (Lidar) has revealed a considerable number of iron extraction sites in the valley, in particular in Gausdal and around Skåbu in northern Fron. Iron production is usually considered to have been an important enterprise for the Iron Age communities (J. H. Larsen, 2016b). Particular interest has also been paid to developing pollen diagrams for northern Gudbrandsdalen, which have provided important data on the agricultural development in the valley countryside and lower mountain areas (Gunnarsdóttir, 1999; Gunnarsdóttir & Høeg, 1996; Høeg, 2011).

Mikkelsen's (1994) excavations of the medieval mass-trapping site at Einsethø, in the northern area of the valley, have been important for the understanding of the scale and character of reindeer trapping. A

number of large-scale surveys have also provided invaluable information on prehistoric hunting and trapping, in particular research conducted by Edvard K. Barth (1996) in Rondane, and the county administration at high mountain snow patches (Finstad, Martinsen, Hole, & Pilø, 2018; Nesje et al., 2011; Pilø, Barrett, et al., 2020; Pilø, Finstad, & Barrett, 2020; Pilø et al., 2018). In recent years considerable effort has also been put into documenting mass-trapping systems in the mountain region (Hole, 2013; Solli, 2018). Excavations have been conducted around mountain lakes, such as Aursjøen in Lesja, Tesse in Lom, and Olstappen in Fron (Bergstøl, 2015b; Bergstøl & Friis, 2020; Bergstøl & Reitan, 2008; Bjørkli et al., 2016), which testify to early prevalence for elk and reindeer hunting. Moreover, systematic fishing instalments dating back to the medieval period have been documented in Lake Tesse, while sinkers from fishing nets have been dated to the Late Iron Age. As in the case of Vuludalen, ethnicity is often discussed in relation to mountain and trapping sites as there is evidence of a possible Sami presence in eastern Norway (H. R. Amundsen & Os, 2020; Bergstøl, 2020; Bergstøl & Reitan, 2008; Wammer, 2016), which, however, will not be further addressed in this thesis.

Until the E6 road construction project in 2011 and 2012, no Iron Age longhouses in Gudbrandsdalen valley had been investigated by machine-assisted topsoil stripping. So far, the E6 project is still not only the largest of its kind in former Oppland County, but also one of the largest in the inlands of eastern Norway. It provided a whole new insight in prehistoric farming and settlement development in the region (published in Gundersen, 2016e). Most of the sites were located in Fron, where three Iron Age farmsteads were uncovered among a larger number of diverse settlement and farming sites. The three farmsteads, Grytting I, Brandrud I, and Brandrud IV, all belong to the Roman Iron Age and Migration Period and were abandoned around the transition to the Merovingian Period. The Late Migration Period House V at Grytting I distinguish itself in sheer size. The full extent of the structure was not uncovered, but it must have been at least 44 meters long, thus making it one of the largest longhouses identified so far in the inlands. Although one should be careful with attributing too much significance to size alone, it does indicate a certain level of wealth (Villumsen, 2016a, pp. 177-179). House V represents the latest of three sequential phases in the settlement development, with each phase representing an increase in the size of the main farm building. Consequently, the farm's development seems to have been progressive up to the point of abandonment. The three farms represent a period of settlement expansion, which is also visible at a number of other agricultural sites in the area (Gundersen, 2016d, pp. 123-125). Besides the E6 project, one more Iron Age farm was excavated at Mo in Øyer in 2012 (J. Kile-Vesik, Loftsgarden, & Lønnaas, 2014). However, after 2012, the Museum of Cultural History has not initiated any more settlement excavations in the valley. A number of minor investigations have nonetheless been orchestrated by the county administration.

Prior to the E6 project, only minor excavations of settlement and agricultural sites had been conducted, and even less had been published. In other words, the archaeological knowledge of the farming landscape in the region prior to 2011 was mainly based on visual heritage, such as burial mounds, or artefacts recovered by locals during farm work (J. H. Larsen, 2016a). Several of these artefacts probably stem from deleted burials, of which some can be described as particularly wealthy. Of considerable importance are the two Late Roman Iron Age graves from Kjorstad in Fron, of which one is a female grave with Roman imports, several gold objects, brooches, and a bucket-shaped pot of probable western Norwegian origin (J. H. Larsen, 2007, p. 192; 2016a, p. 67). Another wealthy female grave has been recovered from Øyer in southern Gudbrandsdalen, where a rare Early Merovingian Period relief brooch with cloisonné decorations was found together with numerous glass beads (Røstad, 2018).

Hundorp in Fron is usually understood as the most important of the Iron Age sites in the region and includes a number of artefact finds, in particular from the Viking Age, including at least one male and one female grave (J. H. Larsen, 2016a, p. 71). However, it is the monumental burial mounds at the site that have gained most attention from locals, visitors, and researchers alike. Today, four mounds are preserved close to the current farmstead, while a fifth is described in antiquarian sources from the late 18th century (Schøning, 1980 [1778]). A few minor burials have been identified, but not excavated, while the remnants of a large stone circle are situated between two of the large mounds. Several more minor mounds are described in antiquarian sources but are non-existent today, and they may be related to the artefact finds from the site (J. H. Larsen, 2016a, p. 71). The concentration of monumental burials at Hundorp stand out in eastern Norway, and is only surpassed in number by the more famous Borre site in Vestfold, which lies further to the south (Myhre, 2015). A minor excavation was conducted at Hundorp in 2002 (Jacobsen & Larsen, 2005), and a few more investigations were initiated later on by the county administration. The lack of large-scale excavations has caused a large gap regarding our knowledge about the site, in particular its development towards the monumental phase. None of the mounds have been scientifically investigated. Two of them were partly dug out by locals in the late 18th and early 19th century, but resulted in no definable artefact finds (J. H. Larsen, 2016a, p. 70). The burials at the site are usually considered Iron Age, with the monumental phase emerging sometime in the Merovingian Period. In the saga literature, Hundorp is described as a chieftain's manor and assembly site, including both judicial and cultic functions for the region. It should be stressed that the saga descriptions are associated with considerable source-critical issues, but nonetheless believed to reflect the presence of a Late Iron Age ruler site (Steinsland, 2005).

The 2011-2012 excavations not only provided the first substantial settlement datasets in the region, but also uncovered hitherto unknown prehistoric flood events that had directly impacted the settlements

(Gundersen, 2016b; Nesje, Gundersen, & Cannell, 2016). All the three farmsteads in Fron had been clearly affected, but damage also extended to several more agricultural sites in the area. Three major events were identified, with two in the Pre-Roman Iron Age and a third in the Early Merovingian Period. The Roman Iron Age and Migration Period seem to have been less exposed to major events of this kind. The Merovingian Period flood has been understood as instrumental for widespread site abandonment and societal change in Fron around this time (Gundersen, 2016a, 2016d). However, as pointed out in Chapter 6.4.2, the significance of the E6 project for the overall archaeological dataset in the region creates uncertainties regarding data representativeness. There is a general lack of comprehensive excavations in other parts of the farming landscape outside the E6 zoning plans, thus creating a certain investigation bias in favour of the Early Iron Age settlements found during the project.

7.4. Chapter conclusion

The research histories of the two regions are of different character, but have also been targeted towards independent research interests. Outfield exploitation is well-researched in Gudbrandsdalen valley, whereas burials, settlements, and the elite milieu associated with Åker has attracted the most attention around Lake Mjøsa. Gudbrandsdalen includes wealthy burials and dynastical complexes, apparently comparable to those in the lake districts, but few excavations or research projects have been directed towards these sites. Little is therefore known concerning site development and site character at places like Hundorp, and there is therefore much to be learned about the emergence of centralised authority in the region.

In general, the Lake Mjøsa region is better investigated, with more settlement and agricultural sites being excavated during the last three decades. This has resulted in a diversified dataset involving both marginal farming areas and large settlement complexes, such as Åker in Hamar, spanning across much of the social hierarchy of the past. This is mainly due to significant differences in the extent and rate of modern construction work, as urban development has been more profound around Lake Mjøsa. The sudden rise in archaeological excavations in Gudbrandsdalen in 2011 and 2012, mainly in relation to road construction work, illustrates this well, especially compared with the low number of investigations in following years. However, several Lake Mjøsa region sites are poorly documented and/or include a limited number of scientific analyses, which have resulted in a low ratio of data per site in the region. In contrast, the Gudbrandsdalen valley dataset mostly comprise of excavation results made available during the last decade. This has resulted in several well-documented sites, including a wide array of scientific results, but also in a dataset somewhat restricted in both spatial and temporal terms, especially for settlement sites.

Gudbrandsdalen valley and Lake Mjøsa represent contrasting landscapes with different preconditions for settlement and agriculture. In spite of increasing specialisation, mechanisation, and use of chemical fertilizers, agriculture remains fundamentally different in the two regions. On the contrary, one might say that modern niche-production has enforced the regional characteristics, as farming is no longer directed towards a broad strategy of self-sufficiency but instead utilises the natural preconditions through specialised production.

Several large estates and extensive fields can be found around Lake Mjøsa, while the farms in the Gudbrandsdalen valley are smaller and the fields more restricted by topographical factors. Modern agriculture in the lake districts is directed towards crop production, while husbandry, in particular sheep, and grass production remains important in Gudbrandsdalen valley. Chalk- and clay-rich sediments offer favourable conditions for crops around Lake Mjøsa. Chalk-rich sediments can also be found in the valley slopes in Gudbrandsdalen, where solar radiation, in particular south-facing terrains, contribute to good farming conditions. However, dry climatic conditions, especially in the northern areas, have traditionally made irrigation a common necessity for crop cultivation.

Although less specialised, these distinctions were also identifiable in pre-modern times, with northern Mjøsa being the traditional 'breadbasket' of eastern Norway, and farming in Gudbrandsdalen being heavily depended on outfields, pastures, and mountain summer farms. However, before chemical fertilizers were introduced in the 20th century, husbandry – in particular cattle – constituted an essential part of farming strategies in the lake districts. This was due, in part, to a strategy based on self-sufficiency, but livestock was also an important source for manure which in turn allowed for better harvests.

Lake Mjøsa region offers favourable conditions for large-scale agriculture, whereas Gudbrandsdalen valley is characterised by vast outfield areas and a wide range of natural resources, such as pastures, fish, and wildlife. Considerable differences in topography, farming conditions, and resource availability can be detected between the two regions, traditionally influencing farming practice and resource exploitation. In the following text (Chapters 8 and 9), the environmental preconditions for farming and settlement will be further explored in relation to the Iron Age.

8 STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

In this chapter, I will explore the archaeological evidence from the settlement and agricultural sites from the two regions, in order to answer research question A, B, and C. Research question A and B are specifically targeted in Chapter 8.1 to 8.7. Research question C will be subject to a preliminary discussion in Chapter 8.8 'Patterns of crisis?', which leads up to a final conclusion in Chapter 10 'The big picture'.

The analysis aims at clarifying overall patterns in site development, farming practice, and subsistence strategies. The analysis is supplemented with radiocarbon records from hunting and trapping sites. The two regions have different environmental characteristics influencing how agriculture was practiced in historical times, and these characteristics continue to shape modern mechanised and specialised farming strategies (Chapter 7). Similar differences can also be expected between the regions in prehistoric times, likely affecting the level of societal vulnerability to a cooling event. In order to highlight similarities and differences between the Lake Mjøsa region and Gudbrandsdalen valley, I aim at systemising the evidence for resource exploitation by utilising a statistical and long-term approach. As outlined in Chapter 5.4 and 6.4, identifying possible risk drivers for an agricultural crisis during a cooling event is of importance, as is identifying developments that may be related to adaptation and improved subsistence robustness.

These four factors are considered potential risk drivers:

- Heat-demanding crop types
- Low crop diversity
- High crop dependency
- Narrow subsistence strategies

Possible adaptational strategies would be:

- More robust crop types
- Increased crop diversity
- Increased pastoral farming
- Increased wildlife exploitation

Of particular interest are site developments and patterns of continuity/disruption, specifically referring to whether or not continuous occupation/activity can be identified on the basis of the current datasets. Site disruption should not be understood literally in this context, as continuous human presence and maintained activity on a given site cannot necessarily be derived from the archaeological record. Significant disruptions in the site chronologies may nonetheless be understood as reflecting altered

practices or reduced labour investments. The exact date distributions on the individual sites are not necessarily important, but rather the overall development in the two regions, including whether major changes in land-use strategies and site biographies can be detected. The statistical analysis forms a starting point from which Iron Age vulnerability can be further explored and put into context. Thus, the statistical analysis does not generate final answers in itself, but aims instead at clarifying overall trends in the settlement and agricultural records.

8.1. Site chronologies

A total of 202 Iron Age agricultural and settlement sites have been excavated in the research area, of which 39 are situated in Gudbrandsdalen valley and 163 in the Lake Mjøsa region (Table 8.1). Thus, there are considerably more proxies from around Lake Mjøsa than there are from the valley districts. However, both datasets display similar trajectories. In both regions, most sites belong to the Late Roman Iron Age and the Migration Period, with a majority in the former period. The chronologies are organised according to a few overall categories in Table 8.1, such as buildings, other settlement contexts, and agricultural contexts. All three categories display the same overall pattern, with the exception of a high number of agricultural contexts in the Pre-Roman Iron Age in the Lake Mjøsa region. Date distributions have been used as a proxy for assessing site continuity/disruption, and the main results can be summarised thusly:

- Few examples of site continuity from the Migration Period and throughout the Merovingian Period.
- House-plot continuity has only been identified at Åker.
- Site disruption is not clear-cut and varies considerably between the sites.
- Small short-term sites reach a sudden peak in the Late Roman Iron Age, and steadily decline in number towards the end of the Iron Age.
- Larger sites display a higher degree of temporal stability

The Lake Mjøsa region includes more than four times as many sites as Gudbrandsdalen valley. However, the ratio for Iron Age buildings and agricultural contexts are less dramatic, with a ratio of 1:2.4 for buildings and 1:1.6 for agricultural contexts, in favour of the Lake Mjøsa region. The significant discrepancy in the overall number of sites is caused by the high number of cooking pit sites from around Lake Mjøsa. In Gudbrandsdalen valley, cooking pits make up 14% of the archaeological features. In 28% of the sites only the cooking pits have been dated. Cooking pits make up 45% of the archaeological features around Lake Mjøsa, and in 53% of the cases only cooking pits have been dated. Thus, cooking pits are more frequently dated than other archaeological features. Other datasets are more comparable. 10% of the valley sites include Iron Age buildings (4 out of 39 sites), against 8.5% in the Lake Mjøsa region (14 out

of 163 sites). In other words, cooking pits appear more often at the archaeological sites around Lake Mjøsa, but also more frequently as a single feature. In Gudbrandsdalen, cooking pits are usually found in connection with other types of settlement traces, and only rarely alone. Large specialised cooking pit-sites, which appear in some numbers around the lake (cf. Gundersen et al., 2020), have so far not been documented in the valley districts.

		<i>n=</i>	<i>PRIA</i>	<i>ERIA</i>	<i>LRIA</i>	<i>EMP</i>	<i>LMP</i>	<i>EMvP</i>	<i>LMvP</i>	<i>EVA</i>	<i>LVA</i>	<i>Count</i>
<i>Gudbrandsdalen valley</i>	Buildings	12	0	0	9	9	7	2	0	0	0	27
	Other settlement contexts	45	12	6	23	16	14	11	5	3	7	97
	Agricultural contexts	27	6	6	11	7	5	4	1	3	4	47
	Sites	39	11	9	24	21	18	14	5	6	10	118
	Sites w. <5 C14 dates	28	4	3	14	12	9	5	3	1	4	55
	Sites w. 5-14 C14 dates	6	4	3	5	4	4	5	1	2	3	31
	Sites w. ≥ 15 C14 dates	5	3	3	5	5	5	4	1	3	3	32
<i>Lake Mjøsa region</i>	Buildings	29	1	3	14	15	8	8	5	4	3	61
	Other settlement contexts	236	61	48	112	101	89	68	32	20	16	547
	Agricultural contexts	43	16	7	10	10	10	8	6	4	5	76
	Sites	163	62	49	95	85	76	57	32	18	18	492
	Sites w. <5 C14 dates	102	33	13	44	33	28	20	11	6	4	192
	Sites w. 5-14 C14 dates	44	21	24	36	37	34	21	9	5	7	194
	Sites w. ≥15 C14 dates	17	8	12	15	15	14	16	12	7	7	106

Table 8.1: Date distribution for sites and contexts in relation to archaeological periods. The sites are divided into small, medium, and large sites according to radiocarbon proxies (cf. Chapter 6.4.3). Smaller sites (<5 C14 dates), despite numbering almost twice as many as medium and large sites, are of considerably shorter duration, thus resulting in a low total count.

In both areas there is a peak in building activity around the Late Roman Iron Age and Early Migration Period. However, the low number of excavated Iron Age farmsteads in Gudbrandsdalen valley makes the dataset susceptible to single results. All Iron Age buildings in the valley are dated within the Late Roman Iron Age to the first half of the Merovingian Period, thus causing considerable lacunas in the earliest and latest parts of the Iron Age. The trajectory is hardly representative for the settlement development as a whole, but probably reflects certain trends in the settlement record. The buildings dataset stands in contrast to other settlement and agricultural contexts, which display a less dramatic decline during the Iron Age. The excavated longhouses coincide in time with a general maximum in settlement and agricultural activity around the same time, which peaks as early as the Late Roman Iron Age. In other words, the excavated farmsteads are best understood as expressions of settlement expansion during the 3rd and 4th centuries in areas that are subsequently abandoned a few centuries later (Gundersen, 2016a). These aspects will be further discussed in Chapter 8.8.1.

Figure 8.1: Date distributions of excavated settlement and agricultural sites in the two research areas, in percentage of the total number of counts for each category (based on the numbers listed in Table 8.1).

The Lake Mjøsa dataset displays similar trajectories, but there are also a few noteworthy differences. Agricultural contexts have a stable representation throughout the Migration Period before it follows the settlement data in the same slight overall decline towards the Middle Ages. Secondly, the number of buildings drop significantly as early as the latter half of the Migration Period, thus suggesting that the root causes of the overall decline in number of sites, at least in some part, predate the 6th century. The site count for each period underpins this impression. Followed by a slight and steady decline, it reaches a

sudden peak as early as the Late Roman Iron Age. By and large, the overall trajectory is conditioned by the significant rise in the number of smaller sites around this time (Figure 8.1).

In both regions, the number of smaller sites peaks quite suddenly in the Late Roman Iron Age, but is then followed by a steady and significant decline until the end of the Iron Age. The curve does not seem to respond to the 6th-century transition in any way, but follows a trajectory set out centuries before. Medium and large sites, with five or more radiocarbon dates, appear in more stable numbers during the Late Roman Iron Age and the Migration Period, but also experience decreasing rates during the Merovingian Period. The largest sites (≥ 15 dates) seem to have been more resilient over time than the other two categories, especially in the Lake Mjøsa region. Small short-term sites seem to be a more typical feature for the early part of the period, while larger clusters of mostly longer durations maintain a stable position into the first half of the Merovingian Period.

The two regions display diverging trajectories towards the end of the Merovingian Period. In Gudbrandsdalen valley, a significant lacuna occurs which is related to the lack of identified Late Iron Age farmsteads. Excavations in the area testify to site abandonment at the transition between the Early and Late Iron Age (cf. Chapter 6.4.2 and 7.3.2). However, at several sites, the activity picks up again in the Viking Age. The development is more gradual around Lake Mjøsa, where large sites have a particularly stable presence in the overall settlement and agricultural record.

In most cases, sites with less than five dates would only provide a keyhole perspective of Iron Age site continuity. In addition, as demonstrated in Figure 8.1, the decrease in the number of smaller sites does not seem to be related to the 6th century in any particular way. Medium and large sites provide a somewhat different picture. In Table 8.2, I have compiled all sites with five or more C14-dates according to the respective site chronologies. The table demonstrates that most sites have a high degree of continuity during the Early Iron Age but that few sites survive throughout the Merovingian Period. Although a number of sites are reoccupied in the Viking Age, most lack evidence for continued Merovingian Period to Viking Age occupation. A number of sites diverge from this picture by including a continuous span of radiocarbon dates that transcends the 6th-century transition and well into the Late Iron Age. In the Lake Mjøsa region, approximately 29% of the medium and large sites have evidence for site continuity from the Migration Period and throughout the Merovingian Period, up against only 9% in Gudbrandsdalen valley. The development during and after the 6th-century thus seems to be somewhat different in the two regions.

	Site ID	Site name	Municipality	n=	PRIA	ERIA	LRIA	EMP	LMP	EMvP	LMvP	EVA	LVA
Gudbrandsdalen valley	98	Gildesvollen	Ringebu	5									
	141	Brandrud IV	Sør-Fron	40			B	B	B				
	142	Brandrud I	Sør-Fron	11				B	B				
	143	Vuludalen	Sør-Fron	5									
	144	Fryasletta	Sør-Fron	23									
	145	Grytting I	Sør-Fron	24			B	B	B	B			
	147	Rolstad I	Sør-Fron	6									
	182	Mo	Øyer	25						B			
	179	Berg I	Øyer	8									
	77	Jørstad	Lillehammer	16									
	114	Romundgard II	Sel	5									
Lake Mjøsa region	42	Hurdal prestegård	Hurdal	17									
	40	Bundli III	Hurdal	5									
	41	Bundli IV	Hurdal	7			B						
	11	Glabakk	Eidsvoll	7									
	13	Stavijord I	Eidsvoll	11									
	7	Berger I	Eidsvoll	8									
	1	Venjar	Eidsvoll	31									
	21	Trollerud	Eidsvoll	22	B	B	B	B	B	B			
	2	Dønnum I	Eidsvoll	8		B	B						
	3	Dønnum II	Eidsvoll	5			B	B	B				
	9	Eidsvold verk I	Eidsvoll	6									
	20	Styri	Eidsvoll	5									
	8	Dorr	Eidsvoll	6									
	211	Eidsvoll prestegård II	Eidsvoll	16									B
	19	Siggerud	Eidsvoll	9									
	90	Englaug V	Løten	6						B	B		B
	84	Englaug I	Løten	8									
	87	Englaug II	Løten	5									
	216	Rømme	Løten	12									
	190	Gjærli III	Løten	11									
	83	Finstad	Løten	7									
	105	Flesaker	Ringsaker	5									
	217	Skapal	Ringsaker	7									
	103	Bjørke	Ringsaker	6									
	104	Lille Bjørke	Ringsaker	15		B	B	B					
	106	Ringsaker prestegård	Ringsaker	6									
	219	Penningrud	Ringsaker	7									
	218	Sveen	Ringsaker	11				B	B				
	220	Stein	Ringsaker	5									
	129	Ljøstad I	Stange	6									
	132	Ljøstad IV	Stange	27				B	B				
	119	Guåker II	Stange	11									
	117	Guåker I	Stange	8									
	120	Guåker III	Stange	10									
	140	Vevla II	Stange	18			B	B					
	136	Ottestad	Stange	10									
	135	Nordstad	Stange	8									
	61	Vold I	Hamar	28									
	64	Vold IV	Hamar	5									
	62	Vold II	Hamar	25									
	65	Snarud	Hamar	12									
73	Åker IV	Hamar	8										
72	Åker II	Hamar	17			B	B	B	B	B	B		
74	Åker V	Hamar	17										
75	Åker VI	Hamar	60										
69	Åker I	Hamar	8										
58	Børstad	Hamar	11										
67	Valum	Hamar	17			B	B	B	B				
59	Kirkebyenga II	Hamar	6										
159	Hoffsvangen III	Østre Toten	24										
161	Hoffsvangen V	Østre Toten	7										
158	Hoffsvangen II	Østre Toten	15										
160	Hoffsvangen IV	Østre Toten	9										
162	Hveem	Østre Toten	6										
163	Trogstad	Østre Toten	27						B	B	B	B	
154	Alvstad	Østre Toten	27										
155	Evang	Østre Toten	11										
52	Klokkergården	Gjøvik	11										
112	Øverbymarka	Gjøvik	5										
54	Gryte store I	Gjøvik	5										
47	Bollerud	Gjøvik	9										

Table 8.2: Site chronologies in Gudbrandsdalen valley and Lake Mjøsa region. Only sites with five or more Iron Age C14-dates (n=) are included in the table. Outliers are excluded. Grey designates settlement traces, red agricultural contexts, green a combination of both, and 'B' the presence of defined and dated buildings.

Figure 8.2: Spatial distribution of sites with evidence for site disruption or continuity around the mid-1st millennium AD. Red marks sites with Migration Period evidence, but lacking in documented Early Merovingian Period activity, meaning that the site was apparently abandoned sometimes during the Late Migration Period. Orange marks sites that include Early Merovingian Period dates but lack evidence for sustained activity further on in the period. Green marks sites with continuous date distributions from the Migration Period and throughout the Merovingian Period, while light green designates sites that experienced abandonment sometimes during the Iron Age but were reoccupied in the Late Iron Age. The Åker sites are merged together. Illustration by author.

Figure 8.2 displays the spatial distribution of sites with evidence for site continuity or disruption around the mid-1st millennium AD. The sites are evenly distributed around Lake Mjøsa, whereas Gudbrandsdalen valley is characterised by widespread abandonment, in particular during the Merovingian Period.

However, 50 % of the sites are apparently reoccupied in the Late Iron Age. A number of sites around Lake Mjøsa also lack evidence for continuous activity. For the most part, the category 'Merovingian Period site disruption' comprises of sites that provide no data after the 6th century, thus being seemingly abandoned during the course of the century.

Most transitional sites provide evidence for continued occupation throughout most of the 1st millennium AD, but they are nonetheless of different character, ranging from the elite settlement at Åker to Bollerud in Gjøvik, which is an agricultural site situated in forested and hilly terrains at the outskirts of the main settlement area (Grindkåsa & Holm, 2009). Cooking pits dominate the archaeological record at Hoffsvangen II and Jørstad, while Ljøstad IV and Valum seem to have been regular farmsteads including several house plots and a variety of settlement traces. Thus, site disruption is not a clear-cut process through which only large and wealthy farms persist. This is further demonstrated by the rate of site abandonment around Lake Mjøsa, where the finds lacuna appears at different times at different sites. Some lack evidence of Merovingian Period activity, while other sites have evidence for human occupation during the same period, but lack evidence for continued Viking Age occupation. A few sites seem to have been abandoned in the Migration Period, but include evidence for reoccupation as early as the first half of the Merovingian Period. To a certain degree, this might be attributed to the fragmented nature of the archaeological record, but the patterns seem unaffected by the small number of radiocarbon dates and types of finds.

In Gudbrandsdalen valley, only Jørstad in Lillehammer provides evidence for continued occupation, but this evidence is mainly comprised of cooking pits. Vuludalen includes Merovingian Period grave finds, but is a lower mountain trapping site with no indications of farming activity or conclusive evidence for permanent settlement (Skjølsvold, 1983). It also lacks Migration Period finds. The site was probably seasonal and repeatedly reoccupied over a considerable time span. All other sites display traits of discontinuity, in several cases involving stratigraphic sequences with evidence for flooding, landslides, and permanent abandonment (Gundersen, 2016b). The latter being particularly true for Brandrud I, Brandrud IV, and Grytting I, whereas Fryasletta, Romundgard II, and Rolstad I includes evidence for Viking Age re-cultivation. At Mo, only a couple of cooking pits have been dated to the Viking Age. In other words, there is only scattered radiocarbon evidence for Late Iron Age activity in the region, which points in the direction of radical changes in land-use patterns.

Figure 8.3: KDE-models of compiled radiocarbon datasets from (left to right) small (n=47), medium (n=40), and large (n=128) sites in the Gudbrandsdalen valley (Ramsey, 2017; Reimer et al., 2020). Outliers are excluded.

KDE-models of radiocarbon datasets from Gudbrandsdalen valley underpin the impression of radical changes in land-use patterns during the Iron Age (Figure 8.3). Small and medium sites peak in the early Migration Period, while large sites peak somewhat later but include an abrupt decline in the Merovingian Period. The number of Late Iron Age dates is quite low in all three categories, and the decline is particularly sharp among the largest sites. Although site chronologies testify to Late Iron Age occupation at a number of sites, the associated dates are rather few and leave an impression of little activity. However, site representativeness constitutes a significant source critical aspect concerning the settlement record from Gudbrandsdalen valley as few excavations have been conducted in the traditional core settlement area in the valley sides (cf. Chapter 6.4.2). The KDE-models are therefore not presenting an accurate picture of past site developments but nonetheless reflect two phases of radical changes in land-use patterns: first in the Roman Iron Age, and later on at the transition to the Late Iron Age. For the Pre-Roman Iron Age and the Late Iron Age, regular farmsteads in Gudbrandsdalen valley have yet to be excavated.

Figure 8.4: KDE-models of compiled radiocarbon datasets from (left to right) small (n=166), medium (n=339), and large (n=403) sites in the Lake Mjøsa region (Ramsey, 2017; Reimer et al., 2020). Outliers are excluded.

The archaeological record from around Lake Mjøsa is more comprehensive and encompasses a wider range of settlement sites. Declining rates of radiocarbon dates are nonetheless a characteristic feature in this region as well (Figure 8.4). Smaller sites display similar patterns when it comes to both site chronologies and compiled C14-datasets, whereas the result is quite different for large sites. The gradual decrease and temporal resilience indicated by Figure 8.1 is contradicted by a sharp trough in the radiocarbon dataset during the Merovingian Period. However, for all three categories, the KDE model peaks in the early 5th century AD. This peak is followed by a sharp decline. Initially there is a more gradual decline for medium and large sites, which is followed by a sharp trough for the late 6th and 7th century. As such, the radiocarbon datasets from Gudbrandsdalen valley and Lake Mjøsa region share the same overall patterns. There is some evidence for Late Iron Age activity but at a significantly lower rate than in preceding centuries. The evidence suggests profound changes in settlement and land-use patterns, as

sites seem to have been either abandoned or located in other parts of the terrain than before, where archaeological excavations are seldom conducted.

Figure 8.5: KDE-models for Iron Age buildings in Gudbrandsdalen valley (left, n=73) and Lake Mjøsa region (right, n=84) (Ramsey, 2017; Reimer et al., 2020). Outliers are excluded.

Radiocarbon datasets from excavated Iron Age buildings illustrate the issue (Figure 8.5). For Gudbrandsdalen valley, evidence for both Pre-Roman Iron Age and Late Iron Age activity are conspicuously absent at the sites, thus demonstrating the source-critical aspects involved. The excavated sites must have been situated outside the main settlement area. For the Lake Mjøsa region, there is a similar peak in activity during the same periods but also a number of Late Iron Age dates. In addition, there is a significant Merovingian trough. The Late Iron Age house plots are found at four sites: Åker II (Hamar), Englaug V (Løten), Trogstad (Østre Toten), and Eidsvoll prestegård (Eidsvoll clergy house). All four sites include evidence for Early Iron Age activity, but only Åker II includes evidence for Early Iron Age buildings. As such, the three other plots are probably established as farmsteads first in the Late Iron Age, of which Trogstad and Englaug both include evidence for Merovingian Period buildings. Combined with the evidence for a significant Merovingian trough in the radiocarbon dataset, this probably reflects a considerable reorganisation of the settlement landscape during or after the transition from the Early to the Late Iron Age. Only the assembly site and chieftain's manor at Åker include evidence for house plot continuity throughout this period. Although seemingly different, the valley and lake region datasets nonetheless seem to reflect the same overall patterns.

A main challenge seems to be identifying the Late Iron Age farmsteads. Few buildings and farmsteads have been identified, and the overall radiocarbon datasets suggest a significant decline in activity (cf. Figure 8.3 and Figure 8.4). However, the radiocarbon datasets are heavily influenced by the high number of dated cooking pits: in the Lake Mjøsa region they account for 58% of the total body of radiocarbon

dates, and 26% in Gudbrandsdalen valley. As demonstrated in Chapter 6.1.1, a considerable number of minor excavations have been conducted during the last decade, which favours small cooking pit sites of short-term use. Considering the differences in temporal patterns for small, medium, and large sites (cf. Figure 8.3 and Figure 8.4), using them as main proxy for settlement activity may distort the overall pattern.

Figure 8.6: KDE-models of C14-dates from cooking pits (left, n=591) and all other settlement traces (right, n=247) from the Lake Mjøsa region (Ramsey, 2017; Reimer et al., 2020). Outliers are excluded.

Figure 8.7: KDE-models of C14-dates from cooking pits (left, n=73) and all other settlement traces (right, n=103) from Gudbrandsdalen valley (Ramsey, 2017; Reimer et al., 2020). Outliers are excluded.

Figure 8.6 compares cooking pit dates from the Lake Mjøsa region with other settlement data. The two diagrams display diverging patterns and demonstrate that the cooking pit dataset is heavily influencing the overall settlement data, an issue which is further exacerbated by the difficulties in identifying Late Iron Age buildings. The cooking pit dates not only create heightened values in the KDE-models for the Early Iron Age but also enhance the impression of decline in the subsequent period. The other settlement data clearly suggests some level of activity. Moreover, there is a significant reduction in cooking pit dates already during the Migration Period, whereas the other settlement data displays a gradual decline lasting

well into the 7th century. This is not to say that major changes did not occur. On the contrary, site character seems to have profoundly changed, probably alongside a relocation of the farmsteads themselves. However, it is important to note that the process appears rooted in the Migration Period.

The Gudbrandsdalen valley dataset is considerably smaller and contains fewer discrepancies between cooking pits and other settlement traces (Figure 8.7). As in the Lake Mjøsa region, the process may have been rooted in the Migration Period, but the subsequent decline in other settlement traces is profoundly different from the results for the lake districts. However, the significant biases in the Gudbrandsdalen settlement record are clearly expressed in the graph, making the rate and magnitude of the process unclear. Interestingly, the cooking pit decline in Gudbrandsdalen valley is not as sharp as in Lake Mjøsa region, and there is also a more gradual build-up during the Early Iron Age.

In conclusion, significant changes in site character were apparently unfolding during the Migration Period that were reinforced sometime around the 6th-century transition. However, data representativeness constitutes a major source-critical aspect, especially for Gudbrandsdalen valley, contributing to uncertainties regarding the character and scale of the development. In particular, the difficulties in identifying Late Iron Age buildings remain a profound challenge for the settlement history of the two regions. Although a major reorganisation of land-use strategies seems apparent, its meaning, implications, and relation to the cooling event is not equally straightforward.

8.2. Arable and pastoral farming

Direct farming evidence (agricultural layers and clearance cairns) has been identified in 70 Iron Age contexts, of which 43 are found around Lake Mjøsa and 27 in Gudbrandsdalen valley (Figure 8.8 and Table 8.3). While several of the Gudbrandsdalen valley sites are found outside the central farmlands, specifically in areas prone to flooding and landslides in the river valley bottom (Gundersen, 2016d), the Lake Mjøsa sites are more evenly distributed in the landscape.

The identification of farming activity is based upon paleo-botanical data, soil micromorphology, and site observations, such as plough marks, as well as stratigraphic sequences, according to the criteria given in Chapter 6.2.5. The data is organised into two main categories: arable and pastoral farming, although not mutually exclusive. Several contexts include evidence for both categories. Animal manure has been identified in several contexts by soil micromorphology and/or macro-botanical analysis.

Figure 8.8: Spatial distribution of agricultural contexts with evidence for pastoral and/or arable farming. 'Undefined farming' denotes agricultural contexts (agricultural layers/clearance cairns) where it was not possible to classify farming practices more specifically. Illustration by author.

A few statistical results stand out:

- Both regions are associated with an early Iron Age agricultural expansion and a Late Iron Age contraction.
- The contraction is accompanied by agricultural intensification.
- Pastoral farming is a distinct feature for Gudbrandsdalen valley, while arable farming is more common in the Lake Mjøsa region.
- In the Lake Mjøsa region, there is a late but distinct development towards a closer integration between pastoral and arable farming.

		<i>n</i> =	<i>PRIA</i>	<i>ERIA</i>	<i>LRIA</i>	<i>EMP</i>	<i>LMP</i>	<i>EMvP</i>	<i>LMvP</i>	<i>EVA</i>	<i>LVA</i>
<i>Gudbrandsdalen valley</i> (16 sites)	Pastoral farming	12	3	2	5	5	5	2	1	3	3
	Arable farming	8	2		4	3	3	3			1
	Undefined farming	13	3	4	5	2		1			1
	Farming contexts	27	6	6	11	7	5	4	1	3	4
	Manuring	6	2	1	3	2	2	2	0	1	1
	Pastoral farming	44 %	50 %	33 %	45 %	71 %	100 %	50 %	100 %	100 %	75 %
	Arable farming	30 %	33 %		36 %	43 %	60 %	75 %			25 %
	Undefined farming	48 %	50 %	67 %	45 %	29 %		25 %			25 %
<i>Lake Mjøsa region</i> (29 sites)	Pastoral farming	9	2	2	3	5	5	3	3	3	3
	Arable farming	16	9	1	4	5	5	4	2	1	2
	Undefined farming	23	6	4	4	2	2	4	3	1	2
	Farming contexts	43	16	7	10	10	10	8	6	4	5
	Manuring	4	4								
	Pastoral farming	21 %	13 %	29 %	30 %	50 %	50 %	38 %	50 %	75 %	60 %
	Arable farming	37 %	56 %	14 %	40 %	50 %	50 %	50 %	33 %	25 %	40 %
	Undefined farming	53 %	38 %	57 %	40 %	20 %	20 %	50 %	50 %	25 %	40 %
Manuring	9 %	25 %									

Table 8.3: Number of contexts with farming indicators in each period, according to the principles outlined for DDA (Chapter 6.4.3). The percentages are in relation to the total number of farming contexts in each period.

The chronology in Table 8.3 is based on date distributions for each specific context, which in some cases covers multiple periods. The numbers given for each specific period, if summed up, is therefore higher than the total number of farming contexts (*n*=) in the database.

As the number of contexts in each category is low, individual results have considerable effect on the overall numbers for each period. Individual anomalies in the dataset should therefore not be given much expressive force in the interpretations. The low number of investigated Late Iron Age contexts in Gudbrandsdalen valley makes the data less representative for this period, especially for the Late Merovingian Period.

As outlined in Chapter 6.4.4, contexts with wide date-ranges are less precise in terms of chronology since the associated data becomes expressive for multiple periods. The numbers are therefore not an accurate measure of the ratio between arable and pastoral farming at different stages during the Iron Age, but first and foremost serve to illustrate the overall characteristics of the long-term developments in each region.

A number of contexts including clearance cairns and/or agricultural layers have produced little or no evidence for either arable or pastoral farming and are therefore designated as 'undefined farming'. In most cases, this is due to a lack of paleo-botanical and soil micro-morphological analysis from the respective sites. The number of undefined farming sites is fairly consistent in both regions, involving approximately 50 % of the investigated contexts (Table 8.3). The number is rather low around the middle 1st century AD which is due to a high number of well-investigated sites dated to around that time.

There is a general reduction in the number of farming contexts in both regions from the Early to the Late Iron Age, but at different rates. In the valley districts, the number of contexts peaks as early as the Late Roman Iron Age, while the process in the lake districts is visible only after the Migration Period (cf. Table 8.3). The development follows more or less in line with the general decline in number of sites during the same time (cf. Chapter 8.1).

Some basic differences in farming practice can be outlined between the two regions. While arable farming is identified in 30% of the Gudbrandsdalen valley contexts, the number is 37% around Lake Mjøsa. There is nonetheless a significant trend in the Gudbrandsdalen valley dataset towards a higher percentage of arable farming from the 3rd to the 6th/7th centuries. A significant share of the excavated farming contexts in the area is dated to this period. It is therefore considered well-documented. Due to a high level of documentation and analysis, few contexts are designated as undefined farming, which conditions the percentage increase in farming indicators. However, even if undefined farming is left out of the basic numbers, there is a percentage increase in arable indicators during this period (see also Figure 8.11 below). The statistical trend is therefore probably diagnostic and reflects a higher emphasis on crop cultivation in the valley around the mid-1st millennium AD. The development is accompanied by a percentage increase in identified manuring, although it should be stressed that the number of contexts is quite low. Animal manure has been identified in six Gudbrandsdalen contexts, of which five also include eggs from intestinal roundworms (cf. Chapter 6.2.4). An additional Viking Age context (no 342) from Rolstad I includes finds from roundworms but lacks other indicators of manuring. It is also interesting that the increase in arable farming occurs simultaneously with a steady decrease in the number of farming contexts. In other words, there seems to have been gradually less cultivated lands from the 3rd to the 6th/7th centuries, but with more grain cultivation involved on the areas that were maintained. Farming practices seem to have been intensified, with more invested labour on a prioritised selection of fields.

Figure 8.9: Rate of identified pastoral and arable farming in Gudbrandsdalen valley and Lake Mjøsa region, according to the percentages given in Table 8.3.

The situation changes quite dramatically during the Merovingian Period, when the number of contexts with crop indicators drops from 75% to 0% in Gudbrandsdalen valley (Figure 8.9, above). The lacuna is connected to widespread site abandonment and falling in the area around the same time (Gundersen, 2016a, 2016b, 2016d), but a general lack of large excavations in the main settlement area makes it

uncertain whether the rate of abandonment was as high as indicated by the statistics. In the Lake Mjøsa region, where more sites have been excavated in different parts of the farming landscape, the rate of arable farming is more consistent and the Late Iron Age decline is less dramatic.

There is a noticeable difference between the two regions concerning pastoral indicators. Only 21% of the contexts around Lake Mjøsa includes evidence for grazing, while the number is as high as 44% in Gudbrandsdalen valley. In other words, there seems to be a more distinct presence of livestock at the farming sites in Gudbrandsdalen valley, whereas the Lake Mjøsa region more often involves sites with only crop indicators. In both regions, however, there is a general trend towards a higher percentage of pastoral indicators during the Iron Age (Figure 8.9).

The numbers are not an exact measure of the ratio between arable and pastoral farming in the two regions, nor the differences between them. For the most part, the data is associated with settlements and infields, or areas in the close vicinity of it. Thus, it does not directly address the importance of livestock in general, as outfield pastures are difficult to track in the archaeological record. It does, however, visualise the frequency of identified arable farming in settlement areas and thus highlights the importance attributed to crop production on available farmlands.

Figure 8.10: Arable and pastoral farming in agricultural contexts in the Lake Mjøsa region, in percentage of the total number of contexts with farming indicators (n=20) in each period.

The difference between the two regions becomes even clearer when considering the number of contexts where either pastoral or arable farming has been identified. 26% of the farming contexts around Lake Mjøsa only include crop indicators, while the number is just 7% in Gudbrandsdalen. For pastoral farming, the numbers are diametrically opposite. Farming contexts with only pastoral indicators make up 22% in Gudbrandsdalen valley, and just 9% in the Lake Mjøsa region. Thus, the overall impression is one of widespread arable farming in the lake districts, and pastoral farming in the valley districts.

However, the numbers are not constant throughout the Iron Age. There are significant changes in farming practices in the Lake Mjøsa region, where pastoral and arable farming becomes increasingly interconnected (Figure 8.10). During the Pre-Roman Iron Age and the Roman Iron Age, most farming contexts include evidence for either of the two. In the Pre-Roman Iron Age, there is also some evidence for active manuring of the cropfields with dung residues and byre and settlement waste which could have made permanent cropfields a possibility (to be further discussed in Chapter 8.8.3). However, during the first centuries AD, there is a gradual development towards a combination of pastoral and arable indicators in some of the same contexts, a phenomenon which can be understood as evidence for an emerging mixed farming economy (cf. Chapter 3.3.3). This development is carried on during the Migration Period and accelerated in the Late Iron Age. At the same time, contexts with only crop indicators disappear from the record, whereas contexts with exclusively pastoral activity maintain a high overall percentage. There are clear long-term statistical tendencies towards increasing livestock presence at the agricultural sites during the Iron Age.

In the Gudbrandsdalen valley, the documented contexts testify to either pastoral farming or a combination of pastoral and arable farming (Figure 8.11). Contexts with exclusively crop indicators do not seem to have been a significant feature in the region, as even Early Iron Age sites are characterised by livestock presence. Only two sites lack pastoral indicators, but the interpretations are based on limited data and must be regarded as uncertain. Paleo-botanical analysis has not been conducted in either case, and the assessments are based on observed plough marks and soil micromorphology. Regardless of the accuracy of these two interpretations, the data presented in Figure 8.11 confirms the overall impression of an emphasis on livestock herding in the farming strategies. Moreover, compared to the Lake Mjøsa region, there seems to be a closer integration of pastoral and arable farming at an early stage.

Figure 8.11: Arable and pastoral farming in agricultural contexts in Gudbrandsdalen valley, in percentage of the total number of contexts with farming indicators (n=14) in each period.

The pastoral character of Gudbrandsdalen valley is further emphasised by the presence of two manured layers at the Fryasletta site, which lack evidence for crop cultivation (cf. Figure 8.8). The contexts have been subject to a wide range of scientific analysis, including paleo-botany and soil micromorphology, and are dated to the Pre-Roman Iron Age and Roman Iron Age to the medieval period (Loktu, 2016; Macphail et al., 2016; Moltsen, 2016). An older layer, dated to the transition between the Bronze and Iron Age, includes both pastoral and arable indicators, whereas only pastoral indicators are identified in the two Iron Age layers. Moreover, the oldest layer included traces of plough marks, but similar traces of soil cultivation were missing in relation to the younger layers. It is therefore assessed as grasslands manured through long time use. Most other strictly pastoral contexts in the database are made up of clearance cairns without associated cultivated layers.

The KDE-models for farming contexts (Figure 8.12) display similar patterns as the date distributions in Table 8.3, which strengthen the overall interpretations. Both regions are associated with a Migration Period peak in activity and a subsequent Late Iron Age decline, but farming development appears more stable around Lake Mjøsa. In addition, the number of dates peaks in the valley districts around AD 400, whereas the same pattern is more gradual and peaks a century later around Lake Mjøsa. The Late Iron Age development in Gudbrandsdalen valley is related to the general decline in the number of sites outlined in Chapter 8.1, but is less abrupt compared to the settlement data. In part, this is due to Late Iron

Age reoccupation of agrarian sites like Fryasletta, Rolstad I, and Romundgard II (cf. Table 8.2), where agriculture was apparently disrupted by floods and landslides sometime around the 6th-century transition. Although site disruption is a significant feature for the agricultural sites, a number of them are also associated with recultivation.

Figure 8.12: KDE-models of C14-dates from agricultural contexts (agricultural layers and clearance cairns) in Gudbrandsdalen valley (left, n=45) and the Lake Mjøsa region (right, n=64) (Ramsey, 2017; Reimer et al., 2020).

To sum up, the two regions seem to have emphasised somewhat different strategies in Early Iron Age farming. In Gudbrandsdalen valley, there is a high presence of livestock on cultivated lands, while the Lake Mjøsa region is characterised by separated cropfields and grasslands. However, the lake districts also went through considerable changes during the Iron Age, with an increasing combination of pastoral and arable farming. The development coincides with agricultural expansion, but it also continues during a Late Iron Age contraction. In Gudbrandsdalen valley, the contraction starts already during the Migration Period, and is accompanied by a higher percentage of cropfields and manuring. In the Late Iron Age, the Lake Mjøsa region experiences a profound combination of pastoral and arable farming on what seems to have been a smaller number of cultivated lands. Considering the early evidence for mixed farming in the region, this is likely to have been the case in Gudbrandsdalen as well, although sufficient proxies are lacking.

8.3. Grain cultivation

Either through pollen or macro-botanical analysis, cultivated cereals have been identified in 43 Iron Age agricultural and settlement contexts. 34 of these also include identified cereal species, specifically barley, rye, oats, wheat, and spelt. 13 are situated in Gudbrandsdalen valley, while 21 are found around Lake Mjøsa (Figure 8.13). The main bulk of the data from Gudbrandsdalen is from the area of Fron in the

central area of the valley, but the sites of Mo in Øyer (southern part) and Romundgard in Sel (northern part) have also contributed important data. The sites are more evenly distributed around Lake Mjøsa, but a significant share is nonetheless located in the Hedmarken area northeast of the lake.

Figure 8.13: Spatial distribution of contexts with identified cereals. Illustration by author.

A few statistical results stand out:

- Barley is by far the most common grain throughout the Iron Age
- There is evidence for rye cultivation before the 6th century, but in restricted numbers
- Species diversity is a prominent feature in Lake Mjøsa region around the mid-1st millennium AD
- Late Iron Age farming is focused on fewer species and more specialisation

The low amount of data from Gudbrandsdalen valley has caused considerable gaps in the record (cf. Table 8.4), making its application in a statistical analysis less useful, especially when studying temporal patterns. By and large, the results from the region are mainly expressive at an overall level.

		All	PRIA	ERIA	LRIA	EMP	LMP	EMvP	LMvP	EVA	LVA
Gudbrandsdalen valley (8 sites)	Barley	88,6 %	100 %		83,6 %	81,5 %	80,3 %	100 %			50 %
	Rye	11,4 %			16,4 %	18,5 %	19,7 %				50 %
	Oats										
	Wheat										
	Spelt										
	No of records	13	4	0	9	8	7	3	0	0	0
Lake Mjøsa region (15 sites)	Barley	59,8 %	50,5 %	72,9 %	59,1 %	54,2 %	50,1 %	57,2 %	30 %	63,4 %	45,8 %
	Rye	16,2 %	18,7 %		8,3 %	12,7 %	17,4 %	19,9 %	33,5 %	33,5 %	39 %
	Oats	14 %	27,1 %	27,1 %	12,6 %	13,9 %	18,6 %	7 %	14,2 %	3,1 %	12,5 %
	Wheat	2,1 %	3,7 %		3,3 %	4 %	5,5 %	6,3 %			2,8 %
	Spelt	7,9 %			16,7 %	15,2 %	8,3 %	9,5 %	22,2 %		
	No of records	21	3	3	10	11	8	7	3	3	3

Table 8.4: DDA of identified cultivated grains in pollen and macro-botanical analysis, in percentage of the total number of contexts with identified cereal species in each period.

A wide range of species has been identified around Lake Mjøsa, whereas only barley and rye have been documented at the Gudbrandsdalen sites (Table 8.4). Barley is the most common species throughout the research areas, followed by rye and, for the Lake Mjøsa region, oats and then spelt. Wheat and spelt are found only at a limited number of sites. The differences between the two regions can in part be explained by the number of conducted excavations, as more sites are included from around the lake. As will be demonstrated in Chapter 9.1.3, pollen diagrams display a somewhat different picture for Gudbrandsdalen valley. However, the statistics nonetheless suggest that crop diversity was a more regular feature around Lake Mjøsa. Some Gudbrandsdalen sites include a large number of preserved cereals, such as Grytting I in Fron and Mo in Øyer, but most include just barley. Comparable sites from around Lake Mjøsa usually involve more species, even when the number of recovered grains is smaller.

Barley shows up in the analysis more often than any other species. Even in the Lake Mjøsa region, the amount of identified barley accounts for more than all other grains combined. In other words, Iron Age farming seems predominantly focused on barley cultivation in both regions. The exception is the latter half of the Merovingian Period, during which barley experiences a significant drop in the records around Lake Mjøsa. During this period, barley only makes up 33% of the data, and only shows up in 20% of the

contexts (Figure 8.14). Rye temporarily surpasses barley, while oats and spelt also show up in higher percentages. In particular, rye and oats are considered resilient species (cf. Chapter 6.3).

Figure 8.14: Identified grains in the Lake Mjøsa region. The upper diagram displays how often the different species are identified in archaeological contexts, regardless of the number of recovered grains. The lower diagram visualises the DDA numbers as provided in Table 8.4. Both figures are in percentage of the total number of contexts with identified cereal species in each period

The low number of involved contexts creates some uncertainty regarding the Merovingian period. This is particularly the case with spelt, which has only been documented in two contexts (Ljøstad IV context 282 and Bundli III context 68). Ljøstad IV context 282 has an especially wide distribution of dates, which results in a low chronological resolution for the related scientific analysis. Thus, the statistical increase in spelt is not due to an increase in the number of recovered grains, but a reduction in the overall number of contexts in this period, which gives the data from Ljøstad IV context 282 more weight in the overall

statistics. Similar challenges exist for wheat. Oats have been found in several more contexts, and the numbers are therefore considered more reliable. The decline in barley cultivation is nonetheless striking and stands in contrast to the paleo-botanical record for the preceding centuries. The decline in barley and increase in rye appears diagnostic – especially when considering the predominance of the two in Viking Age contexts.

The numbers also suggest that rye steadily increased in importance during the Iron Age. The total number of contexts is nonetheless low, which makes the statistics susceptible to single results. For instance, the identification of rye in the Pre-Roman Iron Age should not be taken into consideration as it rests entirely on paleo-botanical remains in one context (Bollerud context 81) with a date distribution covering several Iron Age periods. In other words, the identified grains could consequently belong to any of these.

The introduction of rye to Scandinavia is disputed and early sporadic finds are often dismissed as wild rye rather than evidence for domestication (cf. Myhre, 2002, p. 143; Robinson et al., 2009, p. 129). However, from the 2nd and 3rd century AD and onwards, rye appear more often in the paleo-botanical record in Denmark, and it is therefore suggested that rye cultivation was introduced to southern Scandinavia around this time (Robinson et al., 2009). In the Lake Mjøsa region and Gudbrandsdalen valley, rye has a stable representation from the 3rd century and onwards. The numbers steadily increase during the subsequent centuries and, in the Late Migration Period, make up approximately 17-20% of the identified grains in the two regions. Some of the contexts are considered secure. For instance, rye has been identified in a longhouse at the Brandrud IV site in Gudbrandsdalen valley, which was abandoned towards the end of the Migration Period. This particular area was flooded and only re-cultivated in modern times, which reduces the possibility that subsequent cultivation may have contaminated the paleo-botanical remains. The finds are nonetheless few, and low temporal resolution for many contexts leaves an introduction to the inlands as early as the 3rd century AD uncertain at the present time. The presence of wild rye is a possibility. It seems nonetheless likely that rye was introduced to both areas prior to the 6th-century cooling. This is further supported by Figure 8.15, where the numbers from both regions are placed within overall time periods in order to sort out contexts transcending the 6th-century transition or significantly affected by the Migration Period calibration plateau (cf. Chapter 6.4.3). The latter is sorted out in diagram C, which includes contexts with dates ranging from the Late Roman Iron Age to the Merovingian Period. Although in limited numbers, diagram B confirms the presence of rye in the Roman Iron Age and/or Migration Period. Moreover, diagram D also testifies to a significant increase in rye in the Late Iron Age. Rye may have been a limited cultivar prior to the 6th century, but its later importance in agriculture seems to have been founded on existing knowledge rather than as a newly introduced species.

Figure 8.15: Percentage distribution of identified cereals, compiled in relation to the overall age estimations for the respective contexts from both regions combined.

Another important trait is the evidence for species diversity around the mid-1st millennium AD, in particular in ‘transitional’ contexts. The number of species subsequently decreases during the Late Iron Age – an observation supported by the data given in Figure 8.14. Figure 8.15 C confirms an increasing emphasis on rye sometime between the 3rd to 8th centuries instead of barley. Interestingly, oats retained a relatively stable portion of 6-10% throughout the 1st millennium and seems unaffected by the overall change in farming strategies.

Species diversity is not only decreasing in the Late Iron Age, but seems to have been accompanied by increasing farming specialisation. According to Figure 8.14 A, barley is identified in approximately 70% of

the Pre-Roman Iron Age and Roman Iron Age contexts, but is found at fewer sites in the Late Iron Age. In the Viking Age, less than half of the contexts include barley. Simultaneously, wheat and oats are found in $\leq 20\%$ of the cases. In other words, fewer species are found in each respective context, which might point to increasing specialisation and less alternation or mixing of crops. In particular, farming appears focused on barley and rye. The process seems rooted in the Migration Period, which is characterised by crop diversity but also fewer contexts with evidence for barley (from around 70% to 53-55%). At both the overall and site level, crop diversity is not a significant feature of farming in the Late Iron Age, with the evidence suggesting an increase in specialisation, in particular of either rye or barley cultivation.

To sum up, the analysis of archaeo-botanical remains suggests that species diversity was higher around Lake Mjøsa than in Gudbrandsdalen valley, and that it was more prominent sometime around the 3rd to 8th century. During the Late Iron Age, species diversity is reduced, while farming specialisation seems to have increased. Barley held a dominant position throughout the Iron Age, but lost some importance in favour of rye in the Late Iron Age. Moreover, rye was probably introduced to both regions sometime between the 3rd to 6th centuries (see also Chapters 9.1 and 9.2 for further discussions on this matter).

8.4. The faunal record

Faunal data is provided by 43 settlement and agricultural contexts divided between 23 sites, of which 30 contexts and 14 sites are situated around Lake Mjøsa (Figure 8.16). As with the paleo-botanical data (Chapter 8.3), the Gudbrandsdalen valley record is limited and includes several temporal and spatial gaps (Table 8.5). The Lake Mjøsa region dataset is more coherent and continuous, and provides comparable data for most of the Iron Age. 10,907 fragments of bones have been collected from Iron Age contexts in the lake districts, compared to only 380 from the valley, although a considerable share belongs to the well-preserved contexts at Åker (4391 fragments) (cf. Perdikaris, 1990; Pilø, 2005). However, even if Åker is ruled out, the numbers are considerably higher at the archaeological sites in the Lake Mjøsa region. On average, Gudbrandsdalen valley longhouses include only 60 bone fragments, compared to 130 in the Lake Mjøsa region. For instance, systematic dry sieving was conducted on an Iron Age longhouse at Brandrud I in Gudbrandsdalen valley in 2011, but only one fragment of burnt animal bone was recovered from the entire building (Loktu & Gundersen, 2016, pp. 148-150). The discrepancies between the two datasets make them less comparable, but a few results can nonetheless be pointed out:

- Total domination of mammals and livestock
- An insignificant number of wild mammals
- Birds and fish are only identified in a few well-preserved contexts around Lake Mjøsa

Figure 8.16: Spatial distribution of contexts with identified animal bones. Illustration by author.

In both regions, the main bulk of faunal remains consists of unspecified mammals (61%), followed by livestock (Table 8.5). Artiodactyla (even-toed ungulates) and undefined animals also make up significant numbers. By and large, undefined animals only appear in the records from three Late Iron Age buildings at the site of Trogstad, west of Lake Mjøsa, which might be due to site-specific conditions or differences in laboratory practices. Trogstad is one of very few sites in the database where the faunal remains have been analysed at the Societas Archaeologica Upsaliensis. The faunal remains from most other sites are analysed with identical procedures at the University of Bergen. Artiodactyla and unspecified mammals make up considerable shares at most other sites, but are barely visible in the Trogstad record. However, important in this context is the limited information provided by the main bulk of the faunal data when it comes to subsistence analysis, except from underpinning the total domination of mammals in the records.

All bones from Gudbrandsdalen valley sites are from mammals, whereas mammals account for almost 90% of the DDA for the Lake Mjøsa region.

		<i>All</i>	<i>PRIA</i>	<i>ERIA</i>	<i>LRIA</i>	<i>EMP</i>	<i>LMP</i>	<i>EMvP</i>	<i>LMvP</i>	<i>EVA</i>	<i>LVA</i>
<i>Gudbrandsdalen valley</i> (9 sites)	Livestock	19,9 %		26 %	15 %	2,5 %	3 %		40 %	100 %	70 %
	Wild mammals	11,2 %	50 %	25 %	18,1 %	7,5 %	9 %				
	Artiodactyla	7,7 %			12,5 %	16,7 %	20 %				
	Unspec mammals	61,2 %	50 %	49 %	55 %	73 %	68 %	100 %	60 %		
	Birds	0 %									
	Fish	0 %									
	Undefined animals	0 %									
	No of records	13	2	4	8	6	5	1	1	1	2
<i>Lake Mjøsa region</i> (14 sites)	Livestock	13,6 %		17,7 %	16,2 %	19,3 %	17,8 %	16,8 %	12,4 %	24,3 %	18,2 %
	Wild mammals	0,2 %		0,5 %	0,2 %	0,2 %		0,1 %	0,2 %	0,3 %	0,2 %
	Artiodactyla	13,8 %	50 %	36,5 %	12,7 %	10,3 %	6,4 %	5,2 %	2,9 %	9 %	5 %
	Unspec mammals	59,9 %	50 %	40 %	68 %	63,9 %	70,1 %	65,7 %	64,4 %	50,1 %	62,1 %
	Birds	1,3 %		2 %	1,1 %	2,1 %	1,8 %	1,7 %	1 %	1 %	0,7 %
	Fish	3,4 %		3 %	2,2 %	4,2 %	3,9 %	5,5 %	6,2 %	5,3 %	4,1 %
	Undefined animals	7,8 %						5,2 %	12,9 %	9,9 %	9,7 %
	No of records	30	2	6	13	16	12	15	6	7	9

Table 8.5: DDA of animal bones from Iron Age sites in Gudbrandsdalen valley and the Lake Mjøsa region. Cats and dogs have been included in 'unspecified mammals'. In particular, they have been identified in debris layers at Åker but in low numbers. Human bones (found in four contexts) have been excluded from the dataset.

The low number of identified birds and fish must be understood in light of taphonomy and sampling bias (cf. Chapter 6.4.1), and as a result the data is probably not providing a representative picture of past consumption. Systematic sieving has not been conducted at the majority of the sites and, in most cases, these sites lack evidence for fish, birds, and small mammals. Systematic sampling and sieving were conducted at Åker I and Valum, where fish and birds are identified in numbers of 29% and 9% (Åker I) and 1,3% and 0,6% (Valum) of the total number of identified fragments. The two sites demonstrate the source critical aspects involved. Judging from these two records, birds and fish were part of the Iron Age diet in the area, although the exact proportion remains unclear. Among these, a low number of gamebirds (*Galliformes*) have been identified at four sites, but none are confirmed domesticates. Gamebirds are therefore not included in the livestock category.

Wild mammals are only present at a few dispersed sites, and always in low numbers (see Table 8.7 below). The percentages are considerably higher in Gudbrandsdalen valley, but this is only due to the low

total number of finds in this area. The statistics should therefore not be given too much weight in the interpretations at this point. As will be further discussed in Chapter 8.6, the terrestrial wildlife record is also conditioned by considerable source critical issues, which make wild species less comparable with livestock species in the settlement records.

Figure 8.17: Percentage distribution of analysed faunal remains from both regions combined, in relation to the overall date-range of the respective contexts.

The high number of domesticates among the identified species is nonetheless interesting. On one hand, large mammals are more likely to be preserved over time. The high number of identified livestock is therefore not surprising in itself. On the other hand, the statistics indicate that the amount of livestock may have increased from the Early to the Late Iron Age (Figure 8.17). Unspecified mammals/even-toed

ungulates/undefined animals includes around 3/4 of the analysed remains throughout the Iron Age. Of the remaining data, livestock makes up an increasing share, with 15% in the Roman Iron Age and Migration Period, and 22% in the Late Iron Age. This would be consistent with the contemporaneous increase in pastoral farming and livestock presence in cultivated fields (cf. Chapter 8.2). Although not much can be concluded from the faunal remains at an overall level, the increasing ratio of identified husbandry may suggest a growing emphasis on livestock herding. It should however be noted that the Late Iron Age numbers are considerably affected by two Gudbrandsdalen valley contexts with high percentages of cattle. Without these, the percentages would be more even throughout the Iron Age.

8.5. Livestock

Osteological remains from livestock have been identified in 28 contexts divided over 16 sites, of which the main bulk is located around Lake Mjøsa (Table 8.6). The main statistical data suggests that:

- Cattle is the most common domesticate, but is increasingly replaced by sheep/goat and pig in the Late Iron Age
- There is more species diversity at Early Iron Age sites, while the Late Iron Age experiences increasing specialisation towards fewer species

		<i>All</i>	<i>PRIA</i>	<i>ERIA</i>	<i>LRIA</i>	<i>EMP</i>	<i>LMP</i>	<i>EMvP</i>	<i>LMvP</i>	<i>EVA</i>	<i>LVA</i>
<i>Gudbrandsdalen valley</i> (5 sites)	Cattle	80 %		50 %	67 %	100 %	100 %		100 %	100 %	100 %
	Sheep/goat	0 %									
	Pig	20 %		50 %	33 %						
	Horse	0 %									
	No of contexts	5		2	3	1	1		1	1	2
<i>Lake Mjøsa region</i> (12 sites)	Cattle	44,1 %	100 %	53,6 %	45,9 %	49,7 %	57,2 %	57,7 %	51,2 %	41,5 %	32,5 %
	Sheep/goat	31,1 %		21,4 %	29,9 %	27,6 %	22,1 %	24,3 %	29 %	20,3 %	38,3 %
	Pig	22,1 %		23,7 %	19,2 %	18,4 %	15,8 %	13,7 %	19,2 %	30,5 %	22,5 %
	Horse	2,7 %		1,2 %	5,3 %	4,3 %	4,9 %	4,3 %	0,6 %	7,7 %	6,8 %
	No of contexts	23	1	4	11	14	11	13	5	7	8

Table 8.6: DDA of identified livestock species from Iron Age sites in Gudbrandsdalen valley and the Lake Mjøsa region.

Cattle, sheep/goat, pig, and horse have all been identified in the Lake Mjøsa region, while only cattle and pig appear in the Gudbrandsdalen record (Figure 8.18). A Late Bronze Age/Early Iron Age fragment from Fryasletta (context 326) in Gudbrandsdalen might stem from sheep/goat, but is not securely identified (cf. Loktu, 2016, p. 141). The Gudbrandsdalen record exemplifies how large mammals are favoured in small datasets derived from poorly preserved conditions, with cattle appearing in overall numbers of 80%

compared to 44% around Lake Mjøsa. The Gudbrandsdalen record testifies to the presence of cattle and pig, but provides little supplementary information. In the Lake Mjøsa region, cattle have a stable representation throughout most of the Iron Age, but seem to have been most favoured around the mid-1st millennia AD. In the Late Iron Age, cattle husbandry starts declining in favour of pig and sheep/goat. In total, sheep/goat and pig make up around 30% and 20% in the Lake Mjøsa region, whereas horse has only been identified in overall numbers of slightly less than 3%. There is great variation at site level, and several contexts only include one or two species (Figure 8.18). Horses only occasionally show up in the record, with the exception of Ljøstad IV, where fragments of possible horse teeth in cooking pits make up 48% of the faunal remains.

Figure 8.18: Spatial distribution of bones from identified livestock species.

Only Gladbakk (context 26) in the Lake Mjøsa region includes a radiocarbon date from the Pre-Roman Iron Age, but the finds stem from a variety of structures that cannot be securely identified within a certain time period. The Pre-Roman Iron Age is therefore left out of the following review.

Figure 8.19: Frequency of species identification during the 1st millennium AD, with reference to the total number of contexts in which livestock is identified in each period.

Figure 8.20: Temporal distribution of identified livestock in Lake Mjøsa region, according to the numbers given in Table 8.6.

Figure 8.19 displays the frequency of how often the different livestock species are identified at the sites in the Lake Mjøsa region. The diagram demonstrates that all four species have a stable distribution in the Early Iron Age, with cattle, sheep/goat, and pig in more or less equal shares around 70-80%. In the Late Iron Age, fewer species are showing up in each context. Cattle dominates, but the percentage of bones from pigs and sheep/goat increases in the Viking Age (Figure 8.20). Cattle, sheep/goat, and pig all

represent a common and probably complementary feature in the farming strategies of the region. Horses occur in around 35-55% of the contexts, which is considerably higher than the low percentage of recovered horse bones ($\leq 7.7\%$), thus suggesting that horses were a somewhat common sight in the farming landscape, albeit in restricted numbers. It is more often identified in Viking Age contexts than in preceding periods.

Compared to the Early Iron Age, there is less evidence for species combination in the Late Iron Age. For instance, cattle appear in 82% of the Late Migration Period contexts, but have a frequency of just 38% in the Late Viking Age. A similar development is also visible for sheep/goat and pig, while horses increase from 36% to 50% during the same period. The decrease in species diversity is reminiscent of the development in grain cultivation (cf. Chapter 8.3). In similar ways, the development probably reflects increasing specialisation between the sites. In contrast, at an overall level, the pattern is one of increasing diversity, as the dominance of cattle is gradually replaced by increasing shares of pig and sheep/goat. While farms become more specialised, the farming communities as a whole seem to have become more diversified.

Figure 8.21: Percentage distribution of identified livestock from both regions combined. The inner diagram consists of contexts dated to the Roman Iron Age and Migration Period. The middle diagram marks contexts with long site continuity transcending the Early to Late Iron Age transition (Roman Iron Age to Viking Age). The outer circle is made up of Merovingian Period and Viking Age contexts.

Figure 8.21 adds a few nuances to the overall patterns. Cattle predominates significantly among long-term sites transcending the 6th-century transition (Figure 8.21, middle diagram). When these contexts are sorted out, and the remaining data is organised within the Early or Late Iron Age (Figure 8.21, inner and outer diagram), the amount of cattle is reduced over time from 43% to 35%, whereas sheep/goat increases from 27% to 37%. For pigs, the numbers are more or less the same. In the Late Iron Age, the three categories make up comparable numbers.

The significant emphasis on cattle in widely dated contexts stands out, but the loose chronology also makes the data less useful when discussing subsistence strategies over time. The middle diagram in Figure 8.21 covers the entire 1st millennia AD, making it difficult to assess whether it represents a temporally restricted phenomenon or merely serves as a correction to the data given for the Early and Late Iron Age. However, it is more likely that it is a question about site character. Most of the respective contexts belong to a limited number of sites that stand out in the archaeological record. Among those are Åker, Valum, Ljøstad IV, Hoffsvangen II, Grytting I, and Guåker II (cf. Chapter 8.1). Valum, Ljøstad IV, and Grytting I are regular farmsteads, of which both Grytting I and Valum include buildings of considerable size (Pilø, 2005; Villumsen, 2016a, pp. 105-120), whereas Hoffsvangen II and Guåker II are part of large cooking pit complexes that might have functioned as Early Iron Age assembly sites (Bukkemoen, 2016, pp. 120-122; Gundersen et al., 2020, p. 192; Ødegaard, 2018, p. 97). Guåker II includes Late Iron Age debris layers that indicate the presence of a farmstead close by. Except for Grytting I, all of these sites include large cattle percentages among the faunal remains. Thus, the high proportion of cattle is associated with what seems to have been an exclusive group of sites, and can perhaps be understood as an expression of status (cf. Myhre, 2002, pp. 143-148; Øye, 2002, p. 354). Horses are also in higher percentages in this category.

In general, the predominance of cattle in the Early Iron Age faunal remains is gradually replaced by higher percentages of sheep/goat and pig in the Late Iron Age. At the same time, species diversity is increasing at a communal level, whilst decreasing at site level. This seems to suggest an increasing specialisation at the farm level during the Iron Age, which may have begun to unfold sometime around or after the 6th-century transition. In addition, high occurrences of cattle and horses seem to be associated with an exclusive group of sites, including wealthy farms and places for communal gatherings.

8.6. Terrestrial wildlife exploitation

Terrestrial wildlife species have been documented at seven sites, but in low numbers. The main data can be summarised as following:

- Bones from wildlife appear in insignificant numbers at Iron Age settlements
- Deer constitutes a very small number of the terrestrial wildlife record
- The faunal record stands in contrast to extensive evidence for systematic hunting and trapping

Figure 8.22: DDA of specimens identified as domesticates or wildlife species during the 1st millennium AD. The Pre-Roman Iron Age has been left out of the diagram, as it involves only a few identified species from a very restricted number of contexts.

	Site	Context id	Date-range	Context type	Wild mammals	%	Deer n=	Other n=
LM	Åker I	154	N/A (IA)	Settlement traces	Elk (6), rodents (40)	6,3	6	40
	Åker I	153	RIA-EMP	Cultural layer	Hare (3), canines (3), red fox (6), rodents (5)	2,8		17
	Åker I	152	LIA	Cultural layer	Reindeer (1), hare (6), rodents (15), beaver (2)	1,3	1	23
	Åker I	151	MP-EMvP	Cultural layer	Rodents (4)	<1		4
	Åker II	170	N/A (IA)	Graves	Rodents (1)	<1		1
	Valum	139	LRIA-EMP	House remains	Hare (1)	<1		1
	Valum	144	LRIA-VA	Settlement traces	Hare (2)	<1		2
	Valum	145	VA-MA	Settlement traces	Elk (1)	1,1	1	
	Ljøstad II	275	MvP	Grave	Canines (3)	<1		3
GD	Odenrud I	477	MA	Cultural layer	Reindeer (1)	1,2	1	
	Odenrud II	347	LRIA-MP	Clearance cairn	Hare (9)	45		9
	Vuludalen	312	PRIA-ERIA	Cooking pit	Reindeer (not quantified)	100	>1	

Table 8.7: Contexts with identified bones from wild mammals, in percentage of the total body of faunal remains from each context. Åker I context 154 stems from a variety of settlements structures that have not been C14-dated, but are associated with Iron Age activities and constructions. Context 170 from Åker II has also not been dated. Identified tame dogs and cats are left out of the dataset.

Compared to livestock, non-domesticated species make up an insignificant part of the faunal remains at farming and settlement sites during the 1st millennia AD (Figure 8.22). Wild mammals only constitute major percentages of the total record in the Gudbrandsdalen valley during the Early Iron Age, whereas only 0.2% of the bones from the Lake Mjøsa region belong to the same category (see Table 8.5 above). However, the high percentage of Early Iron Age wild mammals in the valley districts rests entirely on two sites of very different character and finds (Table 8.7), thus raising concerns about its representativeness for the settlements as a whole.

One of the Gudbrandsdalen sites is situated in Vuludalen, where fragments of reindeer have been recovered from an Early Iron Age cooking pit. The second find consists of unburnt bones from hare, recovered from an Early Iron Age clearance cairn at the site Odenrud II in Fron. In addition, it is worth mentioning a bone from reindeer that has been found in a medieval debris layer at the settlement site Odenrud I. The context is disturbed and Late Iron Age structures have been found at the same site, creating some uncertainty regarding the age of the layer. The overall character of the site is nonetheless assessed as medieval (Andersen, 2016). In other words, none of the recovered finds of wild mammals from Gudbrandsdalen have been found at Iron Age farmsteads, and the only find from a secure Iron Age context in the farming area is unburnt bones from hare. In other words, bones from elk and reindeer are absent at Iron Age sites directly associated with the farming community. This is surprising, considering the vast outfield areas and the extensive evidence for Iron Age reindeer and elk trapping in the surrounding area (Barth, 1996; Jacobsen & Larsen, 1992, pp. 107-138; Pilø et al., 2018). At Rustmoen in Fron, just a few kilometres away from the excavated contemporaneous farmsteads of Grytting I and Brandrud I and IV, a trapping system for elk has been documented in a forested area in the valley bottom (Gundersen, 2016c). The system was established in the beginning of the 1st millennium AD and abandoned only in the Middle Ages. Thus, it is probable that the Iron Age farming communities were involved in trapping activity, either directly or through mediators. It is not likely that they were irrelevant to resource exploitation in the immediate vicinity of their settlements, at least in basic economic terms.

From around Lake Mjøsa wild mammals have been recovered from Valum and Åker I, including evidence for elk, hare, and reindeer (Table 8.7). A grave at Ljøstad II also includes a few fragments of canine (dog family). However, when compared to the total number of finds from each context, the recovered finds are extremely few. Furthermore, Sophia Perdikaris (1990, p. 16) points out that the reindeer and elk bones from Åker I mainly show up in the form of worked pieces, and its presence is therefore not primarily understood as waste from consumption. A few other species have also been identified, such as rodents, red fox, beaver, and unspecified members of the canines. Their presence in the record may be somewhat

arbitrary, especially when it comes to rats and mice, but might also reflect other purposes than mere consumption, such as pelts/leather (beaver) or hunting companions (dogs).

All in all, the faunal evidence for terrestrial wildlife exploitation is extremely rare, even in well-persevered and well-documented contexts. Large mammals, like reindeer and elk, are almost absent. However, this is not to say that wild mammals were not utilised for consumption, as waste management, butchery practices, field methods, sampling, and preservation bias must be considered (cf. Chapter 6.4.1). Bones from small animals are less likely to be preserved over time than larger species, which is illustrated by the sole appearance of rodents in the well-preserved contexts at Åker. However, bones from large mammals, like elk and reindeer, are something one would expect to appear frequently in the records if they were utilised in large numbers, even when taking preservation, field methods, and sampling into consideration. Evidence for livestock species is widespread, even in contexts with few bone remains. Butchery practices might nonetheless be a considerable factor, as domesticates are more likely to be represented in waste deposits at the settlement sites than wildlife. Large-scale butchering and defleshing has been documented at mountain trapping sites in southern Norway (Hufthammer et al., 2011), meaning that bones from prey are less likely to appear at the settlements. A considerable number of Iron Age hunting and trapping sites have been investigated in eastern Norway, but no similar faunal deposits have so far been excavated at these sites, causing some uncertainty around the importance of outfield butchery practices for the finds assemblages at the settlements. However, the investigations have provided a considerable number of radiocarbon dates which serve to illustrate the scope and development of hunting and trapping activity. Although not directly addressing consumption, it provides important evidence for understanding the scope, importance, and development of wildlife exploitation. In the following, the radiocarbon data from the former counties of Akershus, Oppland, and Hedmark will be explored in relation to the 6th-century transition, in order to supplement the settlement record.

The archaeological evidence for hunting and trapping consists of three main find categories: bow-and-arrow hunting, pitfall trapping, and mass-trapping enclosures (Solli, 2018). The three categories are associated with different hunting habitats and spatial distributions (Figure 8.23). The evidence for bow-and-arrow hunting primarily consists of hunting blinds and artefacts finds, such as arrows and scaring sticks, of which a considerable number have been retrieved in the high mountain area during the last two decades because of melting snow patches and glaciers (Pilø et al., 2018). Permanent snow covers have offered excellent preservation conditions up to this day, and hunting activity has been documented as early as the Neolithic. However, the main activity phase seems to have been from the Late Roman Iron Age to the Late Iron Age. Pitfalls for deer trapping have been documented throughout southern Norway, but with a high level of concentration in eastern Norway, in particular Hedmark, Oppland, and southern

Trøndelag. The pitfalls are found throughout the forest and lower mountain region, with the oldest documented construction going back almost 8000 years (Bergstøl, 2015a). Pitfalls are associated with considerable difficulty when it comes to dating as structural components are rarely preserved. Pitfall trapping was conducted in Norway until it was prohibited by law in the 19th century (Solli, 2018, p. 12). The mass trapping sites are located in the lower mountain region and geared towards reindeer exploitation, but only a few have been thoroughly investigated (Hole, 2013). In particular, northern Gudbrandsdalen is associated with a significant number of sites. Mass trapping had been conducted as early as the Late Roman Iron Age at Sumtangen at the Hardangervidda mountain plateau, but is primarily associated with medieval times when the exploitation reached an unprecedented level of activity and organisation (Indrelid, 2015; Indrelid & Hufthammer, 2011).

Figure 8.23: KDE maps of hunting and trapping sites in southern Norway, split into hunting blinds and loose finds (bow-and-arrow hunting), pitfalls, and trapping enclosures. Red designates high density, and dark green low density. The light grey field marks the two research areas of Gudbrandsdalen valley and Lake Mjøsa region. Data from the Norwegian Cultural Heritage Database, 'Askeladden' 15th February 2021. Illustration by author.

Most of the pitfalls in eastern Norway have been part of small- or large-scale trapping systems, probably in combination with some kind of enclosure or fence. While some systems are associated with elk trapping (eg. Jacobsen, 1989; Jacobsen & Larsen, 1992), others are understood as directed towards reindeer (eg. Barth, 1996). The morphological difference between pitfalls for elk or reindeer is usually just considered to be a matter of size as the constructions are otherwise quite similar, although the constructions have been a matter of some debate (Bergstøl, 2015b, p. 51; 2020, p. 36; Gundersen, 2016c; Jacobsen, 1989). The interpretations are also conditioned by animal habitats and migration routes, which are considered consistent for several millennia (Jacobsen & Larsen, 1992). While the mountainous pitfall systems in Rondane are understood as directed towards reindeer trapping (Barth, 1996), most pitfall

systems in Hedmark, Dokkfløy in Gausdal, and the valley and lake countryside are associated with elk (T. Amundsen, 2007; Gundersen, 2016c; Jacobsen & Larsen, 1992; Post-Melbye & Bergstøl, 2020). Snow patch hunting is associated with small investments, requiring fewer actors and only minor constructions, while the extensive trapping sites are considered labour-intensive, both in terms of establishment and maintenance (Solli, 2018). Furthermore, snow patch hunting with bow-and-arrow is usually considered more 'active' than pitfall trapping, which does not require direct engagement by the hunter. As such, snow patch hunting and extensive trapping sites represent not only differences in hunting habitats, but also in investments, organisation, strategy, and probably types of prey.

Figure 8.24: KDE models (Ramsey, 2017; Reimer et al., 2020) for 291 C14-dates from hunting and trapping sites in former Akershus, Oppland, and Hedmark counties, categorised as TPQ (n=54), constructions (n=72), TAQ (n=59), and snow patch hunting (n=99).

The radiocarbon record from hunting and trapping sites in Hedmark, Oppland, and Akershus consist of 331 dates, separated into 105 dates from artefacts recovered from high mountain snow patches and 226 dates from pitfall trapping sites (Chapter 6.1.1). The funnel-shaped mass trapping sites are left out of the analysis as they are considered to be mainly a medieval phenomenon (Hole, 2013; Solli, 2018). The radiocarbon evidence from trapping sites in Oppland and Hedmark follow the same overall trajectories, while Akershus only involves a few dates from mostly uncertain contexts. As no significant differences are

observable, all the data is modelled regardless of geographical location. The trapping dataset is divided in three categories: TPQ (terminus post quem), construction elements, and TAQ (terminus ante quem). The three categories reflect different aspects of the lifetime of the respective trapping systems, but are also associated with different levels of sample representativeness, of which the construction elements are considered most reliable. The fourth category, snow patch hunting, only consists of dated objects directly associated with hunting activity and are therefore considered highly reliable.

The hunting and trapping sites display different trajectories in the KDE models, with trapping activity peaking in the Middle Ages and snow patch hunting peaking in the Late Iron Age (Figure 8.24). The TPQ-dates indicate a stable development throughout prehistory and up to the Middle Ages, but are the least reliable in terms of context. As the samples are taken from old ground surface and forest debris preserved underneath the constructions, the TPQ dates can pre-date the use of the sites with significant margins. Thus, the steadily increasing curve is by no means surprising as it reflects organic matter of highly variable age. However, the 12th- to 16th-century decrease in the number of dates shows that new investments in the pit fall trapping systems must have declined sometime during the Late Middle Ages or later.

The TAQ dates are associated with similar challenges as TPQ, but are still somewhat more reliable as they are more closely associated with the abandonment phase than the TPQ-dates are with the construction phase. TAQ samples are taken from layers that have accumulated in the pits after its abandonment, usually consisting of a mixture of forest debris and structural remains. The TAQ-curve has a stable and slightly increasing frequency during the Iron Age, followed by a sharp medieval increase. It peaks shortly after the TPQ curve, thus indicating that the medieval mass-investments in the trapping sites were of rather short duration and were followed soon after by abandonment.

Dated trapping constructions are, in principle, more reliable than the first two categories, but as the trapping systems were often maintained over a considerable time-span, the dates more frequently reflect the latest activity phase rather than the previous ones. In Figure 8.24 dated constructions follows a similar trajectory as TAQ, but with more defined curves. The similarities in the KDE-curves between TAQ and dated constructions strengthen the impression that construction materials are frequently mixed in the abandonment layers and that the TAQ-dates are closely related to the use of the sites. However, the dated constructions also give the impression that trapping peaks around the 13th to 14th centuries, which is somewhat later than the development indicated by TPQ and TAQ, but in accordance with evidence for mountain reindeer mass-trapping at the mountain plateau in Southern Norway during the same period (cf. Hole, 2013; Indrelid, 2015; E. Mikkelsen, 1994; Solli, 2018).

Interestingly, the KDE curve for dated constructions includes a 7th- to 9th-century hiatus. This stands in contrast to the preceding millennium, which includes a low but nonetheless stable frequency of radiocarbon dates, but also attests to the presence of reindeer antler, of Scandinavian origin, in early northern European towns during this period (cf. Ashby, Coutu, & Sindbæk, 2015). In part, this might be due to site formation processes and medieval re-occupation of Late Iron Age trapping sites, which would result in an overrepresentation of construction elements from the last medieval phase. However, as is the case with the preceding millennium, one would still expect more dating results to appear in the Late Iron Age. The 7th- to 9th-century hiatus is unique in the Iron Age dataset, and is arguably due to fewer investments in the pit fall trapping systems during this time.

Figure 8.25: KDE models (Ramsey, 2017; Reimer et al., 2020) for dated artefacts from snow patch hunting (n=99) in Oppland (left), and construction elements in pitfalls (n=72) in former Oppland and Hedmark counties (right).

C14-dates from high mountain snow patches present a contrasting picture. The KDE-diagram testifies to a sharp increase in hunting activity in the high mountains during the Roman Iron Age and Migration Period and sustained high activity throughout the Late Iron Age, followed by a medieval decline. Evidence for snow patch hunting decreases in the Middle Ages, while substantial investments are simultaneously put into the pitfall trapping systems (Figure 8.25). The two trajectories probably reflect changing hunting grounds and strategies during the Iron Age and Middle Ages, with an increasing emphasis on high mountain reindeer hunting around the middle 1st millennia AD. In the Late Iron Age, this development appears to have been accompanied by reduced interest in maintaining the pit fall trapping systems in the forests and low mountain areas. The situation changes once more in the Middle Ages, when snow patch hunting is increasingly abandoned in favour of a return to pit fall trapping.

Figure 8.26: KDE model (Ramsey, 2017; Reimer et al., 2020) for a combined dataset of C14-dates from trapping constructions (n=79) and snow patch hunting (n=99).

A combined dataset for snow patch hunting and pitfall constructions is arranged in Figure 8.26. TPQ and TAQ are left out because of the uncertainties regarding context and chronological precision. The two categories used in Figure 8.26 are of comparable numbers, and are also directly related to the targeted activity. The model is not an exact reproduction of the scale of deer trapping and hunting in the Iron Age and Middle Ages as the datasets are conditioned by numerous variables that are yet to be explored in a coherent manner. Furthermore, medieval funnel-shaped mass-trapping systems are not included in the dataset, and the actual scale of medieval exploitation was therefore probably far higher than illustrated in the model (cf. Hole, 2013; Solli, 2018). It does, however, visualise overall trends in outfield exploitation during the Iron Age and Middle Ages. Notable is the gradual increase around AD 1-500, followed by a seemingly stable situation during AD 500-1000. A second increase is visible around AD 1000-1400, which is followed by a late medieval decline. The summed probability plot (in light grey) may indicate activity peaks around AD 500 and 850, and lower intensity in the Merovingian Period. These fluctuations in the summed probability plot are associated with the snow patch dataset (cf. Figure 8.25, left). It is not entirely clear whether these anomalies reflect actual differences in activity levels, or may be related to taphonomic issues and the morphological development of the snow patches (Pilø, Barrett, et al., 2020), or the calibration curve itself, which has a tendency to create sharpened heights and troughs in the summed probability plots (cf. Chapter 6.4.1). KDE is therefore considered a more reliable visualisation of the radiocarbon dataset. By removing samples associated with high old-wood risk from the radiocarbon

analysis, Pilø et al. (2018) conclude that the Merovingian Period trough in the snow patch hunting dataset disappears from the summed probability plot, whereas the KDE-model suggests that hunting activity might actually have increased further until the 9th century.

Thus, there are clear contradictions between the settlement faunal record and the C14-datasets, in particular around the middle 1st millennia AD, when hunting and trapping activity may have reached, up to this point, an unprecedented level of activity. In spite of several excavated Iron Age farms from around this time, almost no bones of reindeer or elk have been recovered. The lack of Late Iron Age remains is also suspicious, considering the high rate of evidence for snow-patch hunting and the presence of reindeer antlers in remote northern European towns. Clearly, wild deer was systematically exploited and utilised in craft and trade. The question remains to what degree it was also used for human consumption. As will be further discussed in Chapter 8.8.2, the lack of wildlife faunal remains at Iron Age settlements is probably due to two decisive factors: butchery practices, and the driving forces behind increasing wildlife exploitation.

8.7. Birds and fish

Faunal remains of fish and birds have only been documented on Iron Age sites around Lake Mjøsa, where it together makes up 5% of the total body of osteological finds (Table 8.5 above). However, bones from birds and fish are particularly susceptible to decomposition and sampling bias, and the results are therefore probably not representative (Chapter 6.4.1). Fish and birds have a seemingly stable representation throughout the Iron Age, but the finds are restricted to only four sites, of which only two have been subject to systematic sieving (Åker I and Valum). Sieving was, in part, conducted on the third site (Trogstad), but not at the fourth site (Guåker II). Systematic sieving is not regularly conducted at Iron Age settlement excavations, which might explain the general lack of similar results from other sites. In addition, the Åker I contexts outside Hamar have a very low chronological resolution, meaning that it is highly uncertain whether the present faunal data is applicable to the Iron Age as a whole, or only to parts of it. Without Åker I, the dataset becomes highly fragmented. In other words, the data can only be used at an overall level of analysis, as it provides little information on subsistence strategies over time. The main results are:

- Evidence for consumption of birds and fish is present at four Lake Mjøsa region sites
- Most species are native to the Lake Mjøsa region
- Only Åker includes non-local species

The well-preserved debris layers at Åker I includes most of the faunal remains from birds and fish. The specimens were collected through systematic screening of whole-soil samples by using fine mesh sieves (Perdikaris, 1990, p. 11). The procedure was carried out on all of the excavated soil from the cultural layers, resulting in a highly coherent species distribution from the site. Furthermore, the Åker contexts have an exceptionally high proportion of bones from smaller species, with over 50% fish and birds in some contexts.

A similar procedure was employed at the nearby site of Valum, where systematic sieving was conducted on several house remains from an Iron Age farmstead (Pilø, 2005, p. 119). At Valum, fish and birds make up 1-8% of the identified bones in different contexts. This is considerably less than Åker, but underpins that the general lack of fish and birds in Iron Age contexts is, by far, a source-critical question. Fish have only been identified at these two sites, which is probably due to a combination of ideal preservation conditions and sampling strategies. Nevertheless, Valum lacks thick cultural layers and the faunal remains have probably experienced higher decomposition rates than at Åker.

However, the two sites represent two different types of settlements. Being a place where people met for religious, judicial, and political purposes, the thick and extensive waste deposits at Åker do not necessarily reflect ordinary or daily consumption, but rather feasts and rituals in an elite milieu. While seemingly wealthy, the Valum site is still understood in domestic terms (Pilø, 2005, pp. 120, 264), making it more representative for past dietary habits. All identified species of fish and birds from the Valum site are native to inland areas of Eastern Norway, while Åker also includes a few examples of more distant species, such as marine fish and coastal birds. The Åkersvika wetlands is an important resting place for migratory birds (cf. Bekken, 2014), and non-local species might well have been captured locally. In contrast, marine fish must have been caught off the coast and transported to the inland region.

The number of recovered bones from marine fish is nonetheless quite small compared to the rest of the aquatic record (Table 8.8). Freshwater fish dominates in all contexts, with an almost equal overall percentage at both Valum and Åker. Salmonids also appear in comparable numbers at the two sites. In spite of overall similarities, the freshwater species differ significantly. At Åker 70% of the identified aquatic species are assessed as perch, compared to only 17% at Valum. The most common fish at Valum are cyprinids (50%), which only counts 3.3% at Åker. However, Valum includes considerably less fish bones than Åker, and individual variations should not be paid too much attention in the overall assessments.

Site	Context id	Context type	Period	n=	Marine	Freshwater	Diadromous
Åker I	153	Cultural layer	N/A (RIA-EMP)	33	3,0 %	84,8 %	12,1 %
Åker I	151	Cultural layer	MP-EMvP	116	3,4 %	81,9 %	14,7 %
Åker I	152	Cultural layer	N/A (LIA)	213	0,5 %	87,3 %	12,2 %
Åker II	170	Graves	Pre-VA	2	0 %	100 %	0 %
Åker I	154	Other settlement traces	N/A (IA)	61	1,6 %	82 %	16,4 %
		Sum		425	1,6 %	84,9 %	13,4 %
Valum	140	Building	MP	1		100 %	
Valum	139	Building	LRIA-EMP	1		100 %	
Valum	141	Building	LRIA-EMvP	0			
Valum	143	Building	LRIA-EMvP	1		100 %	
Valum	144	Other settlement traces	LRIA-VA	3		66,7 %	33,3 %
		Sum		6		83,3 %	16,7 %

Table 8.8: Distribution of marine, freshwater, and diadromous species in the aquatic record from Åker and Valum. Diadromous species migrate to either freshwater or saltwater during spawning, in this case consisting of salmonids (54) and eel (1). Four Åker contexts are not radiocarbon dated, but belong to the Iron Age milieu at the site. Context 152 and 153 are indirectly dated by context 151, which is located between the two and C14-dated to the mid-1st millennium AD.

A low number of gamebirds have been identified at four sites, but none are confirmed domesticates. Perdikaris (1990, p. 18) separates the bird remains from Åker I in four ecological sub-groupings: ‘edible’ (ducks, geese, pigeons, cranes, plovers, and grouse), ‘scavengers’ (crow family), ‘functional’ (falcons, eagles), and ‘uncertain’ (everything else). The categorisation might be somewhat arbitrary considering that most bird species, in a strict sense, are edible if cooked properly. In the context of this analysis, it might nonetheless serve some purpose to separate between birds usually favoured for consumption and birds favoured for other purposes. In Table 8.9 the data is sorted according to Perdikaris’ categorisation. In short, edible birds occur more frequently on other sites than Åker, while scavengers and functional birds have more or less equal representations. The largest share of uncertain species are passerines (8.7%), but starlings (2.9%) and sterna (2.9%) also make up important parts. All three categories have been subject to human consumption in historical times and should perhaps be included in the list of edibles. In that case, the percentage distribution would be comparable in all four categories.

The Valum site strengthens the assumption that fish and birds only played a minor part in Iron Age diets, but the lack of good comparable datasets involves a high risk of site bias. However, important in this context is that the finds from Åker and Valum (and for some part Trogstad and Guåker II) confirm the consumption of fish and birds, meaning that the local community had access to – and utilised – supplementary non-agrarian resources. By and large, the documented species appear in the Lake Mjøsa region, especially during bird migrations (cf. Bekken, 2014), and most birds can be categorised as ‘edible’.

Site	Context id	Context type	Period	n=	Edible	Uncertain	Functional	Scavengers
Åker I	153	Cultural layer	N/A (RIA-EMP)	11	45,5 %	27,3 %	0 %	27,3 %
Åker I	151	Cultural layer	MP-EMvP	27	51,9 %	18,5 %	7,4 %	22,2 %
Åker I	152	Cultural layer	N/A (LIA)	22	40,9 %	13,6 %	4,5 %	40,9 %
Åker I	154	Other settlement traces	N/A	9	66,7 %	22,2 %	11,1 %	0 %
Åker II	170	Graves	Pre-VA	1	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %
		Sum		70	48,6 %	20 %	5,7 %	25,7 %
Valum	140	Building	MP	1	0 %	0 %	0 %	100 %
Valum	139	Building	LRIA-EMP	1	100 %	0 %	0 %	0 %
Valum	141	Building	LRIA-EMvP	1	100 %	0 %	0 %	0 %
Valum	144	Other settlement traces	LRIA-VA	8	75 %	0 %	0 %	25 %
Trogstad	369	Building	EVA	2	100 %	0 %	0 %	0 %
Guåker II	266	Other settlement traces	LVA	2	0 %	0 %	50 %	50 %
		Sum		15	66,7 %	0 %	6,7 %	26,7 %

Table 8.9: Distribution of bird bones in the Lake Mjøsa region, according to Perdikaris' (1990, p. 18) categorisation of the Åker assemblage.

Figure 8.27: Calibration of T-8132 from context 151 at Åker I, by using OxCal v4.4.2 and IntCal 20 (Ramsey, 2009a; Reimer et al., 2020).

Åker I is the only one of these four sites that offers comparable temporal records. The three cultural layers belong to the same stratigraphic sequence and probably cover most of the 1st millennium AD, but the exact time frames are associated with some uncertainty. Only the middle layer (context 151) has been radiocarbon dated to around the mid-1st millennium AD (Figure 8.27), while the older and younger layers have been interpreted as belonging to the 300-400s and the 600s and later (Perdikaris, 1990, p. 12). However, this cannot be confirmed by radiocarbon dates or other stratigraphic sequences, and the use of the site extends beyond these time frames (cf. Hernæs, 1989a, p. 13; Pilø, 2005). I have therefore decided to label them according to the overall date-range of the Åker sites in the database, which is Roman Iron

Age to Viking Age (cf. Table 8.2, above), with layer 151 (Migration Period-Early Merovingian Period) as a delimiter between layer 153 (Roman Iron Age-Early Migration Period) and 152 (Late Iron Age). It is important to note that the dating of context 151 situates the two other contexts on either side of the 6th-century transition. It is difficult to assess whether context 151 belongs to the time slightly before or after AD 536, or if it actually transcends it. The calibration curve indicates that an age postdating AD 536 is likely, but not definite. Furthermore, as only one C14-date is present, more radiocarbon analysis would probably alter the overall date range in both directions. The excavation results have never been thoroughly published, and Perdikaris' (1990) report from the osteological analysis remains one of our main sources to the Åker I excavation, alongside a preliminary report and a popular article by Per Hernæs (1989a, 1989b).

Figure 8.28: Percentage distribution of faunal remains from cultural layers at Åker I. The inner circle is made up of context 153 (RIA-EMP), the middle is context 151 (MP-EMvP), and the outer context 152 (LIA). Context 153 corresponds to unit 3 (layer F) in Perdikaris' (1990) report, context 152 to unit 1 (layer A), and context 151 to unit 2 (layers C, D, and E). Layer 151 was situated stratigraphically between 152 and 153. The aquatic records from the cultural layers consist only of fish, but a small number of molluscs have also been found in other settlement contexts at the site.

Perdikaris' analysis is visualised in Figure 8.28, and sorted according to overall context (151-153). In the first phase, livestock makes up around 65% of the faunal remains, while birds and fish are in numbers of 12% and 18% respectively. The picture changes dramatically around the mid-1st millennium AD, as context 151 consists of 38% fish and 17% birds, thus reducing the proportion of livestock to only 45%. In the Late

Iron Age, livestock increases in percentage once more, but remains at a lower rate than in the Early Iron Age. Interestingly, aquatic resources remain at almost the same rate in context 151 and 152, while birds are reduced to only 6% in the Late Iron Age. However, in terms of numbers, far more bones from birds and fish are identified in the Late Iron Age compared to the Early Iron Age (Table 8.8 and Table 8.9). Far surpassing 153, both 151 and 152 include a huge number of bones, thus suggesting considerable changes in the site biography around the mid-1st millennia AD.

It is uncertain whether the significant changes from the Early to the Late Iron Age at Åker are diagnostic of Iron Age subsistence strategies as a whole, or if they merely reflect changes in elite consumption and the communal importance of the site itself. The increasing amount of non-domesticated species around the mid-1st millennium is nonetheless interesting. Moreover, the finds from Åker I suggest that consumption of non-domesticates should not necessarily be associated with poorer communities, i.e. as means of supplementing a meagre diet, but appear to have been a significant part of elite consumption and communal feasting. The increase in non-domesticates, as well as the growing magnitude of the deposits, is probably reflecting changes in site character and the growing communal importance of Åker around this time. However, the small number of radiocarbon dates from Hernæs' (1989a, 1989b) excavations leave us with several unanswered questions regarding the development in site biography. In particular, this concerns the possible connection to the 6th-century cooling.

However, important in this context is that the faunal records from Åker, Valum, Guåker II, and Trogstad testify to human consumption of local non-agrarian resources, in particular birds and fish, although in unknown quantities, and with uncertainties regarding whether it was mainly associated with daily consumption or feasting. The lack of substantial evidence is probably due preservation conditions, field methods, and sampling bias, and further explorations of these issues would require different types of proxies, or new and more thorough examinations of settlement sites in the region.

8.8. Patterns of crisis?

The statistical analyses have resulted in a few distinct patterns indicating increasing specialisation and integration in the farming strategies during the Iron Age, which, however, have an unclear temporal relation to the 6th century. On the other hand, site chronologies may suggest significant changes in settlement patterns and land-use strategies around the 6th century, which nevertheless appear rooted in previous circumstances. Wildlife exploitation seems to have increased considerably in importance during the Roman Iron Age and Migration Period, and maintained at a high level during the Late Iron Age, which, however, has not resulted in any increase of bones from wild deer in the waste depositions at the

settlement sites. In the following chapters, these three subjects will be thoroughly discussed up against source-critical factors and site evidence in order to contextualise and evaluate the statistical results.

8.8.1. SITE DISRUPTION

There is a fundamental discrepancy between the two regional datasets, in particular when taking the settlement data into consideration. Notable are the indications of more site continuity in the Lake Mjøsa region, which includes radiocarbon evidence for both Early and Late Iron Age activity. Gudbrandsdalen valley, on the other hand, is lacking in comprehensive Late Iron Age data; this is demonstrated in the KDE-model for Iron Age buildings in Figure 7.5, which includes very limited data for Gudbrandsdalen valley in both temporal and spatial terms. For the Pre-Roman Iron Age and the Late Iron Age, regular house plots in Gudbrandsdalen valley remain to be excavated. This must be due to the lack of excavations in the main settlement areas, and not to the absence of settlements in itself. The temporal gaps in the archaeological and faunal datasets are related issues. In other words, the differences between the two regional datasets should not necessarily be understood as expressions of different regional trajectories, but are more likely to reflect different levels of site representativeness. The differences between the two regions are rooted in the respective research histories (Chapter 7), resulting in different quantitative and qualitative properties for the archaeological datasets (Chapter 6.1.1).

Nevertheless, the evidence presented in Chapter 8.1 suggests a few shared overall statistical trends: the KDE-models peak around AD 400, whereas the number of sites peaks in the Late Roman Iron Age when smaller sites are a characteristic feature. Both regions also share a distinct decline in the number of sites in the Late Iron Age, although at a somewhat different pace for medium and large sites. Agricultural contexts are also associated with a smaller rate of Late Iron Age decline than settlement contexts (Table 8.1 and Figure 8.12). Only a few sites show continuity from the Migration Period and throughout the Merovingian Period, of which most are situated around Lake Mjøsa. Of these, only Åker includes identified buildings in both the Early and Late Iron Age. Admittedly, Early Iron Age activity is frequently identified at other Late Iron Age sites, but lacks defined buildings from both periods. There are also a few examples of house plot continuity into the first half of the Merovingian Period, but they are abandoned shortly after. Other examples of site continuity are based upon a mixture of different archaeological features, but lack direct evidence for house plot continuity. Furthermore, when compared to the first half of the 1st millennium AD, radiocarbon datasets indicate considerably lower activity rates during the second half. At first glance, site disruption seems to be a widespread phenomenon during the transition from the Early to the Late Iron Age. However, a few, but important, nuances can be added.

The evidence for site disruption, as presented in Table 8.2, is not clear-cut, despite the effect of the Migration Period plateau for the site chronologies, which is likely to extend the age determinations towards the AD 550s (cf. Chapter 6.4.1). The sites appear to have been abandoned at different stages during the Migration and Merovingian Periods. Furthermore, several sites include Merovingian Period gaps in the radiocarbon record, but also evidence for Viking Age activity. In these cases, it remains unclear whether the sites are actually abandoned or merely display short-term disruption. In fact, it can also be argued that the excavation results reflect site continuity, but that excavators have failed to identify Merovingian Period remains due to other priorities, such as dating more easily recognisable Early Iron Age cooking pits and house constructions. This was indeed the case at my own excavations of the Iron Age farmstead Brandrud I in Fron in 2011, where a post-settlement, probably 6th-7th century AD, cultivated layer was not prioritised for further examination (Loktu & Gundersen, 2016, p. 148). However, the site also included clear evidence for flooding and fallowing – an interpretation that was subsequently confirmed during the excavations of the neighbouring Iron Age farmstead Brandrud IV in 2012. Thus, Early Merovingian Period site abandonment became well documented at the Brandrud sites after all.

The issue is also relevant for Valum and Ljøstad IV. Both sites include Early Iron Age buildings, but, in spite of C14-evidence for continued site occupation, lack Late Iron Age buildings. Valum is interpreted by Pilø (2005, pp. 105-120) as a site with continuity all the way from the Roman Iron Age up to modern times, as the historical farm plot is situated at the same location as the Iron Age settlement traces. Four houses were radiocarbon dated, with results ranging from the Roman Iron Age to the Early Merovingian Period, and a fifth was also identified but not dated. Furthermore, the site includes Viking Age debris layers and an early medieval pit house and cellar. At Ljøstad IV, clusters of settlement traces make up two house plot areas, of which several structures are C14-dated to the Merovingian Period and Viking Age, including two fireplaces (Axelsen, Sand-Eriksen, & Lønaas, 2018). However, difficult ground conditions made it difficult to identify the buildings themselves and only one Migration Period building has been securely located. Both Ljøstad IV and Valum have probably included Late Iron Age buildings, either at the site or in close vicinity to it.

Although research priorities could explain the lack of continuous datasets at some sites, or a lack of Late Iron Age buildings, the overall dataset is nonetheless quite consistent concerning the Merovingian Period lacuna. The low frequency of Late Iron Age radiocarbon dates in the excavation records likely reflects important changes in the site biographies that cannot be overlooked. In some cases, it also marks the endpoint of a continuous site occupation going all the way back to the beginning of the millennium, such as the Trollerud farmstead in Eidsvoll (Rødsrud Løchsen & Simonsen, 2014). The KDE-model for Iron Age houses in the Lake Mjøsa region (Figure 8.7) is illustrative at this point, as it involves evidence for both

Early and Late Iron Age buildings but also a considerable late 6th-and 7th-century trough separating the dataset in two different parts. When considering that the respective Late Iron Age buildings are situated at sites without older constructions of similar kinds (with the exception of Åker), profound changes in land-use patterns and settlement organisation seem to have happened.

Nevertheless, the overall changes in site biographies, in many cases apparent abandonment, seem gradual and asynchronous, involving several centuries and with varying speed. This is in accordance with the KDE-models, which, by and large, suggest a peak in settlement and agricultural activity as early as AD 400, followed by different rates of decline among different types of sites. There is a certain tendency in the dataset that smaller sites decline in numbers already during the Migration Period, while larger sites prevail towards the end of the Migration Period and the beginning of the Merovingian Period (Figure 8.1). However, in Gudbrandsdalen valley, large sites display a drastic reduction in the number of C14-dates during the 6th century (Figure 8.3). The rate of this development stands out in the overall record and is connected to the abandonment of Iron Age farmsteads at the same time (Figure 8.5).

The radiocarbon record from agricultural contexts in Gudbrandsdalen valley (Figure 8.12) includes less evidence for Late Iron Age farming activity. As discussed in Chapters 6.4.2 and 7, this is in part connected to site representativeness. However, excavation data clearly suggests that sites vulnerable to flood and landslides were abandoned sometimes around the 6th century, for shorter or longer timespans. In Fron, a connection between site abandonment, following, and increased flood-risk has been identified in stratigraphic layers (Gundersen, 2016b), including evidence for post-settlement reforestation at Brandrud IV (Macphail et al., 2016, p. 312). On the other side, there are also some evidence which indicates that the house plot at Grytting I was abandoned prior to a major flood (Villumsen, 2016a, p. 168), which suggests that the circumstances for the abandonment were not necessarily due to sudden catastrophic events, but perhaps planned. As will be discussed more thoroughly in Chapter 9.3.1, environmental factors nonetheless seem to play at least a contributing part to changing land-use strategies in this area, including the abandonment of Grytting.

The excavated farmsteads in Fron are a restricted phenomenon in both spatial and temporal terms, mostly situated in areas that experienced settlement expansion in the early 1st millennia AD and subsequent abandonment sometime around the 6th century (Gundersen, 2016a, 2016d). The settlement and agricultural expansion characteristic for the Roman Iron Age and Migration Period stands in contrast to Late Iron Age land-use practices. In the latter period, farming activity must have been more concentrated around the traditional main settlement area, where excavations have seldom been

conducted, or changed in favour of extensive pastoral activity, which is more difficult to identify in the excavation records. However, both date distributions (Table 8.1) and KDE-models (Figure 8.12) for agricultural contexts indicate a higher level of Late Iron Age investments than the settlement records. Agricultural sites like Fryasletta, Romundgard II, and Rolstad I include evidence for Late Iron Age re-cultivation after an extreme flood/landslide event. The reoccupation of farming lands stands in contrast to the permanent abandonment of the house plots, which may suggest that the farming landscape was to a certain degree maintained whereas the settlement pattern more profoundly changed.

For the Lake Mjøsa region, the circumstances are less clear and the development more gradual (Figure 8.4). The exception is large sites and cooking pits, both displaying a rapid Merovingian Period decline (Figure 8.6). However, cooking pits make up over 57% of the radiocarbon dataset in the Lake Mjøsa region, thus heavily influencing the overall numbers as well. In Norway, the use of cooking pits is closely related to the Early Iron Age, and the decline in their use is often associated with the transition to the Late Iron Age (Bukkemoen, 2016; L. Gustafson, 2005a; Ødegaard, 2019). However, in a recent study, clear regional differences are identified which point in the direction of long-term processes pre-dating the 6th century, especially in the coastal region of Vestfold (Gundersen et al., 2020). By and large, the widespread distribution of cooking pits should be understood as a temporally restricted phenomenon, closely related to the regional cultural dynamics of its time. The cooking pit development in Vestfold has an unclear connection to the overall settlement trajectory of the region, as the number of buildings and cooking pits declines at different stages during the Early Iron Age (Gundersen et al., 2020, p. 193). Using cooking pits as a settlement proxy may therefore constitute peaks and declines in the overall record that cannot be confirmed by other settlement categories. In addition, cooking pits are only occasionally identified at Late Iron Age sites, thus making Early and Late Iron Age datasets less comparable, especially when considering the high number of dated cooking pits at minor excavations during the last decade (cf. Chapter 6.1.1). This assumption is strengthened when studying the Lake Mjøsa region dataset, where cooking pits and other settlement traces display contrasting patterns (Figure 8.6). Both include a peak around AD 400, but the preceding and subsequent rise and decline in settlement development is far less dramatic when cooking pits are excluded from the model. Importantly, the Late Iron Age also becomes more visible in the graph, as the settlement record displays a steady presence from the 7th century and onwards. Whether the latter model presents a more accurate picture of the past is open to debate, but it first and foremost visualises the danger in treating data merely as data. However, it is still notable in this context that the result becomes more consistent with the radiocarbon record from farming contexts in the Lake Mjøsa region (Figure 8.12), which indicates a gradual development of the farming landscape and provides little evidence for abrupt change.

Nevertheless, both regional datasets are characterised by a low number of Late Iron Age sites and the KDE-models include fewer dates for this period compared to the Early Iron Age. This may be understood in terms of less activity, decreased labour investments, or even fewer people (cf. Herschend, 2009, pp. 20-27; Solheim & Iversen, 2019). However, a mere inductive interpretation risks being at odds with the many taphonomic issues involved (cf. Chapter 6.4.1), and, especially for Gudbrandsdalen valley, uncertainties regarding site representativeness (Chapter 6.4.2). In her study of Iron Age burials in the bordering area between the Lake Mjøsa region and Gudbrandsdalen valley, Henriette Aasen (2007, p. 142) concludes that the Late Iron Age represents a period of significant increase in the number of burials, as well as a wider spatial distribution, than in the preceding period. Her results contrast the overall settlement and radiocarbon record from the two regions, and demonstrate the importance of a source-critical approach to the individual results.

Göthberg and Sundkvist (2017) highlight a number of methodological difficulties in identifying Late Iron Age settlements in the Uppland area of Sweden, in which changes in Iron Age architecture have proven to be of considerable importance (cf. Chapter 3.3.4). The authors stress the need to employ systematic metal detecting of the topsoil layers in order to detect artefacts from the settlements, as the buildings themselves are less visible in the ground beneath and may be overlooked during survey. The temporal distribution of Iron Age artefacts from the Lake Mjøsa region and Gudbrandsdalen valley may reflect a similar issue. Artefacts are not included as main proxies in this thesis, but some raw data is presented in this discussion to illustrate the argument of Göthberg and Sundkvist (2017). Figure 8.29 displays compiled artefact datasets from the two regions systemised according to the respective age of each find. All recovered archaeological artefacts from eastern Norway are registered in the digital database at the Museum of Cultural History, and it is therefore the most comprehensive of its kind for this part of the country. The statistics alone display a clear majority of Late Iron Age finds compared to the Early Iron Age. Furthermore, the Merovingian Period represents a considerable increase compared to preceding periods.

The artefacts have not been reviewed by the author and the data is therefore somewhat unrefined. The artefacts are mostly listed with typological dates, but radiocarbon analyses have in some instances been conducted as well. Thus, the dataset is a mixture of absolute and relative dates. Moreover, technology, materials, cultural-historical factors, and the process of recovery are likely to have been instrumental for the overall numbers. The temporal distribution of artefacts will therefore not be given any weight in the interpretations. However, the main argument given here is that the overall trend in the artefact dataset counterbalances the impression provided by radiocarbon datasets alone, and underlines the importance of contextualising the archaeological data.

Figure 8.29: Typological and radiocarbon dated artefacts in the digital database 'Gjenstandsdatbasen' at the Museum of Cultural History (MCH) per 27th of October 2020, sorted according to archaeological period. Samples have been excluded from the overview, alongside artefacts that have not been dated within specific time periods. The dataset consists of 2698 and 1816 artefacts from the Lake Mjøsa region (excluded Eidsvoll and Hurdal) and Gudbrandsdalen valley, respectively, of which 2217 and 1516 are dated within one of the five Iron Age sub-periods.

In both regions, the Late Iron Age includes considerable data that is of profoundly different character than that of the preceding centuries. The Early Iron Age is characterised by widespread settlement records, whereas the Late Iron Age settlements are seemingly more difficult to locate but the sites are quite rich in artefact finds. A common argument is that the Late Iron Age farms are located close by or underneath modern farms, in areas that are more rarely subject to archaeological excavations (cf. Chapter 3.2.5). Both Gjerpe (2017) and Grønnesby (2019) argue that the transition to the Late Iron Age includes profound changes in settlement organisation, from a mobile settlement structure towards permanent farmsteads in a more fixed settlement pattern, a development that lead up to the establishment of the historical farm. Moreover, the mobile settlement pattern of the Early Iron Age is likely to result in a higher number of short-term sites in the landscape than the more permanent farmsteads of the Late Iron Age. The discrepancy between artefact and settlement records strengthens this argument, as the high number of Late Iron Age artefacts, despite the low number of contemporaneous settlement sites, testify to a considerable human presence in the landscape. Although settlement density, population levels, and site character remain as somewhat unanswered questions, the artefact record contrasts the existing Iron Age settlement data. As such, it also functions as a reminder that the settlement data, at present state, does not give the full picture of the overall development, and that Late Iron Age sites should be targeted specifically in future settlement research.

In consequence, the radiocarbon dataset should not be treated as direct proxy for settlement density or Iron Age demographics. First and foremost, it reflects changes in land-use patterns; first in the Roman Iron Age, by a significant expansion of settlements and agriculture, and later on at the transition to the Late Iron Age, in terms of settlement relocation and possible contraction of the farming landscape. The latter process seems to have been a profound one, as illustrated by the widespread lack of house-plot continuity – with the exception of Åker and a couple of more likely examples. Of equal importance is the profound hiatus in radiocarbon dates from buildings in Lake Mjøsa region during the Merovingian Period, which more or less splits the record into two distinctive phases.

The datasets combined demonstrate that both cultural practices and land-use patterns are changing during the Iron Age, and when site chronologies and KDE-models are studied together, it appears that this change is rooted in Late Roman Iron Age and Migration Period dynamics. If so, site disruption is not as connected to the 6th century as it may seem at first hand. It follows in line with an ongoing, but nonetheless significant, development of less evidence for site occupation, followed by temporary or permanent abandonment of many Early Iron Age sites. As the evidence stands, 6th-century circumstances do not seem to have been a root cause for the changes in land-use patterns, but may nonetheless have influenced the later course of actions as a probable catalyst for further change. The noticeable reduction in the number of sites during the Merovingian Period, site evidence from Fron, as well as the many examples of enforced Merovingian Period declines in the KDE-models, especially for cooking pits and medium and large sites, may suggest so.

8.8.2. WILDLIFE EXPLOITATION

Hunting and trapping is usually interpreted in terms of consumption, trade, and craft, in other words as a source for meat, pelts, and antlers. It has been suggested that hunting might have increased in importance during the 6th-century cooling in order to mitigate for failing crops (Pilø et al., 2018). However, the general lack of faunal remains from wildlife causes considerable uncertainties regarding its role in human consumption. The faunal dataset alone does not support the assumption of increased consumption of wildlife species due to agrarian crisis. Wild animals constitute only a minor fraction of the identified species, of which only a few bones are from large mammals like elk and reindeer. However, this is also a matter of data representativeness and taphonomy (cf. Chapter 6.4.1), of which wild deer have proven to be a particularly problematic category. As will be further discussed below, this is probably due to outfield butchery practices. Consequently, it is not possible to determine the scale of wildlife exploitation out of the settlement faunal remains.

Radiocarbon datasets from hunting and trapping sites were therefore included in the study to supplement the analysis. However, site-formation processes at the high-mountain glaciers and snow patches constitute additional source-critical issues that must be addressed (Pilø, Barrett, et al., 2020). Ice movement, meltwater, local climates, and decomposition rates may all affect the find distribution. In a recent study of Langfonne in Jotunheimen, the hunting finds were analysed in relation to glacier curves and paleo-zoological material, including antlers and cranial fragments from reindeer (Pilø, Barrett, et al., 2020). The study concluded that spatial patterning is clearly affected, whereas age-related taphonomy seems to be of less importance as the peaks and troughs in find assemblages displayed a different pattern in the KDE-models than the paleo-zoological record. Thus, periods with abundant finds seem to reflect increased hunting activity, rather than taphonomic biases.

The present analysis of radiocarbon datasets from hunting and trapping sites suggests comprehensive wildlife exploitation in both the Migration Period and the Late Iron Age (cf. Figure 8.26). There is also evidence for a shift in hunting habitats and strategies around the mid-1st millennium AD, which suggests that reindeer and bow-and-arrow hunting may have become of greater importance. The development predates the 6th century by considerable margins, and is reinforced in the Late Iron Age with reduced maintenance of the pitfall trapping systems (of which many are associated with elk). In other words, there is a significant discrepancy between the radiocarbon and faunal datasets that appear related to butchery practices at the hunting and trapping sites, resulting in a consequent lack of faunal remains for wild deer at the settlements.

Osteological analyses at mountainous mass-trapping sites testify to large-scale butchering and carcass defleshing on site, probably as a means to ease the burden of transporting prey back home (Beijersbergen, 2017; Hufthammer et al., 2011). Large amounts of bones and parts of the carcasses were deliberately left behind, meaning that the amount of deer bones at settlement sites would not be proportionate to the actual extent and importance of its exploitation. In contrast, domesticates would be butchered close to or at the farms, thus considerably increasing the possibility for bones from livestock to turn up in the settlement record. The ratio between domesticates and terrestrial wildlife in the settlement faunal record is conditioned by contrasting factors and does not provide an accurate picture of past subsistence strategies. When taking these factors into consideration, it becomes clear that the faunal evidence for terrestrial wildlife exploitation needs to be properly examined in a source-critical and contextual perspective. In doing so, the discussions will have to move towards a more qualitative rather than quantitative approach while also taking a detour into the faunal evidence at the mass-trapping sites.

The scale and magnitude of hunting and trapping activity was significant during medieval times, defined by Anne K. Hufthammer et al. (2011, p. 59) as an “almost industrialized hunt”. Numerous extensive funnel-shaped mass-trapping systems have been documented in the mountain areas of northern Gudbrandsdalen (Hole, 2013; E. Mikkelsen, 1994; Solli, 2018). It has been suggested that mass trapping might have originated as early as in the Roman Iron Age, but only developed into comprehensive and sophisticated systems in the Late Iron Age and Middle Ages (Hole, 2013). A recent study suggests that commercial exploitation of reindeer antler took place as early as the Late Viking Age (Rosvold, Hansen, & Røed, 2019).

In southern Norway, aDNA-studies provide evidence for considerable reindeer depopulation during the 11th to 12th centuries, which resulted in significant changes in the genetic signatures of the respective herds (Røed et al., 2014). According to Liselotte Beijersbergen (2017, p. 358), there is a shift from qualitative to quantitative hunting from the 11th to the 13th centuries. In the early Middle Ages, fewer individuals are represented at butchering sites, suggesting selective hunting aimed at obtaining large quantities of meat with little effort. In the High Middle Ages, meat quantity per animal seems to have been of minor importance as quantity was obtained through the mass trapping of animals from a large catchment area. At Hardangervidda, the mass hunting seems to have been a brief episode, in some cases probably lasting for less than 50 years, as the herds were rapidly wiped out (Indrelid, 2015; Indrelid & Hufthammer, 2011). In the medieval town of Oslo, reindeer bones are more or less absent after 1350 (E. Mikkelsen, 1994, p. 147). The enterprise was of such a large scale that it must have surpassed the needs of the local communities, thus pointing in the direction of some kind of centralised authority, such as king or clergy in cooperation with craftsmen and tradespeople (Indrelid, 2015; Indrelid & Hufthammer, 2011), or local landowning nobility (Solli, 2018, p. 22).

Vast amounts of animal bones were left behind at the medieval mass-trapping sites and testify to extensive on-site butchering and defleshing of the carcasses (Hufthammer et al., 2011). At the medieval mass-trapping site of Tøftom in northern Gudbrandsdalen, osteological analysis suggests that furs, meat-rich parts of the carcass, and antlers were transported away, while less meat-rich parts and marrow were consumed on-site (E. Mikkelsen, 1994, p. 64). As one might expect, bones from wild mammals are underrepresented in the early Norwegian towns, where most recovered mammal bones are from domesticates (cf. E. Mikkelsen, 1994, pp. 142-172). Furthermore, the reindeer record consists mostly of antlers, while only a few bones from calves and young adults testify to meat consumption (Lie, 1988). The faunal evidence from both Norwegian and other Scandinavian Viking and medieval towns highlights the commercial value of reindeer exploitation, in particular as raw material for comb production (Christensen, 1986; E. Mikkelsen, 1994, pp. 142-172). Only a few combs could be made from each antler. Thus, a

significant number was needed. Arne Emil Christensen (1986) argues that comb making and trapping was tightly interwoven and was probably conducted by the same group of people. Artefact finds at the trapping sites and aDNA studies of reindeer antler debris from comb-making in Norwegian medieval towns both demonstrate a close link between the trapping activity in specific mountain areas and commercial interests in nearby towns (Indrelid & Hufthammer, 2011; Rosvold et al., 2019).

More important in this context, excavations of the mass-trapping sites demonstrate how outfield butchery practices condition the settlement faunal records. The medieval evidence shares several similarities with the Iron Age record, in particular when it comes to a fundamental discrepancy between the scale of wildlife exploitation and the low number of non-domesticates in settlement waste deposits.

Although butchery practices may explain the low number of bones from wild mammals in the Iron Age farming areas, it cannot fully explain an almost absence of it. Certain parts of the carcasses are frequently missing at the mountain trapping sites, and are likely to have been brought back to the settlements. The butchery practices seem to have changed sometime between the Early Iron Age and the Middle Ages. Hufthammer et al. (2011) have compared faunal remains from trapping sites at the Hardangervidda mountain plateau and the Dovre mountain region in northern Gudbrandsdalen. Their analysis demonstrates that meat-rich parts of the reindeer are often missing at the Roman Iron Age site at Sørbu in Hardangervidda, while parts with little food value, like the long bones, ribs, scull, and antlers, were frequently left behind. Judging from this site, one might expect the upper legs and vertebrae to show up at the Iron Age settlements. Unfortunately, similar waste deposits have not been excavated at Iron Age mass-trapping complexes in the Gudbrandsdalen vicinity, and one can only speculate whether the evidence from Sørbu is site-specific or expressive for southern Norway as a whole. There are differences between the Hardangervidda and Dovre sites in the Middle Ages which suggest that antler was less utilised at Dovre, while meat might have been of higher importance. The significant differences between the Roman Iron Age and Middle Ages faunal records are nonetheless important and demonstrate that butchery practices had changed considerably in the meantime. There is substantial evidence for defleshing at the medieval mass-trapping sites with most of the bones having been left behind, which explains the small amount of reindeer bones in the medieval towns (cf. Lie, 1988; E. Mikkelsen, 1994, pp. 142-172). The finds exemplify the profound economic and systemised character of medieval trapping (Hufthammer et al., 2011). For instance, antlers, ribs, and upper front legs are frequently missing at the trapping sites. It is suggested that the ribs were used as containers for the meat during transport back to settlements, while the antlers were part of commercialised trade and craft as source material for combs (Hufthammer et al., 2011, p. 60). Drawing upon medieval law codes, Svein Indrelid (2015) argues that the upper front legs were used as payment to the hunters.

When considering the scale and commercial character of medieval trapping, it appears likely that the aim and role of wildlife exploitation must have changed considerably from the Iron Age to the Middle Ages. The question is when, and at what pace. Unfortunately, no comparable Late Iron Age faunal record is available (Hufthammer, pers. comm.), and it remains unclear whether the change in butchery practices is a strictly medieval phenomenon. However, evidence for extensive and systematic reindeer hunting at high mountain snow patches has been recovered in recent years (Pilø et al., 2018; Solli, 2018) and testify to a significant level of hunting activity from the Roman Iron Age up to the Middle Ages (cf. Figure 8.25). A significant increase in wildlife exploitation seems to have taken place sometime around the 4th and 5th centuries AD (cf. Figure 8.26). Considering the distances, terrain, and the scale of high mountain hunting, it is likely that it made necessary changes in organisation and handling of the carcasses. Moreover, the commercial aspect of reindeer trapping does not appear to have been a strictly medieval phenomenon. Several archaeologists argue that the funnel-shaped mass-trapping systems originated in the Iron Age, although conclusive evidence has not yet been put forward (H. R. Amundsen & Os, 2020; Bergstøl, 2020; Hole, 2013). Reindeer antlers from the Scandinavian Peninsula are present at early northern European towns like Ribe, Aarhus, and Aggersborg, and testify to the importance of long-distance resource networks in the Viking Age (Ashby et al., 2015). Apparently, commercial interests seem to have constituted an important motivation behind Late Iron Age hunting and trapping as well, at least for the Viking Age, and this is probably in step with the development of early northern European urbanism and trade (Pilø et al., 2018, p. 7). Outfield butchery practices would probably have developed alongside, in which defleshing, use of ribs for transport containers, and removal of antlers are possible outcomes. Iron Age and medieval wildlife exploitation should probably not be understood as two distinctly different phenomena, but rather as stages in the same overall development from local subsistence strategies towards increasing commercialism, fuelled by the same underlying process of emerging northern European extensive trade systems and urbanism.

Judging from the radiocarbon datasets, the process appears to have gone through several important steps, with a noticeable increase in hunting and trapping during the 3rd-4th centuries, with possible activity peaks in the 5th-6th and 8th-9th centuries (cf. Figure 8.26). The process is accompanied with an increasing emphasis on reindeer as the hunting grounds are moved from forested and lower mountain areas towards the high mountain snow patches. By studying artefacts finds from northern Gudbrandsdalen, E. Mikkelsen (1994, pp. 98-110) argues that hunting went through important changes from AD 400, with bow-and-arrow hunting being the preferred strategy in the Migration and Merovingian Periods. Jostein Bergstøl (2008, pp. 195-198) has made similar observations. Their conclusions correspond with the radiocarbon datasets from the high-mountain snow patches. Large elk pitfall trapping systems, like

Dokkfløy in Gausdal (Jacobsen & Larsen, 1992, pp. 107-138), seem to have been less in use in the Late Iron Age. At Dokkfløy, the overall record suggests two main phases: Early Iron Age and the Middle Ages, with the Late Iron Age being almost absent. High mountain snow patch hunting involves greater distances between the hunting grounds and the settlement areas, with hunting grounds often situated in far more challenging terrains than in the lower mountains and forests. However, snow patch hunting is less labour-demanding than the extensive pitfall trapping systems (Solli, 2018).

Reindeer hunting also has another advantage to elk trapping, as reindeers, in contrast to other species of wild deer, are profound herd animals and are therefore easier to utilise in large numbers within shorter amounts of time, especially in large open terrains. Even in the Middle Ages, when the elk pitfall systems are reoccupied, and probably enlarged, at places like Dokkfløy (Jacobsen & Larsen, 1992, pp. 107-138), reindeer outnumber other deer species in the debris layers in Norwegian towns (E. Mikkelsen, 1994, p. 143). As exemplified with the medieval funnel-shaped mass trapping systems, reindeer seems to have been preferred for large-scale wildlife exploitation. Large pitfall systems for reindeer are also known, for instance in Rondane (Barth, 1996), but nonetheless require more investments in maintenance and establishment than snow patch hunting.

A distinction is sometimes made between active and passive hunting, in which the pitfall trapping systems are considered more passive than bow-and-arrow hunting (cf. Solli, 2018, pp. 12-13). Although this distinction might be misleading, considering the labour involved in the pitfall systems, it nonetheless designates two different types of strategies: short-term intensive hunt, and low-intensity long-term surveillance, during which the individual pits would have to be regularly inspected to avoid prey degradation. Importantly, high mountain snow patch hunting allowed for efficient exploitation of reindeer with little investment and the potential of considerable output, even during short time expeditions. In other words, the change in hunting grounds seems to reflect an increasing demand for resources, in terms of either trade and/or consumption, which made more efficient and less labour-intensive hunting techniques necessary. This development becomes further entrenched in the Middle Ages, when the funnel-shaped mass-trapping systems allowed for systematic exploitation of extensive catchment areas, which, much like the snow patch hunting, can be understood as active, intensive and short-term (H. R. Amundsen & Os, 2020, p. 17; Solli, 2018, p. 15).

The latter development coincides with a significant medieval peak in pitfall trapping (cf. Figure 8.25, right), which not only reflects the last major phase of the pit fall systems but also a significant, and in many ways unprecedented, medieval exploitation of wild game (cf. Hole, 2013; Indreliid, 2015; Solli,

2018). Use of large open mountain plateaus allowed for efficient exploitation of large herds, but the use of mountain areas also seems to have been conditioned by increasing land-use pressure. Intensified outfield exploitation is evident during the Middle Ages, both when it comes to trapping, iron production, charcoal production, and tar production (Gundersen & Andreadakis, 2016; Gundersen & Wenn, 2011; Indrelid, 2015; J. H. Larsen, 2016b; Pilø et al., 2018; Rundberget, 2017). Iron, charcoal, and tar production are all depended on easy access to wood, and these enterprises are therefore usually located below the current tree line. In this, there is a potential conflicting interest with trapping activity, which would then be easier to uphold – and extend – in the mountain region. In the 13th and 14th centuries, several older pitfalls in the woodland areas are reused for charcoal production (cf. T. Amundsen, 2007; Bergstøl, 1997; Gundersen, 2016c; Post-Melbye & Bergstøl, 2020, p. 299). In some cases, like Rustmoen in Gudbrandsdalen, entire trapping systems go out of use and large areas become deforested due to extensive charcoal burning (Gundersen & Andreadakis, 2016). In consequence, the medieval peak in trapping activity is not necessarily synonymous with an extensive reoccupation of the older trapping systems in general, but rather a reoccupation, and perhaps extension, of selected large-scale systems in the mountain areas, such as in Rondane and Dokkfløy, which both testify to considerable medieval activity (Barth, 1996; Jacobsen & Larsen, 1992). It has been suggested that the older pitfall systems were smaller, and only in the Viking Age and Middle Ages developed into extensive systems (Bergstøl, 2020, p. 36). The intensified medieval resource strategies required a major reorganisation of outfield exploitation and, with it, a different land-use pattern.

Land-use pressure must also be put into consideration when it comes to the development of Iron Age hunting and trapping. As shown in Chapters 8.1 and 8.2 (and further discussed in 8.8.3), the turn towards high mountain reindeer hunting coincides with a significant settlement and agricultural expansion during the Roman Iron Age and Migration Period, which, in geographical extension, is unprecedented up to modern times (Myhre, 2002, pp. 127-159; Pedersen & Widgren, 2011, p. 56). Much like the Middle Ages, the period is also characterised by increasing outfield exploitation, in particular iron production (Rundberget, 2010; Stenvik, 2015), but also outfield grazing and the establishment of early mountain summer farms (Bjørngo, Prescott, & Kristoffersen, 1992; Gundersen, 2013, pp. 101-102; Sjögren et al., 2015, p. 162; Skrede, 2005). The overall development reflects increasing demands for resources, not only in terms of consumption and self-sufficiency. The scale of iron production is usually assessed as far surpassing local needs and were likely directed towards emerging trade networks with continental Europe (cf. J. H. Larsen, 2016b, p. 53). I will not go into detail on these matters here, but wish to simply point out that hunting and trapping must be understood within the same overall development as others sectors of society. In addition to meat, it is likely that the increase in wildlife exploitation was oriented towards other means, such as pelts and antlers, thus pointing in the direction of specialised craft and exchange. Bergstøl (2008, pp. 195-198) argues in similar ways, suggesting that land-use pressure from the farming

community might have led to changes in hunting strategies, with a move from trapping systems to bow-and-arrow hunting.

The emergence of early Iron Age power structures in Gudbrandsdalen valley is often interpreted within an economic perspective as expressions of trade and resource control, and in particular is set in relation to the extensive evidence for outfield exploitation in this period (cf. Gundersen, 2016a; J. H. Larsen, 2016a; Sæbø, 2020). Unfortunately, there is no continental record, at this point in time, that directly addresses whether the 3rd-5th centuries' increase in hunting and trapping can be related to trade and exchange (Pilø et al., 2018, p. 7). Numerous pieces of Roman luxury imports found their way to Scandinavia in the Roman Iron Age and Migration Period, but it remains unclear whether it should be understood in terms of commercial trade, or as gift exchange between Roman officials and Germanic nobles (Gundersen, 2010a). However, the character and number of finds gives an impression of increasing commercialisation during the Roman Iron Age, as unique and rare items were gradually replaced by mass-produced goods (cf. Lund Hansen, 1987, p. 255). Considering the distribution of Roman imports to remote inland areas, such as the Gudbrandsdalen valley, it is likely that outfield resources, such as wild game and iron, constituted important prerequisites for the establishment of long-distance networks (Gundersen, 2016a).

With the agricultural expansion in mind, outfield resources would have to be acquired in terrains that were situated further away from the settlement areas. In the high mountains, considerable supplies could be acquired within short time and with little investment in terms of establishment and maintenance.

In short, the primary aim of mountain trapping seems to have changed sometime between the Roman Iron Age and Middle Ages, from meat harvesting for local consumption (and probably furs and other raw materials), towards an institutionalised exploitation directed, at least in part, towards specialised crafts and distant markets. This would also affect find representativeness at the settlements, as one would expect butchery practices to have changed alongside it. The exploitation should primarily be understood as a surplus phenomenon which allowed large parts of the animal to be left behind rather than brought back for consumption. However, this does not explain the full picture, as certain parts of the reindeer carcasses are missing at the trapping sites in both the Iron Age and the Middle Ages. The low frequency of ribs at medieval trapping sites might offer a partial explanation, as the ribs are not easily identifiable at species level (Hufthammer et al., 2011, p. 61). Consequently, the large number of bones from *Artiodactyla* and unspecified mammals at the settlement sites (cf. Table 8.5) might, hypothetically, conceal a significant number of wild deer. However, this assumption rests entirely on an early introduction of the medieval butchery practices, and this cannot be confirmed by the archaeological record at present state.

Until more waste assemblages are discovered and excavated at Iron Age hunting and trapping sites, fundamental issues regarding the development in character and aim of wildlife exploitation will remain unsolved.

The change from labour-intensive trapping systems to snow patch hunting might also reflect a change of organisation, and perhaps the involvement of smaller and more autonomous hunting parties than before. The reasons are probably complex and difficult to assess properly in this short review of the hunting and trapping evidence. However, it is important to note that this shift predates the 6th-century cooling by a considerable margin and must be related to other underlying causes. 6th-century conditions do not seem to have been instrumental for the modification of hunting strategies, but might nonetheless have influenced the scale and importance of wildlife exploitation.

It is generally accepted that the trapping systems gradually went out of use after the Middle Ages, until the use of pitfalls were finally forbidden by law in the 19th century (Solli, 2018, p. 12, with references). Kjetil Bevanger and Per Jordhøy (2004, p. 19) interpret the decline in light of the necessary labour and organisation involved, compounded by depopulation during the late medieval Black Death. As such, the late medieval decline might represent an interesting parallel to the 6th century. The summed probability plot in Figure 8.26 includes a sharp decline from a 5th-century peak to a 7th-century trough, which may indicate a similar process. However, even if this anomaly is taken into account, the activity is nevertheless sustained at a high level – comparable to that of the Late Roman Iron Age and late Viking Age. Furthermore, the 10th-century trough is perhaps even more visible in the summed probability plot, but occurring during an early medieval warm period. Clearly, there are numerous factors involved that have influenced the fluctuations in the dataset, of which the 6th-century cooling, or a possible plague, are not necessarily decisive.

The important conclusion is that the Iron Age communities in eastern Norway had access to significant surplus outfield resources in the mid-1st millennium AD, which, even if the main aim might have been trade and craft, could be utilised for consumption. The radiocarbon datasets provide evidence for comprehensive outfield exploitation during the entire Late Iron Age, which is surpassed only in the Middle Ages.

The contradiction between the radiocarbon and faunal evidence is striking, especially in the Migration Period, which involves several well-investigated farmsteads in both Gudbrandsdalen valley and the Lake Mjøsa region. Although outfield butchery practices explain part of this picture, a few elk and reindeer

bones have been found in Iron Age settlement contexts, although with no proportional increase during this time. Most of them have been found at Åker, which includes debris layers with exceptionally good preservation conditions for faunal remains, as witnessed by the huge amount of bird and fish bones. Furthermore, the respective deer bones are mostly worked, and not primarily interpreted in terms of consumption (Perdikaris, 1990, p. 16). If deer were consumed in large numbers, extensive defleshing must have been conducted at the hunting and trapping sites. Furthermore, there is also the issue of reuse. Use of deer bones as raw material for craft would consequently result in fewer bones being found in the waste deposits. It is nonetheless compelling that reindeer and elk are so under-represented, even as production waste. The same goes for other well-preserved contexts, such as Guåker II, Valum, and Trogstad in the Lake Mjøsa region, where livestock completely dominates the records. Taking the faunal records at the mass-trapping sites into consideration, certain parts of the carcasses should have turned up at the settlements – that is, if wild deer constituted a substantial part of the Iron Age diet. The finds assemblages suggest that terrestrial wildlife exploitation was primarily a surplus phenomenon early on and not necessarily driven by population increase and nutrition needs.

The mid-1st millennium AD also represents important changes in the Åker record, when the number of bones increases dramatically. Although involving quite wide date-ranges, Åker is also the only site with any degree of temporal resolution for bird and fish bones (cf. Chapter 8.7). From the Roman Iron Age and Early Migration Period to the Late Migration Period and Early Merovingian Period, birds and fish increase in percentage from 12% and 17% respectively to 18% and 38%. Most species are found in the local environment, but a few marine and coastal species also testify to long distance networks. The increase in aquatic resources coincides with intensified hunting and trapping activity. First and foremost, the Åker record should be understood as representing elite and communal consumption during feasting, rather than daily dietary habits. Therefore, it remains unclear to what degree the Åker waste deposits reflect overall changes in diet and subsistence strategies. Other records, such as Valum, only include minor percentages of wildlife and aquatic species, although the site, in contrast to Åker, lacks comprehensive and well-preserved cultural layers. However, the finds testify to the presence of non-domesticates in the Iron Age diets. Finds of medieval and Late Iron Age fishing equipment in Lake Tesse in the mountainous areas of Gudbrandsdalen (Wammer, 2016) are a reminder of the significance of wildlife exploitation for human consumption in pre-modern times (cf. Chapter 7).

To sum up, the role of wildlife in human consumption remains an unsolved question for the Iron Age in the Lake Mjøsa region and Gudbrandsdalen valley. The exception is the waste deposits at Åker, where fish and birds make up a considerable share of the faunal remains. The Valum dataset supports the notion that non-livestock species supplemented the subsistence strategies. However, wild mammals are almost

non-existent even in these contexts. This stands in contrast to the radiocarbon evidence for substantial wild deer exploitation from the 3rd century AD and onwards, and must be due to taphonomic issues at both the settlements and the hunting grounds. Hunting and trapping may perhaps be best understood as surplus strategies, in part directed towards craft and trade. Changing strategies, from elk to reindeer, and from trapping to hunting, are probably related to a development of land-use pressure, resource demands, and increasing commercialisation of wildlife exploitation. Hunting and trapping are nonetheless maintained at a high level during the Late Iron Age. In this perspective, the 6th-century cooling event has an unclear causal relation to the shift in wildlife exploitation. It should be noted, however, that the Migration Period societies of eastern Norway had a wide resource base available, which was regularly exploited, and could, if necessary, make up for shortfalls resulting from agricultural difficulties.

8.8.3. FARMING PRACTICE

As shown in Chapters 8.2-8.5, farming goes through significant changes during the 1st millennium AD. Barley gradually loses importance in favour of rye, with comparable percentages between the two in the Late Viking Age. Husbandry goes through a similar development. Cattle make up over 50 percent of the identified livestock species in the Migration Period but is gradually replaced by sheep/goat and pigs in the Late Iron Age. At an overall level, the impression is one of an emerging broader pastoral strategy in the Late Iron Age. However, at farm level, the development is the opposite. There are traces of increasing specialisation and fewer species in each context, both when it comes to livestock and grains. In addition, livestock herding and grain cultivation become more integrated, with increased evidence for grazing in cultivated fields. A probable contraction of the farming landscape is accompanied with more labour invested in a selected number of fields. To be outlined and discussed in this chapter, the development coincides with even more changes in the Iron Age farming communities.

Grain diversity is a prominent feature of the Late Roman Iron Age to the Merovingian Period, during which barley, rye, oats, spelt, and wheat have been identified at sites from around Lake Mjøsa. At the same time, barley holds a prominent position, accounting for over 50% of the identified grains. Rye only appears in smaller amounts during the beginning of this period, but steadily increases during the following centuries. It seems likely that rye was introduced and cultivated prior to the 6th century. However, the situation accelerates during the latter half of the Merovingian Period, when barley is decreasingly cultivated in favour of rye and oats. Crop diversity is reduced as the most temperature- and weather-sensitive of the species, wheat, temporarily disappears from the records. The development is reinforced in the Viking Age, during when spelt disappears from the record and farming seems to have been focused on barley, oats, and rye cultivation. The grain diversity during the 3rd to 7th centuries, coincide, in part, with considerable settlement and agricultural expansion. The Late Roman Iron Age and Migration Period

include more settlement and farming sites than any other Iron Age sub-period (cf. Chapter 8.1) and coincide with a general expansion phase in present-day Norway and Sweden around this time (cf. Chapter 3.3.3). This expansion is usually considered to have been spatially extensive and included areas that were later abandoned and re-cultivated only in modern times, but also included lands that, up to this day, have been left uncultivated (Myhre, 2002, pp. 127-159). In particular, the Late Roman Iron Age represents a considerable increase in the number of sites compared to the preceding centuries (cf. Figure 8.1). Admittedly, a large number are small and short-term sites, but several larger and more permanent sites are also established around this time (cf. Table 8.2). The settlement expansion is accompanied by traits of crop innovation and diversity, as well as intensified and altered strategies for wildlife exploitation (cf. Chapter 8.8.2). By several means, the Late Roman Iron Age and Migration Period is characterised by exploration and rapid development.

The number of sites decreases gradually towards the 7th century, after which it drops significantly. There is also a gradual decrease in the KDE-model for farming contexts from the 6th century and onwards (cf. Figure 8.12). This change is accompanied with a significant decrease in barley, less grain diversity, and an overall standardisation towards fewer and more robust species. Rye is thrifty and grows in nutrient-poor soils and cold climates (cf. Chapter 6.3), meaning that the species allowed for the cultivation of more marginal areas. In this, there seems to be a certain element of more precise adaptation and specialisation to local preconditions for farming. In a parallel process, closer integration of arable and pastoral farming may reflect an agricultural intensification, thus causing more interdependency between the two main farming practices. As discussed in Chapter 8.8.1, statistics and site evidence seem to reflect a profound reorganisation of settlement patterns and land-use strategies sometime around the mid-1st millennium AD. Consequently, the trajectories seem to be connected.

Unfortunately, the Gudbrandsdalen valley dataset is less coherent and less suitable for long-term analyses. In essence, it testifies to the presence of rye in pre-6th-century contexts, the overall predominance of barley, and a 3rd- to 7th-century settlement expansion. As such, the two regions seem to reflect the same overall development. However, some differences can be outlined as well, particularly in connection with frequency of identified pastoral and arable farming. Crops seem to have constituted a more important part of the overall farming strategies in the Lake Mjøsa region, while evidence for livestock and grazing has more often been documented in Gudbrandsdalen valley (cf. Table 8.3). Crop diversity is also a more characteristic feature for the Lake Mjøsa region, including wheat, which is considered temperature demanding (Chapter 6.5.1). In Gudbrandsdalen, farming seems to have been focused on robust species such as barley and rye. However, in spite of a general reduction in the number

of farming contexts, crop cultivation in Gudbrandsdalen valley seems to have been maintained in equal numbers, which may reflect intensified farming strategies on less-cultivated lands.

Presence of dung manure in prehistoric agricultural layers is usually interpreted as an indication of intensified farming techniques in which manure is used to enhance crop production, either through a rotational system involving husbandry and cropfields, or dung being collected and redeposited at the fields (Gjerpe, 2013, pp. 17-19; Myhre, 1985). Six Gudbrandsdalen valley contexts include evidence for manuring. Through soil micromorphology, four of these have been interpreted as evidence for crop cultivation, and two of these cases are supported by paleo-botanical analyses. Three contexts include both pastoral and arable indicators, while the fourth only includes evidence for crops. The contexts have been evenly dated to most of the Iron Age, with a slight maximum of three in the Late Roman Iron Age, and a minimum of zero in the Late Merovingian Period (Table 8.3). The last two contexts belong to the Fryasletta site in Fron and include no firm evidence for arable farming. The layers include byre and settlement waste and resemble a cropfield in appearance in the stratigraphic sequences, and were consequently interpreted as pastures enriched with dung through long time use (Macphail et al., 2016, pp. 310-311). Moreover, a large number of parasite eggs from *Ascaris* have been identified in the layers (Moltsen, 2016, pp. 287-288), something that indicates the presence of infected pigs (cf. Chapter 6.2.4). The area has been used for farming since the Late Bronze Age and is considered fertile, but is also prone to flooding and landslides, thus being more favourable for grasslands than acres. Barley was cultivated in the Bronze Age, but subsequent layers only include evidence for grasslands. The initial Bronze Age clearing in the area seems to have increased the risk for floods and landslides due to deforestation and was succeeded by several incidents covering the fields with colluvial and alluvial sediments (Cannell, 2016; Gundersen, 2016b; Loktu, 2016). This may have led to the introduction of enclosed grasslands, as discussed by Myhre (1985) and Ingvild Øye (2002, pp. 295, 337-341), in the 1st millennium AD, and perhaps as early as the Pre-Roman Iron Age. Dung is described as a valuable resource of limited availability and protected by medieval law (Øye, 2002, pp. 337-340). By letting livestock graze on spatially limited grasslands, manure could easily be collected and redeposited at nearby fields. This could also be part of a rotational system involving crops, grasslands, and fallowing.

A further two sites in Fron involve large numbers of parasite eggs in agricultural layers: context 301 at Brandrud IV, and 342 at Rolstad I, dated to the early Merovingian Period and Viking Age respectively. In both cases, the pollen analyses only testify to grazing and pastoral farming, but soil micromorphological analysis of 301 at Brandrud suggests it was also manured, bioworked, and cultivated for arable farming. The crop indicators are nonetheless weak. Soil micromorphology was not employed on layer 342 at Rolstad I, but it seems likely to have been manured as well, at least indirectly through grazing. Remnants

of *Ascaris* have been found at Brandrud IV, while the samples from Rolstad I include eggs from the *Trichuris* genus, which are usually associated with ruminants, canines, and rodents, but also affect cattle and pigs (Roepstorff & Pearman, 2005). Unfortunately, identification is not at species level and the likely host is therefore uncertain. Nonetheless, when piecing the data from the three sites together, cultivated grasslands seem probable, in combination with pig herding and/or cattle. At Brandrud IV, layer 301 might have been alternated with arable farming. Layer 208 at Øybrekka, dated to around the mid-1st millennium AD, has been identified as a manured and strongly bioworked agricultural soil layer, and include both pastoral and arable indicators (Macphail et al., 2016, p. 313; Moltsen, 2016, pp. 288-289). Similar to the evidence from layer 301 at Brandrud IV, it seems likely that the layer has been subject to alternating grazing and crops, thus suggesting strategy based on a close integration between pastoral and arable farming.

By and large, there is a strong livestock presence in the Gudbrandsdalen valley dataset. Unfortunately, the faunal record itself is rather limited and only provides evidence for cattle and pig, which nonetheless corresponds well with the finds of *Ascaris* and *Trichuris*. The settlement and agricultural dataset from the region is insufficient for long-term analysis and the overall development in farming strategies is uncertain. However, Andreas Sæbø (2020, pp. 47-48) has demonstrated that tools associated with agriculture and fodder harvesting became more common in the Late Iron Age in Gudbrandsdalen valley. In general, the Late Iron Age is characterised by the introduction of new farming tools which allowed for more efficient farming, but also testify to the ever-increasing importance of fodder harvesting (Myhre, 2002, pp. 197-199). Archaeological artefacts are somewhat inadequate for analysing farming strategies in all their complexity, and the general lack of well-investigated Late Iron Age sites leaves important gaps in our understanding of how they developed in the region after the 6th century. Nonetheless, the artefact finds may indicate a development similar to other parts of the country.

Traditional farming is often described as being dependent on a rotational system involving cultivation, fallowing, pasturing, and manuring in order to avoid soil depletion and prevent crop diseases (cf. Behre, 1981; Pedersen & Widgren, 2011). Rotational systems are, for the same reasons, also considered important in modern organic agriculture (Bjørnstad, 2012, pp. 101-102; Frøseth, 2004). In archaeology, particular focus has been paid to manuring, a practice which has been documented at an increasing number of Iron Age sites during the last several decades (Gjerpe, 2013; Gundersen, 2016d; Løken, 1988; Mjærum, 2020; Myhre, 1985). Handling of manure is usually explained in terms of necessity to avoid soil depletion, but also as a means to enhance the agricultural output through intensified cultivation and establishment of permanent cropfields.

A closer integration between pastoral and arable farming seems to have emerged during the 1st millennium BC that allowed for more systematic exploitation of manure (Hougen, 1947; Mjærum, 2020; Myhre, 2002, pp. 94-101; Pedersen & Widgren, 2011, pp. 50-51). The establishment of byres for winter stalling and the introduction of iron tools for fodder harvesting, such as iron sickles and leaf-knives, are considered technological preconditions for the systematic collecting and handling of manure. Accordingly, earlier farming strategies included both permanent fields, which were occasionally manured, and animal husbandry, but not as fully integrated parts in an overall agrarian strategy (Mjærum, 2020). During the Early Iron Age, a mixed farming economy was developed that prevented soil depletion and made higher farming outputs possible. A dynamic system, consisting of intensively cultivated and manured fields, extensive fields with alternating crops, fallowing, and grazing, allowed for a more systematic exploitation of the landscape and the cultivation of otherwise marginal and less fertile areas (Myhre, 2002, p. 129). As such, the emergence of a mixed farming economy can be understood as the structural precondition for the Late Roman Iron Age settlement and agricultural expansion in Gudbrandsdalen valley and the Lake Mjøsa region. Haymaking and stall-feeding became of profound importance, as illustrated by the introduction of the hay-rakes in the Late Roman Iron Age (Myhre, 2002, p. 148; Pedersen & Widgren, 2011, p. 53). Pedersen and Widgren (2011, pp. 56-57) argue that labour-intensive cultivation on small, manured infields made the expansive farming techniques of previous centuries unnecessary. Thus, the agricultural expansion of the first five centuries AD was not an expansion in the proper meaning of the word, but rather an intensification of cultivation in areas previously utilised more extensively. According to Pedersen and Widgren (2011) and Myhre (2002, pp. 197-199) the process was reinforced at the transition to the Late Iron Age and involved the development of new types of agricultural tools, such as the long-scythe, billhooks, and iron ard-shares. Thus, by systematically exploiting the outfields, more fodder could be accumulated for increasing numbers of livestock, which, in turn, allowed for more productive cropfields. Näsman (2009) interprets the development in Iron Age Denmark in similar terms, as an increasingly specialised and efficient agriculture with less areal demands for maintaining crop production. The development up to the 6th century is understood as one from extensive to intensive farming, whereas the development from the Late Iron Age and up to modern times is one of intensified cultivation and extensive pastoralism.

At least in Gudbrandsdalen valley, the archaeological evidence supports this assumption. Intensified pastoral and arable farming should be understood in relation to the evidence for manuring, as complementary components in an integrated agrarian strategy. It made possible not only a thorough exploitation of the landscape for agricultural purposes by carefully adapting to topographical preconditions, but also the systematic handling of animal manure. Indoor stalling has been documented at the Roman Iron Age and Migration Period farmsteads at Grytting I and Brandrud IV (Loktu & Gundersen, 2016; Villumsen, 2016a), and was probably a common feature at other farms in the valley as

well. In addition, enclosed grasslands in areas prone to flooding would make better use of animal manure also possible in summertime, thus maximising the farming potential in an otherwise marginal agrarian landscape.

The evidence from the Lake Mjøsa region is slightly more ambiguous, but nonetheless gives the impression of a similar process. As pointed out by Hagen (1984, pp. 58-60), manuring is not always necessary for arable farming to have taken place. Experimental farming has demonstrated that chalk-rich soils are less prone to exhaustion and can be cultivated for a considerable number of years before left to fallowing and re-cultivation. Holm (1995, p. 137) describes that late 18th-century farmers at Toten cultivated up to ten years in a row before manuring. Both regions, but the lowland countryside around northern Lake Mjøsa in particular, are characterised by chalk-rich sediments (Chapter 7.2). As such, there are geological conditions present which might have made permanent fields possible with little manuring involved. The low number of contexts with identified pastoral farming around Lake Mjøsa might also suggest that agriculture, in the first place, was less dependent on rotational farming and animal manure. Manure is only identified at four contexts in Lake Mjøsa region, divided on two sites (Ljøstad I and Dønnum III). However, this is also a source-critical question. Few contexts have been subject to soil micro-morphology, through which manure is usually identified. Both sites have been excavated in recent years, and more excavations in the area will likely result in more evidence for manuring. Permanent fields also do not rule out late autumn grazing after crop harvesting, which would enrich the soil with dung. Autumn grazing would not favour weeds in the same way as fallowing and grasslands and is therefore more difficult to identify in the paleo-botanical record. In the Lake Mjøsa region, all four contexts with identified manure are dated to the Pre-Roman Iron Age. Soil micro-morphology suggests plough-soil enriched with byre waste and dung, thus pointing in the direction of deliberate manuring of the fields.

Although a development towards a mixed farming economy seems to have been in the making, the general lack of Early Iron Age pastoral indicators in the region does not testify to a close integration between husbandry and crop cultivation at this point in prehistory. In the Lake Mjøsa region, most Early Iron Age agricultural contexts only include evidence for either arable or pastoral farming (cf. Figure 8.10). However, from the Late Roman Iron Age and onwards, there is a slight steady increase in contexts including evidence for both. The development is further enhanced in the Late Iron Age, when contexts only containing crop indicators disappears from the record. Although the number of contexts is rather small (n=20), giving individual numbers considerable weight in the analysis, the overall trend is nonetheless clear: Farming strategies seem to have changed from a system of separated grasslands and cropfields towards a rotational system with alternating sequences of grazing and crops. A major turn seems to have happened around the transition from the Early to the Late Iron Age, when contexts with

only arable indicators drop significantly, while contexts including both pastoral and arable indicators rapidly peak. At the same time, the percentage of cattle peaks in the faunal record (cf. Figure 8.20). These two trends can be understood as connected, as complementary parts of a general development towards a higher integration between pastoral and arable farming. Hence, the process is reminiscent of the development in Gudbrandsdalen valley but is less distinct in the lake Mjøsa region during the Early Iron Age. Due to better topographical preconditions, a mixed farming economy seems to have developed somewhat later around the lake, probably as a response to increasing land-use pressure. In Gudbrandsdalen valley, where cultivable lands are more spatially restricted in the first place, a close integration between pastoral and arable farming may have been necessary at an earlier stage in prehistory. However, the temporal difference between the two regions may also be due to the different qualities inherent in the datasets. The Gudbrandsdalen valley sites include more data per site and often also involve a broader range of scientific analyses (cf. Chapter 6.1.1). Further excavations of farming sites in the Lake Mjøsa region will likely change the overall impression, as illustrated by the identification of manure in Pre-Roman Iron Age contexts at Ljøstad I and Dønnum III, excavated in 2016 and 2017. For the moment, the development in the Lake Mjøsa region appears gradual and unfolding over time, whereas Gudbrandsdalen valley seems to have experienced more significant reorganisations of the farming landscape within shorter timespans. As will be further discussed in Chapter 9, the pattern may be due to site-specific environmental factors.

Cattle have traditionally been important as draft animals, and especially in prehistoric times as an important prerequisite for large-scale crop cultivation. Horses are more efficient than cattle as draft animals, but the question of when horses were introduced as working animals in agriculture is still up for debate (Lunden, 2002, p. 222; Øye, 2002, pp. 333-335). Some sources suggest it might have happened during the Viking Age and Middle Ages. However, horses only show up in minor numbers in the faunal records and do not appear to have played a major part in farming and cultivation in neither Gudbrandsdalen valley nor the Lake Mjøsa region in the Iron Age. When they do show up, it is at a limited selection of sites, in particular Åker, Ljøstad IV, and Valum, all associated with long-term continuity well beyond the 6th-century transition, but there are also single finds at Vidarshov and Guåker II. More intensified and systemised cultivation would require greater investments in labour and organisation, in which access to draft animals is essential. Judging from the high number of bones, cattle were highly-accessible and seem to have shaped a backbone in the farming strategies. Moreover, cattle provide a range of secondary dairy products, important for farm self-sufficiency. Horses were useful and efficient, but also expensive – at least in historical times (Lunden, 2002, p. 222). Alongside practical considerations, such as ploughing and access to dung, cattle are often attributed with status in Scandinavian Iron Age societies, through which wealth was expressed by the size of the cattle herds (Myhre, 2002, pp. 143-148; Näsman, 2009, pp. 100-102). Åker, Valum, and Ljøstad IV have repeatedly been emphasised in the

discussions in this thesis, either due to the number and types of finds, or due the mere character of the sites. Among contexts with a high percentage of cattle, these three sites distinguish themselves once more. In other words, the presence of horses and large numbers of cattle can be understood as expressions of status for an exclusive group of settlements and not as just farming requirements, although the two are by no means mutually exclusive. The economic output could be further enhanced by investments in horses and cattle.

From dominating the faunal record in the Early Iron Age, cattle decrease in percentage during the Late Iron Age. Cattle are also found at a decreasing number of sites. At first glance, it might contradict the overall agricultural development, where the development towards combined pastoral and arable farming is further enhanced. However, there is a clear distinction between the respective sites at this point. At well-documented and large sites, more specifically Åker and Valum, cattle bones further increase in number in the Late Iron Age, while sheep/goat, pig, and horse only experience minor increases. At other sites, the number of bones from cattle drops significantly, while considerably more bones from pigs in particular have been documented in the Viking Age. Sheep/goat remains are also better represented in this category. As shown in Figure 8.19, sheep/goat, cattle, and pig show up in around 70-80% of the contexts in the Early Iron Age. In the Viking Age, it has declined to approximately 40-60%. This means that species diversity, at site level, decreases from the Early to the Late Iron Age. This is a development that resembles the one for crops. In general, there seems to have been a prevalence for either cattle, sheep/goat, or pigs, rather than a broad and balanced combination of species at each site. Thus, at an overall level, the development seems to be of increasing diversity in the farming landscape. However, at a micro level, increasing specialisation is more evident. This is well-illustrated by the Late Iron Age farmstead excavated at Trogstad in Østre Toten, where a high number of animal bones have been recovered, but almost exclusively pigs have been identified at species level (cf. Loktu & Hovd, 2014). Other contexts, like a late Viking Age debris layer (context 266) at Guåker II in Stange, includes a high percentage of sheep/goat. Farm specialisation and overall diversity seem to be distinct features of Late Iron Age farming.

Generally speaking, livestock species have different qualities and are adapted to different circumstances. Sheep and goat are usually considered more suited than cattle to rough outfield terrains, while pigs are able to consume household waste that would otherwise be left unutilized. Pigs have traditionally also been kept at mountain summer pastures, where they can sustain themselves for some time (Lunden, 2002, p. 234; Øye, 2002, p. 355). Cattle are a source of a wide range of secondary products, but must be kept close to farms or mountains summer farms if the milk is to be properly utilised. Large herds therefore require good grasslands and access to large amounts of fodder in the immediate surroundings. For the

17th-19th centuries, an increased emphasis on sheep and goat has been explained in terms of population growth, land-use pressure, and colder climates (Lunden, 2002, pp. 214, 229). Sheep and goat are better adapted to utilising meagre outfield resources. In spite of rising numbers, cattle are reduced from 43% of the total amount of livestock in 1665, to 34% around 1809 (Figure 8.30). During the same period, horses and pigs remain at minor stable percentages, while sheep/goats increase from 49% to 57%. In addition, the number of cattle in proportion to crops drops significantly (Lunden, 2002, pp. 213-215), meaning that the yields increased as well, either by agrarian intensification or by clearing of more cultivable lands. A combination of intensified cultivation and extensive outfield pastoralism seems to have been a way of maintaining or even increasing farming outputs in times of less favourable climatic conditions. Failing harvests were nonetheless a regular feature during the 18th century, in particular after the Icelandic Laki eruption of 1783-84 (Bjørnstad, 2012, p. 107). Combined with growing population numbers, the situation caused subsistence crises which enhanced the social unrest and economic difficulties in Western Europe.

Figure 8.30: Husbandry in Norway in historical times according to official cadastres in 1665 (inner circle), 1723 (middle circle), and c. 1809 (outer circle) (numbers from Lunden, 2002, p. 211). The data suggests an increasing prevalence of sheep and goats, while pigs and horses remain in a minor, but stable, percentage during the 17th and 18th centuries.

When compared to the official cadastres from the 17-19th centuries, the percentage of pigs in the Iron Age faunal record appears rather high (cf. Figure 8.21 and Figure 8.30). However, the faunal record is by no means an accurate measure of past livestock composition as it is conditioned by several source-critical factors, including butchery practices. The human factor, and site representativeness, clearly affects the overall numbers. In well-documented contexts, such as the Åker debris layers, and the longhouses at Valum, the proportion of pigs is considerably lower. Moreover, pigs are only kept for meat and leather, in contrast to sheep, goat, and cattle, which were also favoured for milk and/or wool. Bones from large

mammals, such as cattle and pig, are also better preserved over time, and therefore probably overrepresented in waste deposits at settlement sites (cf. Chapter 6.4.1). Pigs probably made up 10-20% of Iron Age husbandry, and are considered to have increased in importance during the Viking Age and Middle Ages across central and northern Europe (Myhre, 2002, p. 196; Pedersen & Widgren, 2011, p. 67). According to Øye (2002, p. 360), pigs were particularly common in eastern Norway in the Middle Ages, but nonetheless in small numbers compared to other livestock. She refers to a late medieval diploma from a farm in Gudbrandsdalen which had a ratio between pigs and other livestock of just 1:20. Around year 1800, 5-6 pigs would be slaughtered each year at an average farm in Gudbrandsdalen and Hedmark, which is considered high, and five times as much as Setesdal and Telemark (Lunden, 2002, p. 233).

Kåre Lunden (2002, p. 233) argues that pigs are resource- and labour-intensive as they require cereals to grow fat and reach slaughtering weight. In historical times, some sources suggest 1-4 barrels of cereals per pig, alternatively one barrel of barley and two barrels of oats (Lunden, 2002, p. 235). The slaughter weight could reach 30 kg, of which 20 kg was edible meat, which correlates well with existing numbers for the Middle Ages (cf. Øye, 2002, p. 354). However, pigs were slow-growing, and in the 18th century usually slaughtered around 1.5-3 years old. Although mostly kept in pastures in the summer season, pigs would nonetheless require a great deal of fodder until slaughter weight was reached and consequently produce little meat relative to invested labour. In other words, pigs were considered a status marker in historical times and were more common in areas with a high degree of cereal cultivation, like the eastern and middle parts of the country (Lunden, 2002, pp. 233-235). Hence, pig herding does not appear to have been an obvious response to worsened climate conditions and failing crops, as crop cultivation and pig herding are to be understood as closely related. Perhaps for the same reasons, pigs are kept in low numbers during the 17th- and 18th-century cold period – in contrast to sheep and goat. The Late Iron Age increase in pig bones (cf. Figure 8.21) is therefore difficult to explain in light of subsistence difficulties. It is more likely associated with an increasing specialisation in farming strategies, and the ideological significance attributed to pork in Late Iron Age societies. Pedersen and Widgren (2011, pp. 67-68) stress the connection between elite residences and abundant evidence for pig consumption in Viking Age Sweden.

Neither DDA nor KDE-models give proof for substantial agrarian failure in the Lake Mjøsa region at the transition to the Late Iron Age. The exception is the summed probability plot in Figure 8.12, which displays a sharp 6th-century decline. However, the low number of dates in the model makes individual variations highly unreliable, and it should therefore not be given much weight in the interpretations. Similar sharp curves are regular features in the sum plot, with the 6th-century trough being far from the most dramatic. Gudbrandsdalen valley, on the other hand, does have an exceptional peak and trough in the summed

probability plot around the mid-1st millennium AD, but the decline begins already in the 5th century. Thus, if the summed probability plots were to be given great significance in the interpretations, climatic explanations could be ruled out, at least for the valley districts. It is also interesting that the agricultural expansion coincides with a 4th-century cooling, as suggested by temperature reconstructions in Büntgen et al. (2016), Sigl et al. (2015), Christiansen and Ljungqvist (2012), and Newfield (2018). Although not as dramatic and sudden as in the 6th century, there seems to be more variables at play than mere climate variations.

The overall pattern is one of a Late Roman Iron Age and Migration Period agricultural expansion, and a subsequent contraction centred on fewer more intensively-cultivated sites. The evidence points in the direction of an emerging mixed farming economy, with a closer integration between livestock herding and soil cultivation. Late Roman Iron Age and Migration Period farming is characterised by great diversity, whereas the Late Iron Age is distinguished by increasing specialisation. Thus, the development is one of exploration and innovation, followed by more efficient and connected farming practices able to utilise the landscape more systematically. Alongside this, an increasing mutual dependency within the farming communities is likely to have developed as the individual farms seem to have been more directed towards niche production than in the previous centuries.

A few regional differences can be identified. First and foremost, species diversity is more prominent in the Lake Mjøsa region, whereas Gudbrandsdalen valley seems to have developed a closer adaptation to local preconditions earlier on, including an emphasis on robust crop types, livestock, manured grasslands, and integrated pastoral and arable farming. These differences are likely due to the topographical limitations to agriculture in the valley districts, which may have made specialised exploitation necessary at an early stage.

8.9. Chapter conclusion

During the Iron Age, the farming communities around Lake Mjøsa and in the Gudbrandsdalen valley seem to have gone through significant changes in agricultural practices, wildlife exploitation, and land-use strategies. The overall development is one of increasing specialisation and interdependency, with the emergence of more specialised subsistence strategies and a mixed farming economy dependent on labour-intensive cultivation, in combination with livestock herding and systematic manuring. Species diversity at the Early Iron Age sites is, in the Late Iron Age, gradually replaced by fewer species at site level and less emphasis on cattle and barley. In the Late Iron Age, rye becomes a common cultivar, whereas temperature-demanding species more or less disappear from the records. The development can be

understood as traits of a better adaptation to local environmental preconditions, as species specialisation may have allowed for more efficient exploitation of areas otherwise less suited for agriculture. The character of the archaeological datasets makes long-term comparison between the two regions difficult. However, the results indicate that farmers in Gudbrandsdalen valley adapted to local environmental circumstances early on by focusing on livestock and less temperature-demanding crops, and by integrating pastoral and arable farming in order to maintain labour intensive cultivation on selected fields. As part of an emerging mixed farming economy, the flood-susceptible Fryasletta site may have been utilised as cultivated grassland as early as the Pre-Roman Iron Age.

The agricultural development is accompanied with considerable changes in site distribution and site chronologies. Numerous small sites characterise the Late Roman Iron Age record, which nonetheless steadily decrease in numbers during the rest of the Iron Age, whereas larger sites maintain a more stable presence. The number of settlement and agricultural sites decreases, alongside patterns of considerable site disruption, sometime around the mid-1st millennium AD. A considerable challenge is associated with identifying Late Iron Age buildings as the farmsteads of the period seem to be located either outside the Early Iron Age sites or at new points in the terrain. The exception is Åker, which is associated with a strong element of house plot continuity throughout the 1st millennium AD. The area surrounding Lake Mjøsa is nonetheless associated with a noticeable percentage of sites with patterns of continuity throughout the Early to Late Iron Age transition, especially in comparison with Gudbrandsdalen valley where site disruption is well documented at a significant number of agricultural and settlement sites. However, the general lack of large-scale excavations in the main settlement areas of Gudbrandsdalen valley causes considerable uncertainties regarding site representativeness. Although site abandonment is well documented, the scale of abandonment, and the societal context in which it occurred, is less well understood. In the Lake Mjøsa region, the evidence for Late Migration Period and Early Merovingian Period site disruption has an unclear temporal relation to the cooling event as the process seems to be rooted in Early Migration Period circumstances. The hiatus appears at different times at different sites, in some cases involving a Migration Period lacuna and Merovingian Period activity. However, the settlement data nonetheless indicates that the process was probably catalysed during the Merovingian Period. In consequence, a major reorganisation of the farming landscape seems to have taken place, which involved contracted but more labour-intensive strategies for cultivation and settlements situated around what later became historical farm plots.

It is not possible from the present record to determine to what degree the Iron Age societies of the Lake Mjøsa region and Gudbrandsdalen valley were dependent on agricultural outputs (research question A). The archaeo-botanical remains provide little information on the extent and importance of arable farming

compared to other resources and farming strategies, such as pastoral farming. Moreover, taphonomic issues, and the general lack of wildlife faunal remains, make any comparison between domesticated and undomesticated species difficult. However, it can be concluded that pastoral and arable farming became more tightly integrated during the Iron Age and that the Iron Age communities had access to considerable wildlife resource that were regularly exploited (research question B). In particular, wild deer seem to have been more systematically hunted from the Late Roman Iron Age and onwards in a process likely fuelled by emerging extensive trade and exchange networks with continental Europe. The process is characterised by changing hunting habitats and types of prey, from elk towards reindeer, and from labour demanding pitfall trapping systems in the forested and lower mountain region to short-term intensive high mountain snow-patch hunting. Changing habitats may be due to a combination of land-use pressure and new strategies emphasising efficient exploitation of large reindeer herds.

In Chapter 5.4, three possible risk drivers related to agricultural practices were emphasised: temperature-demanding crops, low crop diversity, and narrow subsistence strategies. None of these appear characteristic for the mid-1st millennium AD. On the contrary, the Migration Period is characterised by a broad subsistence strategy and high crop diversity. Admittedly, fewer crop types were cultivated in Gudbrandsdalen valley, but nonetheless species well-adapted to Nordic conditions (barley and rye). Temperature-demanding crops were utilised, at least in Lake Mjøsa region, but apparently played only a minor role in the overall farming strategies. During the Migration Period, a development takes place towards increasing efficiency and closer integration of pastoral and arable farming, a shift which becomes more profound in the Late Iron Age. Thus, specialised production, which potentially may contribute to societal vulnerability (cf. Chapter 5.4), is something that manifests itself more clearly after the cooling event. In other words, the overall changes in farming strategies have an unclear relation to climatic factors (research question C). The exception is the subsequent increase in rye cultivation, an absence of wheat, and marked decline in barley cultivation. Rye seems to have been cultivated in limited numbers before the 6th century and may have gained importance due to experiences of widespread crop failure. Furthermore, the statistical analysis provides some indications of an enforced settlement and agricultural development during the Merovingian Period. However, the issue of causality remains unsolved. A statistical analysis of archaeological datasets provides few answers on its own. On the contrary, it functions as a starting point for a qualitative analysis in which the evidence is further explored. In the next chapter, I will attempt to demonstrate different levels of agricultural vulnerability in the two regions in order to substantiate whether a strong and prolonged cooling could have caused widespread crop failure.

To conclude, it is not possible to properly examine research question A within the scope of this thesis as the source material is too fragmented and biased. However, it appears that a wide array of resources

could be utilised if necessary. Regarding research question B, profound changes can be identified in the settlement and agricultural records, including patterns of site disruption. However, the degree of change around the 6th century varies with the data at hand. On the question of adaptational strategies related to climate cooling (research question C), the picture is even more ambiguous as a few probable measures can be identified, whereas the main development appears embedded in preceding developments. Moreover, as will be discussed in the synthesis in Chapter 10, rye may not have been a particularly reliable adaptational strategy.

9 CASE STUDIES

In the previous chapter, I presented and discussed evidence for a long-term development in the Iron Age societies in the Lake Mjøsa region and Gudbrandsdalen valley, towards increasing specialisation in subsistence strategies and a reorganisation of the cultural landscape. Certain elements, such as an increase in rye cultivation, site disruption, and reduction in the mere number of sites, appear particularly connected to the Merovingian Period, although not in a clear-cut way. The causes appear rooted in Early Iron Age dynamics, but the process seems to have been reinforced sometime around or after the 6th-century transition. In this, there is a certain element of overall societal continuity. Thus, the impression is not one of societal collapse, but perhaps ongoing societal processes fuelled by major environmental events. However, a possible connection between environmental and societal events remains to be substantiated. In order to bridge concurrency and causation, a qualitative approach is needed, one which takes into account both environmental and archaeological datasets. In this chapter, I will explore the aspect of crop vulnerability and use it as an analytical tool for assessing the possible impact of the cooling event on Iron Age societies, and whether major differences can be identified between the research areas (research question D and E).

Figure 9.1: Mean monthly precipitation (mm) in Fron and Hedmarken, based on local weather data for 1961-90. Source: MET.

The analysis is focused on two selected local areas: Fron in Gudbrandsdalen (Chapter 9.1), and Hedmarken in the Lake Mjøsa region (Chapter 9.2). Both areas are considered the best agricultural landscapes in each respective region (cf. Chapter 7). They are also the most extensively excavated areas in both regions. The climatic conditions are similar and only differ slightly in terms of precipitation and

winter temperatures (Figure 9.1 and Figure 9.2). Fron is colder in wintertime and experiences 13% less precipitation than Hedmarken during May, June, July, and August. Fron also experiences slightly colder autumns. However, the temperature conditions are quite similar during the summer season, especially when recalculated to corresponding altitudes (Figure 9.2). In spite of the colder winters in Fron, springtime starts around the same time in both areas, including a more or less identical temperatures from March to July. Due to higher altitudes, Fron still experiences a slightly shorter growing season.

Figure 9.2: The annual temperature variations at Hundorp in Fron and Hamar in Hedmarken, based on local weather data for 1961-90. For comparison, the values are recalculated to an equal altitude of 700 masl, by using a standard lapse rate of 0.6°C per 100 masl. Source: MET.

The analysis will follow a three-step approach (Chapter 6.5). First, by employing GIS-modelling, I will analyse the effect of temperature cooling on the length of the growing season. Thereafter, also by GIS-modelling, I will use growing degree days (GDD) as a way of identifying local crop thresholds during different cooling scenarios. The maps will be combined with archaeological evidence for site disruption and site continuity, as listed in Table 8.2. In the third step, pollen diagrams from both areas will be presented and discussed up against other published vegetation records from the respective regions. The following aspects will be of particular interest:

- Are there any differences between the areas when it comes to crop vulnerability to cooling?
- Can the model output be substantiated by vegetation data?
- Is there any connection between site continuity and local crop thresholds?

As discussed in Chapter 2.3, the 6th-century cooling event is often described as the coldest during the last 2000 years, but exactly how cold it was is still a matter of debate. It all comes down to method, which

scientific proxies that are used, and spatial resolutions. In Chapter 2.3.2, I have presented two temperature curves for AD 450-660, extracted from two continuous reconstructions for the last two millennia based on Northern Hemisphere proxies, which suggest a maximum cooling during the AD 536-550 period of approximately 2-3 °C, and an average temperature decline of 1.7-2.1 °C (with reference to the 1961-90 average). However, considerable differences can be expected at both local and regional scales and within the growing season. The exact temperature decline for eastern Norway, and its local impact, is almost impossible to model with current proxies. Any attempt of modelling its effect on agriculture must therefore be based on an idealised approach. As outlined in Chapter 6.5.1, I have used measured weather data from both areas for 1961-90 as baseline values, and subsequently recalculated them according to an idealised temperature loss of 1, 2, and 3 °C, and a lapse rate of minus 0.6 °C for every 100 masl. 5°C is used to delimitate the length of the growing season, while the GDD requirements are based on individual calculations for each area and determined by taking into consideration local values for latitude and precipitation. Building on the temperature data in Chapter 2.3.2, the minus 1°C models can be considered a minimum and recurrent scenario during the AD 536-550 period, the minus 2°C maps a likely event occurring sometimes during this period, and the minus 3°C maps a maximum cooling incident that may have occurred once or twice.

Barley is the dominant crop species in the Iron Age in both areas (Chapter 8.3), and the GDD calculations are therefore based on the requirements for barley. The maps are combined with cultivation class datasets from NIBIO in order to visualise the extent of the present-day farming landscape. In addition, the GDD maps are combined with a dataset visualising mean solar radiation throughout the growing season. Further clarifications on the method and the input variables are given in Chapter 6.5.1.

The three-step approach leads up to the main discussion in Chapter 9.3, where I will attempt to conclude on the possible effects of the 6th-century cooling on Gudbrandsdalen valley and Lake Mjøsa region. Following the same procedures, additional GDD maps have been made for Ullensaker in Akershus, coastal Vestfold, and Høgsfjorden in Rogaland in order to demonstrate regional variability and the potential of GDD modelling (Chapter 9.4). The three areas include three well-known archaeological sites of considerable importance in Norwegian Iron Age archaeology: Raknehaugen at Ullensaker, Borre in coastal Vestfold, and Forsand in Høgsfjorden. All three sites are also widely used points of reference for the debate on the 6th-century transition as expressions of either societal continuity or crisis (cf. Løken, 1988; Myhre, 2002, pp. 170-184; Näsman, 1988a, p. 241; Price & Gräslund, 2015, pp. 121-122; Solheim & Iversen, 2019). Thus, including them in the study will provide useful supplements for the case studies and contribute to a wider cultural-historical context for the interpretations.

9.1. Fron

19 settlement and agricultural sites have been excavated in Fron, of which most are located in the southern half of the area (Figure 9.3). Pollen coring has been conducted in a bog at Ulberg (Chapter 9.1.3). The Grytting and Brandrud sites include Iron Age longhouses, while the rest is a mixture of agricultural sites and diverse settlement traces. Most sites belong to the Late Roman Iron Age and Early Migration Period, but some also include evidence for Late Iron Age activity. However, the late Merovingian Period and Early Viking Age only include a few sites and remain under-researched.

Figure 9.3: Excavated settlement and agricultural sites in Fron, including the location of the pollen coring at Ulberg. Hundorp is the name of both the historical farm and the modern community centre. Illustration by author.

Fron is usually considered to have the best agricultural lands in Gudbrandsdalen valley (Chapter 7.3), but topography nonetheless represents significant constraints to cultivation. The steep valley sides are prone to erosion (cf. Sommerfeldt, 1972), but also limit the spatial extension of the cultivated field. The upper part is affected by cold mountain winds, and north-facing slopes are shadowed and forested. Most cultivated lands are therefore situated from below 700 masl down to the valley bottom at approximately 200 masl (cf. Figure 6.17 in Chapter 6.5.1). Low mountain fields also exist but are almost exclusively utilised for grass production (Chapter 7.3).

The best lands for barley cultivation are situated between 200-350 masl according to NIBIO's soil classification system. Much of the cultivated lands between 350-700 masl are assessed as less suited or not suited for barley cultivation, due to a combination of steep valley sides, risk of draught, and late ripening, and are utilised for grasses in present-day agriculture. Lower mountain fields at >700 masl are considered not suited for crops in the cultivation class dataset. Most excavated archaeological sites in the area are located between 200-350 masl, but site distribution does not offer an accurate picture of the prehistoric settlement pattern (Chapter 7.3.2). Therefore, it does not reflect the extension of the prehistoric farming landscape as such, but only a part of it. It nonetheless confirms that the valley bottom and lower valley sides were settled and utilised for agriculture.

9.1.1. GROWING SEASON

During the 1961-90 period, the average length of the growing season was 169 days at 200 masl, and down to 134 days at around 700 masl (see Figure 6.17 in Chapter 6.5.1). Most cultivated lands were situated within a >140 days growing season, while most of the best lands were within >160 days.

Scenario	Start of growing season	Length of growing season (days)	Decrease (days)	Decrease (percentage)
200 masl				
1961-90	24 th April	169	-	-
-1°C	28 th April	158	11	7 %
-2°C	3 rd May	146	23	14 %
-3°C	8 th May	134	35	21 %
700 masl				
1961-90	8 th May	134	-	-
-1°C	12 th May	123	11	8 %
-2°C	17 th May	112	22	16 %
-3°C	22 nd May	101	33	25 %

Table 9.1: Average numbers for the growing season in Fron during different temperature scenarios.

With a temperature reduction of 1°C, the growing season would become approximately 10 days shorter (Figure 9.4). In the valley bottom (200 masl), the start of the growing season is moved from 24th April to 28th April, while at 700 masl it changes from 8th May to 12th May. Most of the cultivated lands still have a growing season of 140 days or more, with up to 160 days in the lower valley sides. Most archaeological sites are situated within the latter temperature zone.

Figure 9.4: Average length of the growing season in Fron with a temperature reduction of 1°C. The dashed line marks an altitude of 700 masl. Illustration by author.

With a temperature drop of 2°C, the growing season would be between 112 and 146 days (200/700 masl), thus being shortened by approximately 20 days with reference to the 1961-90 average (Figure 9.5). Depending on the altitude, the growing season starts between 3rd and 17th May. The temperature conditions in the lower valley sides now appear similar to those at altitudes up to approximately 600 masl during the 1961-90 average, which probably means that margins are rapidly decreasing and agriculture becomes increasingly vulnerable to weather anomalies. If not outright crop failure, reduced yields are a probable outcome. In the higher valley sides, agriculture would probably struggle during a minus 2°C scenario.

Figure 9.5: Average length of the growing season in Fron with a temperature reduction of 2°C. Illustration by author.

Figure 9.6: Average length of the growing season in Fron with a temperature reduction of 3°C. Illustration by author.

At a minus 3°C scenario (Figure 9.6), the season is down to 101 to 134 days, with the growing season starting between the 8th to the 22th May. The growing season becomes up to 35 days shorter than during the 1961-90 average, which is a reduction of more than 20%. In the valley bottom, the temperature conditions become comparable to those at 700 masl during the 1961-90 period. Thus, all cultivated areas would probably become susceptible to crop failure as margins would likely be critically low. At higher altitudes, the conditions are likely to become unsuitable for crops. In other words, all the agricultural sites excavated in the area would have faced considerable difficulties during a minus 3°C scenario.

9.1.2. GROWING DEGREE DAYS

In Fron, depending on early or late sowing, the threshold values for barley cultivation range between 1220 and 1300 GDD. During the 1961-90 period, this corresponds to temperature conditions found at altitudes around 700 to 800 masl, which is slightly above the extension of the main agricultural area (see Figure 6.19 in Chapter 6.5.1).

During a minus 1°C scenario, the threshold values are found at altitudes around 550 to 620 masl, which means that high altitude farms would probably face difficulties if they relied on barley cultivation (Figure 9.7). However, solar radiation offers a few important nuances. Due to a more favourable angle, south-facing slopes generate more heat from the sun than north-facing slopes and also experience more sun-hours. Thus, high altitude farms south of the Lågen River are more vulnerable to a 1°C cooling than high altitude farms north of the river. As demonstrated in the maps, there are more high-altitude farms north of the river, likely positioned facing south to capitalise on the optimal conditions for accumulation of sunlight.

In general, the threshold values during the minus 1°C scenario correspond well with the extent of the present-day cultivated landscape, and an average cooling of 1°C would probably represent little risk for agriculture. Small margins appear between 450 to 550 masl, which is mainly above the lands with most potential for barley cultivation and corresponds to areas deemed more vulnerable to climatic variations by NIBIO.

Figure 9.7: Thresholds for barley cultivation in Fron with a temperature reduction of 1°C, combined with a hillshade model visualising mean solar radiation at mid-day during the growing season. The dots mark medium and large sites (≥ 5 C14-dates) classified according to the evidence for site continuity/disruption presented in Chapter 8.1, Table 8.2, and Figure 8.2. Øybrekka in the north-west does not include sufficient C14-dates but involves clear evidence for Early Merovingian Period site abandonment due to floods. It is therefore included in the overview. Illustration by author.

The excavated Iron Age sites in the area, of which several are clearly agricultural, are all situated within the low-risk zone during the minus 1°C scenario. Of these, a few include Migration Period evidence for crop production: Øybrekka (barley), Odenrud II (barley and rye), Brandrud IV (barley and rye), and Grytting I (barley). Grytting I, Brandrud I, and Brandrud IV involve Migration Period longhouses and can be understood as regular farmsteads (Loktu & Gundersen, 2016; Villumsen, 2016a). All medium and large sites (≥ 5 C14 dates) include evidence for site abandonment or temporary disruption around the mid-1st millennium AD, including the three farmsteads, but would probably have been unaffected during a minus 1°C scenario. The site chronologies extend into the Early Merovingian Period but lack evidence for sustained activity further on in the period, thus being seemingly abandoned during the course of the 6th century.

Figure 9.8: Thresholds for barley cultivation in Fron with a temperature reduction of 2°C. Illustration by author.

The situation changes considerably during a minus 2°C scenario, when the threshold values are found at altitudes around 400-450 masl (Figure 9.8). This is still above the best agricultural lands, but nonetheless encompasses much of the present-day farming landscape. Farms at altitudes above 450 masl would experience reduced growth and cereals are not likely to mature. As with the previous map, better conditions are expected in slopes with greater sun accumulation, and crop failure is more likely in shadowy areas. However, the minus 2°C scenario demonstrates significantly decreased margins for crop cultivation in Fron as the low-risk zone disappears in its entirety. Even the best cultivable lands would experience small margins, meaning that weather phenomena, sowing time, soil conditions, topography, and farming practices in general become more important for the final outcome. If the cooling prevails over several years, reduced outputs, or even incidents of crop failure, are likely to become a recurrent phenomenon and marginal farms would likely struggle to maintain crop production.

In any case, a minus 2°C scenario does not seem to be synonymous with an all-encompassing agricultural crisis, as well-situated farms at altitudes below 400 masl, especially in south-facing slopes, would probably be able to maintain some level of production even if the cooling prevails. However, both at individual farms and in the local community at whole, yields would probably be lower than usual. In a prehistoric

setting, vulnerable groups would likely be vulnerable to famine, making other subsistence resources more important to be able to uphold a secure food-base.

All archaeological sites are experiencing decreasing margins in this model but are nonetheless still below the threshold values. However, fields close to the bog-coring site at Ulberg might have faced more difficulties than the rest as the site not only borders on the threshold values but also gains less sunlight than the areas north of the river. Failing crops might have occurred at Ulberg during a minus 2°C scenario.

Figure 9.9: Thresholds for barley cultivation in Fron with a temperature reduction of 3°C. Illustration by author.

The situation worsens during a minus 3°C scenario, when almost all of the cultivated lands experience temperature conditions equal to the minimum requirements for barley cultivation (<280 masl), or become situated within the high risk zone (Figure 9.9). High altitude farms are likely to experience widespread crop failure. At lower altitudes, temperature conditions are similar to those at 700 masl during the 1961-90 average. The lack of temperature margins, even in the best farmlands, means that agriculture is very susceptible to crop failure in general. The human factor becomes increasingly important, as late sowing has the potential of worsening the situation. Minor weather anomalies can also become decisive for the final outcome. Solar radiance would have contributed to reduced risk in certain areas, but the margins

would nonetheless have been dramatically low even for the most ideally situated farms. If the cooling prevails, widespread and recurrent crop failure would be likely to happen.

The archaeological sites are mostly experiencing temperatures within the threshold values for barley cultivation, but the margins are extremely narrow. Some sites, like Øybrekka in the north-west, are situated at the transition to the high-risk zone. Fryasletta in the south-east lies at the intersection between the threshold values and decreasing margins, and is, as such, slightly better off than the other sites in the area. Crop failure is nonetheless a likely scenario here as well, as even minor weather incidents have the potential of becoming critical for cultivation. However, crop production has not been identified at the Fryasletta site during the period in question, which, on the contrary, seems to have been used for grasslands and pastures during the 1st millennium AD (cf. Chapter 8.8.3). Thus, whether the cooling would have affected farming practice at the Fryasletta site is a matter of discussion.

To sum up, a minus 1°C scenario does not represent any major threat for crop cultivation in Fron, but is probably in line with normal year-to-year variations. The situation changes around minus 2°C, when the low-risk zone, with more than 20 % margins to the threshold values, is no longer appearing in the model. However, good yields can still be expected in the best farming areas, where for instance soil quality and solar radiance offer optimised conditions. A minus 2°C scenario nonetheless represents considerable difficulties for high altitude and otherwise marginal farms that may be based on barley cultivation, such as south of the Lågen River. For society at whole, yields would probably be lower than usual, and extreme weather phenomena are likely to cause incidents of crop failure. Other subsistence resources would probably become more important to uphold a secure food-base. An important threshold seems to lie between the minus 2 to 3°C scenarios, when the temperature margins for crop cultivation is rapidly disappearing from the farming landscape. A minus 3°C scenario has the potential of being disastrous for even the best situated farms as there are no more margins to accommodate for weather phenomena and human error.

The archaeological sites are mostly situated within the lower part of the terrain, thus having favourable margins to rely on in times of climate cooling. A minus 1°C scenario would probably not affect the sites significantly and they would likely also be able to produce crops during a minus 2°C scenario. However, a minus 3°C would probably be critical, even in low-lying south-facing slopes.

9.1.3. VEGETATION RECORDS

The pollen coring was conducted in a bog near the Ulberg farm in Fron in 2019 (see Figure 9.3). Ulberg is situated at 275 masl south of the Lågen River at the outskirts of the main settlement area. To a certain extent, it can be described as marginal and limited by topography. The area south of the river is shadowed and forested and mostly includes smaller farms. Ulberg is surrounded by forests on three sides, including steep valley sides in the east and the south and a small hill to the northeast. It nonetheless accumulates a lot of sunlight during the growing season, especially from the southeast, as it is situated where the valley curves in a northerly direction, thus creating a more exposed position than the surrounding areas. However, due to steep terrains in the southwest, it is deprived of the afternoon sunlight that the south-facing slopes north of Lågen River benefit from. It also has easy access to water due to natural inflow from the valley sides, thus reducing the risk for draught. According to NIBIO's cultivation class dataset, the fields have medium or high potential for barley cultivation. The best plots can even be utilised for late wheat. During a minus 1°C scenario, Ulberg is located within a low-risk zone, but would probably experience considerable difficulties during a minus 2°C scenario (see previous chapter). A minus 3°C scenario has the potential of becoming critical, especially when considering that Ulberg is situated at the shadowy part of the Lågen River.

Both coring and pollen analyses have been conducted by palynologist Helge I. Høeg. The description of the diagram (Figure 9.10 and Figure 9.11) given in this chapter follows the main findings presented in his report. The full report is enclosed in the appendix but is written in Norwegian. The coring was conducted to a depth of approximately 5 metres and pollen samples were initially analysed for every 10 cm. A few samples were dispatched early on for radiocarbon dating to delimitate the 1st millennium AD. A tight sequence of pollen analyses was thereafter conducted on the 1st millennium, and more samples sent for radiocarbon dating in an attempt to identify the approximate level for the 6th century. A total of 6 samples were radiocarbon dated.

The first piece of evidence for crop cultivation at Ulberg appears approximately around 4200 BP, which corresponds to the Neolithic Period. Barley cultivation is identified throughout most of the Bronze Age, including one find of wheat. However, there is a significant lacuna in crop indicators during the 1st millennium BC (zone 7B). The situation prevailed into the 2nd century AD, when farming indicators show up once more (zone 7C). Zone 7C encompass much of the Roman Iron Age and includes not only single finds of barley and oats, but also a slight increase in apophytes. Apophytes are found in the natural environment, but are favoured by human activity, in particular agriculture (cf. Chapter 6.2.2). The finds are nonetheless few, and there is little evidence for major changes in land-use strategies during this period.

Substantial evidence for crop production is first identifiable in zone 7D, which roughly corresponds to the Migration Period. The evidence includes pollen from barley, oats, rye, and wheat, but also traces of deforestation and pastures. Pine is declining, while birch and alder rapidly increase. Barley seems to have been preferred. A high occurrence of charcoal dust is visible around the same time as deforestation increases and testifies to increased human activity in the area, likely the clearing of new agricultural lands. There is also an increase in grass-like species (graminids) and apophytes, in particular grass (*Poaceae*), sorrel (*Rumex*), and absinthe (*Artemisia*), which are associated with pastoral farming (see Chapter 6.2). The evidence is interesting, as it coincides in time with the general settlement and agricultural expansion documented through several excavations in the surrounding area. Thus, Ulberg falls within an overall pattern of new land clearances and rapid settlement development.

In addition, the data from Ulberg strengthens the argument that rye was cultivated in Fron prior to the 6th century. However, the excavation data includes no evidence for oats and wheat. As such, the pollen diagram presents a picture of more species diversity than what was indicated in the statistical analysis (cf. Chapter 8.3). All four species seem to have been present in Fron, and even cultivated at marginal sites like Ulberg. From the middle to the upper part of zone 7D, there are traces of reforestation, a process which is accompanied by fewer finds of charcoal dust.

Zone 7E, which more or less corresponds to the Merovingian Period, is lacking in crop indicators. Apophytes, graminids, and charcoal suggest that the area was still occupied and utilised by humans, but the impact on vegetation is clearly reduced. Towards the end of zone 7E, evidence for barley is once more identified, but in low numbers. An increase in dwarf shrubs might indicate long-term fallowing of previously cultivated fields.

Ulberg, Sør-Fron, Gudbrandsdalen valley

Percentage diagram

Figure 9.10: Pollen diagram from bog coring at Ulberg in Fron, Gudbrandsdalen, developed by Helge I. Høeg. The complete diagram goes down to approximately 5 metres. For better temporal resolution, only the last 2000 years (1.4 metres) have been included in this figure. Zone 7D roughly corresponds to the Migration Period, and zone 7E to the Merovingian Period.

Ulberg, Sør-Fron, Gudbrandsdalen

Influx diagram

H. I. Høeg, 2/10-2020.

Figure 9.11: Simplified influx diagram for Ulberg, developed by Helge I. Høeg.

Agriculture once more picks up in zone 8A, which includes less evidence for dwarf shrubs, more pastoral indicators, and finds of barley, rye, and wheat. Barley is still the dominant crop species, and wheat and rye only appear in minor numbers. Oats have not been identified. The renewed agrarian activity in the area does not seem to have affected the forests and there is less charcoal dust than in zone 7E. Human activity and agriculture do not equal the evidence in zone 7D (which stands out in the overall diagram).

Arguably, crop production came to a temporary halt at Ulberg during the Merovingian Period. The change from zones 7D to 7E is of profound character and distinguish between one period with a great deal of farming evidence and another with only weak anthropogenic evidence. The low representation of cultivated species, graminids, and apophytes stands in contrast to the preceding period, which has a high representation of all three categories. The development from 7D to 7E appears sudden.

Figure 9.12: Calibrated dates for the C14-samples included in Figure 9.10 (Ramsey, 2009a; Reimer et al., 2020).

The C14 dates are presented in Figure 9.12 and situate the development sometime during the latter half of the 6th and the first half of the 7th centuries, with a 1 sigma calibration (68.3%) to 591-644 AD. As such, it is not directly aligned with the 6th-century cooling, but too much attention should not be paid to singular C14 dates. Minor incursions of for instance roots can easily affect the chronology. Moreover, it all depends on the precise level of the sampling, which in this case was focused on the last identified cereal, which, quite interestingly, is rye. Barley and wheat disappear from the record slightly before, alongside a

general decline in graminids, apophytes, and other anthropogenic indicators. Within reasonable doubt, the development from zone 7D to 7E appears related to the 6th century.

Unfortunately, no other pollen diagrams exist from Fron, and it is therefore not possible to compare the Ulberg diagram with results from other locations in the same area. However, a number of pollen diagrams have been published for locations in Lesja and Dovre in the northern part of Gudbrandsdalen valley (Gunnarsdóttir, 1999; Gunnarsdóttir & Høeg, 1996; Høeg, 2011).

Gunnarsdóttir (1999) has analysed three cores from between 470-550 masl in Lesja. Her results include some late Neolithic anthropogenic indicators, but it is only in the Bronze Age that more firm farming evidence can be identified, although the evidence is still weak. Small-scale pastoral and arable farming seem to have been present at this time. At one site, continuous grain cultivation was identified from around 400 BC and up to the Middle Ages. Significant deforestation and farming is visible in the Lesja records from around AD 200, which represents a clear break with previous land-use patterns. Of the identified cereals, barley is the most common. Starting in the Roman Iron Age, agriculture begins to leave a more significant mark on the landscape, thus representing a phase of agricultural expansion. This more or less coincides with the evidence from Fron, although it lacks the Merovingian Period hiatus.

The importance of local preconditions is well-illustrated by the lower mountain valley of Haverdalen (1050 masl) in Dovre, which usually is considered above the thresholds for cereal cultivation (Høeg, 2011; Stene, 2015). Surprisingly, the pollen record includes evidence for barley cultivation for a short period in the beginning of the Pre-Roman Iron Age, and then all the way from the Late Roman Iron Age and up to modern times. Until the end of the Viking Age, there is also evidence for oats and some rye. In total, pastoral farming has been identified from around 1000 BC, and cereal cultivation from around AD 200 (Høeg, 2011). There is a notable lack of clear abandonment phases within the pollen record, but there is a short hiatus in crops in the middle part of the diagram which might be related to the 6th century. Grain cultivation has been identified from the Merovingian Period up to the Middle Ages at Ølstadsetri in Dalsida in Lesja at an altitude of 820 masl, including barley, oats, rye, and even a few occurrences of wheat (Gunnarsdóttir, 1999, p. 140; Gunnarsdóttir & Høeg, 1996). The finds support the results from Haverdalen and suggest favourable conditions for high altitude farming in northern Gudbrandsdalen. The northern half of the valley is considered dry and prone to draught, and farming in historical times was largely dependent on watering and irrigation (cf. Chapter 7.3). Evaporation is lower at higher altitudes than in the valley bottom, which might have created more favourable conditions for crop cultivation in the lower mountain areas (Gunnarsdóttir, 1999, p. 140). However, it should be stressed that the dating of

the respective zone at Ølstadsetri to the Merovingian Period is uncertain as it is interpolated and not confirmed by radiocarbon analysis (Gunnarsdottir & Høeg, 1996, p. 25). The results from Ølstadsetri are nonetheless supported by vegetation data from other high altitude sites in Lesja and Dovre which suggest that the Late Iron Age represents a period of considerable increase in human activity in the lower mountains, including grazing and haymaking (Gunnarsdottir & Høeg, 1996, p. 44).

The results from northern Gudbrandsdalen are in agreement with the Ulberg record at a few important points. The farming evidence during the Neolithic and Bronze Age is limited and indicates small-scale activity rather than fully settled agricultural landscapes. Large-scale agricultural expansion is first visible in the pollen records around the Roman Iron Age and Migration Period. In northern Gudbrandsdalen, this marks the beginning of a more or less continuous phase of farming activity up to modern times. In the lower mountains, another phase of expansion seems to have taken place in the Late Iron Age. The latter event is contrasted by the Ulberg record, which indicates fallowing and a temporary halt to cereal cultivation until the Viking Age. However, the northern Gudbrandsdalen diagrams have varying levels of chronological precision, including an often-low number of radiocarbon dates. This means that the exact timing of the agricultural expansion is somewhat unclear and the interpretations might be altered with more targeted investigations in the future. Considering the possibilities of a long-lasting Northern Hemisphere cooling covering most of the 6th and perhaps the 7th century (cf. Chapter 2.3.1), it seems likely that the Late Iron Age expansion in northern Gudbrandsdalen is connected to more favourable climatic conditions from the 8th century and onwards. The Ulberg record specifically targets the 6th century and therefore provides data with better chronological resolution for the period in question. The results are therefore not necessarily comparable in every aspect, especially not when it comes short-term vegetation changes around the mid-1st millennium AD. It is nonetheless interesting that the Ulberg record indicates less activity in the Viking Age than in the Migration Period, which is at odds with the overall results from northern Gudbrandsdalen, no matter the uncertainties regarding dating precision in the latter diagrams. In other words, it appears as though Fron may have experienced more profound and long-term consequences of the cooling event than other parts of the valley. Whether this represents an outright crisis and/or successful adaptational strategies remains to be discussed in the following chapters.

9.2. Hedmarken

79 settlement and agricultural sites have been excavated in Hedmarken, of which there is a clear majority in the south-eastern area around Hamar. Valum, Vidarshov, Åker, Englaug V, Lille Børke, Ljøstad IV, Vevla II, and Sveen include identified longhouses, mostly from the Early Iron Age, but also a few Late Iron Age buildings (Åker and Englaug V). There is a peak in both the number of sites and longhouses around the

Late Roman Iron Age and Early Migration Period, followed by a steady decline towards the end of the Iron Age.

Figure 9.13: Excavated settlement and agricultural sites in Hedmarken and surrounding areas, including the location of the pollen diagram for Narmo. Illustration by author.

Hedmarken is often considered one of the best agricultural regions in eastern Norway due to excellent soil conditions, few topographical restraints, and good temperature conditions (Chapter 7.2). The cultivated landscape goes up to approximately 500 masl, and down to Lake Mjøsa at around 120 masl. According to NIBIO's classifications, most of the agricultural lands in Hedmarken are well suited for barley cultivation. However, due to late ripening, there is a slightly higher frequency of average farmlands at higher altitudes up to 500 masl. In general, there is a low risk for draught in Hedmarken.

The site distribution in the area is quite good and encompasses much of the present-day farming landscape. This is particularly true for the eastern part, where sites are located close to the outermost fringes of the modern main cultivated area. Sites are more scattered in the western part but nonetheless have a good spatial distribution.

9.2.1. GROWING SEASON

During the 1961-90 period, the average length of the growing season was up to 175 days by the lakeshore and down to 149 days at around 500 masl (see Figure 6.18 in Chapter 6.5.1). Most cultivated lands were situated within a >160 days growing season but there were also a significant number of fields within a >170 days growing season. With a temperature reduction of 1°C, the growing season becomes approximately 10 days shorter (Figure 9.14). By the lakeshore, the start of the growing season is moved from 24th to 29th April, while at 500 masl it changes from 4th to 8th May.

Scenario	Start of growing season	Length of growing season (days)	Decrease (days)	Decrease (percentage)
120 masl				
1961-90	24 th April	175	-	-
-1°C	29 th April	164	11	6 %
-2°C	3 rd May	153	22	13 %
-3°C	7 th May	141	34	20 %
500 masl				
1961-90	4 th May	149	-	-
-1°C	8 th May	137	12	8 %
-2°C	13 th May	126	23	15 %
-3°C	17 th May	115	34	23 %

Table 9.2: Average numbers for the growing season in Hedmarken during different temperature scenarios.

With a temperature drop of 2°C, the growing season is between 126 to 153 days long (500/120 masl), thus being shortened by slightly more than 20 days with reference to the 1961-90 average (Figure 9.15). Depending on the altitude, the growing season starts between 3rd and 13th May. In a minus 3°C scenario, the season is cut down to under 115 to 141 days, with the growing season starting between the 7th and 17th May (Figure 9.16). The growing season becomes 34 days shorter than during the 1961-90 average, which is a decrease of more than 20%. The temperature conditions at different altitudes are comparable to those in Fron. However, as the agricultural lands are generally situated at lower altitudes, the growing season is still somewhat longer in Hedmarken. Even with a minus 3°C scenario, considerable parts of the farming landscape are still situated within a growing season of 131-140 days.

Figure 9.14: Average length of the growing season in Hedmarken with a temperature reduction of 1°C. The dashed line marks an altitude of 500 masl. Illustration by author.

Figure 9.15: Average length of the growing season in Hedmarken with a temperature reduction of 2°C. Illustration by author.

Figure 9.16: Average length of the growing season in Hedmarken with a temperature reduction of 3°C. Illustration by author.

9.2.2. GROWING DEGREE DAYS

In Hedmarken, depending on when sowing is conducted, the threshold values for barley cultivation range between 1236 and 1316 GDD, which is slightly more than Fron. During the 1961-90 period, this corresponds to the temperature conditions at altitudes around 700 to 800 masl, which is well above the main agricultural zone below 500 masl (see Figure 6.20 in Chapter 6.5.1). The landscape in Hedmarken is relatively flat, with wide stretching fields and gradually sloping hillsides. Because of this, solar radiation offers more or less equal conditions throughout the area.

During a minus 1°C scenario, the threshold values are found at altitudes around 550 to 630 masl (Figure 9.17), which is comparable to the results for the same altitudes in Fron. However, as almost no fields are located at these altitudes in Hedmarken, a minus 1°C scenario has almost no visible effects on cultivation in the GDD model. Most of the farming landscape is situated within a low-risk zone with $\geq 20\%$ margins to the threshold values, which includes heights up to 330 masl. Of the archaeological sites, only Kirkebyenga II experiences a significant decrease in temperature margins. The site is mainly associated with pastoral farming, but pollen analyses indicate that crops were cultivated close to the site in the Roman Iron Age and Migration Period (Gustavsen & Berg-Hansen, 2008). The site is situated at the uppermost outskirts of 335

the main agricultural area, in a landscape characterised by reforested pastures, rocky terrain, and increasing slopes. Cultivation at these altitudes would be vulnerable to temperature anomalies, especially in times of prolonged cooling.

Figure 9.17: Thresholds for barley cultivation in Hedmarken with a temperature reduction of 1°C. The dots mark medium and large sites (≥ 5 C14-dates) classified according to the evidence for site continuity/disruption presented in Chapter 8.1, Table 8.2, and Figure 8.2. Illustration by author.

During a minus 2°C scenario (Figure 9.18), the threshold values are found around 400 to 450 masl. Thus, the cooling critically affects a limited number of high-altitude fields. Some fields even experience conditions below the required temperature sum. At Kirkebyenga II, crop failure would be a likely outcome. Several fields within the threshold values (>400 masl) and the high-risk zone (>450 masl) are considered average for barley cultivation in NIBIO's soil classification dataset (due to late ripening). Most of the farming landscape now experiences smaller margins with a temperature sum only <20% higher than the threshold values. At the lowest altitudes, a low-risk zone with $\geq 20\%$ margins is still visible. This means that margins are clearly decreasing, but for most areas there are nonetheless temperature conditions above the required GDD. Heat-demanding species, like wheat, would probably struggle throughout the area, while barley and rye are more likely to mature. Weather phenomena, sowing time, soil conditions, topography, and farming practices in general become important for the final outcome. If

the cooling prevails over several years, reduced outputs, or even incidents of crop failure, are likely to become a recurrent, but not necessarily widespread, phenomenon. While a few high-altitude farms would probably struggle, low-altitude farms are less likely to become critically affected and good yields can still be expected. Thus, in the Hedmarken area, an average temperature cooling of 2°C has the potential of having an uneven effect on agriculture – disastrous for some farms, whereas some other farms will probably be able to maintain normal production.

Most archaeological sites experience <20% margins to the threshold values, but a few sites are also located within the low-risk zone. This is particularly true for Åker, but also Valum would experience favourable conditions compared to most other farms.

Figure 9.18: Thresholds for barley cultivation in Hedmarken with a temperature reduction of 2°C. Illustration by author.

Figure 9.19: Thresholds for barley cultivation in Hedmarken with a temperature reduction of 3 °C. Illustration by author.

The minus 3°C scenario offers a profoundly altered situation. The threshold values are now situated around 230 to 290 masl, thus encompassing much of the farming landscape, including the pollen coring site at Narmo. A considerable number of high-altitude fields lie within a high-risk zone. This means that widespread crop failure is a likely result above this limit, but there is high susceptibility also down to around 200 masl. As such, the results from Hedmarken resemble those from Fron. However, there is one significant difference. As Hedmarken is situated at lower altitudes, a number of farms, including Åker, still have some margins (<20 %) to count on before temperatures may become critical. According to the GDD model, low altitude farms (<200 masl) are vulnerable to worsened weather conditions during a minus 3°C scenario but are still able to experience ripened yields if sowing is not delayed and weather is somewhat favourable. Sites with evidence for site continuity during the Early to Late Iron Age transition are situated either within or close to the small margins zone. The model demonstrates that transitional sites are located in areas with slightly better temperature conditions than in the surrounding terrains and might therefore have been somewhat better off during a prolonged cooling. However, a few sites within or close to this zone also provide evidence for site disruption (Sveen, Skapal, Børstad, Vold I, Snarud, and Lille Børke). This will be further discussed in Chapter 9.3.2.

To sum up, the required temperature sums at different altitudes are comparable to those in Fron, but the Hedmarken farms are generally situated at lower heights. Because of this, the Hedmarken area is more resilient to climate cooling than Fron. A minus 2°C scenario would probably only critically affect a limited number of high-altitude farms. Even during a minus 3°C scenario, some farms, including Åker, would be able to experience ripened crops, although the yields are likely to be considerably smaller. A minus 3°C scenario would nonetheless be critical for a large number of farms situated above 200 masl. Even in instances where the cereals reach maturity, one might also expect lowered outputs due to lower temperatures. Due to low margins, unexpected events, like weather anomalies, can cause devastating results for agriculture even in the best situated areas. Although conditions appear better than in Fron, a temperature reduction of more than 2°C has the potential of becoming critical for many farms even in the Hedmarken area. Even without critical weather incidents occurring, reduced crop outcome is a likely result throughout the area during a minus 2°C scenario, and famine could potentially happen among vulnerable groups dependent on crop outputs and with few alternative subsistence resources. However, for widespread famine to occur, temperature conditions closer to the minus 3°C than minus 2°C scenario are likely required.

9.2.3. VEGETATION RECORDS

During his doctoral research, Pilø (2005) initiated bog coring for pollen analysis in Hedmarken, which was undertaken by Høeg. Two pollen diagrams were developed and published in his thesis, one for Narmo and the other for Grytting, both in Hamar municipality. The Grytting diagram has a low chronological resolution for the last three millennia, and therefore contributes very limited data for the Iron Age, except for confirming occasional presence of oats, barley, and rye. In contrast, the Narmo diagram includes regular counts for every ten cm, thus providing important long-term vegetation data. Moreover, one of the radiocarbon dates in the diagram effectually situates important changes in the farming history sometime around the Early to Late Iron Age transition, most likely in the Migration Period (Figure 9.20). I have therefore included the Narmo diagram in this discussion. The diagram is reproduced in Figure 9.21, and the following description is based on the outlines given in Pilø (2005, pp. 520-529).

Figure 9.20: Calibrated age of radiocarbon sample from 135 cm depth in the Narmo bog core.

The Narmo bog is situated at 234 masl on a south-facing slope in the upper part of the main agricultural area, which corresponds to the positioning of the threshold values during a minus 3°C scenario. During a minus 2°C scenario, it is situated in the middle of the small margins zone. The potential for cereals appears to be good. The risk of draught is low, and most fields are assessed as having high potential for both barley and even wheat cultivation in NIBIO's cultivation class system. During the 1961-90 period, an average growing season lasted 161-170 days, and, as demonstrated by the GDD models, Narmo has considerable temperature margins to rely on in case of climate cooling. However, it is still located outside the most heavily and wide-stretching cultivated areas in the south and east, in a landscape more defined by patchy fields and pockets of outfields.

The earliest evidence for cereal cultivation appears at around 460 cm depth (barley) and reappears with low but steady frequencies up to 370 cm, including a few singular finds of oats. This phase approximately corresponds to the Neolithic period, and is followed by a long period with almost no evidence for cereals. A few finds of barley, wheat, and weeds give some proof for farming activity, but not of any substantial or lasting character. Deforestation is nonetheless evident from 260 cm and upwards, which corresponds to the Late Bronze Age and the Early Iron Age, but there is little charcoal in the samples.

Narmo, Hamar, Hedmarken

Percentage diagram

H. I. Høeg, 22/1-2021.

Figure 9.21: Pollen diagram from bog coring at Narmo in Hedmarken, Lake Mjøsa region, developed by Helge I. Høeg and first published in Pilø (2005). The diagram has been redesigned by Høeg. Reproduced with kind permission from Pilø and Høeg.

Narmo, Hamar, Hedmark

Influx diagram

Figure 9.22: Simplified influx diagram for Narmo, developed by Helge I. Høeg and first published in Pilø (2005). Redesigned by Høeg, and reproduced with kind permission from Pilø and Høeg.

Substantial evidence for crops is only identifiable from 135 cm and upwards, which marks the beginning of zone 8. The level is radiocarbon dated to 1595 ± 75 BP, which roughly corresponds to the Migration Period (Figure 9.20). The low measurement precision makes it difficult to pinpoint the exact time of the increase in farming activity, which is further complicated by the Migration Period calibration plateau. However, farming took on a more profound character in the Narmo area around the mid-1st millennia AD. The first identified cereals in zone 8 are oats and barley followed by wheat and rye. The earliest part of zone 8 is nonetheless characterised by limited evidence for cultivation, which becomes more profound only at 110-120 cm with a significant increase in barley and rye. The development is accompanied with a sharp increase in grasses, apophytes, and other weeds. During the first half of zone 8, the forest is open, and farming seems to have made a profound mark on the landscape. The second half is characterised by reforestation, a temporary end to cereal cultivation, and a decrease in grasses, apophytes, and other weeds. This is interpreted by Pilø (2005, p. 529) as an abandonment phase related to the medieval Black Death (dashed line in Figure 9.21).

In sum, the Narmo diagram stands in contrast to the pollen analytical evidence from Fron. It includes no evidence for Early Iron Age cultivation, and significant agricultural expansion is identifiable for the first time in the Late Iron Age. Thus, there is no clear evidence for dramatic effects from the 6th-century cooling. On the contrary, the diagram indicates increasing land-use pressure sometime around the mid-1st millennium AD, which is further enhanced during the Late Iron Age. The only significant abandonment phase concerns the late medieval period. However, one might argue that the chronological resolution is too low to be able to identify short term changes in the pollen distribution. A mere 14 samples have been analysed for a total of 1500 years. Moreover, the lack of Early Iron Age crops in the diagram makes it more difficult to trace the possible effects of climate cooling on agriculture. On the basis of the Narmo diagram itself, it cannot be ruled out that the 6th-century cooling had an effect on agriculture in Hedmarken and the evidence for Merovingian Period farming is also weak. However, at an overall level, the Late Iron Age represents a period of agricultural expansion and deforestation, thus creating a landscape more profoundly shaped by human activity than in the past millennia. Compared to the evidence for a possible Black Death lacuna, the 6th century is strikingly inconspicuous in the Narmo diagram. If the cooling event had an effect on local agriculture, it must have been short term and perhaps not as critical as in Fron.

The results from the Narmo diagram are in accordance with the excavation data from the above-mentioned site of Kirkebyenga II. The site lacks evidence for Early Merovingian Period activity, but is reoccupied in the Late Merovingian Period (Gustavsen & Berg-Hansen, 2008). Despite some indications of

temporary site disruption, analyses of four series of pollen samples indicate more open vegetation and agricultural expansion during the Late Iron Age, including rye cultivation (Gustavsen & Berg-Hansen, 2008). There seems to have been a combination of pastoral and arable activity at the site with an emphasis on grasslands and pastures. If site abandonment did occur, it was of temporary character and with few long-term effects.

From the other side of the lake, pollen coring has been conducted by Høeg close to the agricultural site of Øverbymarka in Gjølvik (published in Holm, 1995). Most farms in the area are situated between 350-550 masl, which is considerably higher than in Hedmarken. For the development of the pollen diagram, counts were made for every 5 cm down to 170 cm, with the Neolithic to the Early Middle Ages situated between 87.5-37.5 cm. Radiocarbon dates have been made for the 87.5, 65, 50, and 32.5 cm samples, with the 50 cm sample resulting in 1515±75 BP (T-10528, 2 sigma cal 414-655 AD). Thus, the chronological resolution is quite good for the period in question, although the low measurement precision makes the exact position of the 6th century in the diagram somewhat unclear. The first weak evidence for agriculture turns up during the Neolithic but becomes more continuous in the Bronze Age and Pre-Roman Iron Age. In the Early Iron Age, there is a steady increase in weeds and the forest becomes more open, thus suggesting more pastoral activity. Cereal cultivation is only identifiable from the Middle Ages and onwards. The process of deforestation and pastoralism seems to have continued in the Late Iron Age, with more evidence for weeds, charcoal, and herbs, and fewer trees. Although cereals have not been identified in this period, the evidence has been interpreted as indicators of cereal cultivation close by (cf. Holm, 1995, pp. 96-97). There are no clear signs of abandonment phases, except from a small decline in anthropogenic indicators around 25-20 cm, which is interpreted as related to the Black Death (Holm, 1995, p. 97). Once more, the Black Death seem to be of more profound character in the Lake Mjøsa region than the 6th-century cooling.

The three sites of Narmo, Kirkebyenga II, and Øverbymarka seem to reflect similar trajectories, with weak anthropogenic indicators up to the Early Iron Age, and stronger evidence for farming activity in the Late Iron Age and Middle Ages. All three sites also have weak Early Iron Age evidence for cereal cultivation in common, but nonetheless traces of deforestation and increased human activity. The results reflect increasing land-use pressure, resulting in a gradual transformation from outfields to farming during the Iron Age. Both the Early and Late Iron Age seem to represent important stages in the farming expansion in the region.

9.3. Social impact

The GIS-models presented in Chapter 9.1 and 9.2 demonstrate that climate cooling can be critical for cultivation in both Hedmarken and Fron. With a mean temperature decrease of minus 3°C (with reference to the 1961-90 average), the growing seasons are shortened by approximately 20% in both areas. The temperature conditions are quite similar in summertime in both areas at corresponding altitudes. However, the models also indicate that Fron may be more vulnerable to climate cooling than Hedmarken, as the former has more cultivable lands at higher altitudes where the growing season is shorter.

However, in both areas, a minor cooling of 1°C is not likely to affect agriculture significantly. A temperature decline of 2-3°C seems to be required for agriculture to become critically affected. Farmers must accommodate to inter-annual temperature variations on a regular basis, which restricts crop cultivation within certain boundaries. Areas close to these thresholds are likely to experience poor harvests on a regular basis, and are therefore more often utilised for grasses than crops. Overall temperature conditions prior to AD 536 were quite stable according to the reconstructions provided by Christiansen and Ljungqvist (2012), and slightly below the 1961-90 reference period. In general, the mean annual temperatures often varied with $\pm 0.5-1^\circ\text{C}$ from one year to the next during AD 450-660 period (see Figure 2.1 in Chapter 2.3.2). At local levels, one might expect occasionally larger variations. Against this background, it is not likely that a minus 1°C cooling would cause widespread crop failure in any case. Admittedly, crop cultivating farms close to the local temperature thresholds would be susceptible to poor harvests, but in this case the crisis would be more of a social phenomenon, restricted to vulnerable and probably marginalised groups, rather than society at whole. The scenario would also be a recurrent one, thus restricting cultivation at these altitudes. The minus 2 and 3°C scenarios are fundamentally different as they have the potential to affect most farms either critically or with reduced outputs, thus paving the way for widespread famine and crisis. However, as will be discussed further in this chapter, important differences can also be detected within the study areas during these two scenarios.

Moreover, there are several source-critical perspectives to take into account before firm conclusions can be made. Among these are topography, changes in precipitation, weather anomalies, cereal types, and the spatial extent of cereal cultivation. Expansive cultivation results in more sites with low temperature margins, thus potentially increasing societal vulnerability to cooling. Finally, the exact temperature conditions during the 6th century remains uncertain, in particular on local and regional levels. The minus 3°C model is used here as a worst-case scenario, but the actual temperature decline might have been colder or warmer than minus 3°C, depending on the area in question. In other words, the models visualise

regional differences in climatic preconditions for agriculture and not necessarily the impact of the 6th-century cooling in and of itself. In this chapter, I will discuss the results of the GIS modelling in light of these perspectives and attempt to conclude whether the suggested impact is substantiated by the archaeological and paleo-botanical records or not. For comparison, three more case-studies are presented in Chapter 9.4, which demonstrate the importance of regionality when discussing possible effects of the 6th-century cooling on Iron Age Scandinavia. These studies are not combined with archaeological datasets but will be discussed up against relevant published literature concerning these areas.

9.3.1. FRON

Drawing on the archaeological record, GDD modelling, and the pollen record from Ulberg, it seems reasonable to suggest that the 6th-century cooling did have a profound effect on local agriculture and land-use strategies in Fron. Important in this respect is also the possibility of altered precipitation. Fron typically experiences low amounts of precipitation, which, on one hand, reduces the required GDD, but on the other hand also makes the area prone to draught in dry years. An increase in precipitation would also increase the required GDD, thus enhancing the effect of the cooling by contributing to smaller margins. In either case, increasing or decreasing amounts of rainfall during the 6th-century cooling would have the potential of worsening the situation. These challenges are also present in modern-day agriculture in the area, which has resulted in a predominance for grasses at higher altitudes (Chapter 7.3.1). In the Iron Age, the main cultivated area would probably have also been at lower altitudes in order to reduce the risk of unripened yields.

However, the archaeological and paleo-botanical evidence testify to increasing land-use pressure in the Roman Iron Age and Migration Period, a shift which might have led to more farms and fields being established in marginal areas. This process could have led to increased vulnerability to climate variations in general, especially to an unprecedented, prolonged cooling event. At the same time, the excavation results seem to point in the direction of husbandry predominance and intensively cultivated crop fields in low-lying areas, conditions which are likely in a farming landscape heavily restricted by topographical factors. Even the fertile Fryasletta plains only includes evidence for pastoral farming in the 1st millennium AD and might have resembled something similar to cultivated grasslands. In any case, a minus 2°C scenario has the potential of becoming critical even for low-lying areas, in particular on the shadowed valley sides south of Lågen River. For well-situated farms, one might expect at least lowered yields and a higher frequency of unripened cereals than usual, outcomes which would probably have affected long-term strategies. A turn towards more robust species and pastoral farming would be favourable during such circumstances.

Figure 9.23: Documentation of continuous sequences of floods, landslides, and agriculture at the Fryasletta site in Fron in 2012. Most flood events also include colluvial sediments from landslides. Layer 8 has been water-saturated and probably occurred during a major flood event (Macphail et al., 2016). Photo: Lise Loktu, Museum of Cultural History.

However, the exact temperature decline is associated with uncertainty. Moreover, floods and landslides represent additional risk factors in this area. Floods are a recurrent phenomenon in the valley, some of which have been extreme and damaging to the local population. The flood history is particularly well-documented at the Fryasletta site (Loktu, 2016), where two major events are identified around 350-200 BC and 50 BC (Figure 9.23). Similar events have been documented around the same time at several other sites in the area, including one more major flood in the Early Merovingian Period (Gundersen, 2016b; Villumsen, 2016b). All three identified Iron Age farms at Grytting and Brandrud are located in areas prone to flooding. In spite of floods being a recurrent and well-known phenomenon, the settlement expansion took place in areas that only a few generations earlier had been affected by these major events, of which there must have been some kind of collective memory.

Moreover, flooding is also a potential danger in the valley sides as loose sediments and several minor mountain streams have often led to heavy landslides during snow melting and heavy rainfalls. During the 1789 extreme flood event, both factors emerged with ruinous effect (Gundersen, 2016b; Sommerfeldt, 1972). The incident is often described as one of the worst natural catastrophes in Norwegian history and had, due to topographical factors, a particularly devastating impact on Lesja and Fron. The flood was probably the result of a combination of several climatic factors (Roald, 2013; Sommerfeldt, 1972; Østmoe, 1985, pp. 62-71). The 1784 Laki eruption in Iceland caused several years of cold summers and bad harvests in northern Europe, including much snow and ice accumulation in the mountain areas. A particularly cold winter in 1788/89 caused deep frost in the Gudbrandsdalen valley, which was followed by a late spring and a sudden hot summer. This led to rapid melting and the ground was quickly saturated as the deep frost prevented natural drainage. Extreme weather struck in July, bringing with it heavy rainfalls and extreme heat. The situation quickly developed into an extreme flood in Lågen River and numerous landslides along the valley sides (Sommerfeldt, 1972).

The 2011-2012 excavations in Fron testify to similar incidents throughout prehistory (Cannell, 2016; Gundersen, 2016b). Most of the sites in Figure 9.7 to Figure 9.9 are associated with site disruption in the Early Merovingian Period, all of which include evidence for floods and/or landslides from this period. It is reasonable to expect that the abandonment of sites is due to the Merovingian Period major flood event, but the evidence is not always that clear. At Grytting I, the last longhouse (House V) is abandoned sometime during the 6th century, and alluvial and colluvial layers from around the same time were clearly visible on the site and the neighbouring site of Rolstad I (Villumsen, 2016a, 2016b). However, the abandonment seems to have been planned. The excavations documented that the wooden posts in the Grytting longhouse had been removed prior to the flood, which means that the farmstead had already been abandoned. At Brandrud I, the longhouse was burnt down after being cleared (Loktu & Gundersen, 2016). The longhouse was well preserved, including half-burnt remains of birch bark that had probably belonged to the roof cover. Even so, almost no artefacts or household waste was recovered. After the abandonment of Brandrud I and IV towards the end of the Migration Period, the previous plots became cultivated for some time, until floods and landslides put a temporary end to the agricultural activity (Loktu & Gundersen, 2016). The continuous cultivation into the Early Merovingian Period should perhaps be understood as attempts of maintaining agricultural production in areas becoming increasingly vulnerable to environmental factors at the same time as the farmsteads themselves were abandoned.

Atle Nesje et al. (2016) have analysed the prehistoric floods up against the overall climate conditions at the time. It is important to note that the first centuries AD represent a period with relatively few events of this kind, as well as including high summer temperatures which are later followed by increasing flood

rates and periods of lower summer temperatures. In other words, the settlement and agricultural expansion documented at sites like Brandrud IV, Grytting I, and Øybrekka takes place during favourable climatic conditions, but these sites became increasingly vulnerable to climate deterioration later on. The fields close to the riverbed are fertile and rich in fluvial soils that are easy to cultivate, but prone to flooding from both the Lågen River and tributary streams along the valley sides (Figure 9.24). Decreasing exposure to floods and landslides may have caused less awareness of its potential danger, leading to new land-use strategies that strengthened agricultural production in a short-term perspective but enhanced societal vulnerability over time. Temperatures are once more increasing during the Migration Period, which corresponds with increasing agricultural and human activity at Ulberg. Next to Brandrud IV, a second farm plot is established at Brandrud I. The warm period lasts until it is terminated by the 6th-century cooling, while the Early Merovingian Period flood event seems to have happened shortly thereafter. The flood is likely to have been conditioned by the climatic circumstances in the preceding period. Low summer temperatures and high winter precipitation resulted in expanding glaciers and increased snow accumulation in the mountain areas (Nesje et al., 2016, pp. 88-90). Combined with rising summer temperatures around AD 600, a greater risk for major flood events might have occurred, particularly if combined with heavy rainfalls in summertime. As such, the conditions at the time may have been similar to those emerging before the 1789 extreme flood event (Gundersen, 2016b, p. 101).

Figure 9.24: Flooding of the excavation site Grytting I in 2013, with Lågen River in the background and tributary river Lauvåa to the left. Lauvåa broke away from its usual course and deposited large amounts of colluvial sediments at the excavation site, following directions identical to those documented for prehistoric floods at the site. Photo: Stig Grytting (previously published in Gundersen, 2016b).

In other words, there seems to have been a complex sequence of settlement expansions in Fron, climate change, and periods of increasing flood risk. As demonstrated in the GDD analysis, the 6th-century cooling alone may have posed a serious threat to local farming, but not necessarily equally over the entire area. Ulberg seems to have gone through a period of fallowing, whereas the evidence for continued cultivation at the Brandrud sites suggests that other farms might have been somewhat better off. Overall, a prolonged cooling would probably have forced the adoption of necessary changes in farming strategies and land-use patterns; the abandonment of the three farmsteads is a possible result of these changes. Whether the farms were simply abandoned, and the fields upheld by others, or moved to another location, remains uncertain.

Figure 9.25: Location of the Brandrud and Grytting Iron Age farms in the present-day farming landscape in Fron. The photo in Figure 9.24 is taken from the fields just below the location of medieval Grytting. Illustration by author.

The lower valley sides would offer somewhat better climatic conditions than alongside the riverbed due to a more favourable angle towards the sun, as well as a somewhat longer growing season. This latter factor is not well reflected in the GIS-models, where the land alongside the riverbed is attributed with the highest temperature sums. However, this also demonstrates the idealised character of the models and the need to contextualise the results. Due to the steep and high valley slopes south of the river, which

result in little sunlight in the valley bottom during wintertime, the areas in which the Iron Age farms were situated experience both colder and longer winters than the lower valley sides above, thus causing delayed springs (Chapter 7.3.1). In addition, these areas are prone to flooding and therefore vulnerable to changing environmental conditions (Gundersen, 2016b). According to local traditional accounts, the two medieval Grytting farms were located somewhat higher in the terrain, on a terrace overlooking the excavation site of Grytting I (Figure 9.25). Whether this also represents a relocation of the Iron Age farm is uncertain, but the historical Grytting farms held ownership over the area where the Early Iron Age farm has been uncovered (Hovdhaugen, 1973, pp. 264-273). Regardless of any direct connection between the Early Iron Age and medieval farms, a farm situated at the medieval location would have had a greater chance of survival if conditions became critical. This may have been a deciding factor for the abandonment of Grytting I and the subsequent positioning of the medieval farm.

A combination of climate cooling and increased flood risk thus seems to have made cultivation difficult to uphold in vulnerable areas in Fron. While Ulberg is re-cultivated in the Viking Age, much of the area along the riverbed remained uncultivated up to historical times. The Breivegen area, where Brandrud I and IV are located, is described as outfield pastures as late as in 18th-century sources (Hovdhaugen, 1973, p. 108). Whether the situation became crucial also in more favourable areas depends on the exact level of cooling. As demonstrated in the GDD models, a minus 2°C situation is not synonymous with crop failure in the lower valley sides. Smaller margins, and probably smaller yields, are nonetheless likely to have made an impact on farming strategies.

The danger for landslides is equally high along the valley sides as in the valley bottom, and several of the most prominent and wealthy farms in the area were seriously damaged during the 1789 extreme flood event (Gundersen, 2016b; Sommerfeldt, 1972). The evidence from Fryasletta testifies to several major landslides throughout prehistory, and cultivation itself is often a contributing factor. Due to deforestation and the removal of vegetation cover close to streams and rivers, the water has more impact on the sediments and results in more frequent and magnified avalanches (Roald, 2013, p. 21). For probably the same reasons, the thickest colluvial layers at Fryasletta postdate the introduction of agriculture in the area (Figure 9.23). In Fron, thick sediment covers and little visible bedrock in the valley slopes significantly increase the risk for landslides (Gundersen, 2016b, p. 100; Sommerfeldt, 1972, p. 18). The agricultural expansion in the Late Roman Iron Age and Migration Period is likely to have increased the flood risk in the area as deforestation could result in even minor events having major consequences. Furthermore, a prolonged cooling increases the risk for bad harvests in general, meaning that even well-situated farms could be critically affected in the long run. Taking these factors into consideration, it is likely that both

marginal and wealthy farms became affected by 6th-century environmental events, either by cooling and/or by floods and landslides.

It is more difficult to assess whether a 6th-century crisis in Fron caused any major changes in their subsistence strategies. The archaeological data in Gudbrandsdalen valley is too limited when it comes to the Late Iron Age, but of the few sites that have been excavated, there is a predominance of pastoral indicators (Table 8.3 in Chapter 8.2). Only barley and rye have been identified at the excavation sites, of which Grytting I includes a significant number of barley grains but no finds of rye. At Brandrud IV, barley dominates as well, but a single find of grain from rye suggests that it may have constituted a minor part of the local cultivars. However, single finds are more prone to errors and one should be careful about attributing much significance to this find alone. On the other hand, the pollen record from Ulberg strengthens the impression of rye cultivation in Fron in the Migration Period. In general, the Ulberg record testifies to greater species diversity than the excavation records and suggests that the local community had access to a wide selection of crop species. With the evidence pieced together, barley apparently constituted the backbone of their grain cultivation and the pollen record from Ulberg does not testify to any major changes after the abandonment phase. Barley remains the most favoured species, while both wheat and rye show up in minor numbers, with the only significant difference being the absence of oats. Thus, the development in cereal cultivation is reminiscent of the one in the Lake Mjøsa region, with fewer species and an apparent specialisation of farming strategies.

It is nonetheless important to note that cultivation seems to have been less emphasised when agriculture picked up again, which may suggest less human activity compared to the Migration Period or altered strategies directed towards more pastoral farming. During the same period, there is evidence in northern Gudbrandsdalen for another phase of agricultural expansion in the lower mountain region, including the possible establishment of permanent mountain summer farms (Chapter 9.1.3). The mountain summer farms are closely associated with livestock herding and the need of effectively utilising the outfield pastures while maintaining dairy production. As stressed in Chapter 9.1.3, the development in the northern part of the valley is apparently somewhat different from the one in Fron, especially due to the lack of clear 6th-century abandonment phases. When all the evidence is pieced together, from the pollen records in the northern part of the valley, via the excavation record in Gudbrandsdalen in general, to the evidence for failing harvests and site abandonment in Fron, there seems to have been an increasing prevalence for extensive livestock herding in the Late Iron Age, likely in combination with intensified cultivation on a more limited number of selected fields. However, as discussed in Chapter 8.8.3, this would also be a continuation of the development that had begun to unfold during the Roman Iron Age

and Migration Period. Rather than being a game-changer, it seems that the 6th-century cooling enforced an ongoing development by entrenching the agricultural strategies within more robust boundaries.

9.3.2. HEDMARKEN

There is less evidence for a significant societal impact from the cooling event in Hedmarken than in Fron. 32% of the medium and large sites in Hedmarken are associated with site continuity (cf. Table 9.3 and Table 9.4), compared to none in Fron. Although this is also a question of site representativeness, a few important differences exist between the two areas that point in the direction of different levels of agricultural vulnerability. As demonstrated in Chapter 9.2.1, the temperature conditions are similar at equal altitudes, but agriculture, in general, is situated at lower heights. This results in slightly better margins for crop production, which can prove decisive during a cooling event. Furthermore, the area is less prone to draught as precipitation is somewhat higher. Floods are a regular feature, but rarely critical. The lake itself restraints the flood impact as the water levels are evened out and slowed down. However, the 1789 extreme flood event caused a significant rise in the water level in Lake Mjøsa as well, which reached as high as 127 masl. The lake was regulated in 1859 and the exact previous average water level is unknown, but it might represent an increase of as much as 8 metres from the pre-regulation average height (Gundersen, 2016b, p. 96). Farms and churches close to the lake shores were flooded, fish in the lake died because of pollution by mud and gravel, and debris were still floating around the year after (Roald, 2013, pp. 65-66). Nevertheless, the situation was by no means as critical as in the Gudbrandsdalen valley due, by and large, to topographical differences. In Hedmarken, the valley slopes are less steep and major landslides are a rare phenomenon. Rising water levels can be devastating for nearby crops and grasslands but have little major long-term effect on the farming landscape. During the 1789 event in Fron, fields damaged by the Lågen River could be put in order within a few years' time, while those struck by landslides in many cases remained unproductive until modern times (Sommerfeldt, 1972). Both the long-term and short-term consequences were thus greater in Fron than in Hedmarken, which reflects different levels of vulnerability to extreme flood events. The landscape in Hedmarken is well-suited for extensive cultivation, and the Early Iron Age agricultural expansion would not have resulted in similar challenges as in the Gudbrandsdalen valley, where the farming landscape is more spatially restricted and situated in steeper terrains. Both in terms of cooling and flood-related natural catastrophes, Hedmarken is associated with more favourable circumstances and better possibilities for avoiding a disastrous outcome.

However, Hedmarken is not invulnerable to climate change, and any cooling between minus 2 to minus 3°C, with reference to 1961-90 average, has the potential of causing poor harvests and even outright crop failure, especially if combined with bad weather. The importance of temperature conditions at different heights, which provide noticeable differences between Fron and Hedmarken, comes into play within

Hedmarken as well. This is clearly visible in the GIS models, and a distinction can be made in this respect between vulnerable and more protected areas. Although the south-facing slopes are somewhat better situated for sun accumulation, solar radiation still offers highly suitable conditions throughout Hedmarken and does not seem to be decisive in this matter. Drawing on the archaeological record, a noticeable difference can mainly be outlined between high and low altitude farms, which corresponds well with the results from the GDD analysis. Hedmarken includes a number of sites with evidence for site continuity from the Early to the Late Iron Age, all of which are situated below 230 masl (Table 9.3). According to the GDD models, farms below an approximate height of 200 masl are more likely to achieve a decent harvest even during a significant cooling than farms above this threshold. All sites above 230 masl lack evidence for either Early or Late Merovingian Period activity, a fact which suggests different levels of vulnerability to cooling between low- and high-altitude farms.

<i>Site name</i>	<i>Site type</i>	<i>Altitude</i>	<i>No of structures</i>	<i>No of C14 dates</i>	<i>Identified buildings</i>	<i>VA activity</i>
Vold II	Settlement/agriculture	216	68	25		Yes
Valum	Settlement/farmstead	155	N/A	17	LRIA-EMvP	Yes
Åker	Settlement/assembly site	133	>300	>100	ERIA-EVA	Yes
Finstad	Settlement/cooking pits	219	N/A	7		Yes
Englaug V	Settlement/farmstead	190	50	6	MvP, LVA	Yes
Ringsaker prestegård	Settlement	141	85	6		
Ljøstad IV	Settlement/farmstead	207	161	27	MP	Yes
Stein	Settlement/cooking pits	138	5	5		

Table 9.3: Sites with evidence for continuous activity from the Early to Late Iron Age in Hedmarken, in accordance with the assessments made in Table 8.2.

The distinction between low- and high-altitude sites is not entirely clear. Admittedly, a number of sites below 230 masl are associated with site disruption (Table 9.4), thus adding some nuances to the topic. However, the pattern of site disruption is both problematic and complex. Only three sites have a distinct settlement character involving buildings. At Lille Børke, the buildings are in use during the Roman Iron Age and first half of the Migration Period and subsequent activity traces are of a much different character (Lislerud & Stene, 2007). Vevla II reflects a similar process, as the longhouse seems to have been abandoned around AD 400 (Eggen & Berg-Hansen, 2011). Only the longhouse at Svein was occupied up towards the end of the Migration Period (Zawalska & Lønnaas, 2019). By and large, the abandoned sites mostly include cooking pits or diverse settlement traces and the end of their occupations may have more to do with changes in site character than climate pressure. Cooking pits remain a particularly problematic category in this respect as the development in their use follows regional patterns seemingly independent of the 6th-century cooling (cf. Gundersen et al., 2020). 25% of the sites associated with continuity are

characterised by cooking pits, compared against 52% of those associated with decline. Consequently, cultural-historical factors clearly shape the impression of widespread site abandonment.

	<i>Site name</i>	<i>Site type</i>	<i>Altitude</i>	<i>No of structures</i>	<i>No of C14 dates</i>	<i>Identified buildings</i>	<i>LIA reoccupation</i>
Below 230 masl	<i>Børstad</i>	Settlement/cooking pits	143	22	11		
	<i>Vold I</i>	Settlement/agriculture	216	67	28		
	<i>Snarud</i>	Settlement/cooking pits	161	54	12		
	<i>Lille Børke</i>	Settlement/farmstead	187	344	15	ERIA-EMP	
	<i>Guåker I</i>	Settlement/cooking pits	226	10	8		
	<i>Guåker II</i>	Settlement	226	35	11		Yes
	<i>Nordstad</i>	Settlement/agriculture	165	32	8		
	<i>Ottestad</i>	Settlement/agriculture	221	65	10		
	<i>Vevla II</i>	Settlement/farmstead	222	78	18	LRIA-EMP	
	<i>Englaug I</i>	Settlement/cooking pits	190	130	8		
	<i>Englaug II</i>	Cooking pits/graves	190	100	5		
	<i>Skapal</i>	Settlement/cooking pits	175	17	7		
	<i>Sveen</i>	Settlement/farmstead	170	150	11	MP	
Above 230 masl	<i>Bjørke</i>	Settlement/cooking pits	367	10	6		
	<i>Kirkebyenga II</i>	Agriculture	403	38	6		Yes
	<i>Flesaker</i>	Settlement/cooking pits	298	98	5		
	<i>Gjærлу III</i>	Cooking pits/agriculture	263	55	11		
	<i>Rømma</i>	Settlement/cooking pits	276	75	12		
	<i>Penningrud</i>	Settlement/cooking pits	298	26	7		

Table 9.4: Sites lacking in evidence for continuous activity from the Migration Period and throughout the Merovingian Period in Hedmarken, in accordance with the assessments made in Table 8.2.

The patterns of abandonment are also unclear when it comes to larger find complexes, such as Englaug and Vold, where continuous activity has been documented at other nearby excavation sites. The Englaug sites in Løten are also located in close proximity to the Iron Age burial ground at By, which also displays a high degree of continuity throughout the 1st millennium AD (I. Martens, 1965). This is further complicated by the fact that only two abandoned sites in Hedmarken were later reoccupied, which stands in contrast to the impression, provided by pollen analytical evidence, for agricultural expansion in the Late Iron Age. There are several reasons, therefore, to assess the evidence as examples of changing land-use strategies and practices and not necessarily abandonment.

Regardless of these source-critical issues, the lack of direct evidence for site continuity above the 230 masl threshold is important in this discussion, suggesting that there is a qualitative difference between the sites in the lower and upper part of the farming landscape. As demonstrated through the GIS-models, temperature is part of this picture. Another is site character. A majority of the sites in Table 9.3 include a significant number of archaeological features (≥ 50), while this is only the case with 42% in Table 9.4. 50% of the sites also involve longhouses, against 16% in the other category, of which none are found above 230 masl. Six out of eight sites in Table 9.3 also include evidence for Viking Age activity. Generally speaking, the sites are characterised not only by long-term continuity, but also distinct settlement characteristics. In sum, sites with patterns for continuity leave an impression of being larger and more robust, especially when compared to sites above 230 masl. In addition, low altitudes would offer slightly better climate conditions which could prove decisive during a prolonged cooling event.

Regardless of whether or not the cooling caused site abandonment at higher altitudes, there is little evidence to suggest that it had long-term effects on farming activity on its own. At the high-altitude site of Kirkebyenga II, a period of fallowing has been identified sometime around the Early to Late Iron Age transition and the site lacks evidence for Early Merovingian Period activity (Gustavsen & Berg-Hansen, 2008). Situated in the outskirts of the present-day farming landscape (Figure 9.13), around 400 masl, Kirkebyenga II can be understood as marginal. The first phase is predominantly made up of grasslands, with some minor evidence for nearby crops. From the Late Merovingian Period and onwards, the area is once more utilised for farming activity and the archaeological record includes evidence for arable farming at the site itself. Thus, the Late Iron Age is one of expansion in crop cultivation in the area. A process of adaption to colder climates might nonetheless have been the case since only rye is present out of the identified cereals.

The evidence from Kirkebyenga II corresponds well with the pollen diagram from the site of Narmo, which acquires the character of significant arable farming only in the Late Iron Age. As discussed in Chapter 9.2.3, a similar process also seems to have been present at Øverbymarka in Gjøvik on the western side of the lake. However, the Narmo diagram does not suggest any major changes in crop composition as all four species are represented, including temperature-demanding wheat. The excavation data from around Lake Mjøsa also suggests considerable species diversity in the region before the cooling event. On the other hand, the pattern of increasing specialisation in farming strategies in the Late Iron Age, as discussed in Chapter 8.8.3, cannot be confirmed by the Narmo diagram. The diagram suggests greater variation at site level than the excavation record indicates and underpins the necessity of not making firm conclusions on quantified excavation data alone. That said, wheat and oats only make up minor parts of the identified

grains and there seems to have been a predominance for barley and rye at Narmo, which is still in accordance with overall excavation results from the region.

To sum up, the case study of Hedmarken confirms the impression of lesser impact of the cooling event around Lake Mjøsa, in particular at the lowermost altitudes, compared to the evidence from Fron. Some reservations should be made concerning site character, but continuity and long-term occupation is clearly associated with sites below 230 masl. Furthermore, the topography of the area reduces the effect of floods and landslides, catastrophic events which have proven disastrous for the more spatially restricted and hilly farming landscape of the valley district.

9.4. Regional diversity

In this chapter, I will present a brief analysis of three more regions in southern Norway – Ullensaker, coastal Vestfold, and Høgsfjorden – in order to demonstrate regional variability and different levels of agricultural vulnerability to cooling. For practical reasons, the models presented in this chapter are somewhat simplified and do not include solar radiation or cultivation classes. Furthermore, I will only model growing degree days and not the growing season. Figure 6.14 in Chapter 6.5.1 visualises the average growing season in southern Norway during the 1961-90 period, thus demonstrating some basic differences between the regions in this respect. Moreover, the GDD models will only be presented with minus 2 and 3°C scenarios, as minus 1°C does not represent any substantial change in any of these areas. The local GDD requirements are listed in Table 9.5 and are based on the same standardised procedure used for Hedmarken and Fron.

<i>Area</i>	<i>Basic requirements at 60° N (barley)</i>	<i>Mean annual precipitation</i>	<i>Growing season (days)</i>	<i>Latitude</i>	<i>Local GDD requirements</i>
Ullensaker		272 mm	161-180	60°N	1265-1345
Coastal Vestfold	1250-1330 GDD	301 mm	181-200	59°N	1306-1386
Høgsfjorden		418 mm	181-200	59°N	1388-1468

Table 9.5: Local weather data and GDD requirements for barley cultivation in Ullensaker, coastal Vestfold, and the Høgsfjorden area in south-eastern Rogaland, with reference to 1961-90 weather data. Weather data: MET.

The Raknehaugen mound at Ullensaker is considered the largest prehistoric burial monument in Scandinavia (Hagen, 1997, p. 31; Price & Gräslund, 2015, p. 121; Skre, 1997, pp. 26-27). It has been excavated twice, in 1869-70 and 1939-40, but a third minor trench was also initiated in 1993. In contrast to its size, no grave artefacts have been found, and C14-dates from the possible cremation burial is significantly older than the mound. It is therefore debated whether it should be understood as a grave, a

cenotaph, or simply as a monumental construction and assembly site (Skre, 1997, pp. 31-37). When it comes to the 6th-century cooling, the mound is important for the debate in two respects. First, the mound includes a huge amount of well-preserved timber mostly cut down during one winter sometime around the early or mid-6th century (Skre, 1997). A so-called “abnormal tree ring” is often considered related to AD 536, as it has the characteristics of low growth during an entire summer (Solheim & Iversen, 2019, p. 428). Although there is some debate on the exact age of the tree ring, it is likely that it is related to one of the cold years between AD 536 and 550. In that case, Ullensaker must have experienced substantial cold conditions during at least one summer which significantly affected terrestrial growth. Secondly, in their 2015 paper, Price and Gräslund argue that the mound is constructed as a direct psychological consequence of the cooling, as a symbolic investment, or sacrifice, to mitigate for a critical situation. Their interpretation is intriguing, and they refer to other similar expressions of symbolic investments, such as the Late Migration Period gold hoards (Axboe, 1999, 2001).

Another site of equal interest is the Forsand complex in Høgsfjorden in Rogaland. Forsand is one of extremely few prehistoric sites in present-day Norway that includes villages. Large parts were excavated in 1980-1990, in what was then a major scientific breakthrough for mechanical top-soil stripping in the country (Løken, 2005, 2020; Løken, Pilø, Hemdorff, & Griffin, 1996). Minor excavations have also been conducted later on (B. I. Dahl, 2008). Important in this context is the evidence for site disruption and abandonment around the mid-1st millennium AD. The site was continuously occupied from the Bronze Age up through the Early Iron Age, with the Roman Iron Age and Migration Period being the most expansive and complex phases. In this period, the settlement gains two organised and centralised villages with site continuity up to approximately AD 650, including traces of increased social and economic stratification. The largest village becomes highly organised in the Migration Period, with the farms aligned alongside two central streets with shared access to the surrounding fields. However, the settlements are in rapid decline during the 6th and 7th centuries. The reasons are debated, but soil depletion is a possible explanation (Løken, 1988). Intensive cultivation is replaced by pastoral farming, and barley and wheat is replaced by oats, a crop which is more resilient to disease and adapted to nutrient-poor soils (cf. Chapter 6.3). Løken (2001; 2020, pp. 283-291) also points in the direction of the 6th-century cooling as a possible contributing factor, as some of the recovered cereals have the characteristics of not having reached maturity and some even have traces of ergot. The last farms were ultimately abandoned during the mid-7th century. A Viking Age grave has been found, but there is no substantial evidence for a new phase of settlement expansion in this period.

The evidence from Forsand has contributed significantly to the notion of an agricultural crisis in southwestern Norway towards the end of the Migration Period. Although a sound critic of the crisis narrative,

Myhre (2002, pp. 170, 189) nevertheless acknowledges that the Forsand record includes clear evidence of crisis and abandonment, but interprets it as a local phenomenon with little expressive value for Rogaland at whole. In his master thesis, Morten Vetrhus (2017) comes to a different conclusion. Accordingly, Forsand can be related to an overall trend with settlement decline in Rogaland from the Early to the Late Iron Age.

Among other things, Myhre (2002, pp. 175-180) draws on the archaeological and paleo-botanical records from the Borre area in Vestfold when he argues against the idea of a widespread 6th-century crisis. By and large, the Merovingian Period at Borre is one of rapid and profound development, with the emergence of a political dynasty of considerable importance in Scandinavian prehistory (Myhre, 2015). Borre is often mentioned alongside a very limited number of ruler sites or central places in Late Iron Age Scandinavia (for instance Andrén, 2020; Skre, 2019). Based on investigations with ground penetrating radar and targeted test excavations, a recent study suggests that important changes in the Borre site biography happened before or during the 6th and 7th centuries AD (Tonning et al., 2020). On the basis of radiocarbon datasets, Solheim and Iversen (2019) argue for widespread crop failure and depopulation in Vestfold during the 6th century which may seem to contradict the contemporaneous evidence from Borre.

Thus, all three sites serve to illustrate the debate on the crisis narrative and are also widely used points of reference in this instance. The sites have so far not been analysed in an environmental perspective, so causal relations between the 6th century cooling and site development are still open to possibility. In order to move the discourse slightly forward, I will in the following use a GDD approach in GIS in order to discuss whether a minus 2 or 3°C cooling is likely to critically affect agriculture in these three areas. The modelled results will be briefly discussed up against published local vegetation data and archaeological literature.

Raknehaugen is situated on the wide and fertile Romerike plains, an area which is part of the *clay soil areas* stretching from Lake Mjøsa in the north to the Oslo fjord in the south (cf. Chapter 7.2.1). The cultivated lands are mostly located below 200 masl and have temperature conditions similar to those in Hedmarken. The GDD analysis of the Raknehaugen area suggests that a 2°C cooling would not represent any major difficulties for the present-day cultivated landscape, as most fields are situated well within $\geq 20\%$ margins to the local GDD requirements. Even with a minus 3°C scenario, all areas are within $< 20\%$ margins. This means that a 3°C cooling is not synonymous with failed barley harvests and that ripened yields are likely to be achieved if significant weather anomalies are avoided. In other words, there is a certain risk associated with a worst-case scenario of minus 3°C, but widespread crop failure would

probably require additional damaging factors. Reduced yields can nonetheless be expected during a minus 3°C scenario.

Figure 9.26: Thresholds for barley cultivation in the Raknehaugen area at Ulleaker during a temperature reduction of 2 and 3°C, based on measured weather data for 1961-90 for Vormsund, Hvam, Egnerfjell, and Gardermoen. Source: MET. Illustration by author.

Several older pollen diagrams are available from the area, but with diverging results (Høeg, 1997). The dating of the diagrams is associated with considerable uncertainties, as radiocarbon dating at the time included low measurement precision and few analyses were usually conducted. The chronological resolution was therefore largely based on interpolation and comparison between the diagrams, which enhances the uncertainties regarding the individual results. Nonetheless, there seems to be good evidence for barley, rye, wheat, and oats cultivation in the area in the Iron Age, but the individual diagrams involve several periods with less evidence for grain cultivation and even incidents of possible discontinuity, of which the mid-1st millennium AD might be one (Høeg, 1997, pp. 127-131). However, one of the diagrams, from Lake Ljøggottjern next to Raknehaugen, indicates continuous cultivation during the last two millennia, with all four grain species well represented throughout most of the period (Høeg, 1997, p. 52). Importantly, there is no clear evidence for incidents of crop failure at this location. The diagram has a good temporal resolution for most of the Iron Age. Recent investigations of Ljøggottjern, which include sediment coring, pollen analysis, and enhanced temporal resolution, supports the general outline of previous interpretations (Bajard et al., in press). The study also suggests that pastoral farming was emphasised during periods of prolonged cooling, whereas arable farming predominates in warmer periods. This seems to have been the case with the 6th century as well. During this period, there is less evidence for cereal cultivation, in particular wheat, but more pastoral indicators. A continuous string of

pollen from cereals demonstrates that crop failure was likely avoided, which corresponds well with the results from the GDD analysis. With considerable temperature margins to rely on, arable farming could be sustained. On the other hand, wheat is more heat-demanding than rye, barley, and oats, and the latter species do not display the same level of decline in the pollen record. The study concludes that the Ljøggottjern record reflects adaptational strategies to climate change, which is a plausible explanation given that pastoral farming, and less wheat cultivation, would contribute to enhanced agricultural robustness during a cooling event. However, neither the GDD analysis nor the pollen record suggest that the cooling alone would have been critical for farming strategies in the area. Compared to Fron and Hedmarken in the inlands, Ullensaker appears more resilient to the changing conditions of the 6th century. If critical conditions did emerge, it was probably short-term and not necessarily an all-out crisis.

Figure 9.27: Thresholds for barley cultivation in the coastal areas of Vestfold during a temperature reduction of 2 and 3°C, based on interpolated weather data for 1961-90 for Horten, Larvik, Tønsberg, and Sandefjord. Source: MET. Illustration by author.

The coastal area of Vestfold offers even better conditions than Ullensaker (Figure 9.27). Temperatures are somewhat higher, the growing season slightly longer, and precipitation levels quite similar. Although the required temperature sum is somewhat higher in the Oslo fjord area than at the Romerike plains, it is counterbalanced by more favourable climate conditions. Consequently, a minus 2°C scenario seems to have little effect on agriculture in coastal Vestfold as all cultivated lands are within a low-risk zone with high temperature margins for barley cultivation. Most cultivated lands are situated along the coastal strip, but a number of fields are also found in river valleys in the inlands. Even a minus 3°C scenario seems to have little effect, as almost all farming lands are still within a low-risk zone. In other words, there is a significant qualitative difference in the climate preconditions for agriculture between the inlands of

eastern Norway and coastal Vestfold, with the latter being more resilient to cooling. Judging from the GDD models, there are few reasons to expect that the 6th-century cooling would have had any profound effect on agriculture in coastal Vestfold, except from perhaps wheat cultivation, if temperatures reached a worst-case scenario. With less heat and therefore less evaporation, it is probable that climate cooling might even be favourable for local cultivation as the risk for draught is reduced. Less water shortfall may also contribute to increased yields (cf. Strand, 1984, pp. 29-33).

Based on radiocarbon datasets made available from archaeological excavations, Solheim and Iversen (2019) argue that Vestfold probably experienced depopulation during or after the 6th-century cooling due to vast crop failures and plague outbreaks. In an earlier paper, Iversen (2013) analysed the rate of farm abandonment in eastern Norway during the Iron Age, and concluded that the 6th century AD stood out in this respect. The study was in part based on excavated farmsteads in Vestfold, and was followed up by toponymical studies of farm names from this area. The radiocarbon dates in Solheim and Iversen's (2019) study are mostly from the cultivated area along the coast. In other words, the dataset stems from the main agricultural area visualised in Figure 9.27. Their study is interesting, as it is one of very few Norwegian studies that attempt to analyse the Fimbulwinter hypothesis up against excavation proxies. The summed probability plot used in the study displays a noticeable trough around AD 536-550, while a 200-year rolling mean indicates a more long-term process of gradual decline that becomes accelerated during the course of the Merovingian Period.

Nevertheless, the trough is not a profound one, and the summed probability plot includes several more sharp peaks and troughs likely caused by sampling bias or the shape of the calibration curve (cf. Chapter 6.4.1), of which the 6th-century trough is by far the most significant. Admittedly, the 200-year rolling mean dataset suggests decreasing levels of activity over time, but the causal and temporal relationship to 6th-century circumstances remains unclear. Importantly, the decline starts in the Roman Iron Age and is only enhanced in the Merovingian Period. This leads us over to another crucial factor, which is the composition of the radiocarbon dataset itself. Cooking pits constitute approximately 1/3 of the input proxies. In Vestfold, the decline in the use of cooking pits begins during the Late Roman Iron Age and follows a steadily-decreasing curve towards the 7th century (Gundersen et al., 2020). Consequently, the development in the use of cooking pits in Vestfold seems related to social and cultural factors and is not specifically linked to the 6th century transition. When comparing the radiocarbon model in Solheim and Iversen (2019, Figure 4) with the cooking pit record in Ingar M. Gundersen et al. (2020, Figure 9.2), it becomes apparent that the many dated cooking pits from the region are heavily influencing the overall trajectory. Consequently, the demographic decline from the Roman Iron Age to the Merovingian Period, as suggested by the former study, seems to be significantly conditioned by the decline in the use of

cooking pits. As shown for Hedmarken in Chapter 8.1, extracting cooking pits from the input dataset would probably display a somewhat different pattern.

The study does not address the available paleo-botanical datasets from the region, which contribute important insights into the possible societal impact of the cooling. Pollen records provide evidence for not only continuous cultivation, but also agricultural expansion and intensification (Høeg, 2004; Myhre, 2015, pp. 103-108). From AD 450 to 700, there is evidence for widespread deforestation and increasing levels of pastoral and arable farming. All four grain species are present. The historical cultural landscape at Borre is shaped during this period, and more or less maintained with similar characteristics up until modern times (Myhre, 2015, p. 105). In contrast to the eastern Norwegian inlands, not even the late medieval Black Death seems to have made a profound impact in the pollen records. Climate change may still offer a partial explanation for the changes in site biography at Borre in the Merovingian Period, but not in terms of crisis and societal upheaval. On the contrary, high levels of agricultural resilience would allow for coastal Vestfold to benefit from the situation at the expense of more vulnerable areas, thus paving the way for increased influence and authority for the local elites. The correlation between the GDD models and the paleo-botanical records are especially notable, as they seem to be mutually supporting. If widespread depopulation occurred, causes other than widespread crop failure are more likely to have been instrumental.

Figure 9.28: Thresholds for barley cultivation in Høgsfjorden in south-eastern Rogaland during a temperature reduction of 2 and 3°C, based on interpolated weather data for 1961-90 for Forsand. Source: MET. Illustration by author.

The results from coastal Vestfold stand in contrast to Forsand and the fjord landscapes of Høgsfjorden in the south-western part of the country (Figure 9.28). Latitude and temperature conditions are equal to those in coastal areas of Vestfold, but precipitation levels are considerably higher (see Figure 6.14 and Figure 6.15 in Chapter 6.5.1). The local GDD requirements are significantly higher than those in the Oslo fjord area, which causes higher levels of agricultural vulnerability to climate cooling. During a minus 2°C scenario, the low-risk zone is limited to small strips of land up to 60 masl, but most areas are still within the <20% margins to the local threshold values. At minus 3°C, most fields are either within or bordering the threshold values, meaning that margins become critically low. Topography plays a significant part in this area; cultivable lands are scattered, small, and located on narrow strips of land surrounded by steep valley sides that reach up to approximately 500-600 masl. Thus, solar radiation is often restricted during certain times of the day, and due to the shifting angles of the sun, during certain times of the year. Several areas in the model would probably have smaller margins to rely on than indicated by the models, in particular in the narrow valleys in the eastern and southern areas.

Pollen diagrams exist from two nearby locations and testify to crop production with varying intensity from around 1000 BC, with the most intensive phase being approximately 100 BC to AD 550 (Løken, 2020, p. 31). During the Early Iron Age, wheat, barley, and oats were cultivated at Forsand, with barley dominating in the Pre-Roman Iron Age (Løken, 2020, pp. 29-31). During the Roman Iron Age, wheat decreases considerably in numbers, whereas oats become the dominant species, accounting for over 60% of the identified grains recovered from the excavation sites. Wheat is almost absent in the Migration Period record. Oats are considered a harsh species well-adapted to cold climates, but both modern and traditional variants have higher temperature requirements than barley (cf. Chapter 6.3 and 6.5.1). Løken (1988, 2001) assesses the development towards oat cultivation as a response to soil depletion, as oats are thrifty even in poor soil conditions, as well as resilient against weeds and diseases. However, according to the GDD models, the cooling could potentially have had considerable impact on barley cultivation in this area, and therefore on oats as well. Finds of oat grains infested with ergot are therefore very interesting, as is an increasing frequency of grains with poor maturation towards the end of the Early Iron Age, a phenomenon which is understood as indicating agricultural difficulties (Løken, 2001, p. 17; 2020, p. 285). It therefore seems reasonable to suggest that the 6th-century cooling may indeed have been decisive for the end of the village complexes at Forsand (Løken, 2020, p. 289).

By and large, the results for Forsand have more in common with the results for the inlands of eastern Norway, in particular Hedmarken, than the coastal areas of Vestfold. However, there is an important difference between Hedmarken and Forsand as well. With decreasing margins, agriculture becomes more vulnerable to weather anomalies and extreme weather phenomena, which is a far more common feature

for the western than the eastern parts of the country. Thus, crop failure is a more likely consequence of climate cooling in the Forsand area than in the inlands of eastern Norway. This assumption is strengthened by the high percentage of oats cultivation at Forsand, which may have further enhanced local vulnerability to temperature decline, whereas barley was preferred around Lake Mjøsa. In that respect, Løken's (2001) and Vetrhus' (2017) suggestions of climate-enforced agricultural crisis seems like a probable explanation. In contrast, similar suggestions for coastal Vestfold and Ullensaker are less substantiated. In particular, coastal Vestfold displays high levels of agricultural resilience to cooling and widespread crop failure is not likely to have happened unless precipitation changed considerably and became more similar to western Norwegian conditions. The result for Ullensaker is more ambiguous, as crops are likely to mature here as well. However, margins are smaller than in coastal Vestfold, and the climatic changes would have favoured a turn in the agricultural strategies towards more husbandry and less heat-demanding crops, as suggested by Manon Bajard et al. (in press). Whether it can be described as an agricultural crisis, however, is far more uncertain.

The three regional studies presented in this chapter demonstrate the importance of regionality when assessing the impact of the 6th-century cooling by displaying different levels of agricultural vulnerability to cooling. However, societal crisis is not necessarily the outcome, even in a worst-case scenario, as it depends not only on a society's dependency to crops in the first place, but also on which grain types were most utilised. In other words, contingency is vital for any study of this kind, as societal characteristics and farming practices must be particularly addressed. Therefore, the GIS analyses presented in this chapter do not prove that climate change is the cause behind the abandonment of the Forsand villages, but nonetheless supports this interpretation. A more thorough investigation of the causal relationships would require in-depth studies of the archaeological and paleo-botanical records from the area.

9.5. Chapter conclusion

By using GIS modelling, I have demonstrated considerable regional differences in southern Norway concerning agricultural vulnerability to cooling (research question D and E). The differences are particularly evident when comparing Høgsfjorden in Rogaland with coastal Vestfold in the Oslo fjord area. In particular, these two areas demonstrate the importance of precipitation for the respective temperature requirements, which may have proven decisive during the 6th-century cooling event. Different levels of agricultural vulnerability can also be outlined within eastern Norway, with Fron in Gudbrandsdalen proving to be particularly exposed to changing climatic conditions, whereas Ullensaker in Akershus appears more resilient. The result for Hedmarken in the Lake Mjøsa region is more ambiguous, as it seems

likely that high-altitude farms would experience considerable agrarian difficulties whereas low-altitude farms may have been able to maintain some level of crop production even during a worst-case scenario.

The results from the GDD models correspond well with available vegetation data and the archaeological record. Site disruption is a particularly widespread phenomenon in Fron but is also evident at the Forsand complex in Rogaland. In Fron, floods and landslides represent an additional risk factor which might have reinforced the long-term effects of the cooling event. The direct consequences of the cooling were likely less critical at Ullensaker, and for coastal Vestfold down to an absolute minimum. The archaeological evidence from Hedmarken indicates that site continuity is related to well-situated farmsteads at lower altitudes, thus supporting the results from the GIS analysis. As such, it appears likely that the cooling event had an impact on the Hedmarken area but to varying degrees, depending on the exact location of the farms, farming practices, and probably the level of economic robustness. Site continuity is most evident at the elite settlement at Åker, which also experienced important changes in site biography around the Early to Late Iron Age with the emergence of the Åker complex. A number of other well-off farms also seem to have been able to maintain site character, although not in terms of a continuous sequence of house constructions.

Whereas the consequences may have been long-term in Fron, the picture is quite different for Hedmarken. Vegetation data indicates significant agricultural expansion in the Late Iron Age, including crop cultivation in areas that previously had been subject to pastoral farming. Thus, the evidence supports the conclusions in Chapter 8.8.3, which outlines a process towards extensive pastoral farming and labour-intensive cultivation, involving a gradual transformation of previous grasslands to cultivated fields through a close integration between the two main farming practices. Moreover, the Late Iron Age expansion is likely related to the contemporaneous changes in crop composition, as the increase in rye cultivation, as exemplified with Kirkebyenga II, would have made clearing of new lands in marginal areas a less risky endeavour. Thus, the process seems to be one of increasing specialisation through close adaptation to local preconditions. However, the fact that most abandoned sites remain unoccupied in the Late Iron Age emphasises an impression of widespread abandonment. On the other hand, it also suggests that a profound change in land-use patterns and cultural practices had occurred which render the Early and Late Iron datasets less comparable. As such, it is not necessarily a question of population decline, but societal reorganisation.

The conclusions for research questions D and E are thus closely connected. It appears likely that the cooling event may have impacted the Iron Age farming communities of southern Norway in contrasting

ways due to differences in environmental factors and human practices, such as farming strategies and land-use patterns. In the final chapters, discussions on the five research questions will be put into a wider socio-cultural context and combined into a coherent synthesis by bringing forth the theoretical perspectives outlined in Chapter 5.

PART IV

SYNTHESIS

10 THE BIG PICTURE

The Fimbulwinter hypothesis has gained considerable influence in Scandinavian archaeology during the last decade, providing a possible explanation for the profound socio-cultural changes associated with the 6th century (Chapter 3.2). However, the hypothesis is also associated with a lack of coherent analytical frameworks that can substantiate the claim of causal chains between climate change and societal change, leading to criticisms of determinism and reductionism (Chapter 3.3). In previous chapters, I have systematised, analysed, and interpreted the archaeological and paleo-botanical evidence from Gudbrandsdalen valley and the Lake Mjøsa region, and modelled agricultural vulnerability to cooling using GIS tools, in order to provide an empirical basis for contextualising and assessing the societal impact of the 6th-century cooling event. Particular focus has been paid to subsistence strategies and long-term trajectories in order to disentangle the preconditions for agricultural crisis during a cooling event. The results testify to considerable social change throughout the Iron Age, towards more specialised and integrated modes of agricultural production, which nevertheless appear mainly independent of 6th-century circumstances. The analysis also suggests considerable regional diversity in agricultural vulnerability to climate change, thus indicating that the cooling event may have been experienced in profoundly different ways within different landscapes throughout Scandinavia. In this chapter, I aim to discuss these results in a wider cultural-historical perspective, with particular focus on the social aspects of disaster risk development in Iron Age Scandinavia (cf. Chapter 5.3.1). By doing so, I intend to demonstrate that the cooling event cannot be treated as a single variable with one common outcome for the entire Scandinavian peninsula, but must be approached with thorough consideration of the topographic, climatic, and social circumstances involved for each particular area in question. This approach results in considerable diversity within our understanding of the 6th-century cooling, but also allows for the consideration of human-environmental interaction in Iron Age Scandinavian in general.

10.1. Regional diversity

Southern Norway is characterised by stark contrasts between the landscape formations, thus opening up for considerable regional diversity in settlement and agriculture, subsistence strategies, and land-use strategies. In addition, there seems to have been considerable differences concerning the social impact of the 6th-century climate downturn. The GIS analysis in Chapter 9 clearly indicates contrasting scenarios not only between eastern and western Norway but also within eastern Norway itself, in particular between the coastal areas of the Oslo fjord and the inlands further north. The geographical differences are equally contrasting, ranging from fjords and expansive cultivated fields to the fertile lake districts and the forested and mountainous areas of the inlands. The Lake Mjøsa region and Gudbrandsdalen valley exemplify how topography plays an important role in subsistence strategies and farming. The climate

conditions in Fron and Hedmarken are comparable at equal altitudes, but farming is significantly constrained by the hilly landscape in the valley districts, whereas the gentle terrain of the lake districts offers excellent opportunities for large-scale crop cultivation. Cultivation in Hedmarken is also situated at lower altitudes than in Fron, resulting in somewhat higher average temperatures. These differences may explain why crop diversity seems to have been a more characteristic feature for the Lake Mjøsa region than the Gudbrandsdalen valley in the Iron Age.

The contrasts between the two regions become even more striking moving further north in the valley, where the high mountains become a more characteristic feature and the climate becomes drier and colder (Chapter 7.3.1). In response, the farming strategies in the two regions have traditionally been somewhat different, and remain so even with modern mechanised agricultural practices. It appears as if modern specialised agriculture has enforced the regional differences, as self-sufficiency is replaced by market-based production focused on efficient exploitation of local resources. Husbandry and grasses constitute fundamental parts of the farming strategies in Gudbrandsdalen valley, whereas the lake districts are traditionally considered the 'breadbasket' of eastern Norway (Chapter 7). The topographical and climatic constraints in Gudbrandsdalen valley seem to have shaped farming strategies at an early stage. The evidence from Gudbrandsdalen testifies to integrated pastoral and arable farming as early as the Pre-Roman Iron Age (Chapter 8.8.3). The evidence from Fryasletta in Fron for what may have been enclosed grasslands is part of this picture, as it demonstrates a means of utilising the landscape for farming purposes through carefully adapting to local conditions. The limited area available for crops is likely to have resulted in farming strategies largely dependent on livestock and grazing, which, in turn, made possible the use of intensified cultivation techniques on a selected number of fields. The overall impression of farming development in the Gudbrandsdalen valley corresponds well with the modern discourse on prehistoric farming in Scandinavia (Mjærum, 2020; Myhre, 2002; Näsman, 2009; Pedersen & Widgren, 2011), although with seemingly more focus on robust crop types and livestock herding in the valley region. Despite the fact that all four main crops have been identified by pollen coring at Ulberg in Fron (Chapter 9.1.3), the general picture is dominated by barley cultivation and, to a lesser degree, rye. The observed pattern in the Lake Mjøsa region also falls in line with this development, but at a different pace. The Lake Mjøsa region includes a high percentage of Early Iron Age fields where only arable indicators have been documented, which may be a consequence of the particularly favourable geological conditions in this area. The chalk- and clay-rich sediments around the lake, especially around the northern half, have traditionally made local farming less dependent on manuring (Chapters 7.2.1 and 8.8.3). Perhaps due to increasing land-use pressure, gradual exhaustion of the soils, or a need to intensify cultivation techniques, livestock became more integrated in the farming strategies during the Iron Age. In the Late Iron Age, fields without pastoral indicators are more-or-less absent from the archaeological

record around the lake. This is accompanied with less species diversity at the sites, which may suggest increasing specialisation in farming strategies.

Regional differences are also expressed during the 6th-century cooling event. Firstly, temperature margins are higher in the agricultural areas in Hedmarken than in Fron, thus creating different levels of vulnerability. Secondly, local topography makes Fron particularly vulnerable to floods and landslides. In the valley districts, where topography is associated with considerable restrictions for cultivation and settlement, clearing of new lands and deforestation would likely contribute to increased flood-risk (Gundersen, 2016b, p. 100). Several sites in Fron include direct evidence for floods and landslides, resulting in abandonment or temporarily disruption in site activity (Chapter 9.3.1). Whether the 6th-century cooling and the Early Merovingian Period extreme flood event should be considered directly related phenomena is unclear, but the combined effect of the two seems nevertheless to have had a profound long-term impact on land-use strategies in Fron. At Ulberg, crop cultivation came to a halt for a couple of centuries. In the valley bottom, the Roman Iron Age and Migration Period settlement expansion, as represented by the three farmsteads Grytting I, Brandrud I, and Brandrud IV, was abandoned (Chapter 9.3.1). The medieval location of the Grytting farms, on a terrace overlooking the Iron Age farmstead, is indicative of a new settlement pattern, either as a relocation of farms from the valley to higher locations, or as a settlement contraction around existing farmsteads with more favourable locations in the terrain. Several sites include evidence for Viking Age activity, which indicates a certain level of landscape reoccupation. However, no buildings have been securely identified and the character of this renewed expansion remains unclear. Parts of the landscape appear to have been left for reforestation and outfield pastures up until the 18th century (Chapter 9.3.1). Although Ulberg was re-cultivated in the Viking Age, it does not seem to equal the Migration Period levels of activity. This is somewhat in contrast to the pollen analytical evidence from the northern region of the valley, which indicates both continuous farming activity from AD 200 and a phase of agricultural expansion in the lower mountain area during the Late Iron Age (Chapter 9.1.3). This may be indicative of contrasting trajectories in the northern and southern areas of the valley, or of a profoundly altered land-use pattern in the Late Iron Age altogether. For southern Norway in general, there are clear patterns of increasing pastoral activity in the lower mountains in the Roman Iron Age and Migration Period (Bjørge et al., 1992; Gundersen, 2013, pp. 101-102; Hjelle, 2015, p. 244; Sjögren et al., 2015, p. 162; Skrede, 2005). This opened up for more systematic exploitation of the mountain outfields for agricultural purposes, leading up to the establishment of the mountain summer farms as an integrated part of the farming system no later than the Late Iron Age. This development should be understood as part of a general trajectory towards a mixed farming economy, as over-exploitation of fodder resources by large livestock herds closer to the farms could thereby be avoided (cf. Timberlid, 2015, for a similar discussion on 19th-century outfield pastoralism). It seems reasonable to expect that a similar process took place in Fron. However, until more pollen coring has been

conducted, preferably in the lower mountain areas of Fron, the similarities and differences between the farming history in the northern and central regions of the Gudbrandsdalen valley remain unclear.

In Hedmarken and the Lake Mjøsa region, the consequences of the environmental events seem to have been more limited. Site continuity throughout the Merovingian Period is more often documented in the archaeological record, whereas site disruption is in many cases associated with the general decline in the use of cooking pits (Chapter 9.3.2). At the same time, vegetation records testify to a Late Iron Age agricultural expansion in areas previously uncultivated. At Narmo in Hedmarken, the clearing of new lands for cultivation seems to have begun during the 5th or 6th century and includes evidence for all four main grain species in addition to grazing (Chapter 9.2.3). A similar process has also been documented at Kirkebyenga II, after a period of fallowing sometime around the Early to Late Iron Age transition, and at Øverbymarka in Gjøvik on the other side of the lake. The fallowing at Kirkebyenga II is particularly interesting as it is a high-altitude site that would be particularly vulnerable to cooling. The site is characterised by pastoral farming in the Early Iron Age, but crops seem to have been cultivated close by (Chapter 9.2.2). In the Late Iron Age, a combination of arable and pastoral indicators becomes more evident. Thus, the consequences of the cooling event around Lake Mjøsa seem to have been short-term. The evidence from these three sites also seems to support the general impression of gradual changes in farming strategies, including a transformation of previous grasslands into croplands in combination with rotational farming.

In both regions, there is reason to believe that a cooling event would unevenly affect the local communities. During a minus 2°C scenario, important temperature margins are still present in low-lying areas, where the Late Iron Age power centres of Hundorp and Åker are located. Given that all sites with evidence for continued occupation in Hedmarken are situated below 230 masl (cf. Chapter 9.3.2), it appears likely that local temperature margins may have been of some importance in regards to how the cooling event affected the community. However, local differences in farming preconditions could also have been a contributing factor. With increasing altitudes, the terrain becomes steeper and includes more rocks. Above 300 masl, there are more fields categorised with medium or low potential for barley cultivation (cf. Chapter 9.2). The combined effect of higher temperatures and slightly better topographical and geological conditions may have proved important for maintaining settlements and agriculture below this threshold. Similar factors are found in Fron, where the best agricultural lands are found on south-facing slopes below 350 masl (Chapter 9.1). High altitude and north-facing slopes have smaller temperature margins to account for, whereas the valley bottom is prone to flooding. Additional threats are posed by the risk of landslides, especially in extensively deforested farming landscapes like the south-facing slopes (Chapter 9.3.1). Unfortunately, very few large-scale excavations have been conducted along

the lower valley sides in Fron, and many issues concerning site continuity remain unexplored. Although Early Merovingian Period site abandonment is a distinct feature in the archaeological record of the area and can be more or less directly related to environmental factors, it is not currently possible to address the overall extent and consequences of these events for the local community. What can be concluded is that farms in certain parts of the landscape would be more vulnerable to the 6th-century climatic events than other farms, meaning that disaster impact, depending on topographical factors, may have been experienced with different levels of severity within the local community (Chapter 9.3.1). In particular, Hundorp is less exposed to flooding and landslides than many other farms in the surrounding area (Gundersen, 2016a, 2016b). In addition, it is situated at low altitudes (240 masl) in an area characterised by high potential for cultivation and with excellent conditions for solar radiance (cf. Figure 9.3 and Figure 9.7 in Chapter 9). As such, compared to many other parts of Fron, Hundorp may have had better prospects for maintaining agricultural production during otherwise turbulent environmental circumstances.

The patterns of regionality become even clearer when the perspectives are broadened to include more areas in southern Norway (Chapter 9.4). Despite similar temperature conditions, there is a stark contrast between the Borre area in coastal Vestfold and Forsand in Høgsfjorden in the southwest, thus demonstrating that precipitation is a crucial factor for crop vulnerability to temperature change. The two examples are particularly interesting as they represent two opposite scenarios which, furthermore, seem to correlate well with the archaeological and paleo-botanical records. The Forsand complex is well documented and represents one of our best-known examples of 6th-century settlement abandonment in Norwegian archaeology (Løken, 2020). The great emphasis on oats cultivation may have been better suited to reduced soil quality and the rough weather conditions in western Norway but would also increase vulnerability to cooling due to higher temperature requirements than barley (cf. Chapter 6.5.1). Consequently, what can be considered a successful adaptational strategy to local preconditions nonetheless reduced society's resilience to other potential risk factors, such as sustained temperature decline. Combined with evidence for ergot and poorly matured grains, there is good reason to believe that the cooling event may have been a main driver, or at least a contributing cause, to the end of the two village complexes at Forsand. The same period is characterised as one of widespread deforestation and increasing levels of farming activity in the Borre area, as well as the emergence of Borre as a ruler site of considerable significance in Scandinavian archaeology (Myhre, 2015). The Raknehaugen area at Ullensaker has temperature margins lower than in coastal Vestfold but are nonetheless sufficient for avoiding outright crop failure, thus representing a scenario in between those modelled for Borre and Forsand. The increase in pastoral indicators and reduction in crop cultivation in local vegetation records supports this interpretation and can be understood as adaptational strategies to colder climates in the 6th

century (cf. Bajard et al., in press). Of particular interest is the decrease in wheat cultivation, whereas rye, barley, and oats only display minor variations.

To summarise, the overall conclusion is that the 6th-century climate event cannot be understood as a singular event throughout Scandinavia, with one shared outcome for those who experienced it, but must be analysed and contextualised with respect to each study area in question. Important parameters include local climates, topography, and farming strategies. The evidence suggests that some areas and communities were more vulnerable to climate change than others, resulting in considerable diversity in disaster impact, mitigation, and long-term consequences. Significant differences can be identified even within eastern Norway. A combination of climate cooling and increased flood rates seem to have proved particularly difficult for the population in Fron, resulting in both site abandonment in vulnerable areas and a reorganisation of the farming landscape. Both the excavation records and the Ulberg pollen diagram strengthen the impression of lasting consequences. In contrast, the consequences seem to have been only short-term in Hedmarken, as the cooling event was soon followed by a new phase of expansion of the farming landscape. However, in both areas, the results from the analyses also suggest that disaster impact may have been unevenly distributed within the local communities as topographical factors resulted in different preconditions for sustaining crop production. In particular, farms situated at high altitudes would be more likely to have experienced devastating consequences of a cooling event, whereas Fron had the additional risk of floods and landslides.

10.2. Iron Age vulnerability

In Chapter 5.4, I listed a set of variables that may have influenced the social construction of vulnerability in Iron Age Scandinavia, structured around the political, economic, and environmental domains. Not all of these aspects can be adequately treated within the scope of this thesis. Focus was therefore put on key sectors that could be analysed directly up against climate change by using vulnerability as an analytical tool: subsistence strategies in general and agricultural productivity in particular. The analysis indicates a broad subsistence strategy that, during the course of the Iron Age, developed towards increasing specialisation and close integration between farming practices. This shift is more or less in line with the overall development in Iron Age Scandinavia. Considering the evidence for species diversity at site level, the agricultural strategies seem to have been robust and diverse at the farms around the mid-1st millennium AD (Chapter 8.9). However, more factors must be included in the interpretations as societal vulnerability is not determined by agricultural strategies alone. In the following, I will discuss the results in a wider societal perspective. In doing so, I will attempt to provide a more coherent interpretation of the

course of events and identify factors that may have strengthened or weakened societal resilience to disruptive events.

First of all, there seems to have been few direct risk drivers in the Migration Period subsistence strategies in Gudbrandsdalen valley and the Lake Mjøsa region, especially in the latter region. Barley dominance decreased during the course of the Early Iron Age, thus contributing to agricultural robustness. Species diversity was high at the documented sites and temperature-demanding crops were less cultivated. The importance of wildlife exploitation for nutrition purposes cannot be answered within the scope of this thesis. However, it can be concluded that the Iron Age communities within the two regions had access to a wide range of resources that were regularly exploited, and these sources could be turned to if the harvests failed (Chapter 8.8.2). The level of self-sufficiency was likely high.

Nonetheless, the prevalence of barley cultivation involved a certain element of risk given that incidents of poor barley harvests could not be readily compensated by good yields for rye or oats, which only constituted smaller percentages of the identified crops. The three species have different qualities and respond differently to weather phenomena, meaning that rye and oats may perform better than barley under certain circumstances. In historical times, oats and barley were therefore often cultivated in the same fields (Bjørnstad, 2012, p. 98). Barley dominance, as suggested by the statistical analysis in Chapter 8, could therefore potentially result in considerable difficulties if climate conditions turned particularly unfavourable for this species. A prolonged cooling, as suggested by temperature reconstructions (Chapter 2.3.2), may have consequently made changes in farming strategies necessary. By turning to rye, yields could potentially improve. The significant decline in barley cultivation during the Merovingian Period in the Lake Mjøsa region, and the simultaneous increase in rye, may reflect adaptational strategies of this kind. In addition, there is a steady increase in pastoral indicators at agricultural sites in the Lake Mjøsa region and Gudbrandsdalen valley during the course of the Iron Age (Chapter 8.2) that may, in part, reflect a response to colder climates.

Whether rye can be understood as a reliable strategy during colder weather is nonetheless questionable. Rye is cold resistant but prone to ergot infection and other fungal diseases (Chapter 6.3). In the western part of the country, where precipitation levels are particularly high, a turn towards rye cultivation during colder summers would be a risky endeavour that could potentially lead to a subsistence crisis due to widespread ergotism. In the eastern regions, where snow covers the fields well into springtime, delayed growing seasons would increase the risk of snow mould and consequently affect the upcoming yields. What can be concluded, however, is that an agricultural strategy based on a wider selection of robust

species, specifically barley, rye, and oats, would make farming communities better suited for coping with unstable weather and climate change. However, the decrease in species diversity at the Late Iron Age sites may suggest that crop robustness was not necessarily the primary aim of this change in agricultural strategies. As for the pastoral indicators, they often appear in combination with arable indicators in the Late Iron Age which may suggest rotational farming rather than an end to crop production. Thus, the process appears primarily related to soil improvement and reflects a general process towards a mixed farming economy (Chapter 8.8.3). Consequently, it seems likely that the process was fuelled by other basic mechanisms than mere climate adaptation and can perhaps be best understood in light of the ongoing change in farming strategies towards specialisation and intensification. The Late Iron Age breakthrough of rye cultivation allowed for cultivating marginal areas previously utilised for grasslands and fodder, thus strengthening farm specialisation by adapting to local preconditions. This development is indicative of increasing land-use pressure throughout the Iron Age, which is supported by vegetation records in the Lake Mjøsa region and northern Gudbrandsdalen.

However, crop robustness may be counterbalanced by other potential risk factors, a possibility which is well-illustrated by the differences in disaster impact for the Lake Mjøsa region and Gudbrandsdalen valley. Although both regions seem to have experienced settlement and agricultural expansion in the Roman Iron Age and Migration Period, taking part in the same overall development in farming strategies, they are associated with dissimilar environmental preconditions. Thus, what was basically the same overall development contributed in very dissimilar ways to the social construction of risk. The evidence from Fron clearly indicates that the subsistence changes taking place during the Early Iron Age exposed the farming community to disruptive environmental events, thus increasing societal vulnerability in general. The situation was profoundly different in the Lake Mjøsa region, where the landscape offers fewer constraints on agriculture and there is less risk for floods and landslides. An expansion towards higher altitudes would nonetheless expose agriculture to colder temperatures, thus reducing important temperature margins. However, as demonstrated for Hedmarken, cultivation is rarely practiced above 500 masl, which is likely due to the easy access to cultivable lands at lower altitudes. Furthermore, the main farming expansion at higher altitudes in Hedmarken seems to have been initiated around the mid-1st millennium AD, thus being more associated with the Late rather than the Early Iron Age. It seems clear that Early Iron Age land-use patterns posed a greater risk in the Gudbrandsdalen valley than the Lake Mjøsa region, which is likely to have influenced the diverging regional trajectories in the aftermath of the 6th-century calamities. In essence, Fron had more geographical and topographical constraints in relation to expanding the farming landscape, thus enhancing social vulnerability to disruptive environmental events in the process.

The settlement expansion in Fron developed despite familiarity with the associated flood risk. The Pre-Roman Iron Age seems to have been particularly turbulent and includes a complex sequence of repeating floods, including what seems to have been a major incident around 50 BC (Chapter 9.3.1). Fryasletta, where settlement and agriculture were repeatedly damaged by these events, is not only an example of considerable site vulnerability to floods, but is also an interesting case of human persistence. Consequently, the population in Fron must have been aware of the risk of erosion and floods and had to relate to it on a regular basis. Knowledge, and familiarity to similar events, is described by Torrence (2019) as an important prerequisite for building social resilience and adapting to disasters. This makes the settlement expansion of the Late Roman Iron Age and Migration Period even more intriguing, in particular for the three farmsteads at Brandrud I, Brandrud IV, and Grytting I. The area of the two Brandrud farms includes evidence for Bronze Age agricultural activity, which probably came to an end due to the unstable Pre-Roman Iron Age conditions (Loktu & Gundersen, 2016). Thick colluvial deposits have been documented, along with only scattered evidence for human activity. Apparently, the favourable and stable climatic conditions during the first centuries AD (Nesje et al., 2016), including low flood rates, caused less awareness of previous experiences of this kind and opened up for new settlements. This expansion proved successful for a few centuries, but when the climate changed and floods became recurrent once more during the Migration Period, the local community faced increasing difficulties. Thus, the evidence from Grytting I and Brandrud I for what seems to have been a planned abandonment likely reflects increasing exposure to events of this kind, thereby forcing an altered settlement pattern. The Early Merovingian Period major flood event seems to have occurred afterwards, thus exemplifying the importance of collective memory and experiences for adapting to changing circumstances (cf. Chapter 5.4).

The 6th-century cooling is usually described as unprecedented during the last two millennia (Chapter 2.3.2), thus raising the question of whether the Iron Age societies would have had similar experiences to draw upon when the situation emerged. It is reasonable to suggest that a rapid summer cooling from one year to the next would be experienced as extraordinary, and perhaps even ominous (as discussed by Axboe, 1999; Axboe, 2001), regardless of whether it directly threatened the crops or not. The early 500s had been warmer than the late 400s (cf. Chapter 2.3.2), likely enhancing the impression of unprecedented change for those who experienced it. However, living at the northernmost part of the agricultural zone, many Scandinavian Iron Age societies would regularly have to relate to temperature anomalies, especially those situated at high latitudes or altitudes. Situating farmlands in areas with small temperature margins would involve considerable risk for recurring bad harvests, making it questionable whether crop cultivation was regularly conducted at a large scale close to the maximum possible extension for cultivation. Certain temperature margins are needed to accommodate for annual variations and weather anomalies. A high dependency on crops becomes decreasingly likely the closer one gets to the threshold

for crop cultivation. Even so, occasional incidents of bad harvests were likely to happen, caused by weather, temperatures, diseases, soil exhaustion, or social unrest and warfare, thus fostering strategies for mitigation and adaptation. As discussed in Chapter 8.8, non-domesticated food sources were highly accessible and also likely exploited on a regular basis, especially if other food strategies failed. Thus, a single year of crop failure would not necessarily be synonymous with a profound crisis for Iron Age farming societies. However, several years in a row with poor harvests would represent a profoundly altered situation, not only because the pressure on outfield resources would increase, but also because available sowing grains would gradually diminish and make it difficult to re-establish a cultivation-based economy. Whether multiple years of bad harvests occurred is a matter of interpretation. As discussed by Newfield (2018), the reconstructed temperature curve for Scandinavia is much more ambiguous than those for the Alpines and Northern Hemisphere (cf. Chapter 2.3.2), with the former including more inter-annual variations and perhaps a shorter duration of the cooling event. Moreover, the risk for recurring bad harvests must have varied considerably within Scandinavia, especially when considering the regional aspects of agricultural vulnerability in southern Norway (Chapter 9). Areas like Fron and Høgsfjorden were more likely to experience sustained agricultural difficulties than coastal Vestfold and Ullensaker. However, what can be asserted is that the risk for bad harvests increased significantly for at least a couple of decades. For some areas, survival may have been dependent on drastic measures, such as profound changes in subsistence strategies, or even conflict with neighbouring groups.

These aspects move the discussion over to the political domain, and the Scandinavian socio-political context in which the cooling event emerged. The Migration Period and Late Iron Age are usually described as periods of not only high mobility and extensive political networks between the ruling elites, but also of increasing competition and escalating warfare (Hedeager & Tvarnø, 2001, pp. 267-289). Herschend (2009, pp. 404-406) describes a process of profound change in the landscapes of war during the Late Roman Iron Age and Migration Period, in short moving from field battles to the sites of the halls, reflecting a change from territorial control to hegemonic control. In her analysis of Iron Age weapon graves from central Norway, Ystgaard (2014) identifies patterns of increasing professionalization of warfare, which is understood as related to new leadership ideals structured around a system of dependencies. The process is related to overall changes in the political structures of the time, from tribal organisations to petty kingdoms, and the emergence of larger legal and political entities (Iversen, 2019; Skre, 2019).

Skre (2019) distinguishes between 1st- and 2nd-generation ruler sites, which are associated with the development of kingship and kingdoms. The ruler sites are understood as institutionalised legal and political arenas where the rulers met with their subjects and exercised their power, thus often constituting a stable presence in the political landscape. In general, the 1st-generation ruler sites were

established as means of organising and controlling production and trade in the Early Iron Age, in particular during the 2nd and 3rd centuries AD, often involving rich archaeological assemblages and sometimes cultic buildings. The 2nd generation is further developed with a distinct monumental display of supremacy through halls, huge mounds, and other symbolic investments. This group of sites seems to be intrinsically linked to the 6th century and the emergence of new royal lineages. A few sites are identified as both 1st- and 2nd-generation sites, among them Åker (Skre, 2019, p. 219).

The process appears connected to extensive warfare during the 3rd to 5th centuries, resulting in a cementation of the kingship structure and more robust political entities during the late 5th and early 6th century AD (Skre, 2019, pp. 224-226). Lotte Hedeager (2011) interprets the political and cultural changes in Scandinavia around the mid-1st millennium AD as influenced, either indirectly or by direct presence, by the Hunnic invasions of central and southern Europe in the late 4th and early 5th centuries. Accordingly, the Hunnic expansion represents a profound ideological shift for Iron Age Scandinavia, influencing ruler ideology, burial customs, the art of war, and political practices, with excessive focus being placed on tribute, warlords, gift-exchange, and subordinate kings and vassals controlled through personal bonds and loyalties. Hedeager (2011, p. 226) compares the monumental burial mounds of the Merovingian Period with the *kurgans* of the eastern steppes, as a symbolic expression of the new royal lineages of the post-Hunnic era. The turbulent political situation of the Migration and Merovingian Periods are contrasted by the institutional stability offered by the ruler sites (Skre, 2019, p. 230). Thus, the socio-political context of the 6th century is one of not only dynastical struggles, unrest, and profound changes in ruler ideology, but also involved a certain element of political robustness centred on the symbolic authority of the halls and the ruler sites. By controlling the ruler sites, power could be achieved and exercised (Skre, 2019, p. 232). However, decision-making is not necessarily to be understood as centralised and authoritative, as power, economic issues, and justice was constantly negotiated with the population through the *thing*-system which was comprised of legal assemblies operating at several geographical levels (cf. Iversen, 2019, p. 251). The thing-system is well known from the medieval sagas, but its age and origin is a matter of some debate, perhaps extending as far back as the Pre-Roman Iron Age (Ødegaard, 2018, 2019).

The 6th-century cooling event emerged in a competitive political landscape of rivalling dynasties nonetheless operating within a legal system of low-level decision-making, thus combining both hierarchical and egalitarian principles of government. This inherent contradiction in the political system may be best understood in relation to the power struggles between the land-owning classes and the warlords (cf. Herschend, 2009, pp. 404-406). It was rooted in the increasing martial proficiency and importance of the military commanders in Germanic societies, fuelled by conflict with the Roman Empire

and shifting alliances between the tribes, and active participation in the imperial armies (cf. Hedeager, 1992, pp. 152-179, 246-255; Hedeager & Tvarnø, 2001, pp. 113-119; Skre, 2019, pp. 222-224).

During a period of a possible subsistence crisis, the ambiguity in the political system represents both potential and danger, being simultaneously dynamic and a clash of interests. On one hand, low-level decision-making allows for quick responses and collective action at local scales. On the other hand, the means for mitigation are limited and often restricted to local resources that may be equally affected by the causes for the unfolding crisis. As is often the case for modern societies, relief and additional resources may be provided by centralised authorities with networks and connections beyond the affected area, but this is something that requires systems for transport, redistribution, and stable and friendly political affiliations with neighbouring groups. The latter opportunities would be highly restricted in a competitive political landscape, and in some cases even virtually non-existent. Although early 6th-century power constellations are described as more stable than the preceding ones, centred on divine kingship rather than personal charisma (Skre, 2019, p. 226), they were nonetheless different from the institutionalised and fixed medieval states (Hedeager & Tvarnø, 2001, p. 285). The political structures were unstable and prone to change in response to shifting personal alliances and dynastical claims. Furthermore, the pre-state polities, with weak central authority and lack of necessary economic infrastructure, would have had few possibilities for providing sufficient relief. The 6th-century decline in the European trade networks (cf. Skre, 2019, p. 231) may have worsened the situation, but this shift can also be understood as an end to surplus production in favour of altered subsistence strategies. Whatever the reason, the lack of political stability would function as an additional risk driver by restricting potential sources of relief, but also represents a risk factor in-and-of itself. An unfolding crisis may have resulted in increased competition and warfare for resources, thus potentially influencing areas and political groups initially unaffected by the environmental events, in what can be understood as indirect consequences taking place outside the catchment area.

However, the analyses in Chapter 8 and 9 provide few indications for widespread and profound crisis. As discussed in the previous chapter, considerable regionality seems to be involved. In all areas, an average temperature decrease of 1°C does not seem to pose any significant threat to the farming landscape, thus somewhat reducing the danger for sustained crop failure over multiple years. This is, to an extent, in contrast to the results of Stamnes (2016) for Nord-Trøndelag in central Norway, who concluded that the consequences of an average decrease of 1°C could have been significant. A few differences can be outlined between the two studies. First, Stamnes uses a stricter delimitation of the growing season, thus operating with less accumulated GDD for his areas than in the present study (Chapter 6.5.1). Second, Stamnes operates at a regional scale, thus missing the high-resolution variations and details provided by

local scales. Finally, his definition of the boundaries for the farming landscape is based on the distribution of burials, whereas this study relates to the full extent of the present farming landscape. Thus, the two studies are associated with different source-critical aspects which are likely to influence the differences between the two results. The results are therefore not directly comparable but illustrate how the input variables influence the model output data, and with it the final interpretations. The basic principles for the GIS models must therefore be put under careful scrutiny during the initial stages of analyses. For the Gudbrandsdalen valley, which includes several known burials in the lower mountain region associated with outfield exploitation (Chapter 7.3.2), giving weight to the burial landscape would be problematic when considering agricultural vulnerability. Considering that the average summer temperatures prior to AD 536 were slightly below the 1961-90 average (cf. Chapter 2.3.2), the climatic restraints for modern cultivation, which are evident in the GDD map for the 1961-90 reference period (Figure 6.19 in Chapter 6.5.1), are likely to have been instrumental for prehistoric farming as well. Consequently, compared to the spatial distribution of burials, the modern extent of the farming landscape in the Gudbrandsdalen valley is probably a better measure for the maximum possible range of cultivation in the Iron Age.

In general, precipitation levels seem to be of greater importance for crop cultivation than temperature variations. This is clearly demonstrated by the different results for Høgsfjorden and coastal Vestfold. The two areas share similar temperature conditions and are situated at equal latitudes, but nonetheless provide dissimilar results in the GDD models due to differences in rainfall during the growing season (Chapter 9.4). Thus, weather anomalies may have been an important variable for the outcome of the cooling event. Importantly, more precipitation increases the temperature requirements, whereas less precipitation requires a lower temperature sum for the cereals to dry up and mature. Water shortfall during spring and early summer is a common concern for precipitation-based crops in eastern Norway since high temperatures require more rainfall (cf. Strand, 1984, pp. 29-33). As discussed in relation to coastal Vestfold (Chapter 9.4), temperature decline may, in some cases, have been favourable for the crops as plant evaporation is consequently reduced. The results from the GDD models find some support in a recent study in solar geoengineering, which simulated the effect of aerosol veils on agriculture on a global scale (Fan et al., 2021). The study concludes that reduced temperatures are an important driver for increased crop yields by reducing plant evaporation. Moreover, depending on particle morphology, aerosol veils may scatter and distribute solar radiance in a way that can be beneficial for densely cultivated crops. The simulated effect is more significant in the global south, but nonetheless illustrates the complex interaction between crops, temperatures, precipitation, and humidity. More studies of this kind may be of some help for understanding the impact of the 6th-century cooling event.

However, a combination of increased precipitation and lower temperatures would have the potential to negatively affect crop cultivation. It has been suggested that the cooling event caused increased humidity and rising water levels in Swedish lakes, which is understood as a possible explanation for settlement relocations to higher grounds (Gräslund & Price, 2012, p. 438). Unfortunately, little is known at present about changes in precipitation levels in Scandinavia as a whole during the dust veil event, which causes some uncertainty in the final interpretations. However, it is worth noting that tree-ring proxies and climate model simulations indicate reduced precipitation in Europe during the 6th century (Büntgen et al., 2011, p. 581; van Dijk et al., in review). The studies of Büntgen et al. (2011) and Evelien van Dijk et al. (in review) show that increased humidity is not necessarily an automatic consequence of a volcanic dust veil event. As with temperatures, regional diversity is an additional factor to take into account. In the climatic aftermath of the 1815 Tambora event, moist conditions seem to have been an important contributing factor for the many examples of agricultural failure in central and western Europe (Chapter 2.2). However, at Åker, where crop failure was avoided, spring and autumn floods were reported with a cold and dry summer in between (Lundstad, 2004, p. 138). The greatest threat to crops at Åker seems to have been the unstable weather, including incidents of heavy rainfalls, draught, cold, and heat.

The difference between the study areas is more clearly visualised with a temperature reduction of 2°C and 3°C. The former scenario is likely to have occurred during the cooling event, whereas the latter represents a worst-case situation that *may* have emerged (cf. Chapter 2.3.2). The 6th-century cooling event had the potential of considerably affecting certain areas, an outcome which may have been exacerbated by the unstable political circumstances of the time. In Fron, the combination of topographical and climatic factors may have been crucial and offers an environmental context in which the profound changes of the farming landscape can be better understood. This case study is particularly interesting because of the seemingly long-term effects, which is something that also characterises the Forsand complex in Høgsfjorden. Forsand never fully recovered, whereas the archaeology at Fron displays some evidence for re-cultivation during the Late Iron Age and, in particular, during the Viking Age. For the Forsand complex, the natural exposure to the rough coastal weather of western Norway may have played a similarly catalysing role as the hilly topography of the Gudbrandsdalen valley. The temporal patterns in Fron and at Forsand may be symptomatic of repeated incidents of bad harvests, involving diminishing storages of sowing grains and difficulties in re-establishing a crop-based agrarian economy.

For Hedmarken, the effects seem to have been short-term, whereas the vegetation records from Ullensaker are indicative of a successful adaptational strategy. Coastal Vestfold displays a diametrically different outcome than Fron and Forsand, thus adding important nuances to the overall interpretations. A sustained agricultural crisis would likely result in significant and long-term consequences visible in the

archaeological and paleo-botanical records. The effect of the cooling event on local agriculture seems to have been rather short-term in Hedmarken and Ullensaker, whereas no clear negative consequences can be identified for coastal Vestfold. If the whole of Scandinavia was profoundly affected by the cooling event, it must have been through a process of escalating warfare rooted in a highly unstable political situation. The cooling event itself is more likely to have affected Iron Age Scandinavia unevenly, both within and between the areas.

10.3. The Iron Age as an adaptive cycle?

In Chapter 5.2, I discussed the potential of and the limitations inherent in resilience theory and the adaptive cycle model for archaeological research. Although systems theory is generally criticised for forcing human behaviour into predictable patterns (cf. Chapter 4.2), the adaptive cycle model nonetheless provides an interpretative framework useful for structuring and analysing long-term social trajectories. As a metaphor for systemic change and adaptational behaviour, it has proved constructive for many archaeological studies when attempting to understand the underlying social mechanisms that construct vulnerability to environmental change (Chapter 5.2.3). In the following, I will briefly discuss some thoughts on how the adaptive cycle model may help to progress our understanding of the societal development in Iron Age Scandinavia, which leads up to the final discussion in Chapter 10.4 'Concurrency or causation?'. As it offers an interesting synthesis on the internal and external dynamics of the Early Iron Age, I will depart from the narrative of Herschend (2009), before discussing it up against resilience theory and the overall historical context of the Migration Period.

Herschend (2009) describes a process of increasing stagnation in the Scandinavian societies during the Late Roman Iron Age and Migration Period, enforced by the loss of a global economic system after the collapse of the Western Roman Empire. However, society is not understood as poor but rather undergoing the process of developing an emerging system of dependencies and growing social stratification, thus causing a loss of social and economic dynamics. Cut off from foreign goods acquisition, power accumulation became difficult to uphold, while population growth put ever-increasing pressure on subsistence resources. Without the ability to reform, the development continued until it became unsustainable, resulting in both profound and rapid changes towards the end of the Migration Period. In a basic sense, Herschend's (2009) approach is not that different from the economic frameworks of Renfrew (1978) and Tainter (1988)(Chapter 4), but nonetheless has a clear focus on the social processes that create acceptance and resistance to change, thus contributing to considerable variability in both spatial and temporal terms.

Herschend's (2009) narrative offers important perspectives on the underlying socio-economic processes of Early Iron Age Scandinavia. Of particular interest is his description of how the end of a system characteristic, while operating within a larger socio-political context, can be both time-consuming and rooted in internal contradictions between growth and sustainability. In this way, the narrative has a lot in common with resilience theory and the idea of nested adaptive cycles, operating from supra-regional down to local scales, and at different sectors within society, mutually affecting each other by exchanging with the overall system (Chapter 5.2.2). In this perspective, the continental economic networks of the Roman era, to which the Germanic societies were connected through gift-exchange, tribute, alliances, conflict, mercenaries, and surplus production aimed at a market system, can be understood as the overall system within which the Germanic societies operated. A classic feature of the adaptive cycle model is the gradual build-up of systemic vulnerability to disruptive events through increasing specialisation and interdependency between individual sectors and practices, in which the system becomes highly effective but also rigid and conservative, thus becoming unable to adapt to changing circumstances (Chapter 5.2.2). Through a disruptive event, the system loses its structural integrity, and the cycle continues into a fast-moving and chaotic phase of systemic destruction through which the system becomes redefined and profoundly altered.

The adaptive cycle model serves as a thought-provoking metaphor of the late Roman Empire, which experienced a growing crisis beginning in the 3rd century AD with increasing economic, political, and military difficulties, including a gradual fragmentation of its territorial integrity (Hedeager & Tvarnø, 2001, pp. 243-247). To the western empire, the real disruption did not occur with the deposition of the last formal emperor in AD 476, which was of little geopolitical consequence for contemporary societies, but with the late 4th-century Hunnic invasions and the push-and-pull effect of Germanic federations to Roman territory; these disruptions resulted in great upheavals, extensive warfare, and plundering in both the eastern and western empire, including threatening Constantinople and the sacking of Rome in AD 410 (cf. Hedeager & Tvarnø, 2001, pp. 247-249). The decades that followed represent the destruction of what had been a relatively stable but highly conservative and vulnerable geopolitical situation, and the establishment of new political entities with weak loyalties to the imperial structure. As discussed previously in this chapter, the mid-1st millennium AD was a period of significant political and ideological change in Scandinavia, a shift which appears closely related to the turbulent geopolitical situation in continental Europe at the time (Skre, 2019, pp. 227-228). Accordingly, the Scandinavian societies should not be viewed as isolated phenomena, but embedded in the same overall development found elsewhere in Germanic Europe. Instead of political and economic stagnation, the Migration Period can be understood as one of confusion and instability, followed by reorganisation and innovation, finally culminating in a process of increasing monopolisation of power which gave way to the petty kingdoms of the Late Iron Age. As stated by Skre (2019, p. 234), the political and ideological development of the mid-

1st millennium have an unclear causal relation to the 6th-century cooling event, and in many ways transcends it, with the emergence of larger polities and ideas of kingship during the Migration Period and the establishment of 2nd-generation ruler sites around AD 600. In this picture, escalating warfare would not be understood as traits of unrest due to stagnation, but a struggle for control in a political landscape characterised by wide-open windows of opportunities, affecting both continental Europe and Scandinavia.

The dynastical struggles of the Migration Period were between the ruling classes. As stated by Herschend (2009, p. 403) and Ystgaard (2014, pp. 369-381), warfare moved from battlefields and territorial control to halls and hegemonic control. In similar ways, Skre (2019, p. 232) emphasises the importance of controlling the ruler sites for obtaining royal power. However, as pointed out by Iversen (2019, p. 251), the legal status of governing was settled at the thing, a process which was instrumental for the acceptance of new kings. As such, kingship was not legitimated through military conquest in its own right, but through settling an agreement with the land-owning classes after disposing of your rivals.

This is not to say that ordinary farmers were unaffected by the dynastical struggles (cf. Herschend, 2009, p. 403). There are several examples of violent settlement destruction, such as the village Vallhagar at Gotland and the Öland ring-forts (Price & Gräslund, 2015, p. 116). Alliances and political networks must have involved the local nobilities, and with them their retainers and clients. Skre (2019, p. 223) suggests that slave-taking constituted an important part of Migration Period warfare. The loss of an economic network also must have affected subsistence strategies, as labour, in order to compensate for the lack of foreign goods acquisition, would have to be directed towards other aims than surplus production for distant markets. Nonetheless, the agricultural development in the Lake Mjøsa region and the Gudbrandsdalen valley appear somewhat detached from the overall dynastical turbulence of the time and can be understood as adaptive cycles in their own respect, operating within the broader framework of societal change. As pointed out in Chapter 5.2.1, there is a profound difference between political and cultural resilience, meaning that power arrangements and societal structures may disintegrate, whereas daily life and cultural expressions within the same communities may still be maintained and practiced in similar ways as before. Changes within the economic domain are more likely to be part of overall economic developments, such as surplus production directed towards markets and foreign goods acquisition, or as a direct response to changing environmental preconditions, rather than shifting dynastical struggles.

In the two research areas, the major turn of events is found in the Late Roman Iron Age with the emergence of a new land-use pattern, involving numerous smaller sites, new settlements, clearing of new

lands, and a more distinct emphasis of species diversity in farming strategies. The process is cemented in the Migration Period with a gradual decrease in smaller sites and a consolidation of larger sites. The process later on followed two distinctly different trajectories in each of the two regions due to dramatic environmental events and different preconditions for mitigation. Those living in the Gudbrandsdalen valley may have experienced a profound crisis, whereas those in the Lake Mjøsa region continued a process of growing specialisation and integration between pastoral and arable farming. Through this, farming practices in the latter region became more interdependent, thus building up towards more efficient modes of production. In the adaptive cycle model (Chapter 5.2.2), this corresponds to a process of increasing connectedness and potential for resource accumulation, often including population growth, but also emerging monopolisation and conservatism. Thus, the process is reminiscent of the development often attributed to the Late Migration Period and Early Merovingian Period towards increased stratification and larger polities (Iversen, 2016, 2019; Myhre, 2015; Røstad, 2016, pp. 410-423; 2020; Skre, 2019).

For the Gudbrandsdalen valley, dramatic environmental events seem to have sparked a profound reorganisation of the farming landscape, at least in central areas. In the case of Fron, the settlement and agricultural expansion of the preceding centuries was indeed a period of agricultural innovation and rapid development, closely adapting farming practices to topographical conditions, but nonetheless henceforth becoming highly vulnerable to environmental change. Fron demonstrates that the adaptive cycle does not necessarily follow all the way through (cf. Redman, 2005, p. 73), as major disruptive events can have radical consequences even in cases where society is going through a process of exploration and dynamic change and is seemingly resilient. The multidimensional character of catastrophes and vulnerability does not allow for a straightforward approach set within fixed frameworks, but demonstrates that systemic thinking, while contributing with useful metaphors, do not provide final explanations in themselves. Their main contributions are as analytical tools, through which social patterns can be disentangled and put into context.

10.4. Concurrency or causation?

When discussing the monumentality of the Early Merovingian Period elites, Skre (2019, p. 229) suggests that it may have functioned as a means of reinstating people's confidence in their rulers through a display of supremacy and perhaps even divinity. Similar ideas have also been put forward by Price and Gräslund (2015, p. 121), who interpret the construction of the Raknehaugen mound as a direct psychological response to distress, anxiety, and unrest. There is indeed an intriguing concurrency between the 6th-century climate downturn and the emergence of a new monumentalised burial custom among the ruling

elites, especially when it comes to the Raknehaugen mound, which has been radiocarbon dated to the first half or middle part of the 6th century AD (Skre, 1997).

Late Iron Age monumental burial mounds are found throughout eastern Norway, many of which have traditionally been understood as associated with the royal lineage of the Ynglingar dynasty (Brøgger, 1937; Myhre, 2015, pp. 123-132; Skre, 2019, pp. 210-211). At Borre in Vestfold, but also at Gamla Uppsala in middle Sweden, the monumental phase seems to have been initiated during the late 6th and early 7th centuries, including mounds and great halls (Ljungkvist & Frölund, 2015; Myhre, 2015; Tonning et al., 2020). The Åker assemblage belongs to the same period and is associated with several large mounds in the surrounding area (cf. Rolfsen & Larsen, 2005; Røstad, 2020). Huge mounds are also found at Hundorp in Fron; although none of them have been scientifically investigated and dated, at least one is generally believed to belong to the Merovingian Period (J. H. Larsen, 2016a, pp. 70-71).

However, the varying regional levels of agricultural vulnerability identified in this thesis raise some questions regarding the issue of causality. Of the sites Åker, Hundorp, Raknehaugen, and Borre, only Hundorp in Fron is associated with patterns which suggest a profound and lasting crisis, whereas the iconic Borre site, involving more monumental mounds than any other location in Norway, is associated with significant agricultural resilience (Chapter 9.4). Thus, despite being a significant characteristic of the Early Merovingian Period, the emergence of ruler site monumentality does not seem to relate, in spatial terms, to agricultural vulnerability and high risk for agricultural crisis during a cooling event. For the Åker and Raknehaugen areas, certain elements of adaptation seem to be present in the paleo-botanical record that may suggest increasing difficulties in maintaining farming outputs. The climate downturn may have contributed to a shift in the farming strategies in the latter area, towards more livestock grazing and less wheat cultivation (Bajard et al., in press). However, the overall changes in farming practices in Lake Mjøsa region seem to follow a trajectory set out in the Early Iron Age, with only crop species composition being altered in a way that may suggest measures against colder climates. The increase in pastoral indicators may be indicative of a related phenomenon. As discussed in Chapter 10.2 above, however, it is questionable whether these changes should primarily be understood in relation to climate change or as means of improving landscape exploitation for farming purposes.

Site chronologies add to the complexity by displaying a rapid development in the Late Roman Iron Age with numerous smaller sites, as well as what seems to be a subsequent process towards larger sites with a high level of temporal resilience. There are also clear patterns of widespread disruption during the Merovingian Period, suggesting that the process may have been enforced during this time. A significant

lacuna in radiocarbon dates from buildings underpins the impression of large-scale reorganisation of the settlement pattern. Moreover, considerably fewer sites are documented for the Late Iron Age than in the Early Iron Age. However, this discrepancy continues even in the Viking Age, despite the fact that the period is rich in both burials and artefact finds (cf. Chapter 8.8.1). As discussed in Chapter 3.3.4, the difficulties in locating Late Iron Age settlements may, in part, be due to changes in building techniques and architecture, including a gradual development away from the classic and easily-identifiable three-aisled longhouses. The emergence of more permanent farmstead plots in the Late Iron Age, as discussed by Grønnesby (2019) and Gjerpe (2017), would also have resulted in a new spatial and temporal settlement pattern. In contrast to the numerous Early Iron Age sites of shorter duration, the Late Iron Age would be characterised by fewer sites of more long-term occupation. Göthberg and Sundkvist (2017, p. 23) furthermore point out that fireplaces are usually preferred for dating purposes, but are more rarely found in Late Iron Age buildings, thus contributing to an under-representation in the excavation records.

The relatively stable distribution of radiocarbon dates from settlement traces in the Lake Mjøsa region during the Late Iron Age (Chapter 8.1), in contrast to the low number of identified houses, may be indicative of similar source-critical challenges. Göthberg and Sundkvist (2017, p. 23) stress the need of employing systematic metal detecting at an early stage during the investigations as the Late Iron Age sites are often characterised by a significant increase in artefact finds, in particular metal objects.

As discussed previously in this chapter, the overall socio-political development is deeply embedded in Migration Period circumstances and events, in which the role of the 6th-century cooling remains somewhat unresolved. In his study of Iron Age settlements in eastern and southern Norway, Gjerpe (2017, pp. 191-204, 222) argues in similar ways by pointing out that the changes in settlement patterns originate in Early Migration Period dynamics, in which the 6th century appears more as catalyst than a cause. The same conclusion has also been reached in a number of other archaeological studies involving ceramics, weaponry, brooches, food technology, or ceramics (Chapter 3.3.5). The results from the statistical analysis in Chapter 8 are suggestive of a similar course of events in the Lake Mjøsa region, with the main trajectories originating in the Late Roman Iron Age. Similar patterns are identifiable in the Gudbrandsdalen valley, at least up to the 6th century. Both Herschend (2009) and Skre (2019) emphasise the complexity of the process, making it difficult to point at one specific cause, something that was also pointed out by Näsman (2012) in his early critique of the climate narrative.

As these studies clearly illustrate, much of the discussion surrounding the possible social impact of the cooling event has so far rested on temporal issues, thus encouraging attempts to develop high-resolution

chronologies for selected archaeological features (for instance Kristoffersen & Røstad, 2020). However, concurrency between archaeological and geoscientific datasets does not equal a causal relationship on its own, but merely functions as one of several analytical tools necessary for substantiating such claims. For the Fimbulwinter hypothesis, as with most other archaeological studies dealing with environmental issues, the main challenge is demonstrating that a natural event could impact human society in the way that it is proposed, thus setting off a range of consequences visible in the archaeological record. The question of cause and effect is often approached through the use of analogies, either to other similar events documented in historical times or to written accounts from other parts of world, where both the social and environmental circumstances are likely to have been fundamentally different than those of Iron Age Scandinavia (cf. Chapter 3.3.2). Without proper analytical justification, the claims of massive depopulation of the Scandinavian Peninsula (as argued by Gräslund, 2018, pp. 193-196; Gräslund & Price, 2012, p. 433; Price & Gräslund, 2015, p. 127) risk becoming a confirmation bias for topical environmental concerns, reflecting a process of collective catastrophisation, rather than contributing with novel explanations to age-old archaeological questions (Chapter 5.1).

Archaeology has struggled with the concept of collapsing societies ever since its very beginning as a scientific discipline, as well as the difficulties in bridging between historical particularism and grand narratives (Chapter 4). During the last decades, however, considerable effort has been put into developing novel methods and analytical frameworks that progress our understanding of social dynamics and the interaction between human and environmental systems. In particular, the concepts of resilience and vulnerability have proven useful within what is often termed the environmental humanities (Chapter 5). As I have discussed in Chapter 5.1, the emergence of the environmental humanities does not offer a ready solution to the concept of causality, as the intricacy of human and environmental systems complicates the interpretative process. It does, however, offer novel opportunities through which it can be approached more systematically and analytically. Through methodically disentangling the varying local preconditions for absorbing and coping with disruptive events, new interpretative frameworks can be achieved that open up for considerable diversity in human and societal responses to what may nonetheless have been shared or similar experiences. Thus, the old dichotomy between particularism and generalisation, and between crisis and a change of practice, can be bridged (cf. Chapter 3 and 4). However, the Fimbulwinter discourse has so far been mainly detached from the overall epistemological development in disaster research, and has instead been based upon well-established crisis narratives which have been unable to overcome the complexity of the archaeological record (Chapter 3.3).

The issue of causality remains enigmatic also for this thesis. Of considerable concern is the fragmented character of the archaeological record, in addition to the basic challenges related to identifying a clear

connection between cause and effect in a prehistoric context mostly reconstructed from material remains. However, this thesis has demonstrated that considerable regional diversity in human responses can be expected even from hemispherical climatic events by taking local preconditions and characteristics into consideration. As pointed out by Eriksen (2016, p. 8) in his study of the modern anthropogenic state of crisis, global change is perceived, understood, and responded to locally. His narrative resonates well with the growing understanding of disasters as multidimensional processes, with shifting properties along spatial, social, and temporal scales (Oliver-Smith et al., 2017). In similar ways, 6th-century climate change was probably not experienced in the same way throughout Scandinavia, influencing a state of crisis among some communities, but not indifferently as one shared disastrous event with uniform consequences throughout the peninsula. Such an explanation would not do justice to the archaeological record (cf. Chapter 3.2). Instead, a more dynamic picture is beginning to emerge, in which climate change interacts with Iron Age societies in multiple ways.

In the present study, the idea of climate-induced agrarian and societal crisis is perhaps best substantiated for Fron in the Gudbrandsdalen valley. To a certain degree, this conclusion can be reached with the help of direct physical deposits from flood events at the excavation sites, occurring in detailed sequences including phases of human occupation and cultivation (Chapter 9.3.1). Combined with paleo-botanical evidence for crop disruption and low temperature margins to accommodate for cold summers, it appears plausible – despite the many uncertainties regarding site representativeness in the area – that site abandonment and fallowing was indeed caused by environmental factors. Remaining questions concern the extent and duration of the crisis for the community as a whole, and whether it caused significant secondary effects, such as social unrest, population decline, and profound changes in subsistence strategies. Unfortunately, the Late Iron Age record from the area is, at present, too limited to explore these issues further. Similar conclusions can also be reached for the Forsand complex in Rogaland. Together, these two case studies demonstrate that the 6th-century cooling event could potentially be highly critical in southern Norway. However, the different course of events in the two areas, with long-term growing agricultural difficulties at Forsand and increasing flood risks in Fron, also illustrate the many variables that must be taken into consideration when assessing disaster impact. Although the basic causes behind site abandonment can be understood as connected to the same overall climate incident, the crisis must nonetheless have been experienced in contrasting ways in the two areas.

The climate event may have been a contributing factor to the ongoing development in the Lake Mjøsa region as well. The evidence for site continuity in Hedmarken suggests that the impact of the cooling may have been unevenly distributed within a local community, with lower risk for crop failure in low lying areas, in particular in the area surrounding Åker. To a certain degree, this is also the case for Hundorp in

Fron. This is not to say that the importance of Åker and Hundorp in their respective communities and regions are due to the climate downturn, as a considerable number of factors are clearly involved in the development of the ruler sites. However, periods of subsistence crisis are likely to have strengthened a system of dependency between those who had surplus resources or better yields to rely on, and those had not. As such, the climate cooling may have contributed to increased social stratification in those areas experiencing considerable agrarian difficulties. However, it should not be understood as the cause for social stratification, ruler site monumentality, and larger polities in itself. On the contrary, the social mechanisms behind the socio-cultural changes of the time appear firmly rooted in Early Migration Period circumstances, through which the petty kingdoms of the Merovingian Period are the apex of long-term development, rather than the beginning of something profoundly new.

11 THE FIMBULWINTER DISCOURSE: COULD THEY ALL BE RIGHT?

In this thesis, I have discussed the premises for the Fimbulwinter discourse in Scandinavian archaeology and analysed the possible effect of the 6th-century cooling event on selected landscape formations by using vulnerability and resilience as analytical tools. By focusing on long-term trajectories, ongoing developments could be studied in relation to the cooling event in an attempt to identify probable consequences and adaptational strategies. The results testify to varying regional impacts and responses, thus adding important nuances to previous assumptions of an all-out crisis throughout most of the Scandinavian Peninsula (cf. Price & Gräslund, 2015). 6th-century events may have nonetheless catalysed an ongoing development, as the Merovingian Period is associated with noticeable changes in the archaeological record. However, whether these changes were influenced by climatic or other instrumental factors remains somewhat unresolved; it is questionable if the changes can be understood as adaptational strategies and traits of population decline. Furthermore, a climate crisis in parts of Scandinavia may have generated other indirect consequences through social unrest that may have spread beyond the initial impact areas. As discussed in Chapter 10, the socio-political context of the Late Migration Period was unstable and prone to change. As such, this study does not provide a full picture of all the potential risk factors involved, a coherent explanation for the course of events, or a final conclusion on the disaster impact of 6th-century climate change. It does, however, demonstrate the potential in utilising a human-environmental approach and the importance of contingency and regionality when studying causes and effects in prehistoric societies. With these aspects in mind, I will now return to where it all started, the Fimbulwinter discourse, for some final remarks on where the debate stands and where its future potential lies.

By introducing climate change as a possible major driver for social change, Gräslund (2007) offered novel perspectives on the century-long discussion about the character and causes behind the transition from the Early to the Late Iron Age in Scandinavia. The general idea of climate being a contributing factor was not new in itself and had been briefly discussed by several archaeologists for some time (for example Axboe, 2001; Gudesen, 1980; Nielsen, 2006; Randsborg, 1997). Gräslund was nonetheless the first to systematically explore this perspective by utilising a combination of dendrochronology, written accounts, paleo-botanical data, archaeological data, myths, and legends. Of particular interest were the Norse myths of the Fimbulwinter, the long cold winter lasting for three years without summer in between, as the tales included several passages reminiscent of the climatic and optical effects of explosive volcanism. His thorough approach and convincing argumentation proved highly influential and was further developed in cooperation with Price, in particular addressing the volcanic evidence, the possible role of

the Justinianic Plague, and large compiled archaeological datasets from central Sweden (Gräslund & Price, 2012; Price & Gräslund, 2015). However, scathing critiques were eventually put forward, addressing long-term trajectories, the complex character of the archaeological record, and the uncritical use of geoscientific datasets, which consequently resulted in deterministic and simplified explanations (Degroot et al., 2021; Moreland, 2018; Näsman, 2012; Pedersen & Widgren, 2011, pp. 60-62). Despite having an environmental perspective, the Fimbulwinter hypothesis lacked a clear human-environmental framework through which the claims of widespread mass mortality could be substantiated (Gundersen, 2019). Instead, significant correlations between geoscientific and archaeological datasets were understood as evidence for a causal connection, further supported by analogous references to contemporary Mediterranean sources and historical incidents of volcanic-induced climate forcing. However, in a parallel process, large amounts of high-resolution climate proxies and model simulations were beginning to mount up and strengthened the idea of an unparalleled and prolonged cooling event for the last two millennia (for example Büntgen et al., 2016; Helama et al., 2018; Sigl et al., 2015; Toohey et al., 2016). Thus, despite the fact that the basic source-critical challenges with the Fimbulwinter hypothesis continue to be a valid source of critique, the 6th-century cooling remains a focal point for Scandinavian Iron Age archaeology and continues to be attributed with considerable explanatory force in a number of recent publications (ie. Gräslund, 2018, 2020; Holmberg et al., 2020; Solheim & Iversen, 2019).

The Fimbulwinter discourse has, to a certain degree, been somewhat detached from the overall epistemological development within past disaster research during the last four decades (Chapter 4). This is, to some extent, in contrast to the 1st half of the 20th century, during which Scandinavian archaeology was at the forefront of incorporating environmental perspectives in prehistoric research (Chapter 3.1 and 4.1). In particular, Scandinavian Iron Age archaeology has been little influenced by the growing importance of the environmental humanities in recent years. Instead, the discourse has, in many ways, been embedded within existing interpretative frameworks addressing the 6th-century transition, thus serving as an extension of previous debates on the crisis narratives (Chapter 3.3.2). The main difference between the older and more recent debates is the significance attributed to the climate factor, whereas the critique follows in line with previous arguments. As stated by Näsman (2012, p. 6): “I see no reason to revise my conclusion from that conference” (with reference to Näsman, 1988a, 1988b). However, as discussed in Chapter 3.3.2, there is little disagreement among archaeologists on the climate event itself, and most assign climate factors with at least some instrumental value in the development of farming societies in Iron Age Scandinavia (Herschend, 2009, p. 288 and note 234; Myhre, 2002, p. 13; Näsman, 2009, p. 107; 2012, p. 14; Pedersen & Widgren, 2011, pp. 49, 52). However, the climate factor is often poorly understood among both critics and proponents of the Fimbulwinter hypothesis alike. Few attempts have been made to contextualise human and environmental datasets, which would provide better opportunities for understanding how prehistoric societies may have been affected by climate change. As

such, the recent environmental turn in Scandinavian Iron Age archaeology, as represented by the Fimbulwinter hypothesis, is not human-environmental in analytical terms, but is based on somewhat deterministic assumptions that the climate *must* have been the main cause behind the profound socio-cultural changes of the mid-1st millennium AD (Gundersen, 2019, p. 110).

A few noteworthy studies on the Scandinavian Iron Age diverge from this picture: Widgren (2013) was to first to point out the analytical importance of the concept of ‘vulnerability’, whereas Stamnes (2016) offered a method through which agricultural vulnerability could be systematically approached. In addition, there is also a growing interest for the 6th-century cooling in international archaeological research, often involving attempts to develop more coherent human-environmental approaches emphasising the ‘spatiotemporal heterogeneity’ of climate change (ie. Degroot et al., 2021; Peregrine, 2020a, 2020b). In the present study, I have attempted to build upon these principles and develop them further by going in-depth on disaster risk research and resilience theory and using them as structural elements for the analyses. Long-term perspectives and proper contextualisation of human and environmental datasets have proven to be of vital importance, resulting in patterns of regionality and diversity. Conclusively, previous suggestions of a halving of the population at the Scandinavian Peninsula (as argued by Gräslund, 2018, pp. 193-196; Gräslund & Price, 2012, p. 433; Price & Gräslund, 2015, p. 127) are up for revision. Nonetheless, many more factors need to be considered and researched before final conclusions can be made. In part, this concerns the need for more regional and local studies taking on agricultural vulnerability, but also a need for incorporating a greater number of factors into the analyses in order to build more comprehensive analytical frameworks. The Justinianic Plague, epidemic ergotism, and the possibility for extensive warfare fuelled by competition for resources may all have contributed to differences in disaster impact and responses throughout Scandinavia.

The Justinianic Plague remains an unsolved enigma for the Merovingian Period. The Early Merovingian Period is often described as one of cultural and economic isolation, during which contact with the new Germanic and Christianised continental kingdoms was less frequent than in preceding and succeeding centuries. Considering its widespread distribution in Post-Antiquity throughout the former Roman world, it seems nonetheless likely that the plague spread to Scandinavia sometime during its 200 years of existence. Although trade disruption is a prominent feature of the age (Skre, 2019, pp. 219-221), it should not be understood as a period of total isolation. Cultural influences across northern Europe are clearly visible in the elite milieus, as expressed through the Åker assemblage (cf. Røstad, 2020). It is likely only a matter of time until the plague bacteria becomes identified in Scandinavian Merovingian Period anthropogenic remains. However, as discussed in Chapter 2.3.4, the importance of the Justinianic Plague for the socio-political and economic development of Europe is not just a matter of its mere presence in a

given region. Considerable uncertainties exist regarding mortality rates and demographic consequences, making direct comparisons to the medieval Black Death uncertain at the present time.

Similar challenges exist for the possible importance of epidemic ergotism. Bondeson and Bondesson (2014) provide a good overview of the causes and effects of the disease, and a few dispersed finds of the fungus testify to its presence in Iron Age Scandinavia (Chapter 2.3.3). However, as pointed out by Bondeson and Bondesson (2014, p. 65), the distribution of ergot is dependent on several environmental factors, including temperatures, cereal types, humidity, and soil conditions. Rye in particular is susceptible to ergot; they suggest it may have contributed to different levels of impact and consequences from place to place, thus serving as an explanation for regional diversity. However, whether the 6th-century cooling event can be associated with increased humidity levels is up for discussion (cf. Büntgen et al., 2011; van Dijk et al., in review). The limited distribution of rye in central Scandinavia prior to the Late Iron Age is also of some concern when assessing the importance of ergot for increased mortality rates in the 6th century. The evidence from Forsand in Rogaland (Løken, 2001, p. 17; 2020, p. 285) nonetheless suggest that it may indeed have been a contributing factor, at least in some areas. Whether it had large-scale consequences in the dry region of eastern Norway is far more uncertain.

However, as suggested by Axboe (1999, 2001) and discussed in depth in Chapter 5, there is no need for dramatic impact rates for human responses and social change to occur. Unstable and vulnerable societies are prone to change even in the face of minor disruptions. However, political, societal, and perhaps even religious unrest due to anxiety and distress would not necessarily cause changes in day-to-day practices, such as farming techniques and subsistence strategies, which would have been directed towards other concerns than shifting political and religious concerns. When discussing the 6th-century transition in light of climate change, distinguishing between cultural and political resilience (Chapter 5.2.1), and analysing them as interrelated but nonetheless fuelled by different underlying mechanisms, may provide fruitful for analysing the many variables that seem to have been in play.

The present study neither rejects the significance of climate change for prehistoric societies nor considers it decisive for the overall societal development in Iron Age Scandinavia. The cooling event had the potential to become highly critical, but that outcome depends on numerous factors of both human and environmental character. Even at Forsand and Fron, both seemingly experiencing dramatic consequences, the development was one of similar crises conditioned by dissimilar circumstances, eventually leading up to dissimilar courses of events. Thus, the crisis, and its causes, must have been locally perceived in contrasting ways as well, probably resulting in diverging explanations among the contemporaneous

societies for what were, in essence, related incidents. The populations of Iron Age Scandinavia would have had no knowledge of the actual causes behind the situation, but experienced its consequences in different ways. In some areas, like coastal Vestfold, they may have observed weather anomalies and stratospheric optical illusions which were of otherwise little consequence for daily farming life. In this perspective, it becomes difficult to interpret the 6th-century cooling as a shared experience throughout the peninsula, with common consequences and explanations. On the contrary, it may have resulted in a multitude of tales, similar in some respect and dissimilar in many more, of which only a few elements are likely to have survived into historical times as folklore, myths, and legends.

It is rather intriguing that the 6th-century cooling left no visible mark on the Norse dynastical sagas, for instance in Snorri Sturluson's *Ynglinga saga* (1964 [~1220-1230], pp. 8-47). In the saga, the only passage mentioning a prolonged famine is the one about king Dómaldi in Uppsala (stanza 15), who was sacrificed after three years of bad harvests. The three-year perspective is indeed reminiscent of a dust-veil event (cf. Chapter 2.1). However, the story likely reflects events which pre-date the Late Migration Period. In his thorough analysis of the Beowulf poem, Gräslund (2018, 2020) argues that the poem reflects early 6th-century circumstances. He furthermore identifies the Uppsala king Aðils in the story, meaning that he as well is regarded as a 6th-century character. However, judging from the genealogy of the Ynglinga saga, Dómaldi lived over ten generations before Aðils, thus dating him to the Late Roman Iron Age or Early Migration Period. No similar incidents of widespread crop failure are known for the reign of King Aðils, or any other kings likely belonging to the Migration or Merovingian Period. Nonetheless, the Ynglinga saga emphasises widespread warfare in Scandinavia during this period as the kings competed for hegemony. Another reference to crop failure is made, but during the reign of the Viking Age king Ólafr trételgja in the bordering areas between present-day Norway and Sweden (stanza 43). One would expect that a severe climate crisis, resulting in a halving of the population at the Scandinavian Peninsula, would have left such a profound mark on their collective memory that it would have been mentioned, at least briefly, in the sagas. However, no such references exist, except from in their eschatological beliefs and mythological worldview. In the saga of King Haakon the Good (Sturluson, 1964 [~1220-1230], pp. 87-114), the late Viking Age local nobleman Ásbjörn from Melhus in Trøndelag refers to history as divided into the (previous) age of cremations and the (present) age of mound constructions (stanza 15), which is reminiscent of a generalised categorisation of Early and Late Iron Age burial customs. The passage is interesting, as it reflects a recognition of ritual change, but also because burial customs appear to have been a structuring element in their perception of the past. Again, no reference is made to the 6th-century cooling event or incidents of mass mortality. Thus, the Fimbulwinter does not seem to have been a point of particular reference in their historical understanding, and is in its entirety dispatched to the mythological sphere. It has recently been suggested that mnemonic remains of an experienced Fimbulwinter have survived in legendary accounts, such as the Rök runestone in central Sweden

(Holmberg et al., 2020) and the Beowulf poem (Gräslund, 2018, 2020), but nonetheless as symbolic embodiments and poetic renditions. A likely explanation is that such an event would be so traumatising that it became unmentionable and had to be dealt with indirectly as part of the supernatural world. However, as has been demonstrated in this thesis, there is little reason to expect that this was indeed the case.

An alternative explanation more in line with the main results of this study is considerable regional diversity in disaster impact. Occurrences of crop failure and hunger may have been experienced as local and/or short-term incidents, thus understood as more bad harvests in line with recurring difficulties of this kind, rather than as a shared existential crisis throughout the peninsula. What then can be said about the Fimbulwinter myth? It may have had nothing to do with the 6th century (as discussed by Nordvig & Riede, 2018), or may have been merely inspired by the cooling event, rather than directly reflecting it. Stories of perceived optical illusions, such as the reddened sky, and incidents of famine, cold, and unrest, may very well have been incorporated into the mythological tales as points of reference the audience could relate to without being an attempt to reiterate a collective trauma.

To conclude, the turn in recent years towards climatic explanations for the profound archaeological changes around the Early to Late Iron Age transition involves a distinct potential for advancing our understanding of the mechanisms at play, but also for the relevance of climatic factors in the development of Scandinavian Iron Age societies in general. However, in order to be able to move beyond mere concurrencies in the archaeological and geoscientific records, and to avoid simplified and deterministic explanations of past societal change, new methods and analytical frameworks which emphasise the importance source criticism, contingency, long-term trajectories, and the concept of human-environmental interactions are required. In this perspective, crisis and a change of practice becomes complementary rather than contradicting, which ultimately opens up for a more dynamic and multifaceted view of the Iron Age in general, and the 6th century in particular. In this thesis, I have demonstrated that a climate cooling may have affected the farming communities in southern Norway in profoundly different ways, thus functioning as a possible explanation for regional diversity in the archaeological record. Some areas may have been critically affected, whereas other areas seem to have been able to successfully adapt. Certain areas do not seem to have been significantly affected at all, and may have even been able to benefit from the situation. Finally, the impact of the climate event had the potential of being unevenly distributed within a given society, which may have enforced a system of dependency between those who had surplus resources and good yields to rely on, and those who had not. Crisis is indeed a matter of perspective and is conditioned by a multitude of factors situated within both human and environmental domains.

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The references are mainly made up of archaeological reports from field surveys and excavations conducted during the last four decades. Many of the former department names are no more in use and are not easily translated to English. The Norwegian titles and names are therefore kept intact, whereas overall institution (university/county administration) is translated to English.

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APPENDIX

Pollenanalytiske undersøkelser av en myr på Ulberg, Sør-Fron, Oppland

av

Helge Irgens Høeg

21/10-2021

INNLEDNING

Bakgrunnen for undersøkelsen var å få en oversikt over tidligere tiders bosetning og spesielt jordbruk på Hundorp, Sør-Fron i Gudbrandsdalen. Spesielt var vi interessert i om det var mulig å påvise en tilbakegang i jordbruket i forbindelse med årene uten sommer – årene etter AD 536. En slik tilbakegang er tidligere blitt påvist i Ljøgottjern ved Gardermoen, Haraldstadmyren ved Sarpsborg, Hagelandsmyren ved Grimstad og Gardbergmyren i Vestre Slidre. Mindre tydelig sees den også i mange andre diagram fra SØ-Norge.

FELTARBEID

Feltarbeidet ble utført 12 /6-19. Det ble prøveboret i flere myrer i midtla øst for elven, bl.a. på Alme. Det var aldri mer enn 30 cm sediment. Vi prøvde også på en elveslette øst for Lågen. Der var det 20 cm vann, så 20 cm organiske avsetninger og videre fin silt ned til mer enn 150 cm. To myrer ble samlet inn. Det var en høytliggende myr på Pyntaberget på vei mot seterområdet øst for Lågen og en på Ulberg, vest for Lågen.

Rundt myren på Pyntaberget bestod skogen av *Picea* og *Betula*. På myren vokste det *Betula nana*, *Cyperaceae*, *Andromeda polifolia* og litt *Salix*. Myren var 130 cm dyp og bestod av sterkt omdannet torv. Sedimentet fra 75 til 85 cm var ganske sort, mulig kullholdig. Under 85 cm var torven litt mindre omdannet. Myren så ikke veldig lovende ut, men den ble innsamlet, og 9 prøver ble analysert. Bunken, 130 cm, ble datert til 8930±50 BP, kalibrert, 10107±157 BP (LuS-14934)

Myren på Ulberg var stor og dyp og virket lovende. Det ble samlet prøver ned til 495 cm. Dette var ikke bunnen av myren.

På myren vokste det *Sphagnum*, *Cyperaceae*, *Andromeda polifolia*, og *Betula nana*. Rundt og tildels på myren var det skog vesentlig av *Picea*. Avstanden til et nå nedlagt gårdsbruk var ca. 100 m.

Sedimentet bestod av lite omdannet *Sphagnum* ned til 30 cm, litt mer omdannet ned til 200 cm og ytterligere litt mer omdannet og mørkere ned til 280 cm. Fra 280 til 290 cm fikk vi ikke opp noe materiale. Fra 290 til 395 cm var *Sphagnum*- torven mindre omdannet. Fra 395 til 425 cm var det gytjeholdig torv (gyttja). Derfra var det gytje videre ned til 495 cm. Fra 90 til 100 cm var det noe gresstorv (grass-turf) sammen med *Sphagnum*. Det var også innhold av gresstorv fra 400 til 470 cm.

Preparering

Prøver ble preparert 24/6-19, 7/1-20 og 8/7-20. I første omgang ble det preparert prøver for hver 10. cm, senere tildels hver eller hver annen cm fra 30 cm og ned til 59 cm. Tilsammen ble det preparert og analysert 83 prøver fra Ulbergmyr. Fra hvert nivå ble det tatt ut 1 cm³ prøve og tilsatt 2 *Lycopodium*-tabletter som hver inneholdt 13679±192 sporer av

myk kråkefot, *Lycopodium clavatum*. Ved at det er brukt 2 tabletter, blir standardavviket mindre. Det tilsatte antallet sporer blir 27358 ± 136 pr. prøve. Prøvene er preparert etter standardmetodene (Fægri & Iversen 1950, 1966, 1975, Høeg 1979b).

3.2. Analyser og diagramtegning

De fleste prøvene var pollenrike. I hver av prøvene er det forsøkt opptalt alle typer pollen, naturlig forekommende sporer, tilsatte *Lycopodium*-sporer og en del andre mikroorganismer til antallet treslagspollen var i overkant av 600. I et lite antall pollenfattige prøver er det talt færre pollenkorn. Totalt er det vanligvis opptalt ca. 700 pollenkorn pluss sporer, andre mikroorganismer, kullstøvpartikler og tilsatte *Lycopodium*-sporer i hver prøve.. I denne myren ble det ikke observert silt.

For hver lokalitet er det laget et diagram som viser forholdet mellom dybden av bassenget og alderen på nivåene i kalibrerte år BP (før AD 2000). I hvert diagram er det tre kurver, en for gjennomsnittsalder minus 2 *standardavvik*, en for gjennomsnittsalder og en for gjennomsnittsalder pluss 2 *standardavvik*.

Resultatene av analysene er oppstilt i et prosent-pollendiagram (pollen percent diagram). Summen av pollenkorn, ΣP , fra terrestriske (terrestric) planter utgjør 100% ved prosentberegningen. Pollen fra vann- og sumpplanter, sporer, andre mikroorganismer (micro-organisms), tilsatte *Lycopodium*-sporer og kullstøvpartikler er regnet i prosent av ΣP + vedkommende gruppe, f.eks. ΣP + Σ vannplanter. Da ^{14}C -år ikke tilsvarer kalenderår er det brukt kalibrerte (calibrated) år BP.

Det er også laget et influksdiagram (influx diagram) som angir gjennomsnittlig årlig pollenedfall/cm² for de viktigste pollentypene ved å ta hensyn til pollen/cm³ og tilveksthastigheten på sedimentet. For å kunne lage et slikt diagram er man avhengig av mange daterte nivåer, og særlig på overgangen mellom to typer sedimenter som på overgangen mellom gytje og torv. Disse kurvene er ganske sagtaggete. Det kan ha mange årsaker. De uttatte prøvene er aldri nøyaktig 1 cm³. Litt større prøve vil gi litt for høy influks og omvendt. En prøve består ikke bare av pollen, men større eller mindre mengder annet organisk eller uorganisk materiale. Større innhold av grovt plantemateriale eller minerogent materiale i en prøve vil f.eks. gi lavere influks enn i prøvene under og over.

Det ideelle tilfellet er hvor det er jevne forandringer i diagrammet, og hvor en økning for en eller noen pollentyper, f.eks. for trær, skjer samtidig med en tilbakegang for andre, f.eks. for urter. En økning for alle pollentyper i en del av diagrammet er sannsynlig når et tidligere vegetasjonsløst område gror til, som f.eks. etter istiden eller når et tjern eller en myr vokser til med blomsterplanter (trær, busker, dvergbusker, urter) da f.eks. vannplanter (aquatics) og *Sphagnum*-spores ikke er med i 100%-summen i motsetning til pollen fra terrestriske planter. Ellers er det sannsynlig i et slikt tilfelle at en eller flere av dateringene er gale. En slik del av et diagram bør omfatte flere år enn det som kommer frem. En annen mulighet er at denne delen av diagrammet inneholder resedimentert materiale, noe som fører til at dateringene blir for gamle. Andre årsaker til gale dateringer er innhold av yngre røtter. Dette gir for ungt resultat. Kalkholdig materiale i området vil føre til oppløst kalk i vannet. Dette gir CO₂ som ikke inneholder ^{14}C -isotopen. Dette vil gi for gammelt resultat. Det er størst fare for dette i gytje hvor algene assimilerer CO₂ fra vannet og ikke fra luften.

Da det er de siste 1900 årene som er mest interessante for denne undersøkelsen, er det laget ekstradiagram, både prosentdiagram og influksdiagram, som bare omfatter tiden tilbake til 1950 BP.

Dateringer

Det er utført 6 ¹⁴C-dateringer fra denne prøveserien. De er som følger:

Ua-67047, 35 cm, 1191±29 BP, AD 832±64, 1168±64 BP kal

LuS-15685, 52 cm, 1455±35 BP, AD 600±55, 1400±55 BP kal

LuS-15686, 92 cm, 1720±35 BP

LuS-15687, 108 cm, 1715±35 BP, AD 280±80, 1680±80 BP kal

LuS-14936, 125 cm, 1880±35 BP, AD 163±107, 1837±107 BP kal

LuS-14935, 495 cm, 4620±40 BP, 3327±192 BC, 5327±192 BP kal

Alle dateringene untagen en virker fornuftige. Enten må en datering være blitt for gammel eller en for ung siden et nivå er blitt eldre enn et nivå dypere i myren. Det virker som om det er nivået 92 cm som er blitt for gammelt da den er blitt eldre enn 108 cm.

Det er interpolert mellom overflaten og den øverste dateringen og mellom dateringene. På den måten har alle de analyserte nivåene fått en alder.

Diagrammet er inndelt i 8 soner som følger:

Sone 6	495 – 375 cm	5350 – 4200 BP	3350 BC – 2200 BC
Sone 7A	375 – 241 cm	4200 – 2950 BP	2200 – 950 BC
Sone 7B	241 – 125 cm	2950 – 1850 BP	950 BC – AD 150
Sone 7C	125 – 101,5 cm	1850 – 1650 BP	AD 150 – 350
Sone 7D	101,5 – 51 cm	1650 – 1400 BP	AD 350 - 600
Sone 7E	51 39,5 cm	1400 – 1250 BP	AD 600 - 750
Sone 8A	39,5 – 17,5 cm	1250 – 650 BP	AD 750 – 1350
Sone 8B	17,5 – 0 cm	650 – 0 BP	AD 1350 – 2000

Sone 6, 495 – 375 cm, 5350 – 4200 BP, 3350 BC – 2200 BC

Det er analysert 15 nivåer i denne sonen. Det var åpent vann på stedet opp til 425 cm og delvis åpent/svært fuktig opp til 395 cm og torv videre. Sonen er karakterisert med meget av algen *Botryococcus*, litt av algen *Pediastrum* og meget Cyperaceae, mest *Carex*. Mengden *Botryococcus* og *Carex* veksler. Der det er meget *Botryococcus* er det lite starr og omvendt. Starr har vokst på grunne områder i vannet. Det kan være snakk om f.eks. *Carex rostrata*. I de nivåene hvor det er meget *Carex*, er det lite trepollen. Det betyr ikke at skogen har vært åpen, siden *Carex* ikke har vokst i skogen, men i vannet. Det ble også funnet ett pollenkorn av *Nymphaea*. Det er mulig at det har vokst *Nymphaea* i tjernet, men ett pollenkorn betyr lite. Hadde vi samlet og analysert myren til bunns, hadde vi sett om det hadde vokst *Nymphaea* og kanskje andre vannplanter i tjernet.

Det har vokst *Alnus* på fuktige steder rundt tjernet, *Betula* og *Pinus* i skogen rundt og litt *Ulmus* på lune steder. I de nederste nivåene er det 1% *Corylus*. Videre opp gjennom diagrammet er det bare snakk om 0,1 – 0,2%. Det er kanskje slutten av den postglasiale varmetiden vi ser i de nederste nivåene. Skogen har vært tett. I noen nivåer er det unormalt høy influks for *Betula* og *Pinus*. Dette kan skyldes manglende ¹⁴C-dateringer. Gytjen vokser vanligvis langsommere enn torv. En cm gytje representerer flere år enn 1 cm torv. Derfor er det blitt tilsynelatende høy influks i gytjen og lav influks i torven over. Hvis dette er riktig, burde øvre sonegrensen vært yngre, kanskje noen hundre år yngre. Dette vil i såfall også forplante seg til neste sone. Det vil gi lavere influks i gytjen og høyere i torven. Forskjellen ville blitt mindre.

I denne sonen er det lite kullstøv, ingen anthropochors, men litt apophytes. Det er ikke noe som tyder på korndyrking, og lite som tyder på beitende husdyr.

Sone 7A, 375 – 241 cm, 4200 – 2950 BP, 2200 – 950 BC

Det er analysert 12 nivåer i denne sonen. Det burde vært en ¹⁴C-datering der sedimentet går over fra gytje til torv. Det ville antagelig gjort denne sonen yngre, særlig begynnelsen.

Nå er tjernet vokst igjen. Alger og *Carex* er erstattet med *Sphagnum* og de encellede dyrene *Assulina* og *Amphitrema* som lever i torvmosen. Skogen har fortsatt vært tett, med *Alnus* på fuktige steder og ellers *Betula* og *Pinus* omtrent som i foregående sone, men etter hvert litt mer *Pinus*. Det er sammenhengende kurve for *Picea*, men den er så lav at det enten må dreie seg om fjernttransport eller at det har vokst ett og annet grantre i området. *Picea* er selvsteril, og for å sette spiredyktige frø kreves pollen fra en other *Picea*. En *Picea* kan imidlertid legge de nederste grenene ned slik at de kan vokse opp til nye trær. Treet sprer seg ikke på den måten, men den overlever gjennom lang tid.

Denne sonen skiller seg ut med at det er pollen av *Hordeum* i nesten alle nivåene og ett pollen av *Triticum* i det øverste nivået. Det er også nesten sammenhengende kurver for apophyts, *Artemisia* og *Rumex*, et par pollenkorn fra *Chenopodiaceae* og et par sporer av *Sordaria*. Apophyter er planter som også har vokst i området tidligere. De er ofte lyskrevende og næringskrevende og begunstiges av alle former for jordbruk. Dette i motsetning til anthropochorer som er planter som er innført av mennesker. Det dreier seg om alle kornartene, *Cannabis* og *Linum*. I tillegg kommer innførte ugressarter som f.eks. *Plantago lanceolata*, *Plantago major*, *Centaurea cyanus*, *Perrisicaria maculata* og *Spergularia*. Det er litt mer kullstøv gjennom hele sonen enn i sonen under. Det er ikke pollen av *Plantago lanceolata*. Det har kanskje vært en liten kornåker i nærheten, men kanskje heller mer korndyrking i midtla på østsiden av dalen. Selvom *Hordeum* stort sett er selvbestøver og lite pollen slippes ut av blomsten under blomstringen, kan noe pollen bli tatt av vinden og bli fraktet et stykke fra åkeren, kanskje særlig under treskingen.

I denne sonen har det vært dyrket litt korn i området. Litt mer kullstøv og litt mer apophytes kan tyde på litt husdyrhold selvom de sikre beiteindikatorene mangler

Sone 7B, 241 – 125 cm, 2950 – 1850 BP, 950 BC – AD 150

Det er analysert 14 nivåer i denne sonen. Også denne sonen begynner muligens noe senere. Skogen er helt som i foregående sone. Det er litt mer røsslyng ved sonens begynnelse, men den viktigste forskjellen fra foregående sone er at anthropochorer mangler fullstendig. Det er også noe mindre *Artemisia* og andre apophytes. Det ser ikke ut til at det har vært noen form for jordbruk i området i dette tidsrommet.

Sone 7C, 125 – 101,5 cm, 1850 – 1650 BP, AD 150 – 350

Det er analysert 7 nivåer i denne sonen. Denne sonen er godt datert. I denne sonen er det noe mindre *Betula* og noe mer *Pinus*, men ellers små forandringer og skogen er like tett. Det er imidlertid ett pollenkorn av *Hordeum* og ett av *Avena*. Det er tilnærmet sammenhengende kurve for *Artemisia* og *Rumex* og noe mer kullstøv, særlig i et nivå. Det har igjen vært litt jordbruk i området, men antagelig ikke mer enn i sone 7A.

Sone 7D, 101,5 – 51 cm, 1650 – 1400 BP, AD 350 - 600

Det er analysert 16 nivåer i denne sonen. Denne sonen er også godt datert. Sonen begynner med maksimum for *Pinus*, så maksimum for *Betula* og så maksimum for *Pinus* igjen mot slutten av sonen. Det er litt mer *Alnus* og mot slutten av sonen ørlite mer *Picea*. Det har imidlertid fortsatt bare vært enkelttrær eller fjernttransport. I midten av sonen er det et minimum i skogstetthet. Det skyldes et maksimum for røsslyng i ett nivå og noe mer *Carex* og *Poaceae* i flere nivåer. Nå vokste det *Rubus chamaemorus* på myren. Det gjør det også videre opp. Denne planten er ikke med i pollensummen (ΣP). I denne sonen er det svært høy influks for alle pollentypene, særlig *Betula*, *Pinus* og *Alnus*. Dette virker ikke helt naturlig. Det burde vært mange flere år i denne sonen og tildels også i den neste sonen. Skulle man få til det, måtte alle 4 dateringene som er brukt være gale, ikke bare den som er utelatt allerede. Det kan kanskje dreie seg om resedimentasjon, men jeg har ellers ingen forklaring på dette.

I denne sonen har det vært jordbruk i nærheten. Det er maksimum for kullstøv og pollen av alle kornslagene. Det er pollen av *Plantago lanceolata* i to nivåer, tilnærmet sammenhengende kurve for *Artemisia* og *Rumex* og pollen av *Chenopodiaceae* og *Rumex longifolius* og sporer av *Sordaria*.

Det har ikke vært kraftig jordbruksaktivitet i denne sonen sammenlignet med f.eks. området rundt Ljøgottjern ved Gardermoen, men det er i dette tidsrommet at jordbruksaktiviteten har vært størst. Dette er sonen med mest korndyrking. Det er både *Avena*, *Hordeum*, *Triticum* og *Secale*. Det er også sonen med mest husdyrhold. Det er *Plantago lanceolata* i to nivåer, og tildels meget *Artemisia* og *Rumex* også andre apophyter. Det er maksimum for *Calluna* og andre *Ericales*, maksimum for gress og *Pteridium*. *Pteridium* er giftig og blir gjerne stående igjen på skogsbeite. I ingen annen sone forekommer så mange forskjellige urteer i pollenspektrene.

Sone 7E, 51 39,5 cm, 1400 – 1250 BP, AD 600 - 750

Det er analysert 7 nivåer i denne sonen. Også denne sonen er godt datert. Det er minimum for *Betula* og maksimum for *Pinus*. Det er et lite maksimum for *Picea*, nå opp i 2%. Midt i sonen er det et minimum for trepollen som skyldes et maksimum for *Calluna*.

Det som gjør denne sonen spesiell, er at anthropochorer mangler nesten fullstendig, men det er fortsatt noe kullstøv. Det er også minimum for apophytes. Bare i de øverste nivåene er det litt *Hordeum*. Det lille maksimumet for *Picea* og *Calluna* i denne sonen kan skyldes at noen trær og dvergbusker har vokst opp på tidligere kornåkre. Det ser ut som om årene uten sommer har ført til stopp i korndyrkingen og kanskje også i husdyrholdet, men kullstøvet tyder på at det fortsatt har bodd mennesker i området.

Sone 8A, 39,5 – 17,5 cm, 1250 – 650 BP, AD 750 – 1350

Det er analysert 9 nivåer i denne sonen. Det er større avstand mellom de analyserte prøvene, både i cm og i år. Sonen skiller seg ikke meget fra sone 7C. Skogen har vært tett. *Pinus* har vært det viktigste treslaget, så *Betula*. *Alnus* går tilbake mot slutten av sonen. Kurven for *Picea* går tilbake til 1% i begynnelsen av sonen for så å øke til 3% og så avta igjen. Det er litt mer *Ericales* og *Carex*. Det er mindre kullstøv, men *Cerealia* i alle nivåene, særlig *Hordeum*, men også litt *Secale* og i det nederste nivået også litt *Triticum*. Det er *Plantago lanceolata* i ett nivå, *Artemisia*, *Rumex longifolius* og *Sordaria* i den nederste delen av sonen og *Rumex* i flere nivåer. Jordbruket har tatt seg opp igjen, men det har ikke vært så stor aktivitet som i sone 7D, kanskje mer som i 7C.

Det er ikke lett å si noe om forholdet mellom korndyrking og husdyrhold. 7D er sonen med mest både korndyrking og husdyr. I sone 7E er det lite både korndyrking og husdyr. I 7C og 8A er det både korndyrking og husdyr, men mindre enn i 7D. Jeg kan ikke si mer om graden av korndyrking i forhold til husdyrhold, bare at det var mindre av begge deler i 7D, svært lite i 7E og noe av begge deler i 7A, 7C og 8A.

Sone 8B, 17,5 – 0 cm, 650 – 0 BP, AD 1350 – 2000

Det er analysert 3 nivåer i denne sonen. Det er stor avstand i år mellom de analyserte nivåene. Skogen er noe mer åpen. Det skyldes at *Pinus* er gått tilbake. *Picea* er iallfall innvandret ved sonens begynnelse og øker til nesten 20% i det øverste nivået. Det er ikke usannsynlig at *Picea* innvandret allerede ved begynnelsen av sone 8A. Det er imidlertid mer *Calluna*, *Empetrum* og andre *Ericales* og litt mer *Poaceae*. Det er *Hordeum* i det nederste nivået og *Hordeum* og *Triticum* i det øverste. Det er apophyter i alle nivåene.

Ved 15 cm, for ca. 500 år siden, er det et minimum for *Pinus* og maksimum for *Rosaceae*, antagelig *Rubus idaeus*. Det kan se ut som om *Pinus* er blitt hugget, og *R. idaeus* er vokst opp på hugstområdene, noe som er svært vanlig.

Når sone 8 er delt i A og B, skyldes det svartedauen. Vi kan ikke se noen tilbakegang i jordbruket AD 1350. Kanskje hadde vi sett det hvis det også her var blitt analysert prøver for hver eller hver annen cm, men kanskje tilbakegangen for *Pinus* for 500 år siden kan skyldes nyrydding eller behov for tømmer etter en periode med lavt folketall etter pesten.